

Interpretation manual of the marine EUNIS habitats in the Nature Restoration Regulation

Authors:

Samuli Korpinen (SYKE), Emanuele Bigagli (BriS), Giulio Farella (ISPRA), Simone Eisenbarth (BfN), Tanya Milkova (Fresh Thoughts), Axel Kreutle (BfN), Lauri Kuismanen (SYKE), Meri Lappalainen (SYKE), Giulia Mo (ISPRA), Sabrina Agnesi (ISPRA), Julian Mönnich (UBA-DE), Marita Arvela (SYKE), Theo Prins (DELTA RES), Leonardo Tunesi (ISPRA)

Cover design: EEA
Cover image © Natural England/Angela Gall, 2009
Layout: Veronica Ressem [NIVA]

Version: 3.0

Publication Date: 20 March 2026

EEA activity: Biodiversity and ecosystems

Legal notice

Preparation of this report has been co-funded by the European Environment Agency as part of a grant with the European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems and expresses the views of the authors. The contents of this publication do not necessarily reflect the position or opinion of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union. Neither the European Environment Agency nor the European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems is liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of the information contained in this publication.

ETC-BE coordinator: Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)

ETC-BE partners: Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN), Association BIOPOLIS (Biopolis), Brilliant Solutions Engineering & Consulting (BRiS), Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, Aarhus University (DCE-AU), Deltares, Dark Matter Laboratories B.V. (DML), Ecologic Institute (Ecologic), Environment Agency Austria (EAA), Fresh Thoughts Consulting GmbH (Fresh Thoughts), Global Footprint Network (GFN), Hot or Cool Institute gGmbH (HoC), International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), French national institute for industrial environment and risks (INERIS), Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), LESPROJEKT-SLUŽBY Ltd (LESP), Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg (MLU), Sapienza University Rome (SAP), Seascope Belgium (SSBE), Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE), Thematic Center for Water Research, Studies and Project Development, Ltd. (TC Vode), German Environment Agency (UBA-DE), University Duisburg-Essen (UDE), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)

Copyright notice

© European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems, 2026
Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged. [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (International)]

More information on the European Union is available on the Internet (<http://europa.eu>).

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19130393

How to cite this report:

Korpinen, S., Bigagli, E., Farella, G., Eisenbarth, S., Milkova, T., Kreutle, A., Kuismanen, L., Lappalainen, M., Mo, G., Agnesi, S., Mönnich, J., Arvela, M., Prins, T. & Tunesi, L. (2025). Interpretation manual of the marine EUNIS habitats in the Nature Restoration Regulation. (ETC BE Report 2025/2). European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and Ecosystems.

European Topic Centre on
Biodiversity and ecosystems
<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-be>

Contents

Acknowledgements	10
Summary.....	10
Introduction.....	11
How to read the habitat descriptions?.....	13
Habitat descriptions	14
Group 1: Seagrass beds.....	14
MA522. Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sand	15
MA623. Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral mud	18
MB522. Seagrass beds on Atlantic infralittoral sand.....	21
MA332. Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged vegetation.....	25
MA432. Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged vegetation.....	27
MA532. Baltic hydrolittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants	28
MA632. Baltic hydrolittoral mud dominated by submerged rooted plants.....	29
MB332. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants	30
MB432. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants	31
MB532. Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants	32
MB632. Baltic infralittoral mud sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants.....	33
MB546. Seagrass and rhizomatous algal meadows in Black Sea freshwater influenced infralittoral muddy sands.....	35
MB547. Black Sea seagrass meadows on moderately exposed upper infralittoral clean sands.....	38
MB548. Black Sea seagrass meadows on lower infralittoral sands.....	41
MB252. Biocenosis of <i>Posidonia oceanica</i>	45
MB2521. Ecomorphosis of striped <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> meadows	49
MB2522. Ecomorphosis of "barrier-reef" <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> meadows	53
MB2523. Facies of dead "mattes" of <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> without much epiflora	57
MB2524. Association with <i>Caulerpa prolifera</i> on <i>Posidonia</i> beds.....	60
MB5521. Association with <i>Cymodocea nodosa</i> on well sorted fine sands	64
MB5534. Association with <i>Cymodocea nodosa</i> on superficial muddy sands in sheltered waters.....	67
MB5535. Association with <i>Zostera noltei</i> on superficial muddy sands in sheltered waters	70
MB5541. Association with <i>Ruppia cirrhosa</i> and/or <i>Ruppia maritima</i> on sand	72
MB5544. Association with <i>Zostera noltei</i> in euryhaline and eurythermal environment on sand	74
MB5545. Association with <i>Zostera marina</i> in euryhaline and eurythermal environment.....	77
Group 2: Macroalgal forests	79
MA123. Seaweed communities on full salinity Atlantic littoral rock	80
MA125. Fucooids on variable salinity Atlantic littoral rock	82
MB121. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral rock.....	84
MB123. Kelp and seaweed communities on sediment-affected or disturbed Atlantic infralittoral rock	86

MB124. Kelp communities on variable salinity Atlantic infralittoral rock.....	88
MB321. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment	90
MB521. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral sand	92
MB621. Vegetated communities on Atlantic infralittoral mud	94
MA131. Baltic hydrolittoral rock and boulders characterised by perennial algae	97
MB131. Perennial algae on Baltic infralittoral rock and boulders.....	99
MB232. Baltic infralittoral bottoms characterised by shell gravel	101
MB333. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by perennial algae.....	103
MB433. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae	105
MB144. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea exposed upper infralittoral rock with fucales.....	108
MB149. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea moderately exposed upper infralittoral rock with fucales ..	111
MB14A. Fucales and other algae on Black Sea sheltered upper infralittoral rock, well illuminated	115
MA1548. Association with <i>Fucus virsoides</i>	120
MB1512. Association with <i>Cystoseira tamariscifolia</i> and <i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	122
MB1513. Association with <i>Cystoseira amentacea</i> (var. <i>amentacea</i> , var. <i>stricta</i> , var. <i>spicata</i>)	125
MB151F. Association with <i>Cystoseira brachycarpa</i>	128
MB151G. Association with <i>Cystoseira crinita</i>	131
MB151H. Association with <i>Cystoseira crinitophylla</i>	134
MB151J. Association with <i>Cystoseira sauvageauana</i>	137
MB151K. Association with <i>Cystoseira spinosa</i>	140
MB151L. Association with <i>Sargassum vulgare</i>	143
MB151M. Association with <i>Dictyopteris polypodioides</i>	145
MB151W. Association with <i>Cystoseira compressa</i>	147
MB1524. Association with <i>Cystoseira barbata</i>	150
MC1511. Association with <i>Cystoseira zosteroides</i>	153
MC1512. Association with <i>Cystoseira usneoides</i>	156
MC1513. Association with <i>Cystoseira dubia</i>	159
MC1514. Association with <i>Cystoseira corniculata</i>	162
MC1515. Association with <i>Sargassum</i> spp.	165
MC1518. Association with <i>Laminaria ochroleuca</i>	167
MC3517. Association with <i>Laminaria rodriguezii</i> on detritic beds.....	169
Group 3: Shellfish beds	172
MA122. <i>Mytilus edulis</i> and/or barnacle communities on wave-exposed Atlantic littoral rock	173
MA124. Mussel and/or barnacle communities with seaweeds on Atlantic littoral rock	175
MA227. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic littoral zone	177
MB222. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic infralittoral zone.....	180
MC223. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.....	182
MB231. Baltic infralittoral bottoms dominated by epibenthic bivalves	186
MC231. Baltic circalittoral bottoms dominated by epibenthic bivalves	188

MD231. Baltic offshore circalittoral biogenic bottoms characterised by epibenthic bivalves.....	190
MD232. Baltic offshore circalittoral shell gravel bottoms characterised by bivalves	191
MD431. Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed bottoms characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures.....	193
MD531. Baltic offshore circalittoral sand characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures	195
MD631. Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic bivalves.....	197
MB141. Invertebrate-dominated Black Sea lower infralittoral rock	199
MB143. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea exposed upper infralittoral rock with foliose algae (no Fucales)	202
MB148. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea moderately exposed upper infralittoral rock with foliose algae (other than Fucales).....	205
MB242. Mussel beds in the Black Sea infralittoral zone	208
MA243. Oyster reefs on Black Sea lower infralittoral rock	211
MB642. Black Sea infralittoral terrigenous muds.....	213
MC141. Invertebrate-dominated Black Sea lower circalittoral rock	215
MC241. Mussel beds on Black Sea circalittoral terrigenous muds.....	218
MC645. Black Sea lower circalittoral mud	221
MA1544. Facies with <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> in waters enriched in organic matter	224
MB1514. Facies with <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	227
Mediterranean infralittoral oyster beds.....	230
Mediterranean circalittoral oyster beds.....	233
Group 4: Maerl beds	236
MB421. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment.....	237
MB322. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment	241
MB622. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral muddy sediment	245
MB3511. Association with rhodolithes in coarse sands and fine gravels mixed by waves	250
MB3521. Association with rhodolithes in coarse sands and fine gravels under the influence of bottom currents.....	252
MB3522. Association with maerl (= Association with <i>Lithothamnion corallioides</i> and <i>Phymatholiton calcareum</i>) on Mediterranean coarse sands and gravel	254
MC3521. Association with rhodolithes on coastal detritic bottoms	257
MC3523. Association with maerl (<i>Lithothamnion corallioides</i> and <i>Phymatholiton calcareum</i>) on coastal dendritic bottoms.....	259
Group 5: Sponge, coral and coralligenous beds.....	262
MC121. Faunal turf communities on Atlantic circalittoral rock	263
MC124. Faunal communities on variable salinity Atlantic circalittoral rock	265
MC126. Communities of Atlantic circalittoral caves and overhangs.....	266
MC222. Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.....	268
MD121. Sponge communities on Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock	270
MD221. Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic offshore circalittoral zone.....	272

ME122. Sponge communities on Atlantic upper bathyal rock	274
ME123. Mixed cold water coral communities on Atlantic upper bathyal rock	276
ME221. Atlantic upper bathyal cold water coral reef	278
ME322. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment	280
ME324. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment	282
ME422. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment	283
ME623. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal mud	284
ME624. Erect coral field on Atlantic upper bathyal mud	285
MF121. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal rock	287
MF221. Atlantic lower bathyal cold water coral reef	289
MF321. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment	291
MF622. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic lower bathyal mud	293
MF623. Erect coral field on Atlantic lower bathyal mud	294
MB138. Baltic infralittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges.....	297
MB43A. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges (Porifera)	299
MC133. Baltic circalittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic cnidarians	301
MC136. Baltic circalittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges.....	303
MC433. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians	305
MC436. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges.....	307
MD24. Black Sea offshore circalittoral biogenic habitats.....	310
ME14. Black Sea upper bathyal rock	313
ME24. Black Sea upper bathyal biogenic habitat	315
MF14. Black Sea lower bathyal rock	317
MB151E. Facies with <i>Cladocora caespitosa</i>	320
MB151Q. Facies with <i>Astroides calycularis</i>	323
MB151α. Facies and association of coralligenous biocenosis (in enclave)	326
MC1519. Facies with <i>Eunicella cavolini</i>	328
MC151A. Facies with <i>Eunicella singularis</i>	330
MC151B. Facies with <i>Paramuricea clavata</i>	332
MC151E. Facies with <i>Leptogorgia sarmentosa</i>	335
MC151F. Facies with <i>Anthipatella subpinnata</i> and sparse red algae.....	338
MC151G. Facies with massive sponges and sparse red algae	341
MC1522. Facies with <i>Corallium rubrum</i>	344
MC1523. Facies with <i>Leptopsammia pruvoti</i>	347
MC251. Coralligenous platforms	349
MC6514. Facies of sticky muds with <i>Alcyonium palmatum</i> and <i>Parastichopus regalis</i> on circalittoral mud.....	353
MD151. Biocenosis of Mediterranean shelf-edge rock	356
MD25. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral biogenic habitats	358

MD6512. Facies of sticky muds with <i>Alcyonium palmatum</i> and <i>Parastichopus regalis</i> on lower circalittoral mud.....	360
ME1511. Mediterranean upper bathyal <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs	362
ME1512. Mediterranean upper bathyal <i>Madrepora oculata</i> reefs.....	366
ME1513. Mediterranean upper bathyal <i>Madrepora oculata</i> and <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs	370
ME6514. Mediterranean upper bathyal facies of with <i>Pheronema carpenteri</i>	374
MF1511. Mediterranean lower bathyal <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs.....	376
MF1512. Mediterranean lower bathyal <i>Madrepora oculata</i> reefs	380
MF1513. Mediterranean lower bathyal <i>Madrepora oculata</i> and <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> reefs	384
MF6511. Mediterranean lower bathyal facies of sandy muds with <i>Thenia muricata</i>	388
MF6513. Mediterranean lower bathyal facies of compact muds with <i>Isidella elongata</i>	390
Group 6: Vents and seeps	393
MB128. Vents and seeps in Atlantic infralittoral rock.....	394
MB627. Vents and seeps in Atlantic infralittoral mud.....	397
MC127. Vents and seeps in Atlantic circalittoral rock.....	399
MC622. Vents and seeps in Atlantic circalittoral mud	402
MD122. Vents and seeps on Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock.....	404
MD622. Vents and seeps in Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud.....	406
Group 7: Soft sediments (not deeper than 1.000 metres of depth).....	408
MA32. Atlantic littoral coarse sediment.....	409
MA42. Atlantic littoral mixed sediment	411
MA52. Atlantic littoral sand.....	413
MA62. Atlantic littoral mud	415
MB32. Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment	417
MB42. Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment	418
MB52. Atlantic infralittoral sand	420
MB62. Atlantic infralittoral mud.....	422
MC32. Atlantic circalittoral coarse sediment	424
MC42. Atlantic circalittoral mixed sediment	427
MC52. Atlantic circalittoral sand	430
MC62. Atlantic circalittoral mud.....	433
MD32. Atlantic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment	437
MD42. Atlantic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment	439
MD52. Atlantic offshore circalittoral sand	441
MD62. Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud.....	443
ME32. Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment	445
ME42. Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment	447
ME52. Atlantic upper bathyal sand	449
ME62. Atlantic upper bathyal mud.....	451

MF32. Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment.....	453
MF42. Atlantic lower bathyal mixed sediment.....	455
MF52. Atlantic lower bathyal sand.....	456
MF62. Atlantic lower bathyal mud.....	457
MA33. Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment.....	460
MA43. Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment.....	462
MA53. Baltic hydrolittoral sand.....	463
MA63. Baltic hydrolittoral mud.....	465
MB33. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment.....	467
MB43. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment.....	469
MB53. Baltic infralittoral sand.....	471
MB63. Baltic infralittoral mud.....	473
MC33. Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment.....	475
MC43. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment.....	477
MC53. Baltic circalittoral sand.....	479
MC63. Baltic circalittoral mud.....	481
MD33. Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment.....	487
MD43. Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment.....	488
MD53. Baltic offshore circalittoral sand.....	489
MD63. Baltic offshore circalittoral mud.....	491
MA34. Black Sea littoral coarse sediment.....	493
MA44. Black Sea littoral mixed sediment.....	495
MA54. Black Sea littoral sand.....	497
MA64. Black Sea littoral mud.....	499
MB34. Black Sea infralittoral coarse sediment.....	501
MB44. Black Sea infralittoral mixed sediment.....	503
MB54. Black Sea infralittoral sands.....	505
MB64. Black Sea infralittoral mud.....	509
MC34. Black Sea circalittoral coarse sediment.....	512
MC44. Black Sea circalittoral mixed sediment.....	514
MC54. Black Sea circalittoral sand.....	516
MC64. Black Sea circalittoral mud.....	518
MD34. Black Sea offshore circalittoral coarse sediment.....	521
MD44. Black Sea offshore circalittoral mixed sediment.....	523
MD54. Black Sea offshore circalittoral sand.....	525
MD64. Black Sea offshore circalittoral mud.....	527
MA35. Mediterranean littoral coarse sediment.....	530
MA45. Mediterranean littoral mixed sediment.....	532
MA55. Mediterranean littoral sand.....	534

MA65. Mediterranean littoral mud	537
MB35. Mediterranean infralittoral coarse sediment	540
MB45. Mediterranean infralittoral mixed sediment	542
MB55. Mediterranean infralittoral sand	543
MB65. Mediterranean infralittoral mud.....	545
MC35. Mediterranean circalittoral coarse sediment	547
MC45. Mediterranean circalittoral mixed sediment	550
MC55. Mediterranean circalittoral sand	552
MC65. Mediterranean circalittoral mud.....	553
MD35. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral coarse sediment	554
MD45. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral mixed sediment	556
MD55. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral sand	558
MD65. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral mud.....	560
ME35. Mediterranean upper bathyal coarse sediment	561
ME45. Mediterranean upper bathyal mixed sediment	563
ME55. Mediterranean upper bathyal sand	564
ME65. Mediterranean upper bathyal mud.....	565
MF35. Mediterranean lower bathyal coarse sediment.....	567
MF45. Mediterranean lower bathyal mixed sediment.....	568
MF55. Mediterranean lower bathyal sand	569
MF65. Mediterranean lower bathyal mud	570
List of abbreviations	572

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Ana Tejedor and Eirini Glyki (EEA) for their guidance and coordination of this task, as well as for the review and inputs provided at all stages of development. Eionet members from European countries are thanked for the feedback which was found very useful for the content. We would also like to thank also Claudia Neitzel (ETC BE) for her continuous support to this work throughout all phases of development, and Shane Hume (LESP) for the English check.

Summary

The recently adopted Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) sets clear restoration targets for marine ecosystems and provides the legal basis for using the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) classification for the implementation of restoration targets for specified EUNIS marine habitat types.

While the NRR categorizes the EUNIS marine habitat types into seven groups, covering greatly differentiated habitats across the four EU marine regions, it does not provide further explanation of the characteristic species communities, geophysical descriptions, habitat distribution, and biogeographical parameters.

The purpose of this manual is to address the need for a more extensive interpretation of the 233 marine habitat types listed in Annex II of the NRR. It guides Member States in the definition of these habitats, their abiotic and biotic characteristics, biogeographical distribution, and in understanding the linkages between other habitat typologies. In addition, this manual brings scattered habitat information together to support the mapping, assessing and planning of effective restoration measures for the national restoration plans.

Introduction

Several EU legal acts and policies address the protection and conservation of terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecosystems: the EU Habitats and Birds Directives, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Water Framework Directive, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR). The NRR, which was adopted on the 24th of June 2024 and came into force on the 18th of August 2024, aims to assist in achieving the environmental objectives of the other Directives by setting active and passive restoration measures with a clear timeframe. It combines an overarching restoration objective for the long-term recovery of nature in the EU's land and seas with binding restoration targets for specific habitats and species. As part of the implementation of the NRR, each Member State needs to prepare a draft National Restoration Plan within two years of the regulation coming into force.

Article 5 of the NRR sets clear restoration targets for marine ecosystems and provides the legal basis for using the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) classification for the implementation of restoration targets for specified EUNIS marine habitat types. Until the adoption of the NRR the legal environmental objectives for marine habitats were established by the Habitats Directive, which included a few broadly defined marine habitats in its Annex I; the Birds Directive, with marine habitats of some bird species; and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, which identified broad habitats and 'other habitat types'.

Annex II of the NRR categorizes the EUNIS marine habitat types into seven groups, indicating their relation to the habitat types in Annex I of the Habitats Directive¹. These seven groups cover greatly differentiated habitats across the four EU marine regions. While the habitat titles are relatively descriptive, they lack further explanation of the characteristic species communities, geophysical descriptions, habitat distribution, and biogeographical parameters. A more extensive interpretation of these habitats is necessary in order to distinguish these in the Member States' marine waters and support the planning of effective restoration measures.

Over the years a few 'crosswalks' between different marine habitat typologies have been developed by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the Regional Sea Conventions, the latter have also prepared habitat definitions as part of their red list assessments of marine habitats. These are essential building blocks for the interpretation of the habitats listed under the NRR.

This interpretation manual provides a description of the 233 marine habitat types listed in Annex II of the NRR with a geographical distribution of 42 EUNIS habitat types in the Baltic Sea, 88 habitat types in the Mediterranean, 35 habitat types in the Black Sea, and 68 habitat types in the NE Atlantic. The NRR divides these habitats into seven groups, of which: groups 1-6 include habitat types EUNIS levels 4-5; group 7 includes habitat types EUNIS levels 4-5 and EUNIS level 3.

The purpose of this manual is to support the implementation of the NRR, guiding Member States in the definition on the marine habitats included in its Annex II, their abiotic and biotic characteristics, biogeographical distribution, and in understanding the linkages between other habitat typologies². In

¹ The habitat types listed in Annex I of the Habitats Directive are described in the related habitats interpretation manual: Interpretation manual of EU habitats listed under Annex I of the Habitats Directive.

² In the manual some finer EUNIS sub-habitats are listed to describe the variation in the habitat description. When sublevels of EUNIS habitats are given, finer sublevels are automatically included, although not specifically listed in the document. Geographical variation of the habitats, especially in the vast NE Atlantic region, cannot be fully included and requires further work. The correspondences presented in this manual for each habitat type do not claim to be complete, neither in terms of classification systems displayed nor in terms of biotope types across different levels, and do not imply a weighting of some national classification systems over others. Best practices for restoration are listed when applicable.

addition, this manual brings scattered habitat information together to support the mapping, assessing and planning of effective restoration measures for the national restoration plans³.

³ The descriptions of the habitat types covered in this manual have been prepared by the European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and Ecosystems (ETC-BE). The main sources used were the Interpretation manual of EU habitats (dated 2013), the European nature information system (EUNIS) and its EUNIS habitat catalogue, EUNIS species database and EUNIS habitat classification and crosswalks tables. A broad consultation with Member States and other stakeholders was conducted by the EEA, resulting in the revision of this work with major inputs. This manual was submitted for consultation to the EUNIS groups, the EU Biodiversity Platform Sub-group on marine issues (Marine Expert Group under the Birds and Habitats Directives), the EIONET TG Ocean and EG Nature Restoration and Protection.

How to read the habitat descriptions?

Name of the habitat type

Location
(marine region)

Group 1 MA522. Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sand

NE Atlantic
EUNIS code: [MA522](#)
EUNIS level: 4
Correspondence with other classifications:
MSFD: <Littoral sediment HD: #1140, #1160, #1130, #1150
European Red List: <Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sediment
Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MA5221](#), [MA5222](#), [MA5223](#), [MA5224](#)
OSPAR:
#Zostera beds
#Cymodocea meadows
IE:
#LS.LMp.LSgr.Znol
#SS.SMp.SSgr.Rup
#SS.SMp.SSgr.Zmar
DE:
#02.01.04.01.01.
<§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

Reference codes for the identification of the habitat

= equal to
overlaps
< included in
> including
≈ relatively similar to

Definition and general description of habitat characteristics (vegetation, syntaxa, abiotic features, origin...)

List of the main species that dominate the habitat

List of the species that can be found in the associated community

Habitat groups are coded by colour:

Group 1
Group 2
Group 3
Group 4
Group 5
Group 6
Group 7

General description

This habitat has a widespread distribution and is not limited to a few locations. Intertidal *Zostera marina* beds may extend into the subtidal zone, where they may develop into a perennial form with broad and long leaf and root systems (rhizomes), which survive in winter.

Mid- and upper-shore wave-sheltered muddy fine sand or sandy mud can have high densities of *Z. noltii* (formerly known as *Z. noltei* or *Z. nana*), *Z. marina* and/or *Ruppia* spp. *Z. noltii* forms stands with a cover of delicate trailing narrow leaves that are up to about 20 cm long. As it survives the winter as rhizomes, the locations remain stable over several years. It may occur as monospecific, or with *Z. marina* or *Ruppia* spp. and with occasional plants of lower salt-marsh species, such as annual *Salicornia* spp. or *Spartina anglica*, as stands of *Z. noltii* may pass down shore not only to *Z. marina*, but also to lower saltmarsh communities, notably the *Salicornietum europaeae*. The factors that determine the distribution of *Z. noltii* are not entirely clear. This species is peculiar of situations where the substrate dries out on exposure, and on flats with a gentle bar/hollow topography, where it forms distinctive mosaics with *Z. marina*. It can also occur in shallow standing water; accordingly, it is often found in small permanently submerged lagoons and pools, and on sediment shores where the muddiness of the sediment retains water and stops the roots from drying out. An anoxic layer is usually present at about 5 cm below the surface of the sediment. Seasonal variation may occur in the area covered by intertidal seagrass beds, as plants die back in winter. Intertidal seagrass beds may also be subject to heavy grazing by geese, which can significantly reduce the extent of the plant cover. The rhizomes of *Z. noltii* will remain in place within the sediment in both

southern Portugal and Spain to Senegal, including Canary Island and Madeira. Southern Portugal constitutes the current northern geographic limit of its distribution.

Characteristic species

Zostera noltii, *Z. marina*, *Ruppia maritima* and/or *R. cirrhosa*, *Cymodocea nodosa*

Associated species

The infaunal community of *Zostera*-beds is often formed by polychaetes *Scoloplos armiger*, *Pygospio elegans* and *Arenicola marina*, oligochaetes, spire shell *Peringia ulvae*, and bivalves *Cerastoderma edule* and *Macoma*

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

OSPAR considers that the widespread loss of seagrass is largely a combination of the direct and indirect impacts of the rapid growth in human activities in the coastal zone. Anthropogenic pressures on this habitat include abrasion,

Best practices in nature restoration

The protection of this habitat is often included in legislation aimed at conservation of seagrass beds, e.g., local by-laws and regulations and cross-

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Dalkin, M.J., Hill, T.O., Holt, R.H.F. & Sanderson, W.G., 1997a. Marine biotope classification for Britain and Ireland. Vol. 2. Sublittoral biotopes. Joint Nature Conservation Committee, Peterborough, JNCC Report no. 230, Version 97.06.](#)

Selection of the literature consulted

Human activities and pressures that are likely to affect the status of the habitat

Group 1
Group 2
Group 3
Group 4
Best practices implemented to protect the habitat

Group 5
Group 6
Group 7

Habitat descriptions

Group 1: Seagrass beds

Figure 01-01, *Zostera marina* bed, NE Atlantic

Source: *Zostera marina*, © Christophe Quintin, 2021

Group 1

MA522. Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sand

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA522](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1140, #1160, #1130, #1150

European Red List:

<Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sediment

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA5221](#), [MA5222](#),

[MA5223](#), [MA5224](#)

OSPAR:

#*Zostera* beds

#*Cymodocea* meadows

IE:

#LS.LMp.LSgr.Znol

#SS.SMp.SSgr.Rup

#SS.SMp.SSgr.Zmar

DE:

#02.01.04.01.01.

<§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

General description

This habitat has a widespread distribution and is not limited to a few locations. Intertidal *Zostera marina* beds may extend into the subtidal zone, where they may develop into a perennial form with broad and long leaf and root systems (rhizomes), which survive in winter.

Mid and upper-shore wave-sheltered muddy fine sand or sandy mud can have high densities of *Z. noltii* (formerly known as *Z. noltei* or *Z. nana*), *Z. marina* and/or *Ruppia* spp. *Z. noltii* forms stands with a cover of delicate trailing narrow leaves that are up to about 20 cm long. As it survives the winter as rhizomes, the locations remain stable over several years. It may occur as monospecific, or with *Z. marina* or *Ruppia* spp. and with occasional plants of lower salt-marsh species, such as annual *Salicornia* spp. or *Spartina anglica*, as stands of *Z. noltii* may pass down shore not only to *Z. marina*, but also to lower saltmarsh communities, notably the *Salicornietum europaeae*. The factors that determine the distribution of *Z. noltii* are not entirely clear. This species is peculiar of situations where the substrate dries out on exposure, and on flats with a gentle bar/hollow topography, where it forms distinctive mosaics with *Z. marina*. It can also occur in shallow standing water; accordingly, it is often found in small permanently submerged lagoons and pools, and on sediment shores where the muddiness of the sediment retains water and stops the roots from drying out. An anoxic layer is usually present at about 5 cm below the surface of the sediment. Seasonal variation may occur in the area covered by intertidal seagrass beds, as plants die back in winter. Intertidal seagrass beds may also be subject to heavy grazing by geese, which can significantly reduce the extent of the plant cover. The rhizomes of *Z. noltii* will remain in place within the sediment in both situations, and plants towards the lower limit may remain winter-green.

In some areas, *Z. marina* may also be interspersed with *Ruppia* beds (Connor et al., 2004).

Expanses of clean or muddy fine sand and sandy mud in shallow water and on the lower shore (typically to about 5 m depth) can have dense stands of *Z. marina/angustifolia*. The community composition may be dominated by these *Zostera* species and, therefore, be characterised by the associated biota. Other biota present can be closely related to that of areas of sediment not supporting seagrass beds, for example *Saccharina latissima*, *Chorda filum*, and infaunal species, such as *Ensis* spp. and *Echinocardium cordatum*.

In southern areas, *Cymodocea nodosa* can also form patches in well sorted fine sands or on superficial muddy sands in sheltered intertidal zones. Frequently is mixed with other habitat forming phanerogams (*Zostera noltii* and *Zostera marina*) in muddy sands rich in organic nutrients. Shallow meadows of *Cymodocea* and *Zostera* are usually found in sheltered bays close to harbours, e.g., Cadiz Bay, or in areas subject to human impact. In the North East Atlantic, *C. nodosa* is nowadays restricted to scattered locations from southern Portugal and Spain to Senegal, including the Canary Islands and Madeira. Southern Portugal constitutes the current northern geographic limit of its distribution.

Characteristic species

Zostera noltii, *Z. marina*, *Ruppia maritima* and/or *R. cirrhosa*, *Cymodocea nodosa*

Associated species

The infaunal community of *Zostera*-beds is often formed by polychaetes *Scoloplos armiger*, *Pygospio elegans* and *Arenicola marina*, oligochaetes, spire shell *Peringia ulvae*, and bivalves *Cerastoderma edule* and *Macoma balthica*. The green algae *Ulva* spp. may be present on the sediment surface.

Ruppia beds may be populated by fish such as *Belone belone*, *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, *Syngnathus acus* and *Spinachia spinachia*, which are less common on filamentous algal-dominated sediments. Seaweeds such as *Chaetomorpha* spp., *Ulva* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Chorda filum* are also often present in addition to occasional fucoids. In some cases, the stoneworts *Lamprothamnium papulosum* and *Chara aspera* occur. Infaunal and epifaunal species may include mysid crustacea, the polychaete *Arenicola marina*, the gastropod *Peringia ulvae*, the amphipod *Corophium volutator*, and oligochaetes such as *Heterochaeta costata*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

OSPAR considers that the widespread loss of seagrass is largely a combination of the direct and indirect impacts of the rapid growth in human activities in the coastal zone. Anthropogenic pressures on this habitat include abrasion, pollution, eutrophication (leading to effects such as smothering by epiphytes and algal blooms), changes in hydrological conditions including wave exposure, change in suspended solids, infilling, but also shellfish fisheries, trampling, coastal development, land reclamation, human intrusion, for example driving across intertidal seagrass beds and bait digging. Moreover, invasive algae species can hamper the growth and distribution of seagrass (e.g., *Gracilaria* spp. in the Wadden Sea).

Best practices in nature restoration

The protection of this habitat is often included in legislation aimed at the conservation of seagrass beds, e.g., local by-laws and regulations and cross-border agreements covering large geographical areas, as in the case of the Wadden Sea. It is also a characteristic feature of several habitat types listed in Annex 1 of the HD. The establishment of protected areas and zoning as part of Integrated Coastal Zone Management plans has also been beneficial for the protection of this habitat. These designations and plans can provide a framework under which specific measures, e.g., restrictions on activities such as bait digging, clam raking, and wastewater management, may be introduced.

Measures: Active seagrass restoration (transplantation and seed-based methods); Fisheries management; Improvement of water quality.

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Dalkin, M.J., Hill, T.O., Holt, R.H.F. & Sanderson, W.G., 1997a. Marine biotope classification for Britain and Ireland. Vol. 2. Sublittoral](#)

[biotopes. Joint Nature Conservation Committee, Peterborough, JNCC Report no. 230, Version 97.06.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[European Red List of Species and habitats: A2.61 Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sediments.](#)

[Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.](#)

[Gamble, C., Glover, A., Debney, A., Bertelli, C., Green, B., Hendy, I., Lilley, R., Nuuttila, H., Potouroglou, M., Ragazzola, F., Unsworth, R., & Preston, J. \(Eds.\), 2021. Seagrass Restoration Handbook: UK and Ireland. Zoological Society of London.](#)

[JNCC: Littoral seagrass beds.](#)

[JNCC: *Zostera marina/angustifolia* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[JNCC: *Zostera noltei* beds in littoral muddy sand.](#)

[OSPAR: *Cymodocea* meadows.](#)

[OSPAR: *Zostera* beds.](#)

[Polte, P., Asmus, H., 2006. Intertidal seagrass beds \(*Zostera noltii*\) as spawning grounds for transient fishes in the Wadden Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 312: 235-243 S.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Ruppia maritima* in reduced salinity infralittoral muddy sand.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Zostera \(Zostera\) marina* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Zostera \(Zosterella\) noltei* beds in littoral muddy sand.](#)

[Unsworth R. K. F., Bertelli C. M., Coals L., Cullen-Unsworth L. C., den Haan S., Jones B. L. H., Rees S. R., Thomsen E., Wookey A., Walter B., 2023. Bottlenecks to seed-based seagrass restoration reveal opportunities for improvement, Global Ecology and Conservation, Volume 48, e02736n.](#)

[Vincent, A. C., Berglund, A. & Ahnesjö, I., 1995. Reproductive ecology of five pipefish species in one eelgrass meadow. Environmental Biology of Fishes 44: 347-361.](#)

Group 1

MA623. Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral mud

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA623](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1140, #1160

European Red List:

<Seagrass beds on Atlantic littoral sediment

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA6231](#), [MA6232](#)

OSPAR:

#*Zostera* beds

#*Cymodocea* meadows

IE:

#LS.LMp.LSgr.Znol

#SS.SMp.SSgr.Rup

#SS.SMp.SSgr.Zmar

DE:

#02.01.05.01.01

<§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und

sonstige marine

Makrophytenbestände"

General description

This habitat has a widespread distribution and is not limited to a few locations. Intertidal *Zostera marina* beds may extend into the subtidal zone, where they may develop into a perennial form with broad and long leaf and root systems (rhizomes), which survive in winter.

Mid and upper-shore wave-sheltered muddy fine sand or sandy mud can have high densities of *Z. noltii* and/or *Z. marina*. *Z. noltii* forms stands with a cover of delicate trailing narrow leaves that are up to about 20 cm long. It survives the winter as rhizomes; therefore, the locations remain stable over several years. It may occur as monospecific, or with *Z. marina* or *Ruppia* spp. and with occasional plants of lower salt-marsh species, such as annual *Salicornia* spp. or *Spartina anglica*, as stands of *Z. noltii* may pass down shore not only to *Z. marina*, but also to communities of the lower saltmarsh, notably the *Salicornietum europaeae*. The factors that determine exactly the distribution of *Z. noltii* are not entirely clear. It is most characteristic of situations where the substrate dries out somewhat on exposure, and of flats with a gentle bar/hollow topography, where it forms distinctive mosaics with *Z. marina*. It can also occur in shallow standing water; in fact, it is often found in small permanently submerged lagoons and pools, and on sediment shores where the muddiness of the sediment retains water and stops the roots from drying out.

An anoxic layer is usually present about 5 cm below the surface of the sediment. There may be seasonal variation in the area covered by intertidal seagrass beds, as plants die back in winter. Intertidal seagrass beds may also be subject to heavy grazing by geese, which can significantly reduce the extent of the plant cover. The rhizomes of *Z. noltii* will remain in place within the sediment in both situations, and plants towards the lower limit may remain winter-green.

In some areas *Zostera marina* may also be interspersed with the *Ruppia* beds (Connor et al., 2004).

In southern areas, *Cymodocea nodosa* can also form patches in well sorted fine sands or on superficial muddy sands in sheltered intertidal zones. Frequently is mixed with other habitat forming phanerogams (*Zostera noltii* and *Zostera marina*) in muddy sands rich in organic nutrients. Shallow meadows of *Cymodocea* and *Zostera* are usually found in sheltered bays close to harbours, e.g., Cadiz Bay, or in areas subject to human impact. In the North East Atlantic, *C. nodosa* is nowadays restricted to scattered locations from southern Portugal and Spain to Senegal, including the Canary Islands and Madeira. Southern Portugal constitutes the current northern geographic limit of its distribution

Characteristic species

Zostera noltii, *Z. marina*, *Ruppia maritima* and/or *R. cirrhosa*, *Cymodocea nodosa*

Associated species

The infaunal community of this habitat is characterised by polychaetes *Scoloplos armiger*, *Pygospio elegans* and *Arenicola marina*, oligochaetes, spire shell *Peringia ulvae*, and bivalves *Cerastoderma edule* and *Macoma balthica*. The green algae *Ulva* spp. may be present on the sediment surface.

Ruppia beds may be populated by fish such as *Belone belone*, *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, *Syngnathus acus* and *Spinachia spinachia*, which are less common on filamentous algal-dominated sediments. Seaweeds such as *Chaetomorpha* spp., *Ulva* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Chorda filum* are also often present in addition to occasional fucoids. In some cases, the stoneworts *Lamprothamnium papulosum* and *Chara aspera* occur. Infaunal and epifaunal species may include mysid crustacea, the polychaete *Arenicola marina*, the gastropod *Peringia ulvae*, the amphipod *Corophium volutator* and oligochaetes such as *Heterochaeta costata*.

In southern regions of the NE Atlantic, the polychaetes *Hediste diversicolor*, *Alkmaria romijni* and *Capitella capitata* are typical as well as the bivalve *Scrobicularia plana* and the red algae *Gracilaria* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

OSPAR considers that the widespread loss of seagrass is largely a combination of the direct and indirect impacts of the rapid growth in human activities in the coastal zone. Anthropogenic pressures on this habitat include pollution, eutrophication (leading to effects such as smothering by epiphytes and algal blooms, forming of mats by associated species such as *Ulva* spp. and *Gracilaria* spp., competing for light with seagrass), change of hydrological conditions including wave exposure, infilling, shellfish fisheries, trampling, coastal development, land reclamation, human intrusion for example driving across intertidal seagrass beds and bait digging. Moreover, invasive algae species can hamper the growth and distribution of seagrass (e.g., *Gracilaria* spp. in the Wadden Sea).

Best practices in nature restoration

The protection of this habitat is often incorporated in legislation aimed at the conservation of seagrass beds, e.g., local by-laws and regulations, as well as cross-border agreements covering large geographical areas, as in the case of the Wadden Sea. It is also a characteristic feature of several habitat types listed in Annex 1 of the HD. The establishment of protected areas and zoning as part of Integrated Coastal Zone Management plans has also been beneficial for the protection of this habitat. These designations and plans can provide a framework under which specific measures, e.g., restrictions on activities such as bait digging, clam raking, and wastewater management, may be introduced.

Measures: Active seagrass restoration (transplantation and seed-based methods); Fisheries management; Improvement of water quality.

Bibliographic sources

[Unsworth R. K. F., Bertelli C. M., Coals L., Cullen-Unsworth L. C., den Haan S., Jones B. L. H., Rees S. R., Thomsen E., Wookey A., Walter B., 2023. Bottlenecks](#)

[to seed-based seagrass restoration reveal opportunities for improvement, Global Ecology and Conservation, Volume 48, e02736n.](#)

[Connor, D.W., Dalkin, M.J., Hill, T.O., Holt, R.H.F. & Sanderson, W.G., 1997a. Marine biotope classification for Britain and Ireland. Vol. 2. Sublittoral biotopes. Joint Nature Conservation Committee, Peterborough, JNCC Report no. 230, Version 97.06.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.](#)

[Gamble, C., Glover, A., Debney, A., Bertelli, C., Green, B., Hendy, I., Lilley, R., Nuuttila, H., Potouroglou, M., Ragazzola, F., Unsworth, R., & Preston, J. \(Eds.\), 2021. Seagrass Restoration Handbook: UK and Ireland. Zoological Society of London.](#)

[JNCC: Littoral seagrass beds.](#)

[JNCC: *Zostera marina/angustifolia* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[JNCC: *Zostera noltei* beds in littoral muddy sand.](#)

[OSPAR: Cymodocea meadows.](#)

[OSPAR: *Zostera* beds.](#)

[Polte, P., Asmus, H., 2006. Intertidal seagrass beds \(*Zostera noltii*\) as spawning grounds for transient fishes in the Wadden Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 312: 235-243 S.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Ruppia maritima* in reduced salinity infralittoral muddy sand.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Zostera \(Zostera\) marina* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Zostera \(Zosterella\) noltei* beds in littoral muddy sand.](#)

[Unsworth R. K. F., Bertelli C. M., Coals L., Cullen-Unsworth L. C., den Haan S., Jones B. L. H., Rees S. R., Thomsen E., Wookey A., Walter B., 2023. Bottlenecks to seed-based seagrass restoration reveal opportunities for improvement, Global Ecology and Conservation, Volume 48, e02736n.](#)

[Vincent, A. C., Berglund, A. & Ahnesjö, I., 1995. Reproductive ecology of five pipefish species in one eelgrass meadow. Environmental Biology of Fishes 44: 347-361.](#)

Group 1

MB522. Seagrass beds on Atlantic infralittoral sand

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB522](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1150, #1160

European Red List: =A5.53

(non-Macaronesian), =A5.53

(Macaronesian)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB5221](#), [MB5222](#),

[MB5223](#), [MB5224](#)

OSPAR:

#*Zostera* beds, #*Cymodocea* meadows

IE:

>SS.SMp.SSgr.Zmar

>SS.SMp.SSgr.Rup

DE:

#02.02.10.01.01.

<§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und

sonstige marine

Makrophytenbestände"

General description

This habitat type covers beds of submerged marine angiosperms in the genera *Zostera*, *Ruppia*, and *Cymodocea*, adjacent to the mainland coasts of the North East Atlantic region. The Iberian coast is a transitional zone where *Zostera*-dominated seagrass beds reach their southern limit and *Cymodocea*-dominated seagrass beds reach their northern and western limits. *Ruppia* beds are restricted to brackish environments, where *Zostera* may be interspersed. Seagrass beds play an important role in the trophic status of marine and estuarine waters, acting in sediment stabilisation and as an important conduit or sink for nutrients. Consequently, some examples of *Z. marina* beds have markedly anoxic sediments associated with them. This habitat type is a spawning area, and harbours increased densities of juvenile and medium-sized fish species.

This habitat occurs in shallow sublittoral sediments, generally in sheltered embayments, marine inlets, estuaries, and lagoons, with weak tidal currents and under conditions of low, variable, and full salinity.

While generally found on muds and muddy sands, particular marine examples of *Zostera* communities may also occur in coarser sediments. *Cymodocea nodosa* forms large and dense patches with green leaves that can reach a length of 100cm and a width of 8mm in well-sorted fine sands or on superficial muddy sands in sheltered waters and at depths of 1-30m. Frequently, it is mixed with other habitat-forming phanerogams, *Z. noltii* and *Z. marina*, on muddy sands rich in organic nutrients. Shallow meadows of *Cymodocea* and *Zostera* are usually found in sheltered bays close to harbours or in areas subject to human impact.

In the southern islands of the Macaronesian region, this habitat consists of beds of submerged marine angiosperms in the genera *Cymodocea*, *Halophila*, *Ruppia*, *Thalassia* and *Zostera* in the southern islands of Macaronesia. It does not occur in the Azores. Seagrass beds are present mainly off the sheltered eastern coasts of the Canary Islands (Spain), on the wide subtidal platforms with sandy substrata and gently sloping coastlines that are sheltered from the Trade Winds. They may occur in patches or form extensive meadows reaching depths of over 30m, where light levels are sufficient to support growth. *C. nodosa* has also been reported in scattered locations along the southern coast of Madeira Island (Portugal). In the Canary Islands, *C. nodosa* can be found forming unispecific meadows, but can also be mixed with *Halophila decipiens* on muddy bottoms or with the green macroalga *Caulerpa prolifera* on sandy bottoms.

Characteristic species

Beds of submerged marine angiosperms in the genera *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Halophila decipiens*, *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera* spp.

Associated species

Other biota present in this habitat include grazing snails, hydrozoans, and infaunal species, such as *Ensis* spp., *Cerastoderma* spp. and *Echinocardium cordatum*. In submerged beds of brackish seas, sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of mud or sand flats, and coastal lagoons along the coasts of the Atlantic, North Sea, and Baltic in boreal and temperate Europe, *Zannichellia palustris*, *Chara* spp., *Lamprothamnium papulosum* and *Tolipella nidifica* can be associated with *Ruppia* and/or *Zostera*. These beds may be populated by fish such as *Belone belone*, *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, which is less common on filamentous algal-dominated sediments. Other present fish are *Hippocampus hippocampus*, *Spinachia spinachia* and *Syngnathus acus*. Seaweeds such as *Chaetomorpha* spp., *Enteromorpha* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Chorda filum* are often present in addition to occasional fucoids. Infaunal and epifaunal species may include mysid crustacea, the polychaete *Arenicola marina*, the gastropod *Peringia ulvae*, the amphipod *Corophium volutator*, and oligochaetes such as *Heterochaeta costata*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Current pressures and threats to this habitat come from coastal development, dredging, shellfisheries, eutrophication, and localised damage from mooring, outdoor sports and leisure activities, recreational activities, motorised nautical sports, other human intrusions and disturbances, shallow surface abrasion and mechanical damage to the seabed surface. Moreover, this habitat has a low to very low resilience towards climate change and related effects, such as global warming and sea level rise.

Best practices in nature restoration

The protection of this habitat is often incorporated in legislation aimed at the protection of seagrass beds, ranging from local by-laws and regulations to cross-border agreements, as in the case of the Wadden Sea. Conservation and management measures include the regulation of fisheries and wastewater treatment (to reduce the risk of eutrophication) and reduction in suspended sediments.

Active seagrass restoration (transplantation and seed-based methods) can enhance restoration success.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Gamble, C., Glover, A., Debney, A., Bertelli, C., Green, B., Hendy, I., Lilley, R., Nuuttila, H., Potouroglou, M., Ragazzola, F., Unsworth, R., & Preston, J. \(Eds.\),](#)

[2021. Seagrass Restoration Handbook: UK and Ireland. Zoological Society of London.](#)

[JNCC: *Ruppia maritima* in reduced salinity infralittoral muddy sand.](#)

[JNCC: *Zostera marina/angustifolia* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[OSPAR: *Cymodocea* meadows.](#)

[OSPAR: *Zostera* beds.](#)

[Polte, P., Asmus, H., 2006. Intertidal seagrass beds \(*Zostera noltii*\) as spawning grounds for transient fishes in the Wadden Sea. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 312: 235-243 S.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Ruppia maritima* in reduced salinity infralittoral muddy sand.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Zostera \(Zostera\) marina* beds on lower shore or infralittoral clean or muddy sand.](#)

[Unsworth R. K. F., Bertelli C. M., Coals L., Cullen-Unsworth L. C., den Haan S., Jones B. L. H., Rees S. R., Thomsen E., Wookey A., Walter B., 2023. Bottlenecks to seed-based seagrass restoration reveal opportunities for improvement, *Global Ecology and Conservation*, Volume 48, e02736n.](#)

[Vincent, A. C., Berglund, A. & Ahnesjö, I., 1995. Reproductive ecology of five pipefish species in one eelgrass meadow. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 44: 347-361.](#)

Figure 01-02, Coral stonewort (*Chara tomentosa*) in the Baltic Sea

Source: Coral stonewort (*Chara tomentosa*), Pyhtää, The Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea, © Juho Lappalainen and Metsähallitus, 2012

Group 1

MA332. Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged vegetation

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA332](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150,

#1160, #1610, #1620, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA3321](#), [MA3322](#),

[MA3323](#), [MA3324](#), [MA3325](#),

[MA3326](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I1B⁴

DE:

=05.01.04.01.01

#§ 30 "Boddengewässer mit
Verlandungsbereichen"

General description

Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone, with at least 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Drift walls often occur above the hydrolittoral zone.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate; Depth range: temporarily exposed due to tide or weather.

Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Zannichellia* spp., *Charales*.

Associated species

Other biota present include grazing snails, hydrozoans, infaunal species such as *Ensis* spp., *Cerastoderma* spp. and *Echinocardium cordatum*. In submerged beds of brackish seas, sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of mud or sand flats, and coastal lagoons of the Atlantic, North Sea and the Baltic coasts of boreal and temperate Europe, *Zannichellia palustris*, *Chara* spp., *Lamprothamnium papulosum* and *Tolipella nidifica* can be associated with *Ruppia* and/or *Zostera*. These beds may be populated by fish such as *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, which is less common on filamentous algal-dominated sediments. Seaweeds such as *Chaetomorpha* spp., *Enteromorpha* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Chorda filum* are often present, in addition to occasional furoids. Infaunal and epifaunal species may include mysid crustacea, the polychaete *Arenicola marina*, the gastropod *Peringia ulvae*, the amphipod *Corophium volutator* and oligochaetes such as *Heterochaeta costata*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Decreased light penetration depth and increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

⁴ AA.I1A is similar but with emergent vegetation, which is different from this habitat type.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013. Baltic esker islands with sandy, rocky and shingle beach vegetation and sublittoral vegetation. BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. AA.11B Baltic photic coarse sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 1

MA432. Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged vegetation

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA432](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150,

#1160, #1180, #1610, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA4321](#), [MA4322](#),

[MA4323](#), [MA4324](#), [MA4325](#)

HELCOM:

AA.M1B

DE:

=05.01.03.01.01

#§ 30 "Boddengewässer mit
Verlandungsbereichen"

General description

Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with a coverage of more than 10%, but less than 90% of both hard and soft substrata. Submerged rooted plants, which also includes plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*), cover at least 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: low to moderate; Exposure range: all; Depth range: temporarily exposed due to tide or weather.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Zannichellia spp., *Chara aspera*.

Associated species

Zannichellia palustris, *Ruppia maritima*, *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera noltii*, *Chara aspera*, *C. baltica*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*, *Stuckenia pectinata*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. AA.I1B Baltic photic mixed substrate characterised by submerged rooted plants.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 1

MA532. Baltic hydrolittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA532](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1140, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1610, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA5321](#), [MA5322](#), [MA5323](#), [MA5324](#), [MA5325](#), [MA5326](#), [MA5327](#), [MA5328](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I1B

DE:

=05.01.05.01.01

#§ 30 "Boddengewässer mit Verlandungsbereichen"

General description

Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate; Depth range: temporarily exposed due to tide or weather

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea

Characteristic species

Zannichellia spp., *Zostera noltii*, *Charales*, *Najas marina*, *Ranunculus peltatus* subsp. *baudotii*, *Eleocharis* spp.

Associated species

Ruppia spp., *Chara aspera*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. baltica*, *Eleocharis acicularis*, *E. parvula*, *E. uniglumis*, *Stuckenia pectinata*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. AA.I1B Baltic photic sand characterised by submerged rooted plants.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 1

MA632. Baltic hydrolittoral mud dominated by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA632](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA6321](#), [MA6322](#),

[MA6333](#), [MA6324](#), [MA6325](#),

[MA6326](#), [MA6327](#), [MA6328](#)

HELCOM:

AA.H1B

DE:

=05.01.06.01.01

#§ 30 "Boddengewässer mit Verlandungsbereichen"

General description

Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: sheltered; Depth range: temporarily exposed due to tide or weather.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Najas marina, *Chara tomentosa*, *Zostera noltii*, *Ruppia* spp., *Ranunculus* spp. *Eleocharis* spp.

Associated species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Eleocharis acicularis*, *E. uniglumis*, *Chara aspera*, *C. baltica*, *C. canescens*, *C. horrida*, *C. tomentosa* and *Tolipella nidifica*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter. Turbidity by activities causing sediment resuspension (dredging, boating).

Best practices in nature restoration

Actions aimed at the reduction of inputs of nutrients and organic matter, as well as of sedimentation from dredging and all construction activities.

Bibliographic sources

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic photic muddy or coarse sediment, sand or mixed substrate dominated by Charales. BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.

HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic photic muddy sediment or sand dominated by spiny naiad (*Najas marina*). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 1

MB332. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB332](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB3321](#), [MB3322](#), [MB3323](#), [MB3324](#), [MB3325](#)

HELCOM:

AA.11B

DE:

=05.02.08.01.01

#§30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

General description

Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate; Depth range: photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Zannichellia* spp., *Zostera marina*, *Charales*.

Associated species

Potamogeton perfoliatus, *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*, *Ranunculus* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter, physical damage leading to loss and destruction of vegetation as well as loss or alteration of the seabed.

Best practices in nature restoration

Actions aimed at the reduction of inputs of nutrients and organic matter, reduction/ban of physical damage (e.g., exclusion of fishing activities with bottom contacting gear) as well as of sedimentation from dredging and all construction activities.

Active seagrass restoration (aiming at *Zostera*) is currently being tested in the southern part of the Baltic Sea (project SeaStore).

Bibliographic sources

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

[Project SeaStore website.](#)

Group 1

MB432. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB432](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: < Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL24 (Near Threatened)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB4321](#), [MB4322](#), [MB4323](#), [MB4324](#), [MB4325](#)

HELCOM:

AA.M1B

DE:

=05.02.06.01.01

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

General description

Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with more than 10%, but less than 90% coverage of both hard and soft substrata. Coverage of submerged rooted plants which also includes plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) covers at least 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: low to moderate; Exposure range: all; Depth range: infralittoral photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Zannichellia* spp., *Chara aspera*.

Associated species

Potamogeton perfoliatus, *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*, *Zostera marina*, *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Myriophyllum sibiricum*, *Chara aspera*, *Chara tomentosa*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *Chara horrida*, *Chara baltica*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter, physical damage leading to loss and destruction of vegetation as well as loss or alteration of the seabed.

Best practices in nature restoration

Actions aimed at the reduction of inputs of nutrients and organic matter, reduction/ban of physical damage (e.g., exclusion of fishing activities with bottom contacting gear) as well as of sedimentation from dredging and all construction activities. Active seagrass restoration (aiming at *Zostera*) is currently being tested in the southern part of the Baltic Sea (project SeaStore).

Bibliographic sources

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

[Project SeaStore website.](#)

Group 1

MB532. Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB532](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1140,

#1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL28

(Near Threatened)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB5321](#), [MB5322](#),

[MB5323](#), [MB5324](#), [MB5325](#),

[MB5326](#), [MB5327](#), [MB5328](#)

HELCOM:

AA.M1B

DE:

=05.02.10.01.01

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und

sonstige marine

Makrophytenbestände"

General description

Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate; Depth range: infralittoral photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Zannichellia* spp., *Zostera marina*, *Charales*.

Associated species

Potamogeton perfoliatus, *Zannichellia* spp., *Ruppia* spp., *Ranunculus peltatus* subsp. *baudotii*, *Zostera noltii*, *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*, *Chara aspera*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. baltica*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter, physical damage leading to loss and destruction of vegetation as well as loss or alteration of the seabed.

Best practices in nature restoration

Actions aimed at the reduction of inputs of nutrients and organic matter, reduction/ban of physical damage (e.g., exclusion of fishing activities with bottom contacting gear) as well as of sedimentation from dredging and all construction activities. Active seagrass restoration (aiming at *Zostera*) is currently being tested in the southern part of the Baltic Sea (project SeaStore).

Bibliographic sources

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

[Project SeaStore website.](#)

Group 1

MB632. Baltic infralittoral mud sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB632](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: < Infralittoral mud
HD: #1130, #1140, #1150,
#1160, #1180, #1650

European Red List: ≈BAL36
(Near Threatened)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB6321](#), [MB6322](#),
[MB6323](#), [MB6324](#), [MB6325](#),
[MB6326](#), [MB6327](#), [MB6328](#)

HELCOM:

AA.H1B

DE:

=05.02.11.01.01

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und
sonstige marine
Makrophytenbestände"

General description

Defined in the HELCOM HUB under AA.H1B "*Baltic photic muddy sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants*". This habitat is defined as Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Submerged rooted plants, including plants with rhizoids (i.e., *Charales*) cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. The salinity range is not limited and covers the entire Baltic Sea, but its distribution is concentrated on zones with a sheltered exposure. This habitat type is assessed in the European Red List of biotopes as "Near Threatened".

Characteristic species

Stuckenia pectinata, *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Chara tomentosa*.

Associated species

Ruppia maritima, *Myriophyllum sibiricum*, *Zannichellia* spp., *Zostera noltii*, *Z. marina*, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Potamogeton* spp., *Ranunculus* spp., *Chara* spp. This habitat is also an important feeding area for water birds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication caused by inputs of nutrients and organic matter, physical damage leading to loss and destruction of vegetation as well as loss or alteration of the seabed.

Best practices in nature restoration

Actions aimed at the reduction of inputs of nutrients and organic matter, reduction/ban of physical damage (e.g., exclusion of fishing activities with bottom contacting gear) as well as of sedimentation from dredging and all construction activities. Active seagrass restoration (aimed so far at *Zostera*) is currently being tested in the southern part of the Baltic Sea (project SeaStore).

Bibliographic sources

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Project SeaStore website.](#)

Figure 01-03, *Zostera noltii* meadow in the Black Sea

Source: *Zostera noltei* meadow in Mangalia, Romania (©NIMRD original photo). Published in: Nita, V., Micu, D., & Nenciu, M. (2014). First attempt of transplanting the key-species *Cystoseira barbata* and *Zostera noltei* at the Romanian coast. *Cercetări Marine - Recherches Marines*, 44(1), 147–163. <https://doi.org/10.55268/CM.2014.44.147>

Group 1

MB546. Seagrass and rhizomatous algal meadows in Black Sea freshwater influenced infralittoral muddy sands

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB546](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

European Red List:

=BLSA5.53

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Underwater seagrass meadows

RO:

Habitat with *Zostera noltei*

General description

This habitat type occurs in sheltered, shallow (0.5-2m) coastal waters (embayments, inlets, bights, harbours) and estuaries, more or less influenced by freshwater (salinity 0.5-10psu), where sedimentary stability leads to mudding of the sand. It is represented by monospecific or mixed species communities formed by *Zostera marina*, *Z. noltii*, *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Ruppia maritima*, *Chara* spp. and two brackish water species (*Stuckenia pectinata*, *Zannichellia palustris*). Commonly found algae species are of the Phylum *Chlorophyta* and *Rhodophyta*, which are tolerant of very low salinities. Phytocenoses are perennial, mono- and oligodominant, oligo- and mesosaprobic. Projective coverage is extremely high-up to 80-100%, and the height sometimes exceeds 1m.

The seagrasses are important for the geomorphology and ecology of coastal ecosystems, as via their root system they stabilize the sediment, help recycle nutrients, and form the basis of the detrital trophic network.

The most extensive seagrass meadows in the Black Sea are found in its northwestern part and along the Crimean coast (Ukraine and Russia), where they grow in large bays and gulfs, coastal lagoons, and river mouths and deltas. The Romanian Black Sea coast is relatively open and exposed to currents and winter storms, offering few suitable habitats for seagrasses, near Mangalia and Vama Veche. Seagrass meadows are distributed along the whole Bulgarian Black Sea coast in sheltered embayments, shallow bays and gulfs, and estuaries, with a higher concentration along the southern coast, according to the hydromorphological conditions. Relatively small seagrass beds are present in bays along the whole Turkish Black Sea coast, particularly near Cape Sinop.

It should be noted that estuaries, although influenced by seawater, are not classified as belonging to marine waters. Accordingly, given the low outflow of the majority of the rivers flowing into the Black Sea from the Bulgarian coast, following the WFD, Bulgaria has identified the transitional waters in the estuaries within inland waters, not in the sea.

Characteristic species

Beds of submerged marine angiosperms in the genera *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera* spp. *Z. marina*, *Z. noltii*, *Z. nana*, *Zannichellia palustris*, *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Ruppia maritima*, *R. cirrhosa*, *Chara* spp., *Stuckenia pectinata* (formerly known as *Potamogeton pectinatus*), *Najas minor*, *Ranunculus baudotii*.

Associated species

Seagrasses are edifiers that create a habitat for diverse epiphytic algal flora (Chlorophyta: *Cladophora* sp., *Ulva* sp.; Rhodophyta: *Ceramium* sp., *Chondria* sp.; Phaeophyta: *Ectocarpus siliquosus*, Heterokontophyta, *Polysiphonia subulifera*; *Gongolaria barbata*) and invertebrate fauna (*Botryllus schlosseri*,

gastropods *Hydrobia acuta*, *Rissoa membranacea*, crustaceans *Dexamine spinosa*, *Diogenes pugilator*, *Gammarus* sp.; polychaetes *Capitella capitata*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys* sp., *Prionospio* sp., *Syllis gracilis*) and the growth of the larvae of various fish and mollusc species.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency, opportunistic green and red algal blooms, as well as bottom hypoxia, and leading to a degradation of phytobenthic communities. Since the 1990s, this pressure has reduced due to the decrease of the inflow of pollutants into the catchment, especially in the northwestern and western parts of the Black Sea.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Dredging activities and construction works in the area of ports and marinas, or construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, and smothering.
- Fishing (pelagic trawling - high pressure, professional passive fishing, and recreational fishing-moderate pressure).
- Shell fishing.
- Sand extraction.
- Hydrological changes, caused by changes to freshwater inputs; and
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

Although the seagrasses are classified as sensitive to oil, more recent studies showed their tolerance to chronic oil pollution and their intensive inhabitation of ports.

This habitat has a low resilience towards climate change and related effects, such as global warming and sea level rise, and flood events causing input of suspended solids and leading to siltation and reduced light penetration. At the same time, this habitat is essential for climate change mitigation, due to its capacity to capture carbon.

Best practices in nature restoration

This habitat shows a good potential for natural recovery when the water quality is improved, and the hydrological regime is stable. Therefore, conservation and management measures related to the regulation of fisheries, the reduction of nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and of suspended sediments, are of high importance. Recovery through intervention is not considered as appropriate for this habitat type.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov, D., Vasilev, V., Hiebaum, G., Biserkov, V., Deyanova, D., Klayn, S., Dimov, K., Vrabcheva, Y., Karamfilov, V., 2022. Current distribution of *Zostera* seagrass meadows along the SW coast of the Black Sea, Bulgaria.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS. Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[SEANOE Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 1

MB547. Black Sea seagrass meadows on moderately exposed upper infralittoral clean sands

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB547](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

=BLSA5.5z

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Underwater seagrass meadows

RO:

<Habitat with *Zostera noltei*

General description

Detailed information on the distribution and specific characteristics of this habitat, including historical or recent trends, is currently lacking. In the context of the purposes of the European Red List assessment, this habitat is considered as Data Deficient.

This habitat occurs in the upper infralittoral zone, on clean sands at depths of between 0.2 to 3m. It is characterised by sedimentary stability and a low silt content (5-10%). The dominant seagrass species is *Zostera noltei*, which may form monospecific or mixed meadows with *Z. marina*, *Ruppia maritima*, *R. cirrhosa*, and *Zannichellia pedicellata*.

Fragmentary data on the habitat indicate its presence in the northwestern part of the Black Sea (Tendrovsky Bay, Karkinitzky Bight, along the Sevastopol coast), Kerch Strait, and fragmented habitats along the Romanian coast, which were greatly reduced in extent due to widespread and severe eutrophication that occurred in the Black Sea in the 1990s. Coastal development (i.e., hydro-technical works) has further contributed to these losses. Along the Bulgarian coast, this habitat occurs within seagrass meadows in the infralittoral zone, with greater density in the southern part. This habitat is also observed along Türkiye's western and eastern coastline, except in the Sinop area.

Overall, the distribution of underwater seagrass meadows is patchy, depending on the availability of suitable inhabiting conditions in sheltered bays with sandy-muddy bottoms. The boundaries are dynamic, depending on the local hydro-meteorological conditions and the strength of the wave impact.

Characteristic species

Zostera noltei is the dominant seagrass species, which may form monospecific or mixed communities with *Z. marina*, *Ruppia maritima*, *R. cirrhosa*, and *Zannichellia pedicellata*.

Associated species

Seagrasses meadows are edifiers that create a habitat for diverse epiphytic algal flora mainly from the phyla Chlorophyta and Rhodophyta, and zoobenthic fauna from the groups Polychaeta, Mollusca, Crustacea. They also provide suitable living conditions for the larval stages of fish, molluscs, and macrozoobenthos.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency, opportunistic green and red algal blooms, as well as bottom hypoxia, and leading to a degradation of phyto-benthic

communities. Since the 1990s, this pressure has decreased due to the reduced inflow of pollutants into the catchment, especially in the northwestern and western parts of the Black Sea.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Dredging activities and construction works in the area of ports and marinas, widening and dredging of channels, or construction of coastal defence facilities, causing siltation, and smothering.
- Fishing (pelagic trawling - high pressure, professional passive fishing and recreational fishing-moderate pressure).
- Shell fishing-high risk of irreversible habitat damage of the habitat due to bottom trawling in the coastal zone.
- Sand extraction.
- Outdoor sports and leisure activities, recreational activities, motorised vehicles.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

This habitat has a low resilience towards climate change and related effects such as global warming and sea level rise, and flood events causing input of suspended solids, and leading to siltation and reduced light penetration.

Best practices in nature restoration

This habitat shows good potential for natural recovery when the water quality is improved, and the hydrological regime is stable. Therefore, conservation and management measures related to the regulation of fisheries, reducing nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds), and reduction in suspended sediments are of high importance.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov, D., Vasilev, V., Hiebaum, G., Biserkov, V., Deyanova, D., Klayn, S., Dimov, K., Vrabcheva, Y., Karamfilov, V., 2022. Current distribution of *Zostera* seagrass meadows along the SW coast of the Black Sea, Bulgaria. SEANOE.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS. Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 1

MB548. Black Sea seagrass meadows on lower infralittoral sands

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB548](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

=BLSA5.5w

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Underwater seagrass meadows

General description

This habitat is found on sandy and sandy-muddy bottoms in sheltered areas in the deeper infralittoral zone, in the 10m depth range with salinity, varying between 11 and 19psu. It is presented by small and fragmented meadows at an average depth of 4-7m. Although six species of seagrass may be present in this habitat, *Zostera marina* is generally dominant and may form monospecific or mixed-species communities of seagrasses and algae species mainly from the phyla Rhodophyta and Chlorophyta.

Species diversity is characterised by two peaks, one in spring and the other in autumn. Seasonal dynamics of the biomass and density are less pronounced due to the depth.

The characteristic Black Sea benthic habitat, including the specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is “*Zostera marina* meadows (4-7m)”. This is one of the seven characteristic habitats identified within the broad habitat type “*Infralittoral sand*” (EUNIS Level 2: MB5) at the Black Sea regional level.

This habitat is distributed all around the Black Sea, except for Romanian waters, depending on the specific hydrological and hydrochemical conditions. The greatest diversity of *Z. marina* communities has been registered in the Kerch Strait (Ukraine).

Characteristic species

Zostera marina is the dominant seagrass species. It may form monodominant communities or associations with *Z. noltii*, *Gongolaria barbata* and *Gracilaria gracilis*. 115 macroalgal species have been recorded in this habitat type in the Black Sea. Typical genera are Ceramium, Cladophora, Kylinia, Laurencia, Melobesia, and Polysiphonia, while green and red algae prevail.

Associated species

Seagrass meadows are edifiers that create a habitat for diverse epiphytic algal flora mainly from the phyla Chlorophyta and Rhodophyta, and zoobenthic fauna from the groups Polychaeta, Mollusca, Crustacea. They also provide suitable living conditions for the larval stages of fish, molluscs, and macrozoobenthos.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Due to its restricted distribution and continued decline, this habitat has been assessed as “endangered” in the EU 28. Due to the overall slight decline in quality, the habitat has been assessed as “Vulnerable” in the EU 28+. The threat is plausible based on losses caused in the recent past and plans to continue coastal development and protection works in both the EU 28 and the EU 28+.

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure, resulting in a decrease in water transparency, opportunistic green and red algal blooms, as well as bottom hypoxia, and leading to a degradation of phytobenthic communities. Since the 1990s, this pressure decreased due to the reduced inflow of pollutants into the catchment, especially in the northwestern and western parts of the Black Sea.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Widening and dredging of channels, or construction of coastal defence facilities, causing siltation, and smothering.
- Fishing (pelagic trawling - high pressure, professional passive fishing and recreational fishing-moderate pressure).
- Shell fishing-high risk of irreversible habitat damage of the habitat due to bottom trawling in the coastal zone.
- Sand extraction.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity. Anthropogenic eutrophication of the coastal zone favours opportunistic and more rival species, and reduced transparency limits the depth of distribution. Eutrophication favours the growth and colonisation of seagrasses by algal epiphytes, leading to the extinction of *Zostera marina* and *Z. noltii*.

This habitat has a low resilience towards climate change and related effects such as global warming and sea level rise, and flood events causing input of suspended solids, and leading to siltation and reduced light penetration.

Best practices in nature restoration

This habitat shows good potential for natural recovery when the water quality is improved, and the hydrological regime is stable. Therefore, conservation and management measures related to the regulation of fisheries, the reduction of nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds), and of suspended sediments, are of high importance.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov, D., Todorova, V., Dimitrov, L., Rinde, E., Karamfilov, V., 2018. Distribution and abundance of phytobenthic communities: Implications for connectivity and ecosystem functioning in a Black Sea Marine Protected Area. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 200: 234-247.](#)

[Berov, D., Vasilev, V., Hiebaum, G., Biserkov, V., Deyanova, D., Klayn, S., Dimov, K., Vrabcheva, Y., Karamfilov, V., 2022. Current distribution of *Zostera* seagrass meadows along the SW coast of the Black Sea, Bulgaria. SEANOE.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Figure 01-04, *Posidonia oceanica* bed

Source: Natural Mediterranean aquascape (*Posidonia oceanica*, *Coris julis*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Mullus surmuletus*), Menorca, © Edu Aguilera, 2024

Group 1

MB252. Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB252](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef⁵

HD: =1120, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB2521](#), [MB2522](#)

Barcelona Convention:

MB2.54

General description

Posidonia oceanica is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms characteristic “meadows” between the surface down to a depth of about 40-45m. The plant structure is composed of creeping or erect stems (rhizomes) that are usually buried in the sediment. Creeping rhizomes are called “plagiotropic” and erect rhizomes “orthotropic”. The rhizomes end in groups of 4-8 leaves (shoots) that are 8-11mm wide and 20-80cm long, although the length may reach 160cm. *P. oceanica* flowers in the autumn (September - November). Flowers are hermaphrodite. *P. oceanica* rhizomes grow in height, even in the absence of sedimentation. To resist being buried, they are capable of speeding up their growth. The “matte” is the whole mass composed of rhizomes, sheaths, roots and the sediment that fills the interstices. The rhizomes, sheaths and roots are not very putrescible and are conserved within the “matte” for several centuries or even thousands of years. Its vertical growth can reach 1 meter a century (0.4 to 1cm per year).

Even if the *P. oceanica* meadows are considered the characteristic climax community of well calibrated infralittoral fine sands, these typical biogenic habitats can develop on heterogeneous kinds of substrata. *P. oceanica* is able to anchor, settle and grow also on rocky substrata, generally with reduced shoot size and higher density compared to meadows on soft bottoms, and availability of light represents one of the main limiting factors. *P. oceanica* prefers well-oxygenated waters and shows a rather wide tolerance to temperature (between 10 and 28°C) and hydrodynamic variations. On the contrary, the plant dislikes low salinity and perishes in conditions under 33‰, while it usually thrives under values between 36‰ and 39‰ (although it can be exceptionally found in lagoons with salinity values up to 46‰). It is, thus, absent at the mouths of rivers and in brackish lagoons.

P. oceanica meadows cover about 1.5% of the total Mediterranean Sea surface (about 1,224,707ha) and occur in 16 Mediterranean countries. The area close to the Gibraltar Strait (Bay of Estepona, Spain) represents the western boundary of *P. oceanica*'s distribution, while it is absent in Morocco (except for the Chafarinas Islands, probably due to the influence of cold Atlantic water) and rare in the north-western Adriatic Sea (due to riverine inputs of freshwater and sediments).

P. oceanica meadows represent a Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot, host spawning and nursery grounds, and play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, nutrient recycling, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability, mitigation of climate change (through the storage of large amounts of carbon within the *matte*).

⁵ Even if biogenic, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows do not form “reefs” *sensu* Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), as they clearly relate to rocky bottoms and their biogenic assemblages.

Characteristic species

Posidonia oceanica (Linnaeus) Delile is a marine angiosperm, capable of forming wide meadows, complex three-dimensional structures.

The *Posidonia* meadow is a priority habitat (1120) listed in Annex I of the HD and is protected under the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species'). This habitat is defined as 'vulnerable' in the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats.

P. oceanica is also listed in the Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect *P. oceanica* and its formations.

Associated species

Associated communities can be distinguished in sessile species living on the leaves (called epiphytes), which are made by diatoms, bacteria, red and brown encrusting algae, erect algae (*Halimeda tuna*, *Flabellia petiolata*, *Peyssonnelia squamaria*, *Rhodomenia* sp.), bryozoans (with the exclusive *Electra posidonia*), hydrozoans (with the exclusive *Tridentata perpusilla*), and ascidians. Epiphytes on the rhizomes are mainly made by sponges (e.g., *Aplysina aerophoba*, *Spirastrella cunctatrix*, *Chondrilla nucula*, *Ircinia variabilis*, and *Sarcotragus foetidus*), ascidians, foraminifera, and bryozoans. The vagile species capable of moving within the meadow are molluscs, crustaceans, polychaetes, echinoderms, and fish species. Herbivores are 70% of the total animal species living within the meadows. Among these, the most abundant are echinoderms, especially *Paracentrotus lividus*, which feed both on epiphytes and the plant material of *P. oceanica*.

The infauna community is dominated by polychaetes and a few molluscs and crustaceans. Among the molluscs, the typical inhabitant of the meadows is *Pinna nobilis*, the largest bivalve in the Mediterranean, which is also an endemic species listed in Annex II of the HD and is considered 'critically endangered' by the IUCN Red List, as it is highly threatened by illegal fishing, pollution, and disease.

Numerous fish species (i.e., *Hippocampus* spp., *Symphodus* spp., *Coris julis*, *Chromis chromes*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Scorpaena porcus*) find in the meadow a spawning and nursery area and a temporary or permanent habitat, showing high variability in specific abundance due to recruitment and migration over the year. In the shallow and sheltered meadows, there is a great abundance of the herbivore *Sarpa salpa*, which represents 40%-70% of the summer fish fauna. This habitat may host other legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, e.g., the grouper *Epinephelus marginatus* ('endangered' by the IUCN), the sea-horse *Hippocampus guttulatus* ('near threatened' by the IUCN), *H. hippocampus* (Annex II SPA/BD Protocol), *Asterina pancerii* (Annex II SPA/BD Protocol), *Ophidiaster ophidianus* (Annex II SPA/BD Protocol), *Sciaena umbra* (Annex III SPA/BD Protocol), and occasionally the slipper lobster *Scyllarides latus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

During the 20th century, *P. oceanica* meadows have undergone a considerable regression. This regression, which may affect both the lower and the upper limit of the meadows, starts with a decrease of the density of the foliage bundles and the increase (or the new formation) of empty areas between mattes. Given their very slow growth rate, destruction of meadows is often irreversible on a human life scale. Destruction is due to numerous factors, the majority of which are of anthropic origin. The main threats are linked to coastal development (causing the decrease in the water transparency, the alteration of the sedimentary regime, direct destruction, pollution), boating (anchoring), fishing activities, and global warming. Another potential threat is linked to the competition with the two non-indigenous invasive species *Caulerpa taxifolia* and *Caulerpa cylindracea*, which have been shown to substitute the seagrass in degraded environments, leading to an ecosystem phase-shift.

Due to its high sensitivity to any environmental alteration, *P. oceanica* is commonly used as an excellent indicator of the overall environmental quality. *P. oceanica* is also considered as an element of biological quality within the EU Directives on water and marine quality assessment, namely the WFD and the MSFD.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist or are still subject to various research activities. With regard to passive restoration activities, it is necessary to ensure that the following activities are prohibited in the presence of this habitat:

- Trawling and other bottom-contact fishing gear.
- Free anchoring.
- Anthropogenic discharges, even if only of freshwater.
- Beach nourishment activities that are not properly designed to prevent adverse effects on the meadow.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

De Los Santos, C. B., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nature Communications* 10, 3356.

Deidun, A, Azzopardi, F, Marrone, A, Massa-Gallucci, A, Cutajar, K, Hayden, B., 2024. Assessing the contribution of *Posidonia oceanica* to Mediterranean secondary production through stable isotope analysis. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(12): 2197.

De Battisti, D., Balestri, E., Pardi G., Menicagli V., Lardicci, C., 2021. Substrate type influences the structure of epiphyte communities and the growth of *Posidonia oceanica* seedlings. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12.

Escandell-Westcott, A., Riera, R., Hernández-Muñoz, N., 2023. *Posidonia oceanica* restoration review: Factors affecting seedlings. *Journal of Sea Research*, 191,102337.

Evcen, A., & Çınar, M. E., 2017. Sponge species associated with *Posidonia oceanica* meadows along the coast of the Aegean Sea (Turkey). In: Proceedings of the 10th World Sponge Conference.

Holzknrecht, M., Albano, P.G., 2022. The molluscan assemblage of a pristine *Posidonia oceanica* meadow in the eastern Mediterranean. *Marine Biodiversity* 52, 59.

Montefalcone, M., 2009. Ecosystem health assessment using the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a review. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 595-604.

Montefalcone, M., Morri, C., Peirano, A., et al., 2007. Substitution and phase shift in *Posidonia oceanica* meadows of NW Mediterranean Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 75 (1), 63-71.

Montefalcone, M., Vacchi, M., Carbone, C., Cabella, R., Schiaffino, C.F., Elter, F.M., Morri, C., Bianchi, C.N., Ferrari, M., 2016. Seagrass on the rocks: *Posidonia oceanica* settled on shallow-water hard substrata withstands wave stress beyond predictions. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 180: 114–122

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Vacchi, M., De Falco, G., Simeone, S., et al., 2017. Biogeomorphology of the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 42, 42-54.

Vassallo, P., Paoli, C., Rovere, A., et al., 2013. The value of the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a natural capital assessment. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 75, 157-167.

Group 1

MB2521. Ecomorphosis of striped *Posidonia oceanica* meadows

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB2521](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef⁶

[HD](#): <1120, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB2.545

General description

Posidonia oceanica is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms characteristic “meadows” between the surface down to a depth of about 40-45m. The plant structure is composed of creeping or erect stems (rhizomes) that are usually buried in the sediment. Creeping rhizomes are called plagiotropic and erect rhizomes orthotropic. The rhizomes end in groups of 4-8 leaves (shoots) that are 8-11mm wide and 20-80cm long although the length may reach 160cm. *P. oceanica* flowers in the autumn (September-November). Flowers are hermaphrodite. *P. oceanica* rhizomes grow in height, even in the absence of sedimentation. To resist being buried, they are capable of speeding up their growth. The “matte” is the whole mass composed of rhizomes, sheaths, roots and the sediment that fills the interstices. The rhizomes, sheaths and roots are not very putrescible and are conserved within the “matte” for several centuries or even thousands of years. Its vertical growth can reach 1 meter a century (0.4cm to 1cm per year). The ecomorphosis of striped *P. oceanica* meadows consists of long, narrow meadow ribbons, which are several dozen meters long and alternated with channels of “dead matte” or bare sand, sometimes occupied by *Cymodocea nodosa* and/or *Caulerpa prolifera* settlements. Each meadow strip shifts, parallel to itself, against the dominant current, at an average speed of 10cm/year. The *P. oceanica* striped meadows develop in shallow areas (less than 5m in depth).

P. oceanica meadows represent a Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot, host spawning and nursery grounds, and play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, nutrient recycling, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability, mitigation of climate change (through the storage of large amounts of carbon within the matte).

Characteristic species

The habitat-forming species is *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) Delile, a marine angiosperm, forming a complex three-dimensional structure. The meadow strips are often separated by stretches of dead matte colonised by a mixed sea bottom composed of *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera noltii* and/or *Caulerpa prolifera*.

Posidonia meadows are a priority habitat (1120) in Annex I of the HD and are protected under the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, ‘Strictly protected flora species’). Moreover, this habitat is defined as ‘vulnerable’ by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats. *P. oceanica* is also listed in Annex II “List of endangered or threatened species” to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and

⁶ Even if biogenic, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows do not form “reefs” *sensu* Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), as they clearly relate to rocky bottoms and their biogenic assemblages. Meadows are widely considered the climax of well calibrated fine sands bottoms, even if *P. oceanica* is able to anchor, settle and grow also on rocky substrata.

management activities to be undertaken to protect *P. oceanica* and its formations.

Associated species

Associated communities can be distinguished in sessile species living on the leaves (called epiphytes), which are made by diatoms, bacteria, red and brown encrusting algae, erect algae (*Halimeda tuna*, *Flabellia petiolata*, *Peyssonnelia squamaria*, *Rhodomenia* sp.), bryozoans (with the exclusive *Electra posidonia*), hydrozoans (with the exclusive *Tridentata perpusilla*), and ascidians. Epiphytes on the rhizomes are mainly made by sponges, ascidians, foraminifera, and bryozoans. The vagile species capable of moving within the meadow are molluscs, crustaceans, polychaetes, echinoderms, and fish. Herbivores are 70% of the total animal species found living within the meadows. Among these, the most abundant are echinoderms, especially *Paracentrotus lividus*, which feed both on epiphytes and the plant material of *P. oceanica*.

The infauna community is dominated by polychaetes and a few molluscs and crustaceans. The channel's walls between the ribbons are a highly suitable sub-habitat for *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean. In this sub-habitat *P. nobilis* can attain density levels that are much higher than those observed within the extended meadow. *P. nobilis* is considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN, as it is highly threatened by illegal fishing, pollution, and disease.

Numerous fish species of commercial interest find in the meadow a spawning and nursery area and a temporary or permanent habitat, showing high variability in specific abundance due to recruitment and migration over the year. In the shallow and sheltered meadows, there is a great abundance of the herbivore *Sarpa salpa*, which represents 40%-70% of the summer fish fauna. This habitat may host other legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, such as the grouper *Epinephelus marginatus* ('endangered' by the IUCN), the sea-horse *Hippocampus guttulatus* ('near threatened' by the IUCN) and, occasionally, the slipper lobster *Scyllarides latus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

During the 20th century, *P. oceanica* meadows have undergone a considerable regression. This regression, which affects both the lower and the upper limit of the meadows, starts with a decrease of the density of the foliage bundles and the increase (or the new formation) of empty areas between mattes. Given their very slow growth rate, destruction of meadows is often irreversible on a human life scale. Destruction is caused by numerous factors, the majority of which are of anthropic origin. The main threats are linked to coastal development (causing the decrease in the water transparency, the alteration of the sedimentary regime, direct destruction, pollution), boating (anchoring), fishing activities, and global warming. Another potential threat is linked to the competition with the two non-indigenous invasive species *Caulerpa taxifolia* and *Caulerpa cylindracea*, which have been shown to substitute the seagrass in degraded environments leading to an ecosystem phase-shift.

Due to its high sensitivity to any environmental alteration, *P. oceanica* is commonly used as an excellent indicator of the overall environmental quality. *P. oceanica* is defined as biological quality element also in the WFD and the MSFD.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist or are still subject to various research activities. With regard to passive restoration activities, it is necessary to ensure that the following activities are prohibited in the presence of this habitat:

- Trawling and other bottom-contact fishing gear.
- Free anchoring.
- Anthropogenic discharges, even if only of freshwater.
- Beach nourishment activities that are not properly designed to prevent adverse effects on the meadow.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

Coppa, S., Quattrocchi, G., Cucco, A., et al., 2019. Self-organisation in striped seagrass meadows affects the distributional pattern of the sessile bivalve *Pinna nobilis*. *Scientific Reports* 9, 7220.

De Los Santos, C. B., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nature Communications* 10, 3356.

Deidun, A, Azzopardi, F, Marrone, A, Massa-Gallucci, A, Cutajar, K, Hayden, B., 2024. Assessing the contribution of *Posidonia oceanica* to Mediterranean secondary production through stable isotope analysis. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(12):2197.

De Battisti, D., Balestri, E., Pardi G., Menicagli V., Lardicci, C., 2021. Substrate type influences the structure of epiphyte communities and the growth of *Posidonia oceanica* seedlings. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12.

Escandell-Westcott, A., Riera, R., Hernández-Muñoz, N., 2023. *Posidonia oceanica* restoration review: Factors affecting seedlings. *Journal of Sea Research*, 191,102337.

Evcen, A., & Çınar, M. E., 2017. Sponge species associated with *Posidonia oceanica* meadows along the coast of the Aegean Sea (Turkey). In: *Proceedings of the 10th World Sponge Conference*.

Holzknrecht, M., Albano, P.G., 2022. The molluscan assemblage of a pristine *Posidonia oceanica* meadow in the eastern Mediterranean. *Marine Biodiversity* 52, 59. Montefalcone, M., 2009. Ecosystem health assessment

using the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a review. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 595-604.

Montefalcone, M., Morri, C., Peirano, A., et al., 2007. Substitution and phaseshift in *Posidonia oceanica* meadows of NW Mediterranean Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 75 (1), 63-71.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Vacchi, M., De Falco, G., Simeone, S., et al., 2017. Biogeomorphology of the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 42, 42-54.

Vassallo, P., Paoli, C., Rovere, A., et al., 2013. The value of the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a natural capital assessment. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 75, 157-167.

Group 1

MB2522. Ecomorphosis of "barrier-reef" *Posidonia oceanica* meadows

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB2522](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef⁷

[HD](#): <1120, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB2.545

General description

Posidonia oceanica is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms characteristic "meadows" between the surface down to a depth of about 40-45m, which are considered the characteristic climax community of the infralittoral soft bottoms and a typical biogenic habitat by the EUNIS classification.

P. oceanica is made of creeping or erect stems usually buried in the sediment. Creeping rhizomes are called plagiotropic and erect rhizomes orthotropic. The rhizomes end in groups of 4-8 leaves (shoots) that are 8-11mm wide and 20-80cm long. The length may reach 156 cm. *P. oceanica* flowers in the autumn (September - November). Flowers are hermaphrodite. *P. oceanica* rhizomes grow in height, even in the absence of sedimentation. To resist being buried, they are capable of speeding up their growth. The "matte" is the whole mass composed of rhizomes, sheaths, roots and the sediment that fills the interstices. For a general description of *P. oceanica* biology and ecology, please refer to the group 4 habitat MB252 "Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*".

The ecomorphosis of "barrier-reef" *P. oceanica* meadows develops in calm conditions and in relatively shallow waters near the shore of sheltered bays, where the vertical growth of the rhizomes leads to a slow rise of the matte that enables the meadow to reach the surface (also coined with the term fringe reef). This tends to occur in a pattern parallel to the coastline, leaving a sheltered area between the shore and the *Posidonia* barrier-reef, thereby creating a back-reef area of shallow water where the sediment settles as in lagoon-like conditions. At barrier reef level, which can be up to several meters wide, the leaves emerge and spread out on the surface of the water, particularly in spring and summer. The reef extends in a gentle slope out to sea, where it constitutes a meadow with a continuous base. The classic form of these reefs, with their front extending parallel to the shore, is the most widespread; however, more extensive structures (reef-like platforms) have been observed in Tunisia, Libya, Sicily and Corsica, and many other reef typologies have been suggested.

Between the emerging front of the reef and the coast, conditions may become unfavourable (due to wide variations in salinity and temperature), causing the meadow's death, resulting in a 'lagoon'-type" condition separated from the open sea by the presence of the 'barrier reef'. This sheltered area is usually occupied by small magnoliophytes (i.e., *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Zostera noltii*), which develop on the *Posidonia* dead matte.

P. oceanica meadows represent a Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot, host spawning and nursery grounds, and play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, nutrient recycling, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline

⁷ Even if biogenic, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows do not form "reefs" *sensu* Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), as they clearly relate to rocky bottoms and their biogenic assemblages. Meadows are widely considered the climax of well calibrated fine sand bottoms, even if *P. oceanica* is able to anchor, settle and grow also on rocky substrata.

stability, mitigation of climate change (through the storage of large amounts of carbon within the mat).

Characteristic species

The habitat-forming species is *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) Delile, a marine angiosperm, forming a complex three-dimensional structure. Meadows are defined as priority habitat in Annex I of the HD and are protected under the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species').

Associated species

The associated communities are the same as those associated to the habitats *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, and can be distinguished in sessile species living on the leaves (called epiphytes), which are made by diatoms, bacteria, red and brown encrusting algae, erect algae (*Halimeda tuna*, *Flabellia petiolata*, *Peyssonnelia squamaria*, *Rhodomenia* sp.), bryozoans (with the exclusive *Electra posidonia*), hydrozoans (with the exclusive *Tridentata perpusilla*), and ascidians. Epiphytes on the rhizomes are mainly made by sponges, ascidians, foraminifera, and bryozoans. The vagile species capable of moving within the meadow are molluscs, crustaceans, polychaetes, echinoderms, and fish. Herbivores are 70% of the total animal species living within the meadows. Among these, the most abundant are echinoderms, especially *Paracentrotus lividus*, which feed both on epiphytes and the plant material of *P. oceanica*.

The infauna community is dominated by polychaetes and a few molluscs and crustaceans. Among the molluscs, the typical inhabitant of the meadows is *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean, which is considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN, as it is highly threatened by illegal fishing, pollution, and disease.

Numerous fish species of commercial interest find in the meadow a spawning and nursery area and a temporary or permanent habitat, showing high variability in specific abundance due to recruitment and migration over the year. In the shallow and sheltered meadows there is a great abundance of the herbivore *Sarpa salpa*, which represents 40%-70% of the summer fish fauna. This habitat may host other legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, such as the grouper *Epinephelus marginatus* ('endangered' by the IUCN), the sea-horse *Hippocampus guttulatus* ('near threatened' by the IUCN), and, occasionally, the slipper lobster *Scyllarides latus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

During the 20th century, *P. oceanica* meadows have undergone a considerable regression. This regression, which affects both the lower and the upper limit of the meadows, starts with a decrease of the density of the foliage bundles and the increase (or the new formation) of empty areas between mattes. Given their very slow growth rate, destruction of meadows is often irreversible on a human life scale. Destruction is caused by numerous factors, the majority of which are of anthropic origin. The main threats are linked to coastal development (causing the decrease in the water transparency, the alteration of the sedimentary regime, direct destruction, pollution), boating (anchoring), fishing activities, and global warming. Another potential threat is

linked to the competition with the two non-indigenous invasive species *Caulerpa taxifolia* and *Caulerpa cylindracea*, which have been shown to substitute the seagrass in degraded environments leading to an ecosystem phase-shift.

Due to its high sensitivity to any environmental alterations, *P. oceanica* is commonly used as an excellent indicator of the overall environmental quality. *P. oceanica* is defined as biological quality element also in the WFD and the MSFD.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist or are still subject to various research activities. With regard to passive restoration activities, it is necessary to ensure that the following activities are prohibited in the presence of this habitat:

- Trawling and other bottom-contact fishing gear.
- Free anchoring.
- Anthropogenic discharges, even if only of freshwater.
- Beach nourishment activities that are not properly designed to prevent adverse effects on the meadow.

Bibliographic sources

Bonhomme, D., Boudouresque, C. F., Astruch, P., et al., 2015. Typology of the reef formations of the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*, and the discovery of extensive reefs in the Gulf of Hyères (Provence, Mediterranean). *Scientific Report Port-Cros National Park* 29: 41-73.

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

Coppa, S., Quattrocchi, G., Cucco, A., et al., 2019. Self-organisation in striped seagrass meadows affects the distributional pattern of the sessile bivalve *Pinna nobilis*. *Scientific Reports* 9, 7220.

De Los Santos, C. B., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nature Communications* 10, 3356.

Deidun, A, Azzopardi, F, Marrone, A, Massa-Gallucci, A, Cutajar, K, Hayden, B., 2024. Assessing the contribution of *Posidonia oceanica* to Mediterranean secondary production through stable isotope analysis. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(12):2197.

Escandell-Westcott, A., Riera, R., Hernández-Muñoz, N., 2023. *Posidonia oceanica* restoration review: Factors affecting seedlings. *Journal of Sea Research*, 191,102337.

Hachani, M. A., Ziadi, B., Langar, H., et al., 2016. The mapping of the *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile barrier reef meadow in the southeastern Gulf of Tunis (Tunisia). *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 121: 358-364.

Montefalcone, M., 2009. Ecosystem health assessment using the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a review. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 595-604. Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Pergent, G., Djellouli, A., Hamza, A. A., et al., 2007. Structure of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows in the vicinity of Ain Al-Ghazala lagoon (Libya): the "macroatoll" ecomorphosis. in: Pergent-Martini, C., El Asmi, S., Le Ravallec, C. (eds), *Proc. third Medit. Symposium on Marine Vegetation*, Marseille, 27-29 March 2007. RAC/SPA Tunis, 135-140.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Vacchi, M., De Falco, G., Simeone, S., et al., 2017. Biogeomorphology of the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 42, 42-54.

Group 1

MB2523. Facies of dead "mattes" of *Posidonia oceanica* without much epiflora

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB2523](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef⁸

[HD](#): <1120, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention:
Sub-habitat of MB2.54,
MB2.547 (partial inclusion)

General description

Posidonia oceanica is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms characteristic "meadows" between the surface down to a depth of about 40-45m, which are considered the characteristic climax community of the infralittoral soft bottoms and a typical biogenic habitat by the EUNIS classification. The plant structure is composed of creeping or erect stems (rhizomes) that are usually buried in the sediment. Creeping rhizomes are called plagiotropic and erect rhizomes orthotropic. The rhizomes end in groups of 4-8 leaves (shoots) that are 8-11mm wide and 20-80cm long. *P. oceanica* rhizomes grow in height, even in the absence of sedimentation and the "matte" is the whole mass composed of rhizomes, sheaths, roots and the sediment that fills the interstices.

This facies is characterised by the sole presence of dead *P. oceanica* "mattes", i.e., the complete death of the *Posidonia* plant, the past presence of which is evidenced by the remnants of the roots, which are imperishable. Dead matte may become a favourable substrate for the instalment of associated species (i.e., *Cymodocea nodosa* and/or by the green algae belonging to the genus *Caulerpa*, either native, *C. prolifera*, or non-indigenous and invasive *C. taxifolia* and *C. cylindracea*), which have a comparatively higher tolerance to altered environmental conditions and a faster growth, and which can spread and establish in a degraded meadow within a few years. For a general description of *P. oceanica* biology and ecology, please refer to the Group 4 habitat MB252 "Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*".

Characteristic species

The original habitat-forming species of this habitat is *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) Delile, a marine angiosperm. However, this habitat bears witness to the death of the species.

Living *Posidonia oceanica* meadows are defined as priority habitat in Annex I of the HD and are protected under the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species'). Moreover, *P. oceanica* is listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, set priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect *P. oceanica* and its formations. This habitat is defined as 'vulnerable' by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats.

⁸ Even if biogenic, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows do not form "reefs" *sensu* Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), as they clearly relate to rocky bottoms and their biogenic assemblages. Meadows are widely considered the climax of well calibrated fine sand bottoms, even if *P. oceanica* is able to anchor, settle and grow also on rocky substrata.

Associated species

Associated communities are epiphytes on the rhizomes (mainly sponges, ascidians, foraminifera and bryozoans), vagile species (crustaceans, polychaetes, echinoderms, and fishes), and an infaunal community dominated by polychaetes, molluscs and crustaceans. Among the molluscs, the typical inhabitant is *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean, which is considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN, as it is highly threatened by illegal fishing, pollution, and disease.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

During the 20th century, *P. oceanica* meadows have undergone a considerable regression. This regression, which affects both the lower and the upper limit of the meadows, starts with a decrease of the density of the foliage bundles and the increase (or the new formation) of empty areas between mattes. Given their very slow growth rate, destruction of meadows is often irreversible on a human life scale. Destruction is caused by numerous factors, the majority of which are of anthropic origin. The main threats are linked to coastal development (causing the decrease in the water transparency, the alteration of the sedimentary regime, direct destruction, pollution), boating (anchoring), fishing activities, and global warming. Another potential threat is linked to the competition with the two non-indigenous invasive species *Caulerpa taxifolia* and *Caulerpa cylindracea*, which have been shown to substitute the seagrass in degraded environments leading to an ecosystem phase-shift.

Due to its high sensitivity to any environmental alterations, *P. oceanica* is commonly used as an excellent indicator of the overall environmental quality. *P. oceanica* is defined as biological quality element also in the WFD and the MSFD.

Best practices in nature restoration

The importance of this habitat for restoration is linked to the fact that it can be chosen for restoration initiatives, but only after ensuring the removal of the causes that led to the death of the former *Posidonia* meadow, the original presence of which is evidenced by the matte, i.e., the remains of the *Posidonia* roots, which are imperishable.

Bibliographic sources

Apostolaki, E.T., Caviglia L., Santinelli, V., Cundy, A.B., Tramati C.D., Mazzola, A., Vizzini S., 2022. The Importance of Dead Seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*) Matte as a Biogeochemical Sink. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9.

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

De Los Santos, C. B., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nature Communications* 10, 3356.

Deidun, A, Azzopardi, F, Marrone, A, Massa-Gallucci, A, Cutajar, K, Hayden, B., 2024. Assessing the contribution of *Posidonia oceanica* to Mediterranean secondary production through stable isotope analysis. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(12):2197.

Escandell-Westcott, A., Riera, R., Hernández-Muñoz, N., 2023. *Posidonia oceanica* restoration review: Factors affecting seedlings. *Journal of Sea Research*, 191,102337.

Montefalcone, M., 2009. Ecosystem health assessment using the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a review. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 595-604.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Pergent, G., Djellouli, A., Hamza, A.A., et al., 2007. Structure of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows in the vicinity of Ain Al-Ghazala lagoon (Libya): the “macroatoll” ecomorphosis. in Pergent-Martini, C., El Asmi, S., Le Ravallec, C. (eds), Proc third Medit Symposium on Marine Vegetation, Marseille, 27-29 March 2007. RAC/SPA Tunis: 135-140.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Vacchi, M., De Falco, G., Simeone, S., et al., 2017. Biogeomorphology of the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 42, 42-54.

Group 1

MB2524. Association with *Caulerpa prolifera* on *Posidonia* beds

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB2524](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef⁹

[HD](#): <1120, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB2.546, MB2.547 (partial inclusion)

General description

This habitat is characterised by the presence of the green alga *Caulerpa prolifera* in association within the *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *P. oceanica* is a seagrass endemic to the Mediterranean. It forms characteristic “meadows” between the surface down to a depth of about 40–45m, which are considered the characteristic climax community of the infralittoral soft bottoms and a typical biogenic habitat according to the EUNIS classification. For the general description of *P. oceanica* biology and ecology, please refer to the Group 4 habitat MB252 “Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*”.

This association may occur under natural conditions (i.e., on soft sediments in sheltered waters or within bays, where some siltation is present) or where *P. oceanica* meadows are degraded due to high levels of human pressure and show reduced density and coverage. The associated species, *C. prolifera*, but also the non-indigenous invasive species *C. taxifolia* and *C. cylindracea*, colonize the sediment and the unvegetated *matte* occurring between the *P. oceanica* shoots. Due to *Caulerpa*'s comparatively higher tolerance to altered environmental conditions and faster growth, dead *matte* may later become a favourable substrate for its species' settlement and spreading within a few years.

This association can potentially occur in all coastal areas of the Mediterranean Sea where *P. oceanica* meadows are present, and where the environmental conditions are suitable for the colonisation by the associated species. The majority of these associations have been described in highly anthropised coastal areas.

Seagrass meadows and macroalgal assemblages play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability, mitigation of climate change (imprisoning huge amounts of carbon within the *matte*).

Characteristic species

The habitat-forming species is *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) Delile, a marine angiosperm, together with the green algae *Caulerpa prolifera*, easily identifiable because it displays a typical morphology and shape of the thallus.

P. oceanica meadows are defined as a priority habitat in Annex I of the HD and are protected under the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, ‘Strictly protected flora species’). This habitat is defined as ‘vulnerable’ by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats. *P. oceanica* is listed in Annex II “List of endangered or threatened species” to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting

⁹ Even if biogenic, *Posidonia oceanica* meadows do not form “reefs” *sensu* Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), as they clearly relate to rocky bottoms and their biogenic assemblages. Meadows are widely considered the climax of well calibrated fine sand bottoms, even if *P. oceanica* is able to anchor, settle and grow also on rocky substrata.

Parties to the Barcelona Convention, set priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect *P. oceanica* and its formations.

Associated species

The associated communities are the same as those associated to the habitats *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. Epiphytes on leaves and rhizomes are mainly made by diatoms, sponges, ascidians, foraminifera and bryozoans. The vagile species capable of moving within the meadow are molluscs, crustaceans, polychaetes, echinoderms, and fish. Herbivores are 70% of the total animal species living within the meadows. Among these, the most abundant are echinoderms, especially *Paracentrotus lividus*, which feed both on epiphytes and the plant material of *P. oceanica*.

The infauna community is dominated by polychaetes and a few molluscs and crustaceans. Among the molluscs, the typical inhabitant of the meadows is *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean, which is considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN, as it is highly threatened by illegal fishing, pollution, and disease

The communities associated with *Caulerpa* spp. are diverse and dominated by polychaetes, gastropods, and amphipods, which change seasonally following the algae vegetative cycle.

This habitat may host other legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, such as the grouper *Epinephelus marginatus* ('endangered' by the IUCN), the sea-horse *Hippocampus guttulatus* ('near threatened' by the IUCN), and, occasionally, the slipper lobster *Scyllarides latus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to this habitat are linked to coastal development (direct destruction, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, increased turbidity, pollution), pleasure boating (anchoring), living resources exploitation (trawling, fish farming), and global warming. All the associated species have high spreading rates and show higher tolerance to altered environmental conditions than *P. oceanica*, and are, thus, prone to replace regressed *P. oceanica* meadows under a human pressure regime. This replacement is not intended as the direct consequence of competition between species, but rather as a process at the ecosystem level: the biota associated with *C. nodosa* or with *Caulerpa* spp. is very different from the more diverse and exclusive one that is associated with meadows. The progressive change of the foundation species may lead to a complete substitution of assemblages within the same habitat, causing what is usually called an ecosystem phase-shift. Due to its high sensitivity to any environmental alterations, *P. oceanica* it is commonly used as an excellent indicator of the overall environmental quality.

P. oceanica is defined as biological quality element also in the WFD and the MSFD.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for *Posidonia oceanica* meadows exist or are still subject to various research activities. With regard to passive restoration

activities, it is necessary to ensure that the following activities are prohibited in the presence of this habitat:

- Trawling and other bottom-contact fishing gear.
- Free anchoring.
- Anthropogenic discharges, even if only of freshwater.
- Beach nourishment activities that are not properly designed so as not to adversely affect the meadow.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

De Los Santos, C. B., Krause-Jensen, D., Alcoverro, T., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nature Communications* 10, 3356.

Montefalcone, M., 2009. Ecosystem health assessment using the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a review. *Ecological Indicators* 9, 595-604.

Montefalcone, M., Morri, C., Peirano, A., et al., 2007. Substitution and phaseshift in *Posidonia oceanica* meadows of NW Mediterranean Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 75 (1), 63-71.

Montefalcone, M., Albertelli, G., Morri, C., et al., 2010. Pattern of wide-scale substitution within *Posidonia oceanica* meadows of NW Mediterranean Sea: invaders are stronger than natives. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20, 507-515.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Resilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Vacchi, M., De Falco, G., Simeone, S., et al., 2017. Biogeomorphology of the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 42, 42-54.

Vassallo, P., Paoli, C., Rovere, A., et al., 2013. The value of the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a natural capital assessment. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 75, 157-167.

Group 1

MB5521. Association with *Cymodocea nodosa* on well sorted fine sands

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5521](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB5.521

General description

This association, characterised by the seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa*, is found on soft bottoms formed by well sorted fine sands, and can constitute a local facies with epiflora. Meadows develop at an average depth of 5m but may be found down to a depth of about 40m according to water transparency, because the light represents one of the main limiting factors. The conformation of *Cymodocea* meadows varies greatly throughout the year due to the marked seasonality of the conformation of this species, which almost completely loses its leaves in the winter months.

The association with *C. nodosa* can develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea where well sorted fine sands occur. Marine angiosperms play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability.

Characteristic species

This habitat is characterised by meadows made by *Cymodocea nodosa*, which is able to create shallow and sparse beds. These meadows have light green or greyish-green narrow leaves (up to 40cm long). The plants produce small rhizomes that are 1mm in diameter and grow on sands and mainly horizontally.

C. nodosa, together with *Zostera noltii* and *Z. marina*, are listed in Annex II “List of endangered or threatened species” to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, set priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect all seagrass meadows. *C. nodosa* and *Z. marina* are also protected within the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, ‘Strictly protected flora species’).

Associated species

The *Cymodocea nodosa* beds assemblages are composed of:

- Epibiotic species living on the leaf blade (called epiphytes), mainly red algae (Ceramiales and Corallinales), with a minor contribution of diatoms, cyanobacteria, hydrozoans, and ascidians.
- Benthic species, such as *Pinna nobilis*, which is the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean (listed in HD Annex II and classified as ‘critically endangered’ by the IUCN).
- Vagile associated species, mainly gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, polychaetes and fishes, including the seahorse *Hippocampus guttulatus* (listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol and in the CITES annex D, classified as ‘near threatened’ by the IUCN).

C. nodosa is often associated with *Posidonia oceanica* on fine sand, as well as with the alien seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* (in the southern sectors of the Mediterranean), and with photophilic algae such as the native *Caulerpa prolifera*. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Seagrass meadows are highly vulnerable, being directly affected by various human pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development (direct destruction, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, increased turbidity, pollution), pleasure boating (anchoring), living resources exploitation (trawling, fish farming), and global warming.

C. nodosa has a faster growth rate and a higher turnover compared to *P. oceanica*; thus, it is considered as a more tolerant species and able to resist the pressures met along the highly anthropised coastlines.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

Bussotti, S. and Guidetti, P., 1996. Preliminary data on the fish fauna associated to a *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers and *Zostera noltii* Hornem mixed meadow in the gulf of Olbia (Sardinia-Tyrrhenian Sea). *Mésogée* 55, 9-14.

Mabrouk, L., Ben Brahim, M., Jebara, A., et al., 2021. Comparison of epiphyte algal assemblages on the leaves of marine seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile, *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers, and the lessepsian *Halophila stipulacea* (Forssk) Aschers in Chebba (East of Tunisia). *Marine Ecology*, e12642.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Bianchi, C. N., 2011. Quantification of coastal ecosystem resilience. *Treatise on Estuarine and Coastal Science* 10 (3), 49-70.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal

Cymodocea habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Résilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Group 1

MB5534. Association with *Cymodocea nodosa* on superficial muddy sands in sheltered waters

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5534](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention:

MB5.52, MB5.521

General description

This association, characterised by the seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa* that develops large meadows with its typical epiflora, is present in sheltered waters. Meadows develop at an average depth of 5m but can be present at depths from as little as a few centimetres up to depths of about 40m depending on water transparency, as light represents one of the main limiting factors.

The conformation of *Cymodocea* meadows varies greatly throughout the year due to the marked seasonality of the conformation of this species, which almost completely loses its leaves in the winter months. The association with *C. nodosa* can develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea where soft sediments occur, in conditions in which the water is actively renewed and there is no desalination. *Cymodocea* meadows, just as other marine phanerogams, play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability.

Characteristic species

Meadows are composed of *Cymodocea nodosa*. *C. nodosa* creates shallow and sparse beds in open and less muddy environments. It has light green or greyish-green narrow leaves (up to 40cm long). The plant produces small rhizomes that are 1mm in diameter, and which grow mainly horizontally. Together with *Zostera noltii* and *Z. marina*, *C. nodosa* is listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect all seagrass meadows. *C. nodosa* and *Z. marina* are also protected within the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species').

Associated species

The *Cymodocea nodosa* beds assemblages are composed of:

- Epibiotic species living on the leaf blade (called epiphytes), which are made mainly by red algae (Ceramiales and Corallinales), with a minor contribution by diatoms, cyanobacteria, hydrozoans, and ascidians.
- Benthic species such as *Pinna nobilis*, which is the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean (listed in HD Annex II and classified as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN).
- Vagile associated species, mainly gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, polychaetes and fishes, including the seahorse *Hippocampus guttulatus* (listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol and in the CITES annex D, classified as 'near threatened' by the IUCN).

C. nodosa is often associated with *Posidonia oceanica* on fine sand, with the alien seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* (in the southern sectors of the Mediterranean), and with photophilic algae such as the native *Caulerpa prolifera*. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Cymodocea meadows, as well as other marine phanerogams, are highly vulnerable, being directly affected by various human pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development (direct destruction, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, increased turbidity, pollution), boating (anchoring), living resources exploitation (trawling, fish farming), and global warming.

C. nodosa has a faster growth rate and a higher turnover compared to *P. oceanica*; thus, it is considered as a more tolerant species and able to resist the pressures met along highly human-encroached coastlines.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

Bussotti, S. and Guidetti, P., 1996. Preliminary data on the fish fauna associated to a *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers and *Zostera noltei* Hornem mixed meadow in the gulf of Olbia (Sardinia-Tyrrhenian Sea). *Mésogée* 55, 9-14.

Mabrouk, L., Ben Brahim, M., Jebara, A., et al., 2021. Comparison of epiphyte algal assemblages on the leaves of marine seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile, *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers, and the lessepsian *Halophila stipulacea* (Forssk) Aschers in Chebba (East of Tunisia), *Marine Ecology*, e12642.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Bianchi, C. N., 2011. Quantification of coastal ecosystem resilience. *Treatise on Estuarine and Coastal Science* 10 (3), 49-70.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal

Cymodocea habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Résilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 1

MB5535. Association with *Zostera noltei* on superficial muddy sands in sheltered waters

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5535](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB5.52, MB5.521

General description

This association is characterised by the seagrass *Zostera noltei*, which develops beds on muddy sands in sheltered and cold waters, especially where there is an active deposit of fine matter. *Z. noltei* has a shallower distribution than other Mediterranean seagrasses and can tolerate various levels of salinity, as it is found on fine sand in the intertidal and the shallow subtidal habitats of bays, estuaries, and lagoons. As other seagrasses, it has very narrow leaves incised at the apex, which can be up to 40-60cm long and 0.7-1.7mm in width and contain air spaces that make it buoyant.

The association with the indigenous marine angiosperm, *Z. noltei*, can develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea where soft sediments occur. Marine angiosperms play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

Characteristic species

Meadows are made by *Zostera noltei*. *Z. noltei* and *Z. marina* are listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect all seagrass meadows.

Associated species

The epifauna of *Zostera noltei* is poor. The vagile associated species are gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, polychaetes, and fishes. It is often associated with *Posidonia oceanica* on fine sand, with the alien seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* (in the southern sectors of the Mediterranean), and with photophilic algae such as the native *Caulerpa prolifera*.

Legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol can be found in the associated assemblages, such as the seahorse *Hippocampus guttulatus* (considered as 'near threatened' by the IUCN) and *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean (considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Zostera meadows are highly vulnerable, being directly affected by various human pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development (direct destruction), boating (anchoring). Moreover, it is very sensitive to eutrophication, increased turbidity, and water pollution.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Bonhomme, P., et al., 2012. *Protection and conservation of Posidonia oceanica meadows*, RAC/SPA & RAMOGE publ., 202 pp.

Burgos, E., Montefalcone, M., Ferrari, M., et al., 2017. Ecosystem functions and economic wealth: trajectories of change in seagrass meadows. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 168, 1108-1119.

Bussotti, S. and Guidetti, P., 1996. Preliminary data on the fish fauna associated to a *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers and *Zostera noltei* Hornem mixed meadow in the gulf of Olbia (Sardinia-Tyrrhenian Sea). *Mésogée* 55, 9-14.

Mabrouk, L., Ben Brahim, M., Jebara, A., et al., 2021. Comparison of epiphyte algal assemblages on the leaves of marine seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile, *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers, and the lessepsian *Halophila stipulacea* (Forssk) Aschers in Chebba (East of Tunisia). *Marine Ecology*, e12642.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Bianchi, C. N., 2011. Quantification of coastal ecosystem resilience. *Treatise on Estuarine and Coastal Science* 10 (3), 49-70.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal *Cymodocea* habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Resilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Group 1

MB5541. Association with *Ruppia cirrhosa* and/or *Ruppia maritima* on sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5541](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral sand

[HD](#): #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB6.5, MB6.51, MB6.511

General description

This association is characterised by submerged beds of *Ruppia maritima* or *R. cirrhosa*. *Ruppia* spp. are phanerogams which live submerged on sandy or muddy bottoms within sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of sand flats, and coastal lagoons of the Mediterranean Sea. This genus is cosmopolitan, and both species are present throughout Europe and the Mediterranean. *R. maritima* is more frequent in temporary peripheral environments, in very shallow waters with low salinity. It is also present in permanent or semi-permanent environments and can withstand extreme conditions such as hypersaline environments. *R. cirrhosa* prefers depths of 0.5-1m where it can form extensive meadows.

Marine angiosperms play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

Characteristic species

Two species occur in the Mediterranean: *Ruppia cirrhosa* and *R. maritima*. These are cosmopolitan, salt-tolerant aquatic angiosperms that live submerged on muddy bottoms in the habitats of transitional waters. *R. maritima* has small leaves (30-40cm long and 0.4-0.7mm in width) with toothed edges at the apical part of the leaves. This species emits the leaf bundles directly from the rhizomes or from herbaceous stems that may reach over 1m in length. Leaves taper to 0.5-0.6mm at the apex with toothed edges at the apical part and numerous tannic cells to avoid grazing.

Associated species

The associated community is that of the euryhaline and eurythermal environments. Depending on salinity, *R. cirrhosa* may be complemented by *R. maritima*, *Stuckenia pectinata*, *Zostera noltii* and/or *Cymodocea nodosa*. *Zannichellia palustris*, *Chara* spp., and *Althenia filiformis* are accompanying plant species. The fauna usually has freshwater affinities, and is dominated by insects (Heteroptera, Odonata, Diptera). A rich infaunal community is found in the sediment colonised by aquatic angiosperms. When leaves emerge from the surface for long periods, they create a multidimensional substrate for macro and microalgae. The sessile species living on the leaf blades (epiphytes) are represented mainly by macro and microalgae, especially diatoms, cyanobacteria and macrofaunal organisms, such as hydrozoans, bryozoans, and ascidians. The associated vagile species are gastropods (i.e., the grazing gastropods *Bittium reticulatum* and *Potamopyrgus antipodarum*), crustaceans, polychaetes, and fishes (e.g., *Syngnathus acus*, *S. abaster*, *S. typhle*, *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, *Anguilla anguilla*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Ruppia spp. meadows are highly vulnerable to physical loss, abrasion, smothering, siltation rate changes, disturbances to the substratum, and are very sensitive to changes in water flows, salinity decrease, changes in suspended solids (water clarity) and pollution.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Mannino, A. M., and Sarà, G., 2006. The effect of *Ruppia cirrhosa* features on macroalgae and suspended matter in a Mediterranean shallow system. *Marine Ecology* 27, 350-360.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Resilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Sfriso, A., Buosi, A., Tomio, Y., et al., 2019. Aquatic angiosperm transplantation: a tool for environmental management and restoring in transitional water systems. *Water* 11 (10), 2135.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Verhoeven, J. T. A., 1980. The ecology of *Ruppia*-dominated communities in Western Europe. II. Synecological classification, structure and dynamics of the macroflora and macrofauna communities. *Aquatic Biology* 8, 1-85.

Viaroli, P., Bartoli, M., Giordani, G., et al., 2008. Community shifts, alternative stable states, biogeochemical controls and feedbacks in eutrophic coastal lagoons: a brief overview. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 18 (S1), S105-S117.

Group 1

MB5544. Association with *Zostera noltei* in euryhaline and eurythermal environment on sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5544](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB6.511

General description

This association is characterised by the seagrass *Zostera noltii*. It develops in the habitats of transitional water systems (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets, marshes, littoral ponds) of the infralittoral zone, on soft bottoms formed by sand, where the salinity is variable over the short or long term (daily to annual), and where also the temperature and all the other environmental parameters show extreme values. *Z. noltii* has a shallower distribution than other Mediterranean seagrasses and can tolerate various levels of salinity, being found on fine sand in the intertidal and the shallow subtidal habitats of bays, estuaries, and lagoons, where it develops monospecific populations. As like other seagrasses, it has very narrow leaves incised at the apex, which can be up to 40-60cm long and 0.7-1.7mm width and contain air spaces that make it buoyant.

This association with indigenous marine angiosperms can develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea where extensive transitional water systems occur. Beds develop in shallow waters, between the surface down to a few meters in depth, but they can support certain periods of emersion, so that the association with marine angiosperms or other halophytes is very common also in the lower mediolittoral zone. Marine angiosperms play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability.

Characteristic species

Meadows are created by *Zostera noltii*. *Z. noltii* and *Z. marina* are listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the PA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect all seagrass meadows. *Z. marina* is also protected within the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species').

Associated species

The epifauna of *Zostera noltii* is poor, but the fauna is rich and is made up of brackish water species of the biocenosis to which it belongs with some addition of marine water species. The vagile associated species are gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, and polychaetes. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

Legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol can be found in the associated assemblages, such as the seahorse *Hippocampus guttulatus* (considered as 'near threatened' by the IUCN) and *Pinna nobilis*,

the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean (considered as ‘critically endangered’ by the IUCN).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Zostera meadows are highly vulnerable, being directly affected by various human pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development (direct destruction), boating (anchoring). It is also very sensitive to eutrophication, increased turbidity, and water pollution.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bussotti, S. and Guidetti, P., 1996. Preliminary data on the fish fauna associated to a *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers and *Zostera noltei* Hornem mixed meadow in the gulf of Olbia (Sardinia-Tyrrhenian Sea). *Mésogée* 55, 9-14.

Mabrouk, L., Ben Brahim, M., Jebara, A., et al., 2021. Comparison of epiphyte algal assemblages on the leaves of marine seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile, *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers, and the lessepsian *Halophila stipulacea* (Forssk) Aschers in Chebba (East of Tunisia). *Marine Ecology*, e12642.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Bianchi, C. N., 2011. Quantification of coastal ecosystem resilience. *Treatise on Estuarine and Coastal Science* 10 (3), 49-70.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal *Cymodocea* habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Resilience et contribution à l’atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Sfriso, A., Buosi, A., Tomio Y., et al., 2019. Aquatic angiosperm transplantation: a tool for environmental management and restoring in transitional water systems. *Water* 11 (10), 2135.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Group 1

MB5545. Association with *Zostera marina* in euryhaline and eurythermal environment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB5545](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral sand

[HD](#): #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB6.511

General description

This association is characterised by the seagrass *Zostera marina* and develops in the habitats of transitional water systems (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets) of the infralittoral zone, on soft bottoms formed by mud (clay and silt), where the salinity is low, and where also the temperature and all the other environmental parameters show extreme values. *Z. marina* has a shallow distribution and dislikes high salinity, being highly sensitive to levels over 35‰. As like other seagrasses, it has very narrow leaves, slightly curved, 5-7mm large, >1m high and featuring rounded apexes with a cavity in the middle due to the central vein.

This association with indigenous marine angiosperms can develop across the whole Mediterranean Sea where extensive transitional water systems occur. Beds develop in shallow waters, between the surface down to a few meters in depth, but they can support certain periods of emersion, so that the association with marine angiosperms or other halophytes is very common also in the lower mediolittoral zone. Marine angiosperms play an essential ecological role in terms of primary production (partly exported to other ecosystems), water oxygenation, associated biodiversity, sedimentary balance, bottom and shoreline stability.

Characteristic species

Meadows are made by *Zostera marina*. *Z. marina* can be considered a relict species, as its distribution is extremely localised in the Mediterranean and Black Seas and is limited to coastal areas with freshwater inflows. Today, the species distribution is in strong regression. In Italy, it is reported in the Gulf of Trieste and the Venetian lagoon.

Z. noltii and *Z. marina* are listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol. The Action Plan for the Conservation of Marine Vegetation in the Mediterranean, adopted in 1999 by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, sets priorities and management activities to be undertaken to protect all seagrass meadows. *Z. marina* is also protected within the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment of Europe (Annex I, 'Strictly protected flora species').

Associated species

The epifauna of *Zostera marina* is poor, but the fauna is rich and is made up of brackish water species of the biocenosis to which it belongs with some addition of marine water species. The vagile associated species are gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, and polychaetes. Seagrass meadows are also an important nursery ground for juvenile fishes.

The assemblage can host legally protected species listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, such as the seahorse *Hippocampus guttulatus* (considered as 'near threatened' by the IUCN) and *Pinna nobilis*, the largest endemic bivalve in the Mediterranean (considered as 'critically endangered' by the IUCN).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Zostera meadows are highly vulnerable, being directly affected by various human pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development (direct destruction), boating (anchoring). It is also very sensitive to eutrophication, increased turbidity and salinity, and water pollution.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Mabrouk, L., Ben Brahim, M., Jebara, A., et al., 2021. Comparison of epiphyte algal assemblages on the leaves of marine seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile, *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Aschers, and the lessepsian *Halophila stipulacea* (Forssk) Aschers in Chebba (East of Tunisia), *Marine Ecology*, e12642.

Molinier, R. and Picard, J., 1952. Recherches sur les herbiers de phanérogames marines du littoral méditerranéen français. *Annales Institut Océanographique*, Paris 27 (3), 157-234.

Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Bianchi, C. N., 2011. Quantification of coastal ecosystem resilience. *Treatise on Estuarine and Coastal Science* 10 (3), 49-70.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal *Cymodocea* habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Méditerranée. Resilience et contribution à l'atténuation des changements climatiques, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Pergent, G., Hocein, B., Bianchi, C. N., et al., 2014. Climate change and Mediterranean seagrass meadows: a synopsis for environmental managers. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15 (2), 462-473.

Sfriso, A., Buosi, A., Tomio Y., et al., 2019. Aquatic angiosperm transplantation: a tool for environmental management and restoring in transitional water systems. *Water* 11 (10), 2135.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Telesca, L., Belluscio, A., Criscoli, A., et al., 2015. Seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*) distribution and trajectories of change. *Scientific Reports* 5, 12505.

UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA, 1999. Plan d'action relatif à la conservation de la végétation marine de Méditerranée, RAC/SPA publ., Tunis, 47 pp.

Group 2: Macroalgal forests

Figure 02-01, *Chorda filum* off the Scottish Coast

Source: Sea lace *Chorda filum* with other seaweeds and sponges in the shallow margins of Taynish Rapids, Loch Sween, NatureScot, © Ben James. 2021

Group 2

MA123. Seaweed communities on full salinity Atlantic littoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA123](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1160, <1170

European Red List:

>NEAA1.45, >NEAA1.31,

>NEAA1.15, >NEAA1.12,

>NEAA1.25

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA1231](#), [MA1233](#),

[MA1234](#), [MA1235](#), [MA1236](#),

[MA1237](#), [MA1238](#), [MA1239](#),

[MA123A](#), [MA123B](#),

[MA123C](#), [MA123D](#),

[MA123E](#), [MA123F](#),

[MA123G](#), [MA123H](#)

DE:

>02.01.01.01.01

>02.01.01.01.03

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

IE:

=LR.LLR.F

>LR.LLR.F.Fserr.FS

>LR.LLR.F.Asc.FS

#LR.FLR.Eph, #LR.HLR.FR

>LR.MLR.BF.Fser.R

>LR.HLR.FR.Him

General description

This habitat type encompasses littoral rock habitats dominated by seaweeds. The seaweed community varies depending on the wave exposure and tidal currents. In areas of high energy, the physical stresses caused by wave action often results in dwarf forms of the individual seaweeds.

These are biotopes with a low species diversity and the relatively high number of species in the characterising species list are due to a variation in the species composition from site to site, not to high species richness on individual sites.

Characteristic species

Ascophyllum nodosum, *Bifurcaria bifurcata*, *Ceramium* sp., *Chondrus crispus*, *Corallina officinalis*, *Enteromorpha* spp., *Fucus distichus*, *F. spiralis* f. *nana*, *F. spiralis*, *F. vesiculosus*, *F. serratus*, *Halopteris scoparia*, *Himanthalia elongata*, *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mastocarpus stellatus*, *Osmundea pinnatifida*, *Palmaria palmata*, *Pelvetia canaliculata*, *Porphyra purpurea*.

Associated species

Asciidiella scabra, *Barnea candida*, *Cladophora rupestris*, *Clava multicornis*, *Carcinus maenas*, *Chondrus crispus*, *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Dynamena pumila*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Elminius modestus*, *Grantia compressa*, *Gelidium pusillum*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Hymeniacidon perleve*, *Lomentaria articulata*, *Littorina littorea*, *Littorina fabalis*, *Littorina obtusata*, *Membranoptera alata*, *Mytilus edulis*, *Nucella lapillus*, *Paracentrotus lividus*, *Patella vulgata*, *Petricola pholadiformis*, *Polysiphonia lanosa*, *Rhodothamniella floridula*, *Semibalanus balanoides*, *Ulva lactuca*. Many associated species are typically found in rock pools during low tide.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Physical loss or physical change, abrasion, disturbance, invasive species.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation of construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination, pollution and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Seaweed communities on full salinity Atlantic littoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: Ascophyllum nodosum on full salinity mid eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Furoids on sheltered marine shores.](#)

[JNCC: Fucus serratus and red seaweeds on moderately exposed lower eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Fucus serratus on full salinity sheltered lower eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Himanthalia elongata and red seaweeds on exposed to moderately exposed lower eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Robust furoid and/or red seaweed communities.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Ascophyllum nodosum on full salinity mid eulittoral rock.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Fucus serratus on full salinity sheltered lower eulittoral rock.](#)

Group 2

MA125. Fucoids on variable salinity Atlantic littoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA125](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, <1170

European Red List:

=NEAA1.32, #NEAA1.31,

#NEAA1.15, #NEAA1.21,

#NEAA1.22

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA1251](#), [MA1252](#),

[MA1253](#), [MA1254](#), [MA1255](#),

[MA1256](#), [MA1257](#)

IE:

<LR.LLR.F

=LR.LLR.FVS

#LR.MLR.BF

>LR.LLR.FVS.AscVS

#LR.LLR.FVS.FvesVS

#LR.MLR.MusF.MytFves

#LR.MLR.MusF.MytFR

General description

Blankets of furoid seaweeds, dominating sheltered to extremely sheltered rocky shores with variable salinity, such as sea lochs or estuaries. The extent of rocky habitat in estuaries can range from a narrow strip restricted to the top of the shore to littoral reef structures extending to the subtidal zone, particularly in rias. The topography of estuarine rocky shores also varies from flat and gently sloping to rugged reefs and large boulders with multiple microhabitats.

Rocky habitats in estuaries are typically located in low wave-energy environments with reduced salinity, and experience accelerated tidal streams with increased turbidity and siltation. The communities present are adapted to these conditions; consequently, their composition and character are different from those found on similar substrata on the open coast.

Estuarine rocky habitats often display a transition of community types down the length of an estuary, reflecting the different environmental conditions. More in detail, communities at the upper ends of estuaries are specific to ultra sheltered and low salinity, while towards the mouth of estuaries, communities are similar to open coast rock communities.

Characteristic species

The wrack *Pelvetia canaliculata* occurs on the upper shore, while *Fucus spiralis* occurs below. The middle shore is dominated by vast areas of *Ascophyllum nodosum*, *F. vesiculosus*, or a mixture of both. *F. serratus* covers lower shore bedrock and boulders. *F. ceranoides* can be found on extremely sheltered shores with variable or low salinity, as it is more tolerant of reduced salinity than the other fucoids; therefore, it tends to replace *F. spiralis*, *F. vesiculosus* and *A. nodosum* towards the upper reaches of estuaries and sea lochs. This biotope may contain other fucoids, although *F. ceranoides* always dominates.

Associated species

The variable salinity communities are poorer compared to those in full salinity or in tide-swept conditions, as red seaweeds and sponges are usually absent. Underneath a canopy of fucoids, are a few green seaweeds including *Ulva intestinalis* and *Cladophora* spp.

The red seaweed *Polysiphonia lanosa* can be found as an epiphyte on *A. nodosum*. On the rock and among the boulders are the winkles *Littorina littorea* and *L. saxatilis*, the crab *Carcinus maenas*, the barnacles *Semibalanus balanoides* and *Elminius modestus*, and the occasional mussel *Mytilus edulis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat occurs in estuaries and sea lochs that are naturally sheltered and also subject to reduced salinity. These can be major areas of urban and industrial development, generating pressures on intertidal habitats associated

with deteriorating water quality, mainly through industrial contaminants and runoff from agricultural land, which result in enhanced nutrient input and silt loading. Other anthropogenic pressures include coastal defence works, impoundments and the dredging of navigational channels.

Sea level rise and increased storminess associated with climate change are an additional pressure. In the UK, for example, this is considered likely to exacerbate the existing infilling of south- and west-facing estuaries, where eroded sediment is deposited within the estuary, gradually covering rocky outcrops.

Best practices in nature restoration

The conservation and management of this habitat need to be integrated into the management of the sheltered inlets in which it occurs. This includes the planning and regulation of activities such as coastal works, the discharge of hazardous substances, the establishment of nitrate sensitive zones, specifications relating to the dredging of navigational channels and dredge spoil disposal.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: *Ascophyllum nodosum* and *Fucus vesiculosus* on variable salinity mid eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Barnacles and fucoids on moderately exposed shores.](#)

[JNCC: Fucoids in variable salinity.](#)

[JNCC: Fucoids on sheltered marine shores.](#)

[JNCC: *Fucus vesiculosus* on variable salinity mid eulittoral boulders and stable mixed substrata.](#)

[JNCC: *Mytilus edulis* and *Fucus vesiculosus* on moderately exposed mid eulittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: *Mytilus edulis*, *Fucus serratus* and red seaweeds on moderately exposed lower eulittoral rock.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Ascophyllum nodosum* and *Fucus vesiculosus* on variable salinity mid eulittoral rock.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Fucus serratus* on full salinity sheltered lower eulittoral rock.](#)

Group 2

MB121. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB121](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, #1170

European Red List:

=NEAA3.1, >NEAA3.22,

>NEAA3.21

Links to finer EUNIS habitats:

[MB1211](#), [MB1212](#), [MB1213](#),

[MB1214](#), [MB1215](#), [MB1216](#),

[MB1217](#), [MB1218](#), [MB1219](#),

[MB121A](#), [MB121B](#), [MB121C](#),

[MB121D](#), [MB121E](#), [MB121F](#),

[MB121G](#), [MB121H](#), [MB121I](#),

[MB121K](#)

OSPAR:

#Kelp Forests

DE:

#02.01.01.01.01

#02.01.01.01.03

#02.02.01.01.01

#02.02.01.01.07

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

=IR.HIR.KFaR

>IR.MIR.KR

>IR.MIR.KT

>IR.LIR.KVS

>IR.LIR.IFaVS

>IR.LIR.Lag

General description

Infralittoral rock includes habitats of bedrock, boulders and cobbles that occur in the shallow subtidal zone, and typically support seaweed and kelp communities. The upper limit is marked by the top of the kelp zone, while the lower limit is marked by the lower limit of kelp growth or the lower limit of dense seaweed growth. Infralittoral rock typically has an upper zone of dense kelp (forest) and a lower zone of sparse kelp (park), both with an understorey of erect seaweeds. In exposed conditions the kelp is *Laminaria hyperborea*, while in more sheltered habitats it is usually *Saccharina latissima*. Along the Spanish coastline, *Laminaria ochroleuca* can form monospecific but also mixed forests with *L. hyperborea*. In Portugal, the upper zone is typically dominated by *Saccorhiza polyschides*, while the lower zone is also dominated by *Laminaria hyperborea* and/or *Laminaria ochroleuca*. Other kelp species (e.g., *Phyllariopsis* spp.) may dominate under certain conditions. On the extreme lower shore and in the very shallow subtidal (sublittoral fringe) there is usually a narrow band of dabberlocks *Alaria esculenta* (exposed coasts) or the kelps *L. digitata* (moderately exposed) or *S. latissima* (very sheltered). Areas of mixed ground, lacking stable rock, may lack kelps, but support seaweed communities. In estuaries and other turbid-water areas, the shallow subtidal zone may be dominated by animal communities, with only poorly developed seaweed communities. Winter storms may remove patches of kelp, and fast-growing annuals may form a temporary forest.

Communities associated with this habitat are typically highly biodiverse. Besides, these habitats also play an important role as nursery grounds, supporting and protecting large numbers of juveniles from various species. Some fish species even use the seaweeds to develop their nests or as substrates for egg deposition.

Characteristic species

Laminaria hyperborea, *Laminaria ochroleuca*, *Saccharina latissima*, *L. digitata*, *Alaria esculenta*, *Saccorhiza polyschides*, *Phyllariopsis* spp.

Associated species

Bryozoa, Balanidae, *Echinus esculentus*, *Asterias rubens*, *Mytilus edulis*, *Paracentrotus lividus*, *Marthasterias glacialis*. Present fish species can be *Ctenolabrus rupestris*, *Centrolabrus exoletus*, *Cyclopterus lumpus*, *Clupea harengus* and *Taurulus bubalis*, *Symphodus* spp., *Parablennius gattorugine*, and *Diplodus* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Destructive fishing practices and coastal pollution are known to have negative effects on kelp forests. In some northern European regions, including the west coast of Norway, the French channel coast, parts of the coast of the UK and along the northern coast of Spain, harvesting also has the most direct

pressure on this habitat. Removal of *Laminaria* species would also result in a loss of a large proportion of the associated fauna. Habitat loss is also induced by coastal defence measures. Climate change is foreseen to add to these multiple pressures.

Best practices in nature restoration

Kelp forest restoration has been largely disconnected all over the globe, with varying methodologies that have been trialled by different actors in different countries (Eger et al. 2022). A review by Eger et al. (2022) has shown that projects are more successful when they are located near existing kelp forests. Green gravel may potentially become a best practice in European waters (Fredriksen et al. 2020); however, it is still under development. Moreover, the exclusion of bottom trawling and other harmful fishing gear, harvesting control and pollution prevention measures can enable passive restoration, as well as the designation of Marine Protected Areas that allow the natural development of this coastal habitat type without disruption (including e.g., artificial coastal defence and urbanisation).

Bibliographic sources

[Eger, A. M., Marzinelli, E. M., Christie, H., Fagerli, C. W., Fujita, D., Gonzalez, A. P., Hong, S. W., Kim, J. H., Lee, L. C., McHugh, T. A., Nishihara, G.N., Tatsumi, M., Steinberg, P. D., Vergés, A., 2022. Global kelp forest restoration: past lessons, present status, and future directions. *Biol. Rev.* 97: 1449 - 1475.](#)

[EIONET A3.21 “Kelp and red seaweeds on moderate energy Atlantic infralittoral rock”.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Fredriksen S., Filbee-Dexter K., Norderhaug K. M., Stehen H., Bodvin T., Coleman M. A., Moy F., Wernberg T. \(2020\): Green gravel: a novel restoration tool to combat kelp forest decline. *Sci Rep* 10, 3983.](#)

[JNCC: Infralittoral rock \(and other hard substrata\).](#)

[OSPAR: Kelp Forest.](#)

[Tulp, I., Bolle, L. J., Dänhardt, A., de Vries, P., Haslob, H., Jespen, N., Scholle, J., & van der Veer, H. W., 2017. Wadden Sea Quality Status Report: Fish. Common Wadden Sea Secretariat.](#)

Group 2

MB123. Kelp and seaweed communities on sediment-affected or disturbed Atlantic infralittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB123](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, #1170

European Red List:

=NEAA3.12

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB1231](#), [MB1232](#),

[MB1233](#), [MB1234](#), [MB1235](#),

[MB1236](#), [MB1237](#), [MB1238](#),

[MB1239](#), [MB123A](#), [MB123B](#),

[MB123C](#)

OSPAR:

#Kelp Forest

IE:

=IR.HIR.KSed

>IR.LIR.K

#IR.LIR.KVS

General description

This habitat type describes infralittoral rock habitats that are subject to disturbance through the mobility of the substratum (boulders or cobbles), abrasion/covering by nearby coarse sediments, or suspended particulate matter (sand). The associated communities can be quite variable, depending on conditions. *Laminaria hyperborea* and red seaweed communities that are typical of stable open coast rocky habitats, are replaced by those including more ephemeral species, or which are tolerant of sand and gravel abrasion. As such, *Saccharina latissima*, *Saccorhiza polyschides* or *Halidrys siliquosa* may be prominent components of the associated community. The foliose green seaweed *Ulva* spp. is fast to colonise newly cleared areas of rock and is often present, along with the foliose brown seaweed *Dictyota dichotoma*.

It is known to have a widespread distribution. Data on the quantity and quality of this habitat, including any historical or recent trends across the region, are unknown.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Saccorhiza polyschides* or *Halidrys siliquosa*, *Ulva* spp., *Dictyota dichotoma*.

In locations where *S. polyschides* and other opportunistic kelps occur, scour-tolerant red seaweeds, including *Corallina officinalis*, *Kallymenia reniformis*, *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Chondrus crispus*, *Dilsea carnosa* and encrusting coralline algae, are often present beneath the kelp. Foliose red seaweeds, such as *Callophyllis laciniata*, *Cryptopleura ramosa* and *Palmaria palmata*, also occur in this habitat. *P. palmata* and *Delesseria sanguinea* often occur as epiphytes on the stipes of *L. hyperborea*, when it is present.

In locations where there are seasonally disturbed unstable boulders and cobbles in very shallow water, the brown seaweeds *Chorda filum* and *S. latissima* can dominate, while *Desmarestia aculeata* and encrusting coralline algae are also typical. Other red seaweeds, which can be found here, include *Chondria dasyphylla*, *Brongniartella byssoides*, *Polysiphonia elongata*, *Ceramium nodulosum*, *Cystoclonium purpureum*, *Heterosiphonia plumosa*, *Rhodomela confervoides* and *Plocamium cartilagineum*. The brown seaweeds *Punctaria* sp. and *Cladostephus spongiosus* are generally present.

In locations with dense stands of *Halidrys siliquosa*, it can be mixed with the foliose brown seaweed, *Dictyota dichotoma* and kelp, such as *Saccharina latissima* and *Laminaria hyperborea*. Below the canopy there is an undergrowth of red seaweeds that are tolerant of sand-scour, such as *Phyllophora crispa*, *P. pseudoceranoides*, *Rhodomela confervoides*, *Corallina officinalis* and *Chondrus crispus*. Other red seaweeds, such as *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Calliblepharis ciliata*, *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Delesseria sanguinea*, *Heterosiphonia plumosa*, *Dilsea carnosa*, *Hypoglossum*

hypoglossoides and *Brongiartella byssoides*, may be locally abundant, particularly in the summer months.

Associated species

Due to the disturbed nature of this habitat, fauna is generally sparse and limited to encrusting bryozoans and/or sponges, such as *Halichondria panacea* and the gastropod *Gibbula cineraria*. The starfish *Asterias rubens* and the crabs *Pagurus bernhardus* and *Necora puber* are among the most conspicuous animals. The bryozoan crust *Electra pilosa* colonises many of the algae, along with the ascidian *Botryllus schlosseri*. Occasionally, the polychaete *Lanice conchilega* may occur in the sand between pebbles, and the anthozoan *Urticina felina* may be found among pockets of gravel. At some sites, the rock beneath the algae can be occupied by the tube-building polychaete *Pomatoceros triqueter*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Pollution, invasive species, natural system modifications (e.g., human induced changes in hydraulic conditions, abrasion), climate change.

Best practices in nature restoration

The beneficial management of this habitat includes passive restoration measures, such as the regulation of coastal developments that might affect adjacent areas of this habitat by altering sediment movement patterns and wave exposure, as well as pollution control and regulation of discharges to the marine environment, the development of contingency plans to be followed in the event of a major pollution incident, and control on the potential introduction of non-native invasive species.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: *Mytilus edulis* and/or barnacle communities on wave-exposed Atlantic littoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Sediment-affected or disturbed kelp and seaweed communities.](#)

[JNCC: Silted kelp communities \(sheltered infralittoral rock\).](#)

[OSPAR: Kelp Forest.](#)

Group 2

MB124. Kelp communities on variable salinity Atlantic infralittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB124](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1160, <1170

European Red List:

=NEAA3.32

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB1241](#), [MB1242](#), [MB1243](#)

OSPAR:

#Kelp forest

IE:

<IR.LIR

=IR.LIR.KVS

#IR.LIR.IFaVS

#IR.LIR.Lag

#IR.LIR.K

General description

This habitat type describes very wave-sheltered bedrock, boulders and cobbles subject to only weak tidal streams in the sublittoral fringe and infralittoral zone, in areas of variable/reduced salinity. This biotope complex is characterised by the kelp *Saccharina latissima* and coralline crusts, such as *Lithothamnion glaciale*.

A wide range of microhabitats exists within this biotope. These include sediments, sometimes maerl, where infauna will occur, underboulder habitats, the sides and tops of boulders (which often have different dominant species), the interstices of massive sponge growths, the holdfasts of kelp plants, and the fronds of kelps and other algae.

Red algal communities are composed primarily of *Phycodrys rubens*.

Depth range: 0-10m.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Lithothamnion glaciale*, *Phycodrys rubens*.

Associated species

Due to the disturbed nature of this habitat, fauna is generally sparse and limited to encrusting bryozoans and/or sponges, such as *Halichondria panacea* and the gastropod *Gibbula cineraria*. The starfish *Asterias rubens* and the crabs *Pagurus bernhardus* and *Necora puber* are among the most conspicuous animals. The bryozoan crust *Electra pilosa* colonises many of the algae, along with the ascidian *Botryllus schlosseri*. Occasionally, the polychaete *Lanice conchilega* may occur in the sand between pebbles, and the anthozoan *Urticina felina* may be found among pockets of gravel. At some sites, the rock beneath the algae can be occupied by the tube-building polychaete *Pomatoceros triqueter*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

A major decline in species richness has been observed because of the following pressures: substratum loss, decrease in suspended sediment, increase in emergence regime, increase in wave exposure, abrasion and physical disturbance.

Best practices in nature restoration

The main approach to the conservation and management of this habitat should be through regulation of fishing methods that damage or disturb seabed communities. In addition, controls on activities that change the hydrological regime, such as coastal development and hard coastal defence structures, are also important. Furthermore, water quality improvement programmes to reduce the risk of contamination should also be considered. Lastly, measures to reduce climate change effects will benefit this habitat.

This habitat is protected within some Marine Protected Areas. Its recovery potential is high to very high.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Kelp communities on variable salinity Atlantic infralittoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Kelp in variable or reduced salinity.](#)

[OSPAR: Kelp Forest.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Kelp in variable or reduced salinity.](#)

Group 2

MB321. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB321](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1160

European Red List:

=NEAA5.52

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB3211](#), [MB3212](#), [MB3213](#), [MB3214](#)

OSPAR:

#Kelp forest

DE:

#02.02.06.01.01

#02.02.06.01.08.

#02.02.08.01

#§ 30 "Seegräsflächen und

sonstige marine

Makrophytenbestände"

#§ 30 "Riffe"

IE:

=SS.SMp.KSwSS

#SS.SCS.SCSVS

<SS.SCS.ICS

General description

This habitat type describes shallow sublittoral sediments that support seaweed communities, typically including the kelp *Saccharina latissima* (former *Laminaria saccharina*), the bootlace weed *Chorda filum* and various red and brown seaweeds, particularly filamentous types. The generally sheltered nature of these habitats enables the seaweeds to grow on shells and small stones that lie on the sediment surface. Some communities develop as loose-lying mats on the sediment surface.

Survey information confirms that this habitat has a widespread distribution in the North East Atlantic. Although it has been studied in detail in some localities, there is insufficient information to determine any historical, recent trends in quantity or quality.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Chorda filum*.

Associated species

A diverse array of animals is associated with these kelps and seaweeds, including burrowing polychaete worms and bivalves, scavenging hermit crabs, crabs, starfish, fish and grazing top shells. Kelps and seaweeds growing on sediment greatly increase the primary production of an area and create a more diverse habitat. Gastropods, amphipods, sea urchins and fish graze the seaweeds; starfish, urchins, hermit crabs and crabs are scavengers; crabs and fish are opportunistic predators; and a mixed infauna of deposit feeders and suspension feeders develops, depending on sediment type.

Other associated species include: *Bonnemaisonia hamifera*, *Gracilaria gracilis*, *Corophium volutator*, *Nematoda*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Kurtiella bidentate*, *Capitella capitata*, *Mya arenaria*, *Scoloplos armiger*, *Ampelisca brevicornis*, *Heterochaeta costata*, *Tubificoides benedii*, *Mysella bidentata*, *Pagurus bernhardus*, *Liocarcinus depurator*, *Asterias rubens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is vulnerable to inshore fishing activity where trawls, dredges or the laying and recovery of creels may disturb, damage or remove the epibiota, in particular the characterising seaweed species.

Disturbance or removal of the substratum, together with an associated increase in sediment loading resulting from dredging activities, is a serious threat to the habitat biota, as it reduces critical light penetration to seaweeds and provides an advantage to filter feeding fauna that compete with the algal species for space. In addition, pollution and nutrient enrichment are a significant pressure that can lead to a decline in species richness.

Best practices in nature restoration

Saccharina latissima and *Chorda filum* have the potential to rapidly recover following disturbance. *S. latissima* showed to be an early colonizer within algal succession, appearing within two weeks of clearance, and can reach sexual maturity within 15-20 months. *Chorda filum* has rapid growth rates and is capable of reaching sexual maturity within a year.

Beneficial management and conservation of this habitat include passive restoration measures, such as protection within Marine Protected Areas, the regulation of nutrient discharges, the regulation of fishing methods that damage or disturb seabed communities, and the control of dredging activity, coastal development, and of the construction of hard coastal defence structures. Green Gravel (Fredriksen et al. 2020) may also work as a restoration measure on sand when natural conditions (e.g., gravel size and distribution on coarse sediment) are carefully considered.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Fredriksen, S., Filbee-Dexter, K., Norderhaug, K.M. et al. Green gravel: a novel restoration tool to combat kelp forest decline. Sci Rep 10, 3983 \(2020\).](#)

[JNCC: Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: Kelp Forest.](#)

Group 2

MB521. Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral sand

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB521](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral sand

[HD](#): #1160

[European Red List](#):

<NEAA5.52

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB5211](#)

OSPAR:

#Kelp forest

IE:

#SS.SMp.KSwSS

>SS.SMp.KSwSS.SlatR.Sa¹⁰

General description

This habitat type describes shallow sublittoral sediments that support seaweed communities, and which typically include the kelp *Laminaria saccharina*, the bootlace weed *Chorda filum* and various red and brown seaweeds, particularly filamentous types. The generally sheltered nature of these habitats enables the seaweeds to grow on shells and small stones which lie on the sediment surface. Some communities develop as loose-lying mats on the sediment surface.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Chorda filum*.

Characteristic red seaweeds: *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Polyides rotunda*, *Polysiphonia elongata* and *Lomentaria clavellosa*.

Associated species

The sandy substrate is home to a variety of typical sand dwelling infauna including polychaetes (*Scoloplos armiger*, *Parexogone hebes*, and *Aricidea (Aricidea) minuta*), amphipods (*Ampelisca brevicornis*), and bivalves (*Lucinoma borealis* and *Abra alba*). Arenicola worm casts and Lanice worm tubes may be visible at the sediment surface.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main pressures threatening this habitat type are those induced by climate change, such as rising water temperatures and sea level rise, as well as physical disturbance, sediment loss, alteration and abrasion.

Best practices in nature restoration

Saccharina latissima and *Chorda filum* have the potential to rapidly recover following disturbance. *S. latissima* showed to be an early colonizer within algal succession, appearing within two weeks of clearance, and can reach sexual maturity within 15-20 months. *Chorda filum* has rapid growth rates and can reach sexual maturity within a year. Green Gravel (Fredriksen et al. 2020) may also work as a restoration measure on sand when natural conditions (e.g., gravel size and distribution on sand) are carefully considered. Also, the management and regulation of fishing activities with mobile, bottom-contacting gear can allow the recovery of this biotope.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

¹⁰ This habitat type is equal to the related EUNIS subtype.

[EUNIS habitat classification: Kelp and seaweed communities on Atlantic infralittoral sand.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Fredriksen, S., Filbee-Dexter, K., Norderhaug, K.M. et al. Green gravel: a novel restoration tool to combat kelp forest decline. Sci Rep 10, 3983 \(2020\).](#)

[JNCC: Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment.](#)

[JNCC: *Saccharina latissima* and filamentous red algae on infralittoral sand.](#)

[Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Saccharina latissima* and filamentous red algae on infralittoral sand.](#)

[OSPAR: Kelp Forest.](#)

Group 2

MB621. Vegetated communities on Atlantic infralittoral mud

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB621](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mud

HD: <1160

European Red List:

<NEAA5.52

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB6211](#), [MB6212](#),

[MB6213](#)

IE:

<SS.SMp.KSwSS

>SS.SMp.KSwSS.Pcri¹¹

>SS.SMp.KSwSS.SlatCho¹²

>SS.SMp.KSwSS.Tra¹³

General description

This habitat type describes shallow sublittoral sediments that support seaweed communities, typically including the kelp *Laminaria saccharina*, the bootlace weed *Chorda filum* and various red and brown seaweeds, particularly filamentous types. The generally sheltered nature of these habitats enables the seaweeds to grow on shells and small stones which lie on the sediment surface. Some communities develop as loose-lying mats on the sediment surface.

This habitat type describes also beds of submerged or slightly emergent vascular vegetation of brackish seas, sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of mud or sand flats, and coastal lagoons.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Chorda filum*.

Dense loose-lying beds of the 'Trailliella' phase of *Bonnemaisonia hamifera* may occur in extremely sheltered shallow muddy environments. Beds of this alga are often 10cm thick and may reach 100 cm at some sites. Other loose-lying algae may also occur, such as *Audouinella floridula*, *Phyllophora crispa* and species of *Derbesia*.

Associated species

At the sediment surface, ubiquitous fauna such as *Asterias rubens*, crabs such as *Pagurus bernhardus*, *Carcinus maenas*, and the gastropod *Steromphala cineraria* may be visible. In some areas, *Sabella pavonina* may be present. Given the nature of the sediment, it is likely that a wide range of infaunal bivalves and polychaetes are present, including *Arenicola marina*, *Mediomastus fragilis* and *Phyllodoce mucosa*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main pressures threatening this habitat type are those induced by climate change, such as rising water temperatures and sea level rise, as well as physical disturbance, sediment abrasion, alteration and loss. Contamination and pollution are also relevant factors.

Best practices in nature restoration

Saccharina latissima and *Chorda filum* have the potential to rapidly recover following disturbance. *S. latissima* showed to be an early colonizer within algal succession, appearing within two weeks of clearance, and can reach sexual maturity within 15-20 months. *Chorda filum* has rapid growth rates and can

¹¹ This habitat type is equal to the related EUNIS subtype.

¹² This habitat type is equal to the related EUNIS subtype.

¹³ This habitat type is equal to the related EUNIS subtype.

reach sexual maturity within a year. Green Gravel (Fredriksen et al. 2020) may also work as a restoration measure when natural conditions (e.g., gravel size and distribution on sediment) are carefully considered. Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its function (for example as carbon sink) are still necessary, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Vegetated communities on Atlantic infralittoral mud.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment.](#)

[JNCC: *Saccharina latissima* and *Chorda filum* on sheltered upper infralittoral muddy sediment.](#)

[Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Saccharina latissima* and *Chorda filum* on sheltered upper infralittoral muddy sediment.](#)

Figure 02-02, *Cladophora rupestris*, Black Sea

Source: *Cladophora rupestris*, Pyhtää, The Gulf of Finland, Baltic, Sea, © Maiju Lanki and Metsähallitus, 2012

Group 2

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA131](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1150, <1160, <1170, #1180, #1610, #1620, #1650, #8330

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MA1311](#), [MA1312](#)

HELCOM:
AA.A1C¹⁴

DE:
=05.01.01.01.01
#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"
< § 30 "Riffe"

MA131. Baltic hydrolittoral rock and boulders characterised by perennial algae

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the hydrolittoral zone (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) with at least 90% coverage of rock, boulders or stones of more than 63mm in diameter. Perennial attached algae cover at least 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups (fauna).

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all, more common in exposed areas.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

The characterising species are often annual due to the harsh environmental conditions, especially on the sites that are more exposed. Also ice-scraping removes perennial macroalgae during winters. The hydrolittoral zone typically has seasonally differing algae communities, where the following species may dominate: *Cladophora glomerata*, *Pilayella littoralis*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, *Ceramium teniocrone*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *U. flexuosa*, *U. linza*, *Zygnema* spp., *Spongomorpha aeruginosa*, *Ulothrix zonata*.

Associated species

Aegagropila linnaei, *Chaetomorpha linum*, *Bryopsis plumosa*, *Acrosiphonia arcta*, *Scytosiphon lomentaria*.

A typical invertebrate community consists of sessile species, such as the barnacle *Amphibalanus improvisus* and mobile invertebrate grazers such as the gastropods *Theodoxus fluviatilis* and *Hydrobia* spp., isopods (*Jaera* spp., *Idotea* spp., especially juveniles) and amphipods (e.g., *Gammarus* spp., especially juveniles).

Waders (e.g., turnstone and migrating species), as well as juvenile benthic-feeding seabirds, use the habitat as a feeding ground, e.g., eider *Somateria mollissima*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by reduced water transparency (shadowing), sedimentation (inhibiting recruitment) and nutrient increase (competition with ephemeral algae). Also, the replacement of the natural substrate by artificial vertical substrate causes reduced recruitment by larger perennial macroalgae.

¹⁴ AA.A1C and MA131 are almost identical, but MA131 is limited to the hydrolittoral zone and lacking most perennial macroalgae, and AA.A1C does not include man-made substrate.

Best practices in nature restoration

Green Gravel (Fredriksen et al. 2020) may work as an active restoration measure when natural conditions (e.g., gravel size and distribution) are carefully considered.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.A1C Baltic photic rock and boulders characterized by perennial algae.](#)

[Kraufvelin, P., Salovius, S., 2004. Animal diversity in Baltic rocky shore macroalgae: can *Cladophora glomerata* compensate for lost *Fucus vesiculosus*? Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 61\(2\): 369-378.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 2

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB131](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1150, #1160, <1170, #1180, #1650, #8330
European Red List: ~BAL2

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM:
AA.A1C¹⁵

DE:
=05.02.01.01.01
#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"
< § 30 "Riffe"

MB131. Perennial algae on Baltic infralittoral rock and boulders

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic (infralittoral) zone with at least 90% coverage of rock, boulders or stones of more than 63mm in diameter. The upper depth range is sublittoral (below tidal range), and its lower end is limited by light availability at the compensation point. Man-made substrates such as seawalls, boulder reefs, or wind turbine foundations are included in the definition.

This habitat is defined by at least 10% cover of perennial macroalgae and more than other perennial attached erect groups. The algal community consists of green algae, brown algae and red algae, typically creating zones where the canopy is formed by perennial species and the underlying species may be perennial or ephemeral (annual or shorter-lived).

This habitat is found in the entire Baltic Sea region, where macroalgae and rocky/boulder substrates occur.

Characteristic species

The perennial macroalgae *Fucus vesiculosus*, *F. serratus*, *F. radicans*, *Laminaria* spp., *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, *Coccotylus truncatus*, *Deleseria sanguinea* or species of the genera *Phyllophora*, *Polysiphonia* or *Sphacelaria* spp.

Associated species

The typical macroalgae community consists of brown algae such as *Fucus* spp., green algae such as *Cladophora rupestris*, *C. glomerata*, *Aegagropila linnaei*, *Ulva* spp. and/or red algae such as *Ceramium tenuicorne*, *Phyllophora* spp., *Polysiphonia* spp. and *Furcellaria lumbricalis*.

A typical invertebrate community consists of sessile species, such as mussels (e.g., *Mytilus edulis*, *M. trossulus*, *Modiolus modiolus*, *Dreissena polymorpha*), clams (*Cerastoderma glaucum*), the ascidians (e.g., *Ascidia* spp., *Ciona intestinalis*, *Dendrodoa grossularia*), the barnacle *Amphibalanus improvisus* and the bryozoans *Electra crustulenta* and *Flustra foliacea*, and mobile invertebrate grazers such as the gastropods *Hydrobia* spp. and *Theodoxus fluviatilis*, amphipods (e.g., *Gammarus* spp., *Calliopius laeviusculus*), isopods (*Idothea* spp., *Jaera* spp.), mysids (*Praunus flexuosus*, *P. inermis*), and decapods (*Palaemon adspersus*).

The typical fish species within the habitat are the sticklebacks (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*, *Spinachia spinachia*), the goby *Gobiusculus flavescens* and the eelpout *Zoarces viviparus*. Also, flounders (*Platichthys flesus*, *Scophthalmus maximus*) and other predatory species are often found.

¹⁵ Note that AA.A1C does not include man-made substrate.

Benthic-feeding seabirds use the habitat as a feeding ground, e.g., the eider *Somateria mollissima*, auks (e.g., *Alca torda*, *Cepphus grylle*) and the wintering long-tailed duck (*Clangula hyemalis*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by reduced water transparency (shadowing), sedimentation (inhibiting recruitment) and nutrient increase (competition with ephemeral algae). Also, the replacement of the natural substrate by artificial vertical substrate causes reduced recruitment by larger perennial macroalgae.

Best practices in nature restoration

Green Gravel (Fredriksen et al. 2020) may work as an active restoration measure when natural conditions (e.g., gravel size and distribution) are carefully considered.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[Fredriksen, S., Filbee-Dexter, K., Norderhaug, K.M. et al. Green gravel: a novel restoration tool to combat kelp forest decline. Sci Rep 10, 3983 \(2020\).](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.A1C Baltic photic rock and boulders characterised by perennial algae.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 2

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB232](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, #1110¹⁶

[European Red List](#): BAL10, BAL20, BAL22

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB2321](#), [MB2322](#), [MB2323](#), [MB2324](#), [MB2325](#), [MB2326](#), [MB2327](#), [MB2328](#)

HELCOM:

≈AA.AE

DE:

<05.02.04

#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

MB232. Baltic infralittoral bottoms characterised by shell gravel

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of shell gravel. The substrate is found from moderate to high energy bottoms. The biotope may shift from one location to another (HELCOM, 2013a). HELCOM HUB divides the habitat into kelp-dominated (HELCOM, 2013b), tunicate-dominated (HELCOM, 2013a) and mussel-dominated (HELCOM, 2013c, Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Salinity range: down to 5 psu; Exposure range: moderate to high; Depth range: Photic zone.

Geographic range: Many level 5 habitats of shell gravel are only found in the Southern or Southwestern Baltic Sea, while shell gravel bottoms can be found up to the Quark in the North and to the 5psu salinity gradient in the Eastern Gulf of Finland (HELCOM, 2019. Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Characteristic species

In the Southern and Southwestern Baltic: *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria digitata*, *Laminaria hyperborea*, *Mytilus* spp., *Modiolus modiolus*, *Ciona intestinalis* and interstitial fauna such as *Amphioxus* spp.

In the Northern Baltic Sea, found within the shell gravel are the blue mussel (*Mytilus trossulus*), the sand gaper (*Mya arenaria*), the Baltic tellin (*Macoma balthica*) and/or the lagoon cockle (*Cerastoderma glaucum*; Kotilainen et al. 2020). The interstitial fauna exists but is not adequately known.

Associated species

Benthic macroinfauna species that occur in the biotope burrow down into the substrate that is similar in structure to coarse sand. The community composition of macroinfauna is presumed to be different in the finer shell gravel than in the coarser shell gravel, among which many different animals can be found including non-burrowing animals. The interstitial space is smaller in the sand-like shell gravel substrate, enabling also burrowing polychaetes and amphipods to build tunnels using the small grains (HELCOM, 2013b).

In the areas with higher salinity, the associated species are predominantly mobile polychaetes and young individuals of the cockle *Cerastoderma edule* (Callaway 2018). The polychaetes *Phyllodoce maculate* and *Nephtys* spp., the amphipods *Melita palmata*, *Echinogammarus stoerensis*, *Nototropis swammerdamei* and *Gammarus zaddachi*, the isopod *Idotea pelagica* (Callaway 2018) can also be found.

¹⁶ As MB232 is a specific substrate, the similarity of this habitat with habitats 1160 and 1110 is not specific.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by sedimentation (covering the shell gravel and filling the interstitial spaces), eutrophication (increasing organic matter, hypoxia), acidification, bottom trawling, sand and gravel extraction, construction.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Callaway R. 2018. Interstitial Space and Trapped Sediment Drive Benthic Communities in Artificial Shell and Rock Reefs. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 5.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic photic or aphotic shell gravel dominated by vase tunicate \(*Ciona intestinalis*\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic photic shell gravel dominated by kelp. BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013c. Baltic photic or aphotic shell gravel characterised by mixed infaunal macrocommunity in fine sand-like shell fragments. BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA. E Baltic photic shell gravel.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. *The Finnish Environment* 23/2020.](#)

Group 2

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB333](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160¹⁷, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL10, <BAL11

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB3331](#), [MB3332](#), [MB3333](#), [MB3334](#), [MB3335](#)

HELCOM:

=AA.I1C

DE:

=05.02.08.01.02

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

MB333. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by perennial algae

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Perennial algae cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate; Depth range: photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Fucus vesiculosus*, *F. radicans*, *F. serratus*, *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, *Coccotylus truncatus*, *Phyllophora* spp., *Polysiphonia* spp.

Associated species

Flora: *Cladophora glomerata*, *Pylaiella littoralis*, *Ectocarpus siliculosus*, *Elachista fucicola*, *Fontinalis antipyretica* (in low salinity areas), *Ceramium tenuicorne*.

Invertebrate fauna: *Mytilus* spp., *Gammarus* spp., *Idotea balthica*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Theodoxus fluviatilis*.

Fish fauna: viviparous eelpout (*Zoarces viviparus*) and the three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by sedimentation (covering the gravel and stones and filling the interstitial spaces), eutrophication (decreased water transparency).

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

¹⁷ As MB333 is a specific substrate, the similarity with the habitats 1160 and 1110 is not specific.

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.I1C Baltic photic coarse sediment characterised by perennial algae.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 2

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB433](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL1, BAL2, BAL10

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB4331](#), [MB4332](#), [MB4333](#), [MB4334](#), [MB4335](#)

HELCOM:

=AA.M1C

DE:

=05.02.06.01.02

#§ 30 "Seegraswiesen und sonstige marine Makrophytenbestände"

MB433. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with more than 10%, but less than 90% coverage of both hard and soft substrata. Coverage of perennial attached algae is at least 10%, and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Salinity range: low to moderate; Exposure range: moderate to high; Depth range: photic zone down from about 0.5m.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Saccharina latissima, *Laminaria digitata*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, *F. radicans*, *F. serratus maritimus*, *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, *Coccotylus truncatus*, *Deleseria sanguinea*, *Polysiphonia* spp., *Cladophora rupestris*, *Sphacelaria* spp., *Polysiphonia fucooides*, *Aegagrophila linnaei*, *Cladophora rupestris*, *Rhodomela confervoides*.

Associated species

The communities depend on the species of perennial habitat-forming algae and on salinity gradient. See the habitat "MB131-Perennial algae on Baltic infralittoral rock and boulders" for an indication of the species that can be associated with this habitat type.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by sedimentation (covering the gravel and stones and filling the interstitial spaces), eutrophication (decreased water transparency).

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.M1C Baltic photic mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Figure 02-03, *Cystoseira bosporica*, Black Sea

Source: An underwater photo of *Cystoseira bosporica*, Black Sea, by Dimitar Nikolov Berov, EU funded project RECONNECT Balkan-Mediterranean 2014-2020, 2010

Group 2

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB144](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

[European Red List](#): BLSA3.17

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Infralittoral rock bottom with perennial brown algae from the *Cystoseira* sp.

<Infralittoral rock dominated by Mytilids: *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus*

RO:

<Habitat with *Cystoseira barbata*

MB144. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea exposed upper infralittoral rock with fucales

General description

This habitat occurs on very exposed rocky coasts, subject to strong wave action and typically covered with Fucales and Mytilid communities. *Cystoseira* species are the most common species, represented by *Ericaria crinita* and *E. bosphorica*. Under the exposed conditions, winter storms may cause changes to species compositions and coverage.

The association of *E. crinita* is widely distributed on sloping rock blocks and on the bottoms of open coasts, directly exposed to wave action, at depths between 0.5 and 4m (up to 6-7m in very clean waters), in well-illuminated areas (up to 40-50% of the surface photosynthetically active radiation) and with low biogenic concentrations.

E. bosphorica inhabits depths between 0.5-10m in open and exposed rocky shores.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottoms are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, as well as at greater depth, the black mussels become the main habitat species.

More detailed studies of this habitat's characteristics and distribution area are needed.

Characteristic species

Characteristic species include: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, *E. bosphorica*, *Gongolaria barbata*, *Cladostephus spongiosus*, *Corallina elongata*, *E. crinita*, *Dictyota fasciola*, *Polysiphonia subulifera* and *Ulva rigida*.

Associated species

Characteristic inhabitants of the rock bottom are the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), sea acorn (*Balanus improvisus*), serpulid polychaetes *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Janua pagenstecheri*, *Serpula vermicularis*.

A variety of fauna (benthic invertebrates and fish) and flora (micro- and macro epiphytes) are associated with the *Cystoseira* sp. Mussels are also colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *L. caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoides*, *Rissoa splendida*, *Bittium reticulatum*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, and *Athanas nitescens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency. Reduced light penetration has caused a reduction in the extent and quality of the algal component of the habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the mytilid element of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat include:

- Construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, smothering, and changes in the hydrological and hydrochemical regime.
- Temperature changes and/or extreme temperatures (both summer and winter) can cause die-offs of *Cystoseira* spp. Canopies.
- Severe storm events - causing damage to *Cystoseira* spp. canopies, resulting in habitat fragmentation and loss.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Due to the slow growth rate and colonisation of the key species, habitat fragmentation and loss can result in long-term declines. Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (e.g., wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *R. venosa* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov D., Ballesteros E., Sales M., Verlaque M., 2015. Reinstatement of species rank for *Cystoseira bosporica* Sauvageau \(Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae\), *Cryptogamie, Algologie*, 2015. 36 \(1\): 65-80.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\)](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS. Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 2

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB149](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

European Red List: BLSA3.25

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Upper-infralittoral (3-10 m) rock dominated by *Cystoseira* sp.

>Upper infralittoral rock with variable annual green and red macroalgae

<Infralittoral rock dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and *Mytilaster lineatus*

RO:

<Habitat with *Cystoseira barbata*

MB149. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea moderately exposed upper infralittoral rock with fucales

General description

This habitat is widespread in the shallow waters of the Black Sea, along moderately exposed coasts on rocky substrates presented by a range of rock sizes, from whole uninterrupted bedrock to fragmented rocks and boulder fields. It occurs at a depth of up to 10m and up to 12-13m in clean waters, with high levels of illumination (up to 10%-20% of the surface photosynthetically active radiation) and low concentrations of nutrients. In areas of low direct wave impact, the canopy-forming dominant species is *Gongolaria barbata*. *G. barbata* is found at shallow depths (1-3m). On open coasts, where the wave impact decreases in depth, it is widespread in depths from 4-5m to 10-12m. The other habitat-forming fucal species, *Cystoseira bosporica* Sauvageau, inhabits depths of 5-10m.

Among all the predominant habitats, the shallow rock bottom provides the highest biodiversity of species and biological communities. *Cystoseira sensu lato* species are the most common species encountered. The association of *Ericaria crinita* (formerly *Cystoseira*) is widely distributed on sloping rock blocks and bottoms of open coasts, directly exposed to wave action, at depths between 0.5 and 4m (up to 6-7m in very clean waters), in well-illuminated areas (up to 40-50% of the surface photosynthetically active radiation) and with low biogenic concentrations. Mytilids are a constant component, and Corallines are also present.

The distribution of *Cystoseira* s.l. stands is patchy. Under suitable conditions, i.e., rocky substrate, illumination, and transparency, continuous underwater meadows with high projective coverage are formed. The boundaries are dynamic, depending on local hydrodynamic conditions.

At depth, the total projective cover of *G. barbata* gradually decreases (from up to 100% at 2-3m to 10-20% at 10-12m), and the presence of some species adapted to lower light levels, such as *Polysiphonia elongata*, *Lomentaria clavellosa*, *Zanardinia typus*, and *Antithamniom cruciatum* increases.

In conditions of increased eutrophication, the relative presence of brown and red algae in the composition of the community decreases.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottoms are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, as well as at greater depth, under low light, algae are rare, and black mussels become the main habitat species.

Characteristic species

The moderately exposed nature of this habitat allows the inhabiting of species that are less tolerant to wave action. Characteristic species include: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, *G. barbata*, *Ericaria crinita*, *E.*

bosporica, *Ulva rigida*, *Polysiphonia subulifera*/*P. opaca*, and *Cladostephus spongiosus* - *Corallina elongata* communities.

Associated species

The *Cystoseira* canopy in this habitat provides substrate, shelter, food, and spawning grounds for a huge variety of species.

The associated invertebrate fauna is very diverse, and the species abundance greatly surpasses that of the soft bottom. Characteristic inhabitants of the rock bottom are the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), sea acorn (*Balanus improvisus*), serpulid polychaetes *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Janua pagenstecheri*, *Serpula vermicularis*. Mussels are colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoidea*, *Rissoa splendida*, *Bittium reticulatum*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, *Athanas nitescens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency. Reduced light penetration has caused a decrease in the extent and quality of the algal component of the habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the mytilid element of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, smothering, and changes in the hydrological and hydrochemical regime.
- Creation of artificial beaches.
- Temperature changes and/or extreme temperatures (both summer and winter) can cause die-offs of *Cystoseira* spp. canopies.
- Severe storm events - causing damage to *Cystoseira* spp. canopies, resulting in habitat fragmentation and loss.

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Due to the slow growth rate and colonisation of the key species, habitat fragmentation and loss can result in long-term declines. Conservation and management measures related to reducing the nutrients enrichment (e.g., wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov D., Ballesteros E., Sales M., Verlaque M., 2015. Reinstatement of species rank for *Cystoseira bosporica* Sauvageau \(Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae\), *Cryptogamie, Algologie*, 2015. 36 \(1\): 65-80.](#)

Berov, D., Deyanova, D., Georgieva, I., Gyosheva, B., & Hiebaum, G. (2012). *Cystoseira* sp.-dominated macroalgal communities in the SW Black Sea (Burgas Bay, Bulgaria). Current state and possible long-term effects of eutrophication. *Comptes rendus de l'académie Bulgare des sciences*, 65(6), 821-830.

Berov, D., Todorova, V., Dimitrov, L., Rinde, E., & Karamfilov, V. (2018). Distribution and abundance of phytobenthic communities: Implications for connectivity and ecosystem functioning in a Black Sea Marine Protected Area. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 200, 234-247.

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 2

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB14A](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

European Red List: BLSA3.34

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Upper-infralittoral (3-10 m) rock dominated by *Cystoseira* sp.

>Upper infralittoral rock with variable annual green and red macroalgae

<Infralittoral rock

dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and *Mytilaster lineatus*

RO:

<Habitat with *Cystoseira barbata*

MB14A. Fucales and other algae on Black Sea sheltered upper infralittoral rock, well illuminated

General description

This habitat is widespread in the shallow waters of the Black Sea, along sheltered coasts and semi-enclosed bays on rocky substrates. It occurs at a depth of up to 14m but has also been found at greater depth.

Shallow rock substrates appear in various structures on the relief of the seabed-rock banks (reefs), structural terraces, and landslides. Different lithological varieties are observed: limestones, sandstones, marls, clay rock complexes, volcanogenic complexes, and conglomerates.

Among all the predominant habitats, the shallow rock bottom provides the highest biodiversity of species and biological communities. A key feature of this habitat is its biomass. The productivity is very high and is considerably greater than in the Mediterranean.

Gongolaria barbata is the dominant canopy-forming species in this sheltered habitat. The distribution of *Cystoseira* stands is patchy. Under suitable conditions (rocky substrate, illumination, transparency), continuous underwater meadows with high projective coverage are formed. The boundaries are dynamic, depending on local hydrodynamic conditions.

In conditions of increased eutrophication, the relative presence of brown and red algae in the composition of the community decreases and the biodiversity significantly declines, accompanied by a massive development of green macroalgae-opportunists that are adapted to an environment with high concentrations of biogens, such as *Ulva rigida*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Urospora penicilliformis*, *Bryopsis plumosa*, *Cladophora albida*, *Cladophora sericea*, *Cladophora vagabunda*.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottom are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, as well as at greater depth, under low light conditions, algae are rare, and black mussels become the main habitat species.

Characteristic species

G. barbata in associations with *Ulva rigida*, *Polysiphonia subulifera*, *Cladophora* spp., *Gelidium spinosum*, and *Ceramium virgatum*; bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus*.

Red macroalgae are represented by *Gelidium crinale*, *Callithamnion corymbosum*, *Ceramium virgatum*.

Areas dominated by *Coccotylus truncatus* occur along the Romanian coast.

About 140-170 species of zoobenthos and 110 species of macroalgae are represented.

Associated species

The *Cystoseira* canopy in this habitat provides substrate, shelter, food, and spawning grounds for a significant variety of species.

The associated invertebrate fauna is very diverse, and the species abundance greatly surpasses that of the soft bottom. Characteristic inhabitants of the rock bottom are the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), sea acorn (*Balanus improvisus*), serpulid polychaetes *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Janua pagenstecheri*, *Serpula vermicularis*. Mussels are colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoides*, *Rissoa splendida*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods, such as *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, and *Athanas nitescens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency. In Romania, since 1971, up to 90% of the habitat has been reduced, while it was previously found on all rocky coasts. The extent of this loss has occurred mainly at lower depths, due to reduced light penetration. In Romania, the lowest recorded depth has shifted from 7m in the 1930s to 3m in the 2000s and presently is improving (5m). In Varna Bay, Bulgaria, 85% of biomass reduction was recorded between 1968 and 2001. Overall, the degradation has resulted in fragmentation, reduced depth, reduced cover, reduced thallus length and reduced diversity in associated communities.

Over the last two decades, signs of recovery have been observed at several locations in Romania, the Crimea, and Türkiye. Nevertheless, the extent of this habitat is still considerably reduced compared to the pre-eutrophication period.

Over the last 50 years, the reductions in the extent of this habitat were caused by coastal development in Romania, Bulgaria, and Türkiye. In some regions (e.g., Türkiye), the habitat has colonised artificial substrates.

The predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa* can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom, representing a significant threat to this habitat. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, smothering, and changes in the hydrological and hydrochemical regime.
- Creation of artificial beaches.
- Temperature changes and/or extreme temperatures (both summer and winter) can cause die-offs of *Cystoseira* spp. Canopies.
- Severe storm events - causing damage of *Cystoseira* spp. canopies, resulting in habitat fragmentation and loss.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Due to the slow growth rate and colonisation of the key species, habitat fragmentation and loss can result in long-term declines. Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS. Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Figure 02-04, *Cystoseira sp.*, Mediterranean Sea

Source: *Cystoseira sp.* - Mediterranean Sea, © Esculapio, 2018

Group 2

MA1548. Association with *Fucus virsoides*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA1548](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock and biogenic reef
HD: <1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA1.542

General description

The association is primarily constituted by the brown alga *Fucus virsoides*. *F. virsoides* is a common species of the intertidal part of the littoral zone of the northern Adriatic Sea. It is also distributed in a few sites in the eastern coast of the Adriatic Sea, and its southern range limit is situated along the Albanian coast. The association is typical of intertidal hard substrata (both natural and artificial), and it can be found mostly in areas characterised by mean sea level, lower exposure to wave action, the presence of significant tidal excursion, low temperature eutrophic water and close to freshwater inputs. *F. virsoides* is a canopy-forming species that creates a peculiar habitat increasing the biodiversity of the system. Moreover, the sub-layer assemblage may be considered an infralittoral enclave, with species finding a favourable biotope under the *F. virsoides* fronds.

Characteristic species

The characteristic species of this association is the brown alga *Fucus virsoides*, endemic of the Adriatic Sea. *F. virsoides* is considered a glacial relict, thus this association is extremely important from the floristic and heritage point of view. Although this association is primarily constituted by *F. virsoides*, other *Fucales* species can also be found in the infralittoral zone in correspondence of well or moderately illuminated infralittoral rock, both exposed and sheltered, and in transitional waters. *F. virsoides* is listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

This association may also be characterised by the macroalgae *Gelidium spathulatum*, *G. pulvinatum*, *Bangia* spp. and *Rivularia polyotis*. *Patella caerulea*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Actinia equina* and *Balanus* spp. are among the invertebrates that may inhabit the algal assemblages, finding a favourable biotope under the *Fucus* fronds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The *Fucus virsoides* assemblage has suffered a regression in recent decades, due to long-term natural and human-induced changes in the biotic and abiotic conditions. This species is tolerant to wide fluctuations in temperature, salinity, and nutrient concentration. However, climate-driven threats, in the form of severe storm events and/or extreme high tides and temperatures, are considered an important factor influencing its distribution and abundance. Moreover, it is sensitive to increased bedrock instability and overgrazing by limpets. Recent studies have also indicated deleterious effects of exposure of *F. virsoides* to low concentrations of glyphosate-based herbicides.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are still subject to research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic

pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Battelli, C., 2016. Disappearance of *Fucus virsoides* J. Agardh from the Slovenian coast (Gulf of Trieste, northern Adriatic). *Annales, Series Historia Naturalis* 26, 1-12.

Falace, A., Tamburello, L., Guarnieri, G., et al., 2018. Effects of a glyphosate-based herbicide on *Fucus virsoides* (Fucales, Ochrophyta) photosynthetic efficiency. *Environmental Pollution* 243, 912-918.

Felline, S., Del Coco, L., Kaleb, S., et al. 2019. The response of the algae *Fucus virsoides* (Fucales, Ochrophyta) to Roundup® solution exposure: A metabolomics approach. *Environmental Pollution* 254, 112977- 12987.

Gljučić, E., Bilajac, A., Smith, S.M., Najdek, M., and Iveša, L., 2023. First restoration experiment for endemic *Fucus virsoides* on the Western Istrian Coast—Is it feasible? *Plants*, 12(7), 1445.

Mačič, V., 2006. Distribution of seaweed *Fucus virsoides* J. Agardh in Boka Kotorska Bay (South Adriatic Sea). *Annales, Series Historia Naturalis* 16, 1-4.

Munda, I. M., 1997. *Fucus virsoides* (Don.) J. Ag. as indicator of changing environments in the Adriatic Sea. *Phycologia* 36, 75.

Munda, I. M. and Veber, M., 1996. Simultaneous effects of trace metals and excess nutrients on the Adriatic seaweed *Fucus virsoides* (Don.) J. Ag. (Phaeophyceae, Fucales). *Botanica Marina* 39, 297-309.

Orlando-Bonaca, M., Mannoni, P.A., et al., 2013. Assessment of *Fucus virsoides* distribution in the Gulf of Trieste (Adriatic Sea) and its relation to environmental variables. *Botanica Marina* 65, 451-459.

Rindi, F. and Battelli C., 2005. Spatio-temporal variability of intertidal algal assemblages of the Slovenian coast (Gulf of Trieste, northern Adriatic Sea). *Botanica Marina* 48, 96-105.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 2

MB1512. Association with *Cystoseira tamariscifolia* and *Saccorhiza polyschides*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB1512](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c¹⁸

General description

This association, characterised by the two brown-algae *Ericaria selaginoides* and *Saccorhiza polyschides*, is characteristic of the upper part of the infralittoral zone (near the surface down to 2m in depth). These algal assemblages mostly occur in exposed and well-illuminated rocky bottoms, in large intertidal rock pools and lagoons, where there is strong wave action, and the water is cooled by the rising of deep water. This association is uncommon in the Mediterranean Sea, where it is distributed only in the Western basin. These canopy-forming macroalgae constitute important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and the productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages play a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

The algal-dominated assemblage is characterised by beds of the canopy-forming Fucales *Ericaria selaginoides* (former name *Cystoseira tamariscifolia*) in association with *Saccorhiza polyschides*. Both species are distributed mainly in the North-Eastern Atlantic. *E. selaginoides* features solitary thalli, up to 1 m long, bushy, with a pronounced blue iridescence when submerged. The amount of available light drives the intensity of the colour. On the coasts of Morocco in the Strait of Gibraltar, *E. selaginoides* may constitute autonomous associations. The seaweed *S. polyschides* is a yellowish to dark brown annual kelp generally up to 3m in length, essentially an opportunist that colonises any vacant space in the algal forest. In the Mediterranean Sea it is extremely rare, with permanent populations only in the Alboran Sea and in the Strait of Messina (Italy).

The majority of Mediterranean Fucales are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to the characteristic brown algal species, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae (e.g., forming a species complex with *Ericaria amentacea*), sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and several *Didemnidae* ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods and polychaetes.

¹⁸ According to the exposition to waves.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by some non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii* and *Womersleyella setacea*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15;326(Pt A):116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

- Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.
- Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.
- Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.
- Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.
- Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.
- Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.
- SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).
- Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB1513. Association with *Cystoseira amentacea* (var. *amentacea*, var. *stricta*, var. *spicata*)

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB1513](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c¹⁹

General description

The association with the brown algae *Cystoseira amentacea* (var. *amentacea*, var. *stricta*, var. *spicata*) is characteristic of the upper part of the infralittoral zone (near the surface down to 2 m in depth). These algal assemblages mostly occur in exposed and well-illuminated rocky shores, under strong wave action. The association with *C. amentacea* is represented in the three major Mediterranean subregions by different varieties: the association with *C. amentacea* var. *amentacea* is endemic to the Eastern Mediterranean, whereas *C. amentacea* var. *stricta* is mainly found in the Northwestern Mediterranean and *C. var. spicata* in the Adriatic Sea. The three varieties are good indicators of the upper limit of the infralittoral zone. These canopy-forming macroalgae constitute important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages play a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is an algal-dominated assemblage characterised by beds of canopy-forming Fucales of the species *Cystoseira amentacea* (var. *amentacea*, var. *stricta*, var. *spicata*).

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *Cystoseira compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, and *C. amentacea* is listed in Appendix I “Strictly protected flora species” of the Bern Convention.

Associated species

In addition to the characteristic brown algal species, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. This association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and

¹⁹ According to the exposition to waves.

overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European WFD. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

- Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the Ex Situ Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.
- Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.
- Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.
- Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.
- Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.
- Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.
- Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.
- SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).
- Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151F. Association with *Cystoseira brachycarpa*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151F](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²⁰

General description

This association is characterised by dense meadows of the brown alga *Ericaria brachycarpa*. It colonizes the upper part of the infralittoral zone where it can form extensive and dense beds on well-lit rocky bottoms, subject to moderate hydrodynamism.

As most canopy-forming macroalgae, it constitutes an important secondary substrate that increases the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is an algal-dominated assemblage characterised by beds of canopy-forming Fucales of the species *Ericaria brachycarpa* (former name *Cystoseira brachycarpa*; J. Agardh, Molinari & Guiry, 2020). It can be found in association with *C. amentacea*.

Associated species

In addition to the characteristic brown algal species, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

²⁰ According to the exposition to waves.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 1990. Structure and dynamics of the *Cystoseira caespitosa* Sauvageau (Fucales, Phaeophyceae) community in the North-Western Mediterranean. *Scientia Marina* 54(2), 155-168.

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

- Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the *Ex Situ* Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.
- Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.
- Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.
- Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.
- Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.
- Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.
- Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.
- Pizzuto, F., 1999. On the structure, typology and periodism of a *Cystoseira brachycarpa* J. Agardh *emend* Giaccone community and of a *Cystoseira crinita* Duby community from the eastern coast of Sicily (Mediterranean Sea). *Plant Biosystems* 133(1), 15-35.
- SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).
- Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151G. Association with *Cystoseira crinita*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151G](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef
HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²¹

General description

This association is characterised by dense meadows of the brown alga *Ericaria crinita*. It colonizes the upper part of the infralittoral zone (0 to 0.5m depth range) where it can form dense beds on rocky bottoms, in well-lit environments, both sheltered from waves or subject to moderate hydrodynamism. In places with weak hydrodynamics, it tolerates sedimentation.

As most canopy-forming macroalgae, this habitat creates important secondary substrate that increases the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by beds of canopy forming Fucales of the species *Ericaria crinita* (Molinari & Guiry 2020). Its vicariants can also be found in several Mediterranean regions, as follows: *E. mediterranea* in the Western Mediterranean; *C. crinitophylla* and *C. sedoides* in the Strait of Sicily; *C. sedoides* in Algeria, Tunisia, and Pantelleria; and *Gongolaria barbata* in the Venice lagoon. In the Eastern Mediterranean, the species forming this habitat are *E. barbatula* and *C. corniculata* et al. with local distribution (i.e., *T. susanensis*, *E. giacconeii*, *Gongolaria rayssiae*).

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to Fucales, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. This association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-

²¹ According to the exposition to waves.

indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

- Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the *Ex Situ* Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.
- Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.
- Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.
- Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.
- Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.
- Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.
- Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.
- Pizzuto, F., 1999. On the structure, typology and periodism of a *Cystoseira brachycarpa* J. Agardh *emend* Giaccone community and of a *Cystoseira crinita* Duby community from the eastern coast of Sicily (Mediterranean Sea). *Plant Biosystems* 133(1), 15-35.
- Sales, M. and Ballesteros, E., 2012. Seasonal dynamics and annual production of *Cystoseira crinita* (Fucales: Ochrophyta) -dominated assemblages from the northwestern Mediterranean. *Scientia Marina* 76, 391-401.
- Sales, M., Ballesteros, E., Anderson, M. J., et al., 2012. Biogeographical patterns of algal communities in the Mediterranean Sea: *Cystoseira crinita*-dominated assemblages as a case study. *Journal of Biogeography* 39, 140-152.
- SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).
- Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151H. Association with *Cystoseira crinitophylla*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151H](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²²

General description

This association is characterised by the dominance of the brown alga *Cystoseira crinitophylla*. *C. crinitophylla* is a relatively sciaphilous species with evident and erect stems bearing more fluffy fronds developed in the apical part. It can be observed in the infralittoral zone at low depths, from one meter to about ten meters below sea level. It tends to develop in sunny areas, on rocks, but it can also be found on sandy bottoms. Generally, the typical environment in which it thrives is that of cold water, with temperatures lower than 18°C and high turbidity.

As most canopy-forming macroalgae, this habitat creates important secondary substrate that increases the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming Fucales of the species *Cystoseira crinitophylla*, endemic of the Mediterranean Sea. At first it was thought to be endemic to the Adriatic Sea only, but gradually it was also observed in other areas of the Mediterranean Sea, almost exclusively associated with other species of the same genus. Therefore, it does not form pure beds, being often associated with other species of the same family typical of the infralittoral plane: with *Gongolaria barbata* (upper Adriatic-Gulf of Trieste), with *Ericaria barbatula* (in the Aegean Sea) and with *E. brachycarpa* and *E. crinita* in other areas (Ionian Sea, Corsica and the Strait of Sicily).

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to Fucales, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. Axes and topophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

²² According to the exposition to waves.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests?. *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I.,

Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the *Ex Situ* Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151J. Association with *Cystoseira sauvageauana*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151J](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef)

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²³

General description

This association is characterised by the dominance of the brown alga *Gongolaria sauvageauana*. This infralittoral species generally lives within the first meter of water under the surface of the sea, on rocky shores in sheltered areas such as natural pools. *G. sauvageauana* also lives on sunny and sheltered rocky bottoms, where it can be found from the surface down to a depth of 10 meters. This canopy-forming macroalgae constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. In general canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages play a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the brown-algae canopy forming *Gongolaria sauvageauana*, (homotypic synonyms *Cystoseira sauvageauana* Hamel 1939 and *Treptacantha sauvageauana* Orellana & Sansón 2019), species, endemic of the Mediterranean Sea, and belonging to the Order Fucales. It is very rare in the Adriatic Sea. It features an erect and slightly iridescent thallus, of a brownish or greenish brown colour.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

This association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-

²³ According to the exposition to waves.

indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European WFD. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to

eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the *Ex Situ* Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151K. Association with *Cystoseira spinosa*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151K](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²⁴

General description

This association is characterised by the brown algae *Treptacantha ballesterosii* (formerly known as *Cystoseira spinosa*). The species is characteristic of well-lit environments of the lower infralittoral zone and is present on rocky substrates. It prefers clear waters with low sedimentation and environments with unidirectional hydrodynamics.

Canopy-forming macroalgae constitute important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming *Treptacantha ballesterosii* (Orellana & Sansón, 2019; formerly known as *Cystoseira spinosa*), belonging to the Order Fucales. This species, endemic of the Mediterranean Sea, is a perennial and its thallus may reach up to 20-50cm in height. In the Eastern Mediterranean and in the Adriatic Sea, it can replace *Gongolaria sauvageauana* and associate with *Ericaria brachycarpa* and *C. foeniculacea* in the upper and middle infralittoral zone. This habitat may also be co-dominated by the endemic colonial coral *Cladocora caespitosa*.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, and *C. spinosa* is listed in Appendix I "Strictly protected flora species" of the Bern Convention.

Associated species

In addition to Fucales, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. Axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians and the endemic colonial coral *Cladocora caespitosa*. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and

²⁴ According to the exposition to waves.

indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

Clausing, R.J., Falace, A., De La Fuente, G., Della Torre, C., Chiantore, M., Asnaghi, V., 2024. *Ex-situ* restoration of the Mediterranean forest-forming macroalga *Ericaria amentacea*: Optimizing growth in culture may not be the key to growth in the field. *Marine Environmental Research*, 202, 106718.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emeryg assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to

eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Lokovšek, A., Pitacco, V., Trkov, D., Zamuda, L.L., Falace, A., Orlando-Bonaca, M., 2023. Keep It Simple: Improving the Ex Situ Culture of *Cystoseira* s.l. to Restore Macroalgal Forests. *Plants*, 12(14), 2615.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.

Pizzuto, F., 1999. On the structure, typology and periodism of a *Cystoseira brachycarpa* J. Agardh *emend* Giaccone community and of a *Cystoseira crinita* Duby community from the eastern coast of Sicily (Mediterranean Sea). *Plant Biosystems* 133(1), 15-35.

Pons-Fita, A., Verdura, J., Santamaría, J., et al., 2020. Coexistence of the reef-building coral *Cladocora caespitosa* and the canopy-forming alga *Treptacantha ballesterosii*: Description of a new Mediterranean habitat. *scimar* [Internet]. 2020Sep.15 [cited 2023Apr.3]; 84(3), 263-71.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151L. Association with *Sargassum vulgare*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151L](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²⁵

General description

This association is characterised by the brown alga *Sargassum vulgare*, which is generally found in clean waters with strong light. However, in the Mediterranean, this infralittoral association achieves its maximum development in rough, shady biotopes. *S. vulgare* forms dense populations at depths between 10m and 20m; in particularly favourable conditions, it can reach a depth of 40m. It mainly grows on substrata whose slopes vary from the subvertical to the horizontal.

This canopy-forming brown macroalgae constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, this canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy-forming brown alga (phaeophyceae) of the species *Sargassum vulgare*. It is a characteristic species of rocky bottoms, cosmopolitan, present in the whole Mediterranean basin, except for the Northern Adriatic Sea and the Gulf of Lion.

Associated species

In addition to the characteristic species, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. Axes and topophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

²⁵ According to the exposition to waves.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.

Orlando-Bonaca, M., Mavrič B., 2014. Recurrence of *Sargassum vulgare* c. agardh in Slovenian coastal waters (Adriatic Sea). *Annales Ser. Hist. Nat.* 24(2), 109–114.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB151M. Association with *Dictyopteris polypodioides*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151M](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: #MB1.51e

General description

This association is characterised by the brown alga *Dictyopteris polypodioides*. This sciaphilous algae lives on rocky bottoms from the surface down to a depth of 40m. It can also be found in photophilous biotopes in the Southern Mediterranean Sea.

This canopy-forming macroalgae constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, this canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, this assemblage has a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy-forming brown alga *Dictyopteris polypodioides*, described as the holotype of the genus *Dictyopteris*. This species has been reported in South America (Brazil), Atlantic Islands, North America, Caribbean Islands, Africa, Asia and Europe. *Dictyopteris* spp. algae emanate a strong odour when out of the water, mainly because they contain C₁₁-hydrocarbons.

The genus belongs to the Order Dictyotales, and includes species with flattened, generally dichotomously branched thalli with a distinct central midrib.

Thalli are attached by a matted rhizoidal holdfast, up to 60cm long. Growth is via a row of meristematic cells that lie in a shallow depression on the branch apex. The genus comprises 35 species and considerable morphological and anatomical variation may occur between the small and the larger robust species.

Associated species

The species is often highly developed in association with other species such as *Padina pavonica*, *Halopteris filicina*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Peyssonnelia* sp., etc., described under the term "*Dictyopteris* forests". Associated vagile communities of the lower infralittoral rock are mainly dominated by crustaceans, molluscs, echinoderms, and fishes. Availability of high algal biomasses supports many herbivorous fish species and higher predators, and the appearance of erect alcyonaceans and calcified scleractinians promotes the creation of a three-dimensional environment increasing the habitat complexity and diversity.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, non-indigenous invasive species may

also contribute to the decline of these assemblages, such as *Caulerpa cylindracea* and *Womersleyella setacea*.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Boland, W. and Müller, D. G., 1987. On the odor of the Mediterranean seaweed *Dictyopteris membranacea*; New C11 hydrocarbons from marine brown algae - III. *Tetrahedron Letters*, 28:3.

[Lamare, V., Wacquant, C., Verlaque, M. in: DORIS, 07/12/2021: *Dictyopteris polypodioides* \(A.P. De Candolle\) J.V. Lamouroux.](#)

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 2

MB151W. Association with *Cystoseira compressa*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151W](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.511a or MB1.511c²⁶

General description

This infralittoral association is characterised by *Cystoseira compressa*, a brown alga living in well-lit surface environments, even moderately polluted. *C. compressa* is generally found in the first meter of water from the surface of the sea, both in areas with strong wave action at mid-wave level and in sheltered areas. This canopy-forming macroalga constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, this canopy-forming alga enhances biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, this assemblage plays a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming alga *Cystoseira compressa* (Esper) Gerloff & Nizamuddin, 1975, a species that is endemic of the Mediterranean and belongs to the Order Fucales. In the Eastern Mediterranean, *C. compressa* may be found, together with *Sargassum vulgare* and *Palisada perforata*, on the outside edges of the *Dendropoma cristatum* platforms.

Associated species

In addition to Fucales, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. Axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. This association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*. However, *C. compressa* shows higher tolerance to anthropogenic pressures than other species of the genus.

²⁶ According to the exposition to waves.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European WFD. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Cimini, J., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Onida, A., Falace, A., 2024. Can thermal anomalies impair the restoration of *Cystoseira* s.l. forests? *Marine Environmental Research*, 198, 106537.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15;326(Pt A):116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Moreda, U., Mazarrasa, I., Cebrian, E., Kaal, J., Ricart, A.M., Serrano, E., Serrano, O., 2024. Role of macroalgal forests within Mediterranean shallow bays in blue carbon storage. *Science of The Total Environment*, 934, 173219.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

Pinna, S., Piazzì, L., Ceccherelli, G., et al., 2020. Macroalgal forest vs sea urchin barren: patterns of macro-zoobenthic diversity in a large-scale Mediterranean study. *Marine Environmental Research* 159, 104955.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

MB1524. Association with *Cystoseira barbata*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB1524](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.5, MB1.51, MB1.51c, MB1.511c

General description

This association is characterised by the brown alga *Gongolaria barbata* (formerly known as *Cystoseira barbata*), living in well-lit and sheltered infralittoral environments. *G. barbata* is often present in lagoon environments in a freely floating form. This canopy-forming macroalgae constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance the biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages play a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming Fucales of the species *Gongolaria barbata* (Stackhouse) Kuntze 1891: 89.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to the characteristic species, this association may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges and bryozoans that can emerge from the canopy. The axes and tophules of canopy forming Fucales support many epibionts including algae, bryozoans, hydrozoans and ascidians. The association hosts a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods, and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fucales are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures and climate change related factors. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. The main threats are coastal urbanisation, pollution, eutrophication, sedimentation, increased turbidity, net fishing, human trampling and overgrazing by sea urchins. Moreover, invasion by alien species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as direct and indirect effects have been observed in assemblages invaded by non-indigenous invasive algae, such as *Lophocladia lallemandii*, *Womersleyella setacea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., Torras, X., Pinedo, S., et al., 2007. A new methodology based on littoral community cartography for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 55, 172-180.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

De La Fuente, G., Asnaghi, V., Chiantore, M., et al., 2019. The effect of *Cystoseira* canopy on the value of midlittoral habitats in NW Mediterranean, an emergy assessment. *Ecological Modelling* 404, 1-11.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Orlando-Bonaca, M., Savonitto, G., Asnaghi, V., Trkov, D., Pitacco, V., Šiško M., Makovec, T., Slavinec, P., Lokovšek, A., Ciriaco, S., Chiantore, M., Kaleb, S., Descourvières, E.P., Srijemsi, M., Falace, A., 2022. Where and how - new insight for brown algal forest restoration in the Adriatic. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9.

Piazzì, L. and Ceccherelli, G., 2017. Concomitance of oligotrophy and low grazing pressure is essential for the resilience of Mediterranean subtidal forests. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 123, 197-204.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1511](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Cirralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1511. Association with *Cystoseira zosteroides*

General description

This association is characterised by the high abundance of the brown alga *Ericaria zosteroides* (formerly known as *Cystoseira zosteroides*); it pertains to the coralligenous assemblage and can be present at a depth of up to 80m. *E. zosteroides* grows on calcareous coralline structures in deep water, but it is also able to colonize artificial habitats. This canopy-forming macroalga constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, this species enhances the biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, this assemblage has a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by *Ericaria zosteroides* Molinari & Guiry, 2020 (former name *Cystoseira zosteroides*), an endemic perennial and habitat-forming Mediterranean brown alga belonging to the Order Fucales, and one of the most representative brown seaweeds of deep-water assemblages.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, and *C. zosteroides* (now known as *E. zosteroides*) is in Appendix I “Strictly protected flora species” of the Bern Convention.

Associated species

In addition to *Ericaria zosteroides*, this association can include in the shallower bathymetric interval range, both sciaphilous and photophilous species such as *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, *Arthrocladia villosa*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Cutleria chilosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Dictyopteris* spp., *Halopteris filicina* and *Polysiphonia foeniculacea*. Branches, axes and tophules of these canopy-forming taxa support a large amount of epibionts including algae, bryozoans, small hydrozoans, and several Didemnidae ascidians. The basal layer is usually built by sciaphilous coralline algae such as *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mesophyllum alternans* and *Peyssonnelia rosa-marina* which may compose the largest part of the assemblage. This association may feature invertebrate species typical of the coralligenous assemblage such as sponges (i.e., *Axinella* spp., *Petrosia ficiformis*, *Spongia coelosia*, and *Sarcotragus* spp.), bryozoans, ascidians and the gorgonians *Paramuricea clavata* and *Eunicella cavolini*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Deep-water Fucales assemblages are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures, such as changes in water turbidity and sedimentation, fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. Recruitment of Fucales in deep water is low, enhancing their

vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances. Moreover, invasion by non-indigenous species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as the recruitment of canopy-forming algae may be inhibited by the overgrowth of invasive algae, such as *Womersleyella setacea*, *Caulerpa cylindracea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge' *Oceanography and Marine Biology* 44, 123-195.

Ballesteros, E., Garrabou, J., Hereu, B., et al., 2009. Deep-water stands of *Cystoseira zosteroides* C. Agardh (Fucales, Ochrophyta) in the Northwestern Mediterranean: insights into assemblage structure and population dynamics. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 82, 477-484.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15; 326 (Pt A): 116834.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

Reynes, L., Aurelle, D., Chevalier, C., et al., 2021. Population genomics and Lagrangian modeling shed light on dispersal events in the Mediterranean endemic *Ericaria zosteroides* (= *Cystoseira zosteroides* (Fucales)). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8, 683528.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1512](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1512. Association with *Cystoseira usneoides*

General description

This circalittoral association, pertaining to the coralligenous assemblage, is characterised by the high abundance of the brown alga *Treptacantha usneoides* (former name *Cystoseira usneoides*, homotypic synonym *Gongolaria usneoides* Molinari & Guiry 2020), and it can be present at a depth of up to 80m. *T. usneoides* grows on calcareous coralline structures in relatively deep rocky areas crossed by currents. This canopy-forming macroalga constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, this canopy-forming alga enhances the biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, this assemblage plays a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy-forming *Treptacantha usneoides* (Linnaeus) Orellana & Sansón, 2019 (former name *Cystoseira usneoides*, homotypic synonym *Gongolaria usneoides* Molinari & Guiry 2020), a perennial and habitat-forming seaweed species of deep-water assemblages belonging to the Order Fucales.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to *Treptacantha usneoides*, the association can include both sciaphilous and photophilous species such as *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, *Arthrocladia villosa*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Cutleria chilosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Dictyopteris* spp., *Halopteris filicina*, *Laminaria ochroleuca*, *Phyllariopsis purpurascens*, *Umbraulva dangeardii*, *Metacallophyllis laciniata*, *Phyllophora heredia* and *Polysiphonia foeniculacea*. Branches, axes and tophules of these canopy-forming taxa support a large amount of epibionts including algae, bryozoans, small hydrozoans, and several Didemnidae ascidians. The basal layer is usually built by sciaphilous coralline algae such as *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mesophyllum alternans* and *Peyssonnelia rosamarina* which may compose the largest part of the assemblage. The association may feature invertebrate species typical of the coralligenous assemblages, such as sponges (i.e., *Axinella* spp., *Petrosia ficiformis*, *Spongia coelosia*, and *Sarcotragus* spp.), bryozoans, ascidians and the gorgonians *Paramuricea clavata* and *Eunicella cavolini*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Deep-water Fucales assemblages are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures, such as changes in water turbidity and sedimentation, fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. Recruitment of Fucales in deep water is low, enhancing their

vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances. Moreover, invasion by non-indigenous species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as the recruitment of canopy-forming algae may be inhibited by the overgrowth of invasive algae, such as *Womersleyella setacea*, *Caulerpa cylindracea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge' *Oceanography and Marine Biology* 44, 123-195.

Ballesteros, E., Garrabou, J., Hereu, B., et al., 2009. Deep-water stands of *Cystoseira zosteroides* C. Agardh (Fucales, Ochrophyta) in the Northwestern Mediterranean: insights into assemblage structure and population dynamics. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 82, 477-484.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10:1213184.

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15;326(Pt A):116834.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia* 19 (1-2), 129-144.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to

eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1513](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1513. Association with *Cystoseira dubia*

General description

This circalittoral association is characterised by a high abundance of the brown alga *Cystoseira dubia*, occurring on hard substrata in areas subject to weak hydrodynamics and relatively strong sedimentation. This canopy-forming macroalga constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy-forming Fucales of the species *Cystoseira dubia* Valiante, 1883, a perennial and habitat-forming seaweed species of deep-water assemblages, often in association with *Nitophyllum tristromaticum*, *Ceramium bertholdii* and *Kallymenia patens*. Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to *Cystoseira dubia*, this association can include both sciaphilous and photophilous species such as *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, *Arthrocladia villosa*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Cutleria chilosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Dictyopteris* spp., *Halopteris filicina*, *Laminariales*, *Phyllariopsis purpurascens*, *Umbraulva dangeardii*, *Metacallophyllis laciniata*, *Phyllophora heredia* and *Polysiphonia foeniculacea*. The association may feature a very rich fauna made up of bryozoans, molluscs and polychaetes. The basal layer is usually built by sciaphilous coralline algae such as *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mesophyllum alternans* and *Peyssonnelia rosa-marina*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Deep-water Fucales assemblages are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures, such as changes in water turbidity and sedimentation, fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. Recruitment of Fucales in deep water is low, enhancing their vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances. Moreover, invasion by non-indigenous species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as the recruitment of canopy-forming algae may be inhibited by the overgrowth of invasive algae, such as *Womersleyella setacea*, *Caulerpa cylindracea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge' *Oceanography and Marine Biology* 44, 123-195.

Bianchelli, S., Frascchetti, S., Martini, F., Lo Martire, M., Nepote, E., Ippoliti, D., Rindi, F., and Danovaro R., 2023. Macroalgal forest restoration: the effect of the foundation species. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10: 1213184.

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Frascchetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Frascchetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15;326(Pt A):116834.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia* 19 (1-2), 129-144.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1514](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1514. Association with *Cystoseira corniculata*

General description

This association of the rocky circalittoral zone is characterised by high abundances of the brown alga *Cystoseira corniculata*. In the Mediterranean Sea, it develops on hard bottoms and rocky substrates down to depths of 70m. It is characterised by different morphotypes, depending on the depth to which they have adapted to live (i.e., the length of the primary branches, which are relatively shorter in the algae that develop close to the surface). This canopy-forming macroalga constitutes important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance biodiversity and the productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy-forming Fucales of the species *Cystoseira corniculata* (Turner) Zanardini, 1841, a perennial and habitat-forming seaweed species of deep-water assemblages, often in association with *Nitophyllum tristromaticum*, *Ceramium bertholdii* and *Kallymenia patens*.

Species of the *Cystoseira* genus (with the exclusion of *C. compressa*) are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to *Cystoseira corniculata*, the association can include both sciaphilous and photophilous species such as *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, *Arthrocladia villosa*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Cutleria chilosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Dictyopteris* spp., *Halopteris filicina*, *Laminariales*, *Phyllariopsis purpurascens*, *Umbraulva dangeardii*, *Metacallophyllis laciniata*, *Phyllophora heredia* and *Polysiphonia foeniculacea*. The association may feature a rich fauna made up of bryozoans, molluscs and polychaetes. The basal layer is usually built by sciaphilous coralline algae such as *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mesophyllum alternans* and *Peyssonnelia rosa-marina*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Deep-water Fucales assemblages are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures, such as changes in water turbidity and sedimentation, fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. Recruitment of Fucales in deep water is low, enhancing their vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances. Moreover, invasion by non-indigenous species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as the recruitment of canopy-forming algae may be inhibited by

the overgrowth of invasive algae, such as *Womersleyella setacea*, *Caulerpa cylindracea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge' *Oceanography and Marine Biology* 44, 123-195.

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Cebrian, E., Tamburello, L., Verdura, J., Guarnieri, G., Medrano, A., Linares, C., Hereu, B., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., Galobart, C. and Fraschetti, S., 2021. A Roadmap for the Restoration of Mediterranean Macroalgal Forests. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8:709219.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Fabbrizzi, E., Giakoumi, S., De Leo, F., Tamburello, L., Chiarore, A., Colletti, A., Coppola, M., Munari, M., Musco, L., Rindi, F., Rizzo, L., Savinelli, B., Franzitta, G., Grech, D., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Bianchelli, S., Mangialajo, L., Nasto, I., Sota, D., Orfanidis, S., Papadopoulou, N.K., Danovaro, R., Fraschetti, S., 2023. The challenge of setting restoration targets for macroalgal forests under climate changes. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 15;326(Pt A):116834.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia* 19 (1-2), 129-144.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74.

Molinari-Novoa, E. A. and Guiry, M. D., 2020. Reinstatement of the genera *Gongolaria* Boehmer and *Ericaria* Stackhouse (Sargassaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Notulae Algarum* 172, 1-10.

Montesanto, B. and Panayotidis, P., 2001. The *Cystoseira* spp. communities from the Aegean Sea (NE Mediterranean), *Mediterranean Marine Science* 2, 57-67.

Piazzì, L., Bonaviri, C., Castelli, A., et al., 2018. Biodiversity in canopy-forming algae: structure and spatial variability of the Mediterranean *Cystoseira* assemblages. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Sciences* 207, 132-141.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1515](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1515. Association with *Sargassum* spp.

General description

This circalittoral association is characterised by high abundances of the brown algae species of the Genus *Sargassum* on deep but well-lit hard substrata in oligotrophic conditions. These canopy-forming macroalgae constitute important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of hard bottoms, providing habitat, shelter, food, and nursery areas suitable for a multitude of marine organisms, both epiphytic and mobile. Thus, canopy-forming algae enhance the biodiversity and productivity of benthic systems. Moreover, these assemblages have a key role in carbon dioxide sequestration and climate change mitigation.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming Fucales of the Genus *Sargassum*, such as *S. hornschurchii* (usually growing in the sublittoral zone at a depth of 30-60m) and *S. acinarium* (growing in the sublittoral zone at a depth of 30-40m), often in association with other Fucales.

S. acinarium, *S. flavifolium*, *S. hornschurchii* and *S. trichocarpum* are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Associated species

In addition to the species of the genus *Sargassum*, this association can include both sciaphilous and photophilous species such as *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, *Arthrocladia villosa*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Cutleria chilosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Dictyopterus* spp., *Halopteris filicina*, Laminariales, *Phyllariopsis purpurascens*, *Umbraulva dangeardii*, *Metacallophyllis laciniata*, *Phyllophora heredia* and *Polysiphonia foeniculacea*. This association may feature a very rich fauna made up of bryozoans, molluscs and polychaetes. The basal layer is usually built by sciaphilous coralline algae such as *Lithophyllum incrustans*, *Mesophyllum alternans* and *Peyssonnelia rosa-marina*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Deep-water Fucales assemblages are in decline in several areas of the Mediterranean due to several anthropogenic pressures, such as changes in water turbidity and sedimentation, fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. The causes of this decline can change in relation to species, depth and geographic area. Recruitment of Fucales in deep water is low, enhancing their vulnerability to anthropogenic disturbances. Moreover, invasion by non-indigenous species may also contribute to the observed decline of these assemblages, as the recruitment of canopy-forming algae may be inhibited by the overgrowth of invasive algae, such as *Womersleyella setacea*, *Caulerpa cylindracea* and, in the Western basin, *Rugulopteryx okamura*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic

pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge' *Oceanography and Marine Biology* 44, 123-195.

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Cheminee, A., Sala, E., Pastor, J., et al., 2013. Nursery value of *Cystoseira* forests for Mediterranean rocky reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 442, 70-79.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia* 19 (1-2), 129-144.

Ivesa, L., Djakovac, T., Devescovi, M., 2016. Long-term fluctuations in *Cystoseira* populations along the west Istrian Coast (Croatia) related to eutrophication patterns in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 106, 162-173.

Mangialajo, L., Chiantore, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2008. Loss of furoid algae along a gradient of urbanisation and relationships with the structure of benthic assemblages. *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 358, 63-74.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2015. Decline and local extinction of Fucales in the French Riviera: the harbinger of future extinctions? *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 206-224.

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Verlaque, M., et al., 2016. The *Sargassum* conundrum: very rare, threatened or locally extinct in the NW Mediterranean and still lacking protection. *Hydrobiologia* 781, 3-23.

Thibaut, T., Blanfune, A., Boudouresque C.-F., et al., 2016. Unexpected temporal stability of *Cystoseira* and *Sargassum* forests in Port-Cros, one of the oldest Mediterranean marine National Parks. *Cryptogamie Algologie* 37, 61-90.

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1518](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512a

MC1518. Association with *Laminaria ochroleuca*

General description

This association is characterised by the brown algae *Laminaria ochroleuca* and occurs on hard or detritic substrata composed of sparse rocks, in areas affected by strong currents and the Atlantic influx (e.g., Sea of Alborán, Algerian coasts, Strait of Messina).

In the Mediterranean, this assemblage is observed in the circalittoral zone. In the Strait of Messina, it is found at depths between 30-95m, where it is exposed to unidirectional strong currents. *L. ochroleuca* may form continuous canopies, with fronds in wide blades that can be 6 m high, and densities of the order of one adult per 2 square meters or more. The association with Laminariales constitutes a habitat of high conservation value, as these Mediterranean deep-sea kelp forests increase the structural complexity of hard and soft bottoms providing suitable habitats, shelter and food for many epiphytic and mobile organisms.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming *Laminaria ochroleuca* Bachelot de la Pylaie, 1824. *L. ochroleuca* is listed in Appendix I “Strictly protected flora species” of the Bern Convention.

Associated species

In addition to *L. ochroleuca*, this association can include other sciaphilous species, with the substrata and spikes heavily covered in calcareous algae, sponges, bryozoans and ascidians. The three-dimensional development of these canopies offers habitats to a diversified fish fauna.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This species is protected above all due to its limited distribution in the Mediterranean. It is sensitive to changes in the chemical-physical conditions of deep waters and to the changes in sedimentation on rocky and detritic substrates. It can suffer mechanical damage caused by fishing, especially with trawled gear. There is also a possible threat due to direct harvesting for commercial purposes as the species contains numerous substances used in medicine and cosmetics.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral

reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Drew, E. A., 1972. Growth of a kelp forest at 60 m in the Straits of Messina. *Memorie di Biologia Marina Oceanografica N.S. 2*, 135-157.

Drew, E. A., Ireland, J. F., Muir, C., et al., 1982. Photosynthesis, respiration, and other factors influencing the growth of *Laminaria ochroleuca* Pyl. below 50 meters in the Straits of Messina. *Marine Ecology 3*, 335-355.

Flores-Moya, A., 2012. Warm Temperate Seaweed Communities: A Case Study of Deep-Water Kelp Forests from the Alboran Sea (SW Mediterranean Sea) and the Strait of Gibraltar' in: Wiencke, C., Bischof, K. (eds), *Seaweed Biology*. Ecological Studies, vol 219. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

Giaccone, G., 1972. Struttura, ecologia e corologia dei popolamenti a laminarie dello Stretto di Messina e del mare di Alboran. *Mem Biol Mar Oceanogr NS 2*, 37-59.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia 19* (1-2), 129-144.

Chemello, S., Sousa-Pinto, I. and Pereira, T.R., 2023. Optimising Kelp Cultivation to Scale up Habitat Restoration Efforts: Effect of Light Intensity on "Green Gravel" Production. *Hydrobiology 2*(2), 347-353.

Chemello, S., Dos Santos, I.A., Sousa-Pinto, I., and Pereira, T.R., 2024. Unlocking the potential of Green Gravel Production for efficient Kelp Restoration: how seeding density affects the development of the Golden Kelp *Laminaria ochroleuca*. *Phycology*, 4(3), 443-449.

Relini, G. and Tunesi, L. (eds), 2009. Le specie protette del protocollo SPA/BIO (Convenzione di Barcellona) presenti in Italia-Schede descrittive per l'identificazione. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea 16* (Suppl. 2), 172-174.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 2

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC3517](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC3.511

MC3517. Association with *Laminaria rodriguezii* on detritic beds

General description

This association is characterised by the brown algae *Laminaria rodriguezii*. The association occurs on circalittoral detritic beds, especially where rhodolith beds are present (the hooks of *L. rodriguezii* often take root in these rhodoliths), and on deep rocky bottoms or sea mounts, slopes, and rocky ledges of offshore islands. The association has been observed mostly at depths between 70m and 150m but can also be found at shallower depths (up to 40m) on the seafloor or in upwelling systems. The association develops under conditions of dim light, stable temperatures between 14°C and 15°C, in highly transparent seawater, and steady unidirectional currents. The association with Laminariales constitutes a habitat of high conservation value, as these Mediterranean deep-sea kelp forests increase the structural complexity of hard and soft bottoms providing suitable habitats, shelter and food for many epiphytic and mobile organisms.

Characteristic species

This association is characterised by the canopy forming *Laminaria rodriguezii* Bornet, 1888, a paleoendemic Mediterranean species. This association is distributed in the Western Mediterranean Sea, the Strait of Sicily, Adriatic Sea, and the Sea of Marmara.

L. rodriguezii is listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, and in Appendix I "Strictly protected flora species" of the Bern Convention.

Associated species

This habitat type is very often associated with unattached rhodoliths of the genus *Melobesia*. The endobiosis of the sediment is that of the biocenosis of the coastal detritic bottom, with a certain abundance of gravellicolous species. The epibiosis may be enriched by calcareous Rhodophyceae such as *Peyssonnelia rosa-marina*, *Neurocaulon* spp., and by species of the coralligenous biocenosis and of its facies, and other erect algae, such as *Cystoseira montagnei* var. *compressa*, *Ericaria zosteroides*, *Phyllariopsis brevipes*, and *P. purpurascens*. Many epibionts (hydrozoans and bryozoans, sponges, polychaetes and ascidians) are present between the fronds, one side being clearly more populated than the other because the thalli are laid down flat, overlapping on the seabed.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The deep-water Laminariales assemblages is declining in several areas of the Mediterranean under the influence of anthropogenic pressures and climate change. It is sensitive to changes in the chemical-physical conditions of deep waters and to the changes in sedimentation on rocky and detritic substrates. It can suffer mechanical damage caused by fishing, especially with trawled gear. There is also a possible threat due to direct harvesting for commercial

purposes as the species contains numerous substances used in medicine and cosmetics.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Barcelo, I. M. M. C., 1985. New reports of *Chondrymenia lobata* and *Laminaria rodriguezii* for the Iberian Peninsula. *Collectanea Botanica* (Barcelona) 16, 229.

Bo, M., Bertolino, M., Borghini, M., et al., 2011. Characteristics of the Mesophotic Megabenthic Assemblages of the Vercelli Seamount (North Tyrrhenian Sea). *Plos One* 6, e16357.

Boisset, F., Ferrer-gallego, P. P., Furnari, G., et al., 2016. Typification of the Mediterranean endemic deep-water macroalga *Laminaria rodriguezii* Bornet (Laminariaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Cryptogamie Algologie* 37, 121-132

Boudouresque, C. F., Blanfuné, A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., et al., 2017. Where seaweed forests meet animal forests: the examples of macroalgae in coral reefs and the Mediterranean coralligenous ecosystem' in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests*, Springer International Publishing (Switzerland), 369-396.

Drew, E. A., 1972. Growth of a kelp forest at 60 m in the Straits of Messina. *Memorie di Biologia Marina Oceanografica N.S.* 2, 135-157.

Drew, E. A., Ireland, J. F., Muir, C., et al., 1982. Photosynthesis, respiration, and other factors influencing the growth of *Laminaria ochroleuca* Pyl. below 50 meters in the Straits of Messina. *Marine Ecology* 3, 335-355.

Flores-Moya, A., 2012. Warm Temperate Seaweed Communities: A Case Study of Deep-Water Kelp Forests from the Alboran Sea (SW Mediterranean Sea) and the Strait of Gibraltar' in: Wiencke, C., Bischof, K. (eds), *Seaweed Biology*. Ecological Studies, vol 219. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

Giaccone, G., 1967. Popolamenti a *Laminaria rodriguezii* Bornet sul Banco Apollo dell'Isola di Ustica (Mar Tirreno). *Nuova Thalassia* 3, 1-9.

Giaccone G., 1969. Note sistematiche ed osservazioni fitosociologiche sulla *Laminaria rodriguezii* del Mediterraneo occidentale. *Giornale Botanico Italiano* 103, 407-474.

Giaccone, G., 1972. Struttura, ecologia e corologia dei popolamenti a laminarie dello Stretto di Messina e del mare di Alboran. *Mem Biol Mar Oceanogr NS* 2, 37-59.

Giaccone, G. and Di Martino, V, 1997. Syntaxonomic relationships of the Mediterranean phytobenthos assemblages: paleoclimatic bases and evolutive tendencies. *Lagascalia* 19 (1-2), 129-144.

Joher, S., Ballesteros, E., Cebrian, E., et al., 2012. Deep-water macroalgal-dominated coastal detritic assemblages on the continental shelf off Mallorca and Menorca (Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean). *Botanica Marina* 55, 485-497.

Relini, G. and Tunesi, L. (eds), 2009. Le specie protette del protocollo SPA/BIO (Convenzione di Barcellona) presenti in Italia-Schede descrittive per l'identificazione. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 16 (Suppl. 2), 172-174.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Žuljević, A., Peters, A. F., Nikolić, V., et al., 2016. The Mediterranean deep-water kelp *Laminaria rodriguezii* is an endangered species in the Adriatic Sea. *Marine Biology* 163, 69.

Group 3: Shellfish beds

Figure 03-01, Native *Ostrea edulis* bed in Brittany, France, NE Atlantic]

Source: Pouvreau Stephane (2017). Underwater images of the last native oysters beds in Brittany (France). Ifremer. <https://doi.org/10.24351/48842>

Group 3

MA122. *Mytilus edulis* and/or barnacle communities on wave-exposed Atlantic littoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA122](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock

HD: <1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MA1221](#), [MA1222](#), [MA1223](#)

OSPAR:

#Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds on mixed and sandy sediment

DE:

=02.01.01.01.02.02

IE:

#LS.LBR.LMus.Myt.Mx

#LR.HLR.MusB.MytB

General description

This habitat has a large natural range in the North East Atlantic region, extending from the Canary Islands and Azores in the west to the Skagerrak coast of Sweden in the east. The precise extent is unknown.

This habitat type is found in the mid to upper eulittoral zone, on shores that are moderately or very exposed to wave action. It is characterised by bedrock and boulders dominated by the mussel *Mytilus edulis*, barnacles *Chthamalus* spp. and/or *Semibalanus balanoides* and limpets *Patella* spp. There is considerable regional variation in the species and zonation of the barnacles. Although this habitat with its associated communities is naturally resilient, it is also subject to considerable natural variability (for example following storm damage), making trends difficult to distinguish. It has been suggested that climate change may not lead to a simple poleward shift in the distribution of intertidal organisms on rocky shores, but could cause localised extinctions in a series of hotspots due to the inability of species to spread to suitable habitats.

Characteristic species

Mytilus edulis, *Semibalanus balanoides*, *Chthamalus* spp.

Associated species

Flatfish (*Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Limanda limanda*). Seabirds such as oystercatcher (*Haematopus* spp.), herring gull (*Larus argentatus*), eider ducks (*Somateria mollissima*).

Some shores are characterised by dense bands of the barnacle *Semibalanus balanoides* and the limpet *Patella vulgata*. The barnacles may be covered by *Porphyra umbilicalis* on the upper shore of exposed sites. Cracks and crevices in the rock provide a refuge for small individuals of the mussel *M. edulis*, winkles *Littorina saxatilis* and the whelk *Nucella lapillus*. Red seaweeds also frequently occupy damp crevices, particularly *Ceramium shuttleworthianum*, *Corallina officinalis*, *Osmundea pinnatifida* and encrusting coralline algae, but the non-vesiculate form of the wrack *Fucus vesiculosus* might be present. Large numbers of the winkle *Littorina littorea* often dominate fields of large boulders or shores with a more mixed substratum.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This is a relatively robust habitat, as it develops on wave exposed rocky shores, although it is vulnerable to several pressures. The two pressures that are mostly likely to have an impact on this habitat are pollution incidents, such as oil spills, and climate change. It has been suggested that climate change may not lead to a simple poleward shift in the distribution of intertidal organisms

on rocky shores, but could cause localised extinctions in a series of hotspots due to the inability of species to spread to suitable habitats.

Coastal development, including coast protection works that can alter the degree of exposure, as well as shore collection, trampling and chronic effects of chemical contamination, e.g., from Tributyl tin, are also potential pressures, but are likely to be less significant than for more sheltered rocky shores.

Best practices in nature restoration

There are limited options for specific conservation and management measures for this habitat. More general beneficial measures include pollution control and regulation, development control and contingency plans to be followed in the event of a major pollution incident, representation in Marine Protected Areas, and measures to reduce global warming and sea level rise.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: *Mytilus edulis* and/or barnacle communities on wave-exposed Atlantic littoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: *Mytilus edulis* and barnacles on very exposed eulittoral rock.](#)

[OSPAR: Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Mytilus edulis* and barnacles on very exposed eulittoral rock.](#)

Group 3

MA124. Mussel and/or barnacle communities with seaweeds on Atlantic littoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA124](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral rock

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MA1241](#), [MA1243](#), [MA1244](#), [MA123F1](#)

DE:
<02.01.01.01

IE:
=LR.MLR.BF

General description

This habitat type describes moderately exposed rocky shores characterised by a mosaic of fucoids and barnacles on bedrock and boulders, where the extent of the fucoid cover is typically less than the blanket cover associated with sheltered shores. Other species are normally present as well in this habitat, including the winkle *Littorina littorea*, the whelk *Nucella lapillus* and the red seaweed *Mastocarpus stellatus*. Beneath the band of yellow and grey lichens at the top of the shore, there is a zone dominated by the wrack *Pelvetia canaliculata*, scattered barnacles, while the black lichen *Verrucaria maura* covers the rock surface (MA1241). Below, on the mid shore, the wrack *Fucus vesiculosus* generally forms a mosaic with the barnacle *Semibalanus balanoides* and the limpet *Patella vulgata* (MA1243). Finally, the wrack *Fucus serratus* dominates the lower shore, while a variety of red seaweeds can be found underneath the *F. serratus* canopy (MA1244).

Several variants have been described: lower shore bedrock and boulders characterised by mosaics of *F. serratus* and turf-forming red seaweeds (MA12441); where the density of *F. serratus* is greater (typically Common-Superabundant) and the abundance of red seaweeds less MA123F1 should be recorded. The presence of boulders and cobbles on the shore can increase the micro-habitat diversity, which often results in a greater species richness. Although the upper surface of the boulders may bear very similar communities to MA123F1, there is often an increase in fauna (crabs, tube-forming polychaetes, sponges and bryozoans) and MA12442 should be recorded. Sand-influenced exposed to moderately exposed lower shore rock can be characterised by dense mats of *Rhodothamniella floridula* (MA1245).

The littoral community of fucoids, barnacles and limpets on moderately exposed shores is relatively unstable, existing in a state of dynamic equilibrium in which biological or physical changes can create quite drastic effects on the pattern of the community (Southward & Southward, 1978); therefore, the biotope itself is subject to change and may cycle between different biotopes or sub-biotopes.

Characteristic species

Three biotopes have been described. In the mid eulittoral zone, the mussels may form a band or large patches with scattered bladder wrack *Fucus vesiculosus* (MA1246). In the lower eulittoral zone, a range of red seaweeds including *Mastocarpus stellatus* and *Palmaria palmata* occur among the mussels, in higher abundance than the mid eulittoral (MA1247). Clay outcrops in the mid to lower eulittoral may be bored by a variety of piddocks including *Pholas dactylus*, *Barnea candida* and *Petricola pholadiformis*, while the surface is characterised by small clumps of the mussel *M. edulis*, the barnacle *Elminius modestus* and the winkle *Littorina littorea* (MA1248).

Associated species

Ephemeral green seaweeds, such as *Ulva intestinalis* and *Ulva Lactuca*, commonly occur on the shells of the mussels. Barnacles are common on both the mussel valves and on patches of bare rock, where the limpet *Patella vulgata* is found as well, often in high abundance. The whelk *Nucella lapillus* and a range of littorinids also occur within the mussel bed.

Other species that may also occur are *Ulva intestinalis*, *Fucus serratus*, *Pelvetia canaliculata*, *Rhodothamniella floridula*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

As the community is naturally unstable, impacts of anthropogenic pressures are not well-known. It can be assumed that similar pressures as for MA122 could be relevant (pollution incidents such as oil spills, climate change with temperature regime shifts, coastal development with effects on wave exposure).

Best practices in nature restoration

It is assumed that similar general beneficial measures as for MA122 could be relevant (pollution control, development control, representation in Marine Protected Areas, measures to reduce global warming and sea level rise).

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Mussel and/or barnacle communities with seaweeds on Atlantic littoral rock.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Barnacles and fucooids on moderately exposed shores.](#)

Group 3

MA227. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic littoral zone

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA227](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Littoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1140, <1170

[European Red List](#):

=NEAA2.72

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA2271](#)

OSPAR:

#*Ostrea edulis* beds

#Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds on mixed and sandy sediment

DE:

>02.01.02.01

>02.01.04.01

>02.01.05.01

#02.01.01.01.02

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

<LS.LBR

<LS.LBR.LMus

#LS.LBR.LMus.Myt

General description

Sediment shores characterised by beds of adult mussels *Mytilus edulis* occur principally on mid and lower eulittoral mixed substrata (mainly cobbles and pebbles on muddy sediments) in a wide range of exposure conditions. In high densities, the mussels bind the substratum and provide a habitat for many infaunal and epifaunal species. This biotope is also found in lower shore tide-swept areas, such as in the tidal narrows of Scottish sea lochs. A fauna of dense juvenile mussels may be found in sheltered firths, attached to algae on shores of pebbles, gravel, sand, mud and shell debris with a strandline of fucoid algae.

Adult mussel beds can be found below a band of ephemeral green seaweeds (MA4211) on more exposed, predominantly rocky shores. On sheltered, predominantly rocky shores either a *Fucus vesiculosus* dominated biotope or a biotope dominated by the wrack *Ascophyllum nodosum* (MA123D2; MA123E2) can be found above, or the barnacle dominated biotope (MA12233).

The temporal stability of mussel beds can vary considerably. Some beds are permanent, maintained by recruitment of spat in amongst adults. Other beds are ephemeral, large amounts of spat settle intermittently on a cobble basement. The mussels rapidly build up mud and are unable to remain attached to the stable cobbles; then, they can be washed away during gales. A second example of ephemeral mussel dominated biotopes occurs when mussel spat ("mussel crumble") settles on the superficial shell of cockle beds.

"Mussel Mud", composed of faeces, pseudofaeces and sediment, accumulates underneath mussel beds. In sheltered habitats, pseudofaeces (undigested, filtered particles) can build up forming a thick layer of anoxic mud. The layer of mud may prevent the attachment of mussels to the underlying substratum, but the silt layer often consolidates and forms a firm clay bank which is very erosion resistant including the mussels embedded into it. "Mussel Mud" (that is not anoxic) supports a diverse range of infauna.

OSPAR habitat: Beds of the oyster *Ostrea edulis* occurring at densities of 5 or more per square meter on shallow mostly sheltered sediments (typically 0-10m in depth, but occasionally down to a depth of 30m). There may be considerable quantities of dead oyster shell making up a substantial portion of the substratum.

Characteristic species

Mytilus edulis, *Ostrea edulis*

Associated species

The wrack *Fucus vesiculosus* is often found attached to either the mussels or cobbles and it can be abundant. The mussels are often encrusted with the barnacles *Semibalanus balanoides*, *Austrominius modestus* or *Balanus crenatus*. Where boulders are present, they can support the limpet *Patella*

vulgata. The winkles *Littorina littorea* and *L. saxatilis*, and small individuals of the crab *Carcinus maenas*, are common among the mussels, while areas of sediment may contain the lugworm *Arenicola marina*, the sand mason *Lanice conchilega*, the cockle *Cerastoderma edule*, and other infaunal species.

Although a wide range of species are associated with *Mytilus edulis* bed biotopes, these characterizing species occur in a range of other biotopes and are, therefore, not considered to be obligate associates. Associated fish species are *Myoxocephalus scorpius*, *Zoarces viviparus*, *Pomatoschistus microps*, *P. minutus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Clupea harengus*, *Syngnathus rotellatus* and *Platichthys flesus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fisheries are the principal anthropogenic threat to this habitat. The pressures from fisheries activities, especially with mobile bottom-contacting gear, are exacerbated when the settlement of spatfall is low. Another threat to this habitat comes from alien species. The introduced Pacific Oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*) has increased significantly in the Wadden Sea since the beginning of the 21st century, and one of the preferred settlement structures for the larvae are existing mussel beds. This resulted in the conversion of a large parts of mussel beds into oyster beds. In the Lower Saxony part of the Wadden Sea, for example, every intertidal mussel bed holds at least some oysters. Bait collection can have a localised effect, while phytoplankton blooms, produced by nutrient enrichment (e.g., industrial and residential sewage discharge, agriculture), are another potential threat. Mussel beds could also have intermediate sensitivity to anti-fouling substances and heavy metal contaminants. Climate change impacts the reproductive success directly or indirectly, e.g., via a higher abundance of shrimp (*C. crangon*) surviving the winter, which are major predators of spat.

Other threats are discharges from urbanisation, residential and commercial development, aquaculture, pollution and nutrient enrichment (eutrophication), human induced changes in hydraulic conditions, and climate change (change in abiotic conditions, temperature changes, alien species).

Best practices in nature restoration

The mussel beds that characterise this habitat may be transient and dynamic or permanent and persistent. Their capacity to recover is generally strong where there are good spatfalls, although development into established beds will be influenced by many factors, such as the presence of predators, local hydrographic conditions, and exposure of the location.

Blue mussels are sessile, attached organisms that are unable to repair significant damage to individuals. They do not reproduce asexually; therefore, the only mechanism for recovery from significant impacts is larval recruitment to the bed or the area where a bed previously existed. Recruitment is often sporadic, occurring in unpredictable pulses, although persistent mussel beds can be maintained by relatively low levels or sporadic recruitment. Recovery from human activity impacts may take at least 5 years, although in certain circumstances and under some environmental conditions (e.g., recurring physical disturbance or sporadic recruitment) recovery may take significantly longer. Nearly complete recovery from disturbance is a characteristic

common to *Mytilus* beds throughout the world. The main management measures to assist the conservation of this habitat are the regulation of the fisheries that target the mussel beds, and the protection from physical damage. Specific measures include control of fisheries through quotas, closed areas, specified fishing methods, regulations on the movement of spat including collection of spat for aquaculture, and prohibiting spat collection from intertidal areas. An example is given in the Wadden Sea, where a mussel fishing programme has been in place for decades (last updated in 2017). The programme regulates the mussel industry regarding the extraction of seed and stocked mussels and specifies which areas are accessible for extraction and cultivation.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: Littoral biogenic reefs.](#)

[JNCC: Littoral mussel beds on sediment.](#)

[Mussel fishing programme in the Wadden Sea.](#)

[OSPAR: Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds.](#)

[OSPAR: *Ostrea edulis* beds.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Mytilus edulis* beds on littoral sediments.](#)

[Tulp, I., Bolle, L. J., Dänhardt, A., de Vries, P., Haslob, H., Jespen, N., Scholle, J., & van der Veer, H. W., 2017. Wadden Sea Quality Status Report: Fish. Common Wadden Sea Secretariat.](#)

Group 3

MB222. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic infralittoral zone

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB222](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1130, #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB2221](#), [MB2222](#), [MB2223](#)

OSPAR:

#*Ostrea edulis* beds

#Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds on mixed and sandy sediment

DE:

#02.02.01.01.02

>02.02.04.01.01

#02.02.06.01.02

>02.02.08.01.01

>02.02.10.01.02

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

=SS.SMx.IMx.Ost

=SS.SMx.IMx.Lim

General description

This habitat has a depth range of 0-5m, 5-10m, or 10-20m. It has a sheltered to very sheltered, or even extremely sheltered location preference, and a salinity that may be full (30-35‰) to variable (18-35‰). This habitat type describes mixed muddy gravel and sand often in tide-swept narrows in the entrances or sills of sea lochs with beds or 'nests' of *Limaria hians*. The *Limaria* form woven 'nests' or galleries from byssus and fragments of seaweeds, so that the animals themselves cannot be seen from above the seabed. *Modiolus modiolus* sometimes occur at the same sites, lying over the top of the *Limaria* bed. Other fauna associated with this biotope include echinoderms (*Ophiothrix fragilis*, *Ophiocomina nigra* and *Asterias rubens*), *Buccinum undatum*, mobile crustaceans (e.g., *Pagurus bernhardus*), *Alcyonium digitatum* and hydroids such as *Plumularia setacea*, *Kirchenpaueria pinnata* and *Nemertesia* spp. Sometimes, red seaweeds such as *Phycodrys rubens* occur if the beds are in shallow enough water. The carpet of byssus threads, coarse sediment, and shell produced by *L. hians* provides refugia, and substratum for attachment for a wide variety of sessile and sedentary species.

Dense beds of the oyster *Ostrea edulis* can occur on muddy fine sand or sandy mud mixed sediments. There may be considerable quantities of dead oyster shell making up a substantial portion of the substratum. The clumps of dead shells and oysters can support large numbers of *Ascidella aspersa* and *Ascidella scabra*. Sponges such as *Halichondria bowerbanki* may also be present. Several conspicuously large polychaetes, such as *Chaetopterus variopedatus* and terebellids, as well as additional suspension-feeding polychaetes, such as *Myxicola infundibulum* and *Sabella pavonine*, may be important in distinguishing this biotope, while the *opisthobranch* *Philine aperta* may also be frequent in some areas. A turf of seaweeds such as *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Nitophyllum punctatum* and *Spyridia filamentosa* may also be present.

Characteristic species

Modiolus modiolus, *Mytilus edulis* or *Limaria hians* or *Ostrea edulis* (see subsection "General description"), *Sabella pavonina*, *Ascidella aspersa*, *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Myxicola infundibulum*, *Spyridia filamentosa*, Seraphsidae, *Ascidella scabra*, *Philine aperta*, Corallinacea, barnacles (*Elminius modestus* and *Balanus Balanus*).

Associated species

Lanice conchilega, *Fabulina fabula*, *Polydora ciliate*, *Pagurus bernhardus*, *Buccinum undatum*, *Asterias rubens*, *Carcinus maenas*, *Hyas araneus*, *Ophiothrix fragilis*, *Ophiocomina nigra*.

Associated fish species are *Gobius niger*, *Pholis gunnellus*, *Myoxocephalus scorpius* and *Zoarces vivparus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures on this habitat are chemical pressures (contamination), physical loss (extraction, removal of substratum, abrasion, surface disturbance), and biological pressures (invasive species, microbial pathogens, removal of target and non-target species).

Best practices in nature restoration

Essential management measures include continued regulation of fisheries, control of the spread of introduced species, reduction of the risk of transmission of disease and maintenance of a suitable habitat to support successful spat fall. The active restoration of oyster beds is already taking place and has proven to be a successful measure. Moreover, measures to improve water quality are to be taken into consideration.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: *Limaria hians* beds in tide-swept sublittoral muddy mixed sediments.](#)

[JNCC: *Ostrea edulis* beds on shallow sublittoral mixed sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: Intertidal *Mytilus edulis* beds.](#)

[OSPAR: *Ostrea edulis* beds.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Limaria hians* beds in tide-swept sublittoral muddy mixed sediments.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Ostrea edulis* beds on shallow sublittoral muddy mixed sediment.](#)

Group 3

MC223. Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC223](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC2231](#), [MC2232](#), [MC2233](#), [MC2234](#), [MC2235](#), [MC2236](#)

OSPAR:

#Oyster beds

#*Modiolus modiolus* beds

DE:

#02.02.01.01.02

>02.02.04.01.01

#02.02.06.01.02

>02.02.08.01.01

>02.02.10.01.02

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

>SS.SBR.SMus.ModMx

>SS.SBR.SMus.ModT

>SS.SBR.SMus.ModMvar

=SS.SBR.SMus.MytSS

General description

Sublittoral mussel beds comprised of either the horse mussel *Modiolus modiolus* or the common mussel *Mytilus edulis*. These communities may be sublittoral extensions of littoral reefs or exist independently. They are found in a variety of habitats, ranging from sheltered estuaries and marine inlets to open coasts and offshore areas, and may occupy a range of substrata, although due to the stabilising effect that such communities have on the substratum, muddy mixed sediments are typical. A diverse range of epibiota and infauna often exists in these communities.

Muddy gravels and coarse sands in the deeper waters of continental seas may contain venerid bivalves with beds of *Modiolus modiolus* (depth range 50-100m).

Shallow sublittoral mixed sediment, in fully marine coastal habitats or sometimes in variable salinity conditions in the outer regions of estuaries, are characterised by beds of the common mussel *Mytilus edulis* (depth range 0-20m).

In the southern region around the Macaronesian islands as well as along the Iberian Coast and in the Bay of Biscay, circalittoral bivalve reefs can also be dominated by the oyster *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, potentially in association with the coral *Dendrophyllia cornigera* and the brachiopods *Megerlia truncata*, *Novocrania anomala*.

Characteristic species

The main habitat-forming species are *Modiolus modiolus*, *Mytilus edulis*, *Hiatella arctica* (only MC2236), *Ostrea edulis* and *Neopycnodonte cochlear*.

Associated species

Other species that are also characteristic (but whose presence is not mandatory) are *Alcyonium digitatum* and *Urticina felina*, hydroids such as *Abietinaria abietina* and *Sertularia argentea*, *Mimachlamys varia*, *Gammarus salinus*, *Tubificoides*, *Harmothoe* spp., *Kefersteinia cirrata*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Asterias rubens*.

The clumping of the byssus threads of the *Modiolus modiolus* creates a stable habitat that attracts a very rich infaunal community with a high density of polychaete species, including *Glycera lapidum*, *Paradoneis lyra*, *Aonides paucibranchiata*, *Laonice bahusiensis*, *Protomystides bidentata*, *Lumbrineris* spp., *Mediomastus fragilis* and syllids such as *Exogone* spp. and *Sphaerosyllis* spp. Bivalves such as *Spisula elliptica*, *Timoclea ovata* and other venerid species are also common. Brittlestars such as *Amphipholis squamata* may also occur with this community.

Epifaunal species in addition to the *M. edulis* include the whelks *Nucella lapillus* and *Buccinum undatum*, the common starfish *Asterias rubens*, the spider crab *Maja squinado* and the anemone *Urticina felina*. Relatively few records are available for this biotope, and it is possible that as more data is

accumulated, separate estuarine and fully marine sub-biotopes may be described.

Other species that are also occurring in this habitat include *Ophiothrix fragilis*, *Spirobranchus triqueter*, *Halecium* spp., *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*, ascidians such as *Ascidiella aspersa*, *Corella parallelogramma* and *Ciona intestinalis*.

Associated fish species are *Gobius niger*, *Pholis gunnellus*, *Myoxocephalus scorpius* and *Zoarces vivparus*.

Although a wide range of species are associated with *Mytilus edulis* reefs or bed biotopes, these characterizing species occur in a range of other biotopes and are, therefore, not considered to be obligate associates. *Mytilus edulis* beds are not dependent on associated species to create or modify habitat, or to provide food or other resources, although their loss would represent a loss of diversity. It should be noted that for attached organisms the sensitivity of the *Mytilus edulis* biotope would be of primary concern, as removal of the reef would also lead to removal of the attached species.

The *Neopycnodonta* reefs can be accompanied by the algae *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, the sponge *Petrosia (Petrosia) ficiformis*, the anthozoan *Parazoanthus axinellae*, gorgonians *Eunicella verrucosa* and hydrozoan *Gymnangium montagui* as well as polychaetes from the family Serpulidae. Also, echinoderms are common such as *Antedon bifida*, *Holothuria forskali*, *Echinus* spp. and *Sphaerechinus granularis* as well as the bryozoan *Myriapora truncata*. Associated fish species are *Coris julis*, *Ctenolabrus rupestres*, *Diplodus cervinus*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Pollachius pollachius*, and *Serranus cabrilla*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are physical loss or physical change to another seabed or sediment type, abrasion, penetration or disturbance of the seabed, habitat structure changes, siltation rate changes, invasive species, and chemical pressures (contamination).

Best practices in nature restoration

Habitat restoration projects may translocate stock to repopulate areas of suitable habitat (Elsässer et al., 2013). No evidence was found for detrimental, genetic effects arising from this practice, although there is the potential also for the movement of pathogens and non-indigenous, invasive species. Translocation of individuals was demonstrated to support larval settlement on artificial reefs, when measured against cultch alone, and is a useful technique to support habitat restoration (Fariñas-Franco et al., 2016). Inter-site differences in shell morphology, reflecting phenotypic differences, have been observed between populations that relate to adaptation to local environmental conditions. Translocating individuals with ecophenotypes that are different to local populations may impact on the success of translocation and may result in negative impacts on local populations through gene flow.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Elsäßer, B., Fariñas-Franco, J.M., Wilson, C.D., Kregting, L. & Roberts, D., 2013. Identifying optimal sites for natural recovery and restoration of impacted biogenic habitats in a special area of conservation using hydrodynamic and habitat suitability modelling. *Journal of Sea Research*, 77, 11-21.

[EUNIS habitat classification: Bivalve reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: *Modiolus modiolus* beds with *Chlamys varia*, sponges, hydroids and bryozoans on slightly tide-swept very sheltered Atlantic circalittoral mixed substrata.](#)

[EUNIS: *Mytilus edulis* beds on Atlantic circalittoral sediment.](#)

Fariñas-Franco, J.M., Sanderson, W.G., and Roberts, D., 2016. Phenotypic differences may limit the potential for habitat restoration involving species translocation: a case study of shape ecophenotypes in different populations of *Modiolus modiolus* (Mollusca: Bivalvia). *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26: 76-94.

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natusch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: *Modiolus modiolus* beds on open coast circalittoral mixed sediment.](#)

[JNCC: *Modiolus modiolus* beds with hydroids and red seaweeds on tide-swept circalittoral mixed substrata.](#)

[MarLIN: *Modiolus modiolus* beds with hydroids and red seaweeds on tide-swept circalittoral mixed substrata.](#)

[MarLIN: *Mytilus edulis* beds on sublittoral sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: *Modiolus modiolus* beds.](#)

[OSPAR: *Ostrea edulis* beds.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): *Modiolus modiolus* beds on open coast circalittoral mixed sediment.](#)

Figure 03-02, Bay barnacle and bryozoan (*Electra crustulenta*), Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea

Source: Bay barnacle and bryozoan (*Electra crustulenta*), Pyhtää, The Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea, © Maiju Lanki and Metsähallitus, 2012

Group 3

MB231. Baltic infralittoral bottoms dominated by epibenthic bivalves

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB231](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Partial overlap with all infralittoral substrates²⁷

HD: #1160, <1170

European Red List:

≈BAL38²⁸, <BAL7, <BAL9, <BAL17

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB2311](#), [MB2312](#), [MB2313](#)

HELCOM

#AA.A1E

#AA.B1E

#AA.E1E

#AA.H1E

#AA.I1E

#AA.J1E

#AA.M1E

DE:

#05.02.01.01.03

#05.02.06.01.04

#05.02.08.01.03

#05.02.10.01.02

#05.02.11.01.02

#§ 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone of which sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic bivalves cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Substrate can be rocky, hard clay, shell gravel, coarse, sandy or muddy.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all, more common in exposed areas; Depth range: photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Mytilus spp., *Modiolus modiolus*, *Dreissena polymorpha*, *Valvata* spp.

Associated species

Epibenthic bivalves are consumed by the common eider (*Somateria mollissima*), the long-tailed duck (*Clangula hyemalis*), common scoter (*Melanitta nigra*) and velvet scoter (*M. fusca*), as well as several species of *Cyprinidae* and the flounder (*Platichthys flesus*).

Mytilus communities host snails *Hydrobia* spp. and *Theodoxus fluviatilis*, *Gammarus amphipods*, *Idotea* isopods, polychaetes, nemertean worms and Platyhelminthes flatworms (Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by sedimentation (covering the bivalves) and physical disturbance (e.g., caused by bottom trawling).

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration by regulation of activities that result in physical damage (e.g., fishing with bottom contacting gear) or in high sedimentation nearby the habitat (e.g., sand extraction or deposition), measures to reduce eutrophication and general management in terms of inclusion of this habitat into marine protected areas.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

²⁷ Not a good correlation, because the MB231 does not limit to any substrate.

²⁸ BAL38 is relatively similar to MB231.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.M1C Baltic photic mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MC231. Baltic circalittoral bottoms dominated by epibenthic bivalves

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC231](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Partial overlap with all circalittoral substrates²⁹

HD: <1170

European Red List: BAL42³⁰, BAL44³¹, BAL45³², BAL49³³, BAL56³⁴

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC2311](#), [MC2312](#)

HELCOM:

#AB.A1E

#AB.B1E

#AB.H1E

#AB.I1E

#AB.J1E

#AB.M1E

DE:

#05.02.01.01.03

#05.02.06.01.04

#05.02.08.01.03

#05.02.10.01.02

#05.02.11.01.02

#§ 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone of various sediments. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic bivalves cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Typical depth range is approximately from 15-20m downwards.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Mytilus spp., *Modiolus modiolus*, *Astarte* spp.

Associated species

Epibenthic bivalves are consumed by the common eider (*Somateria mollissima*), the long-tailed duck (*Clangula hyemalis*), common scoter (*Melanitta nigra*) and velvet scoter (*M. fusca*), as well as several species of *Cyprinidae* and the flounder (*Platichthys flesus*).

Mytilus communities host snails *Hydrobia* spp. and *Theodoxus fluviatilis*, *Gammarus* amphipods, *Idotea* isopods, polychaetes, nemertean worms and Platyhelminthes flatworms (Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by sedimentation (covering the bivalves) and physical disturbance (e.g., caused by bottom trawling).

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration by regulation of activities that result in physical damage (e.g., fishing with bottom contacting gear) or in high sedimentation nearby the habitat (e.g., sand extraction or deposition), measures to reduce eutrophication and general management in terms of inclusion of this habitat into marine protected areas.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

²⁹ Not a good correlation, because the MC231 does not limit to any substrate.

³⁰ BAL42 is related to MC231, but not specific.

³¹ BAL44 is related to MC231, but not specific.

³² BAL45 is related to MC231, but not specific.

³³ BAL49 is related to MC231, but not specific.

³⁴ BAL56 is related to MC231, but not specific.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.M1C Baltic photic mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MD231. Baltic offshore circalittoral biogenic bottoms characterised by epibenthic bivalves

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD231](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD2312](#), [MD2313](#), [MB2314](#)

HELCOM
#AB.A1E

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone below the halocline/pycnocline formed of shell gravel. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic bivalves cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

Characteristic species

Mytilus spp., *Amphibalanus improvisus* and the sponge *Ephydatia fluviatilis*.

Associated species

Gonothyraea loveni, *Cordylophora caspia*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by hypoxia.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.A1E Baltic aphotic rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic bivalves.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MD232. Baltic offshore circalittoral shell gravel bottoms characterised by bivalves

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD232](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM
AB.E1E

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with at least 90% coverage of shell gravel. Epibenthic bivalves cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups.

The depth in the Baltic is below the halocline, which is approximately 60 m. It appears mostly in high-energy exposure areas. The offshore circalittoral shell gravel bottoms are relatively stable, i.e., they do not shift areas.

Geographic range: Southern Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

In zones with a higher salinity, the typical species are the northern horse mussel *Modiolus modiolus*, the vase tunicate *Ciona intestinalis* and the lancelet *Amphioxus* spp. (HELCOM, 2013a; EEA, 2022a).

In brackish waters, the shell gravel is located by *Mytilus* sp., *Mya arenaria* or *Cerastoderma glaucum* (Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Associated species

This habitat type is inhabited by a unique combination of endobenthic and epibenthic species. Benthic macroinfauna species are burrowing infauna, and species are similar as those found in coarse sand. In finer shell gravel, the community is different than in coarser shell gravel where epifauna is also found. The finer substrate hosts mainly burrowing polychaetes and amphipods (HELCOM, 2013b).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by hypoxia. Other threats are bottom-trawling, acidification, construction and sand and gravel extraction.

Best practices in nature restoration

Bottom trawling should not be allowed. Inputs of nutrients should be reduced to decrease eutrophication and improve the oxygen conditions of the biotope and also reduce the overgrowth of annual brown algae (HELCOM, 2013).

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic photic or aphotic shell gravel dominated by vase tunicate \(*Ciona intestinalis*\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic photic or aphotic shell gravel characterised by mixed infaunal macrocommunity in fine sand-like shell fragments. BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.A1E Baltic aphotic rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic bivalves.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MD431. Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed bottoms characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD431](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore circalittoral sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD4311](#), [MD4312](#), [MD4313](#)

HELCOM AB.M1E1 (modified)

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with less than 90% coverage of a certain substrate type. Mixed substrates comprise any proportion of a mix of any substrate type of soft/mobile and/or hard/non-mobile substrates. Coverage of sessile macroscopic epifauna is $\geq 10\%$.

Geographic range: Southern and Southwestern Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Ascidiacea: *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Molgula* spp.

Alcyonacea: *Alcyonium digitatum* and *Swiftia rosea* (in the Kattegat; HELCOM, 2013a).

Scleractinida: *Caryophylla smithii*.

Bryozoa: *Einhornia (Electra) crustulenta*.

Porifera: *Halichondria panicea*, *Haliclona* (Syn: *Chalina*) *oculata*, *Halisarca dujardini* (HELCOM, 2013b).

Actiniarida: *Metridium senile*, *Urticina felina* (HELCOM, 2013d).

Associated species

The nudibranch *Tritonia hombergii* is common among *Alcyonium digitatum*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is primarily threatened by hypoxia and bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Best practices include the protection of areas from bottom trawling, sand and gravel extraction and all kinds of construction.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by soft corals \(Alcyonacea\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed substrates dominated by sponges \(Porifera\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013c. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by stone corals \(Scleractinida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013d. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by sea anemones \(Actiniarida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.M1E1 Baltic aphotic mixed substrate dominated by Mytilidae.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MD531. Baltic offshore circalittoral sand characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD531](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore circalittoral sand

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD5311](#), [MD5312](#)

HELCOM AB.J1

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with at least 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63 µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2 mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. Coverage of sessile macroscopic epifauna is ≥10%.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Mytilus spp. in the whole Baltic Sea. Ocean quahog *Arctica islandica* and the striped Venus clam (*Chamelea gallina*) are characteristic in the Southern and Southwestern Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2013a, 2013b).

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Sand extraction, sedimentation, dredging, bottom trawling, hypoxia.

Best practices in nature restoration

Best practices include the protection of areas from bottom trawling, sand and gravel extraction and all kinds of construction, as well as reducing inputs of nutrients.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic aphotic sand dominated by ocean quahog \(*Arctica islandica*\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic aphotic sand dominated by striped venus \(*Chamelea gallina*\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.J1 Baltic aphotic sand characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Group 3

MD631. Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic bivalves

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD631](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM
AB.H1E

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with at least 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63 µm). characterised by sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic bivalves which cover less than 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Substrate is muddy sediment.

Depth is below halocline/pycnocline. It appears in all energy exposure classes.

Geographic range: more in the Southern Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Arctica islandica in the Southern and Southwestern Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2013).

Associated species

In the entire Baltic Sea, *Macoma balthica*, *Saduria entomon*, *Marenzelleria spp*, *Monoporeia affinis*.

In the Southwestern Baltic Sea: *Diastylis rathkei*, *Abra alba*, *Corbula gibba*, *Ophiura albida* (Gogina et al. 2016).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Sand extraction, sedimentation, dredging, bottom trawling, hypoxia.

Best practices in nature restoration

Best practices include the protection of areas from bottom trawling, sand and gravel extraction and all kinds of construction, as well as reducing inputs of nutrients.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic aphotic sand dominated by ocean quahog \(*Arctica islandica*\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.H1E Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by epibenthic bivalves.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

Figure 03-03. *Mytilaster lineatus* in the Black Sea

Source: *Mytilaster lineatus* in the Black Sea, © Tarsus, 2025

Group 3

MB141. Invertebrate-dominated Black Sea lower infralittoral rock

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB141](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

European Red List:

BLSA3.3w

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Infralittoral rock dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and *Mytilaster lineatus*

>Infralittoral soft rock with piddocks (*Pholas dactylus*, *Barnea candida*, *Petricola lithophaga*)

General description

In this habitat type, the rock substrates of the seabed are presented by different lithological varieties: limestones, sandstones, marls, clay rock complexes, volcanogenic complexes, and conglomerates, inhabited by diverse fauna.

This habitat occurs in the lower infralittoral zone, where invertebrates dominate. In low light conditions, red (*Phyllophora crispa*, *Delesseria ruscifolia*, *Polysiphonia elongata*, *Lomentaria clavellosa*, *Antithamnion cruciatum*), brown (*Zanardinia typus*), and green (*Cladophora albida*, *C. coelothrix*) sciaphilic algae may also be present.

Characteristic habitat subtypes, including the specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the MSFD criteria are:

- Infralittoral rock dominated by Mytilids: *Mytilaster lineatus*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*.
- Infralittoral rock with faunal turf: colonial ascidians (*Botryllus schlosseri*), hydrozoans, bryozoans, and sponges.
- Infralittoral soft rock with piddocks (*Pholas dactylus*, *Barnea candida*).

Mussel beds develop on hard monolithic rock bottoms, rock blocks, and biogenic *Ostrea edulis* reefs at a depth of 0-20 m, with the black mussel also spreading at a higher depth and deeper into the shelf sublittoral rock habitat, up to the maximum distribution depth of the rock substrate. The probable distribution range includes all hard and moderately hard rock types providing attachment conditions, such as calcareous complex, sandstones, volcanics, and conglomerates. They form monolithic colonies, or participate in mixed communities with algae.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottoms are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, and at greater depth, under low light, algae are rare, and black mussels become the main habitat species.

The actual area occupied by black mussel beds is undetermined.

The physically burrowing piddocks *Pholas dactylus* and *Barnea candida* inhabit soft rocks such as marl, sandstone, and compact clay in the infralittoral zone where suitable substrate is found. *Petricola lithophaga* (chemically burrowing) inhabits harder limestone rocks and has a limited patchy distribution. Information about the distribution and state of this subtype is extremely scarce.

Characteristic species

The main characteristic species of this habitat type include: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*; *Barnea candida*, *Botryllus schlosseri*. Algae species: *Phyllophora crispa*, *Delesseria ruscifolia*, *Polysiphonia elongata*,

Lomentaria clavellosa, *Antithamnion cruciatum*, *Zanardinia typus*, *Cladophora albida*, *Cladophora coelothrix*.

Associated species

Mussels are colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), barnacle (*Balanus improvisus*), hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoides*, *Rissoa splendida*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods such as *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, *Athanas nitescens*. Particularly sensitive species in the habitat are the chitons *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Lepidochitona cinerea*, and *Acanthochitona fascicularis*.

The invasive species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation press can lead to the destruction of mussel colonies.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters disturbing bottom sediments.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Plastic micro-particles pollution can be ingested and lead to mortality of the benthic macroinvertebrate fauna.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the

adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MB143. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea exposed upper infralittoral rock with foliose algae (no Fucales)

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB143](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

European Red List: BLSA3.15

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

<Infralittoral rock

dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and

Mytilaster lineatus

General description

This habitat occurs on very exposed rocky coasts, subject to strong wave action at a depth of up to 10 m and typically covered with Mytilid and foliose algal communities. Under the exposed conditions, winter storms may cause changes to species compositions and coverage.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottoms are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, and at a greater depth, the black mussels become the main habitat species.

More detailed studies of this habitat's characteristics and distribution area are needed.

Characteristic species

Characteristic species include: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, *Cladostephus spongiosus*, *Corallina elongata*, *Dictyota fasciola*, *Polysiphonia subulifera*, *Ceramium virgatum*, *Gelidium spinosum*, *G. crinale*, *Corallina mediterranea*, *Ulva rigida*, *Ulva linza*, *U. intestinalis*, *Cladophora sericea*, *C. albida*, *Bryopsis plumosa*.

Associated species

Characteristic inhabitants of the rock bottom are the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), barnacle (*Balanus improvisus*), serpulid polychaetes *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Janua pagenstecheri*, *Serpula vermicularis*.

A variety of fauna (benthic invertebrates and fish) and flora (micro- and macro epiphytes) are associated with the *Cystoseira* sp. Mussels are also colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acontochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoides*, *Rissoa splendida*, *Bittium reticulatum*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods such as *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, *Athanas nitescens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency.

Reduced light penetration has caused a reduction in the extent and quality of the algal component of the habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the Mytilid element of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, smothering, and changes in the hydrological and hydrochemical regime.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing the nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov, D., Todorova, V., Dimitrov, L., Rinde, E., Karamfilov, V., 2018. Distribution and abundance of phytobenthic communities: Implications for connectivity and ecosystem functioning in a Black Sea Marine Protected Area. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 200: 234-247.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MB148. Mytilid-dominated Black Sea moderately exposed upper infralittoral rock with foliose algae (other than Fucales)

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB148](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

European Red List: BLSA3.26

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

#Upper infralittoral rock with variable annual green and red macroalgae

<Infralittoral rock dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and *Mytilaster lineatus*

General description

This habitat occurs in shallow waters, along moderately exposed coasts on rocky substrates presented by a range of rock sizes at a depth of up to 10 m. The rocks are typically covered by foliose algal communities.

In conditions of increased eutrophication, the relative presence of brown and red algae in the composition of the community decreases.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottoms are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, as well as at greater depth, under low light, algae are rare, with black mussels becoming the main habitat species.

The actual extent and area of distribution of this habitat is not determined.

Characteristic species

The moderately exposed nature of the habitat allows the inhabiting of species, less tolerant of wave action. Characteristic species include: *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, *Ceramium virgatum*, *Gelidium spinosum*, *G. crinale*, *Corallina mediterranea*, *Polysiphonia subulifera*/*P. opaca*, *Ulva rigida*, *Ulva linza*, *U. intestinalis*, *Cladophora sericea*, *C. albida*, *Bryopsis plumosa* and others.

Associated species

Characteristic inhabitants of the rock bottom are the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), barnacle (*Balanus improvisus*), serpulid polychaetes *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Janua pagenstecheri*, *Serpula vermicularis*. Mussels are colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatooides*, *Rissoa splendida*, *Bittium reticulatum*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods such as *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, *Athanas nitescens*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency.

Reduced light penetration has caused a reduction in the extent and quality of the algal component of the habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the Mytilid element of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, smothering, and changes in the hydrological and hydrochemical regime.
- Creation of artificial beaches.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Berov, D., Todorova, V., Dimitrov, L., Rinde, E., Karamfilov, V., 2018. Distribution and abundance of phyto-benthic communities: Implications for connectivity and ecosystem functioning in a Black Sea Marine Protected Area. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 200: 234-247.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MB242. Mussel beds in the Black Sea infralittoral zone

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB242](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1130, #1160, <1170

[European Red List](#): BLSA5.62

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

#Infralittoral rock

dominated by Mytilids:

Mytilus galloprovincialis and

Mytilaster lineatus

General description

Mussel beds develop on hard monolithic rock bottoms, rock blocks, and biogenic *Ostrea edulis* reefs at a depth of 0-20m, with the black mussel also spreading into a higher depth deeper into the shelf sublittoral rock habitat, up to the maximum distribution depth of the rock substrate. The probable distribution range includes all hard and moderately hard rock types providing attachment conditions-calcareous complex, sandstones, volcanics, and conglomerates. They form monolithic colonies or participate in mixed communities with Fucales and other algae.

The colonies of bivalves *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* on infralittoral rock bottom are widespread and overlap with the photophilic algal zone. In areas of increased eutrophication and turbidity, as well as at greater depth, under low light, algae are rare, with black mussels becoming the main habitat species.

The actual area occupied by black mussel beds is undetermined.

Among all the predominant habitats, the shallow rock bottom provides the highest biodiversity of species and biological communities.

Characteristic species

Mytilus galloprovincialis, *Mytilaster lineatus*.

Associated species

The associated invertebrate fauna is very diverse. Mussels are colonised by a variety of epifauna, including aquatic sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Petrosia dura*, the common sea anemone (*Actinia equina*), sea acorn (*Balanus improvisus*), hydrozoa *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Campanularia integriformis*, *Obelia* spp., encrusting bryozoans *Membranipora membranacea*, *Lepralia pallasiana*, colonial ascidians *Botryllus schlosseri*. The mobile fauna is represented by the chitons *Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Lepidochitona caprearum*, *Acantochitona fascicularis*, the snails *Gibbula divaricata*, *Nana donovani*, *Tricolia pullus*, *Setia valvatoides*, *Rissoa splendida*, *Bittium reticulatum*, the polychaetes *Platynereis dumerilii*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, isopods, amphipods, decapods such as *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Xantho poressa*, *Pisidia longicornis*, *Clibanarius erythropus* and shrimps *Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte leptocerus*, *Athanas nitescens*.

The invasive species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation press can lead to the destruction of mussel colonies.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency. Reduced light penetration has caused a reduction in the extent and quality of the algal component of the habitat. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the Mytilid element of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters, disturbing bottom sediments.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Due to the slow growth rate and colonisation of the key species, habitat fragmentation and loss can result in long-term declines. Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.

[National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MA243. Oyster reefs on Black Sea lower infralittoral rock

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB243](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

[European Red List](#): BLSA5.64

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

=Biogenic reefs of *Ostrea edulis*

General description

This habitat occurs along the moderately exposed shores of the central and southern part of the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast, on a rocky and mixed bottom at a depth of 7-25m (Todorova et al., 2009. Todorova et al. 2012). Oyster clumps (5-10 oysters) on rocky outcrops are found along the Turkish Black Sea Coast at depths of 10-20m, in some cases at depths of 0-5m (Ordu Province).

The oyster reefs along the Bulgarian Coast are massive biogenic structures reaching a height of 7m, a length of 30-50m, and a width of 10m. They are characterised by a jagged, branched, irregular shape and high structural complexity, providing microhabitats for a wide variety of marine invertebrates and fish. The reefs are mainly built of aggregated shells of *Ostrea edulis* and limestone tubes of polychaetes.

Detailed habitat mapping surveys are lacking.

Characteristic species

Ostrea edulis.

Presently, no living specimens of *Ostrea edulis* are found in the structure of the reefs along the Bulgarian Coast. The reefs are colonised by *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, aquatic sponges, red (*Phyllophora crispa*, *Delesseria ruscifolia*), and brown (*Zanardinia typus*) sciaphilous algae.

Associated species

Oyster reefs are inhabited by the decapods *Eriphia verrucosa* and fishes from the *Gobiidae*, *Blenniidae*, *Labridae*, and *Scorpaenidae* families. The bivalve *Petricola lithophaga* is also found.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The extinction of the typical species after probably millennia of existence, which allowed the construction of these massive biogenic reefs, testifies to a reversal in ecological conditions. One of the likely causes is anthropogenic eutrophication. The last time live oysters were observed on these reefs was in the 1970s, which coincides with the severe eutrophication period in the Black Sea (between the 1970s and early 2000s). Other likely causes are the predatory press of the alien whelk *Rapana venosa*, or infection by the protozoan parasite *Bonamia ostreae*.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Aydin M., Biltekin D., 2020. First morphometric aspects and growth parameters of the European flat oyster \(*Ostrea edulis* Linnaeus, 1758\) for the Black Sea, Turkey, Natural and Engineering Sciences, 5\(2\): 101-109.](#)

[Berov, D., Todorova, V., Dimitrov, L., Rinde, E., Karamfilov, V., 2018. Distribution and abundance of phytobenthic communities: Implications for connectivity and ecosystem functioning in a Black Sea Marine Protected Area. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 200: 234-247.](#)

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

[Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EC.](#)

[National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MB642. Black Sea infralittoral terrigenous muds

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB642](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mud

HD: >1160

European Red List: BLSA5.33

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Infralittoral mud with *Melinna palmata*

General description

This habitat is presented by mud and sandy mud substrates, mixed with terrestrial and freshwater detritus inhabited by bivalve molluscs and polychaete worms.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Infralittoral mud (at depths of 7-18m) with *Mya arenaria*, *Anadara kagoshimensis*, *Upogebia pussila*, *Nephtys* sp., *Melinna palmata* and other polychaetes” (Romania); and “Infralittoral mud (at depths of 9-25m) dominated by *Aricidea claudiae*, *Prionospio maciolekae*, *Melinna palmata* and *Lucinella* (Türkiye)”.

The main distribution of mussel banks on sandy-muddy and muddy substrate is at a depth of 30m to 80m, but individual banks are found at a shallower depth in the so-called "depressions" on the seabed.

Detailed information on the abundance and extent of the habitat is scarce.

Characteristic species

Melinna palmata, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Pitar rudis*, *Terebellides stroemii*, *Aricidea claudiae*, *Abra* sp., *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus*.

Associated species

The invasive species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation pressure can lead to the destruction of mussel beds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

A significant threat is also the predatory pressure of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters disturbing bottom sediments.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Plastic micro-particles pollution can be ingested and lead to mortality of the benthic macroinvertebrate fauna.
- Predatory pressure of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MC141. Invertebrate-dominated Black Sea lower circalittoral rock

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC141](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

[European Red List](#): BLSA4.24

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

Circalittoral rock overgrown by *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, hydrozoans and sponges

General description

This habitat is widespread all around the Black Sea except for Ukrainian waters. It occurs at depths between 10-15m (depending on local conditions of light penetration, the upper limit of the habitat is defined as the lower limit of photophilic plants), down to the lower limit of rock substrate distribution. The lower limit on the Northwestern Black Sea shelf is about 30-70m. In front of the Bulgarian Coast, it is about 35-45m in depth, and the most significant areas of the habitat are located on the southern shelf.

The fauna is highly diverse, including many invertebrate and fish species. The dominant species is often the blue mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Other typical inhabitants are some species of hydrozoa and aquatic sponges, but the species composition is still insufficiently studied.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including the specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is "Circalittoral rock overgrown by *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, hydrozoans, and sponges".

In certain locations, other benthic species may dominate:

- Crusts and turfs formed by bryozoans, crust sponges (*Dysidea* spp.) or colonial tunicates *Botryllus schlosseri*.
- Vertical walls and ridges can be covered either by dense colonies of erect, branched sponges *Halichondria* sp. and *Haliclona* sp. or by solitary ascidians *Molgula manhattensis*, *Asciella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*.
- Hydrozoans can form dense turfs or tall canopies in the case of larger species (*Obelia longissima*).

The actual area occupied by black mussel beds is undetermined.

Characteristic species

Characteristic species include *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Dysidea* spp., *Botryllus schlosseri*, *Halichondria* sp., *Haliclona* sp., *Molgula manhattensis*, *Asciella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*, *Obelia longissima*.

Associated species

The invasive alien species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation pressure can lead to the destruction of mussel colonies.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters disturbing bottom sediments.
 - Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

Aiming to reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MC241. Mussel beds on Black Sea circalittoral terrigenous muds

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC241](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: >1170

European Red List: BLSA5.62

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

=Sublittoral mussel beds of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* on sediments

General description

This habitat occurs on mixed circalittoral sediments - terrigenous muds, mixed with variable amounts of recent or subfossil shells, most of them belonging to the black mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. The main distribution of mussel banks on sandy-muddy and muddy substrate is at a depth of 20 to 80m, but individual banks are found at a shallower depth in the so-called "depressions" on the seabed, as well as at a greater depth.

The habitat is present all around the coasts of Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Russia, and Georgia at variable depths between 20m and 45-80m. Historically, this habitat used to be present in front of the Turkish Coast as well, but over the last century it has been significantly destroyed due to intensive bottom trawling.

A characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are Mussel beds of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* on circalittoral (at depths of 20-70m) mud and mixed sediments (mud and shells).

Detailed information on the abundance and extent of the habitat is scarce. The available data do not allow estimation of the change in the distribution and area of the habitat, and assessment of the trends.

The recorded percentage coverage by mussels ranged from 0% to >20%. The reference value is unknown, but it is assumed that it was around 25%, due to available information on the occurrence frequency of 25.6% of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* in the borders of the mussel beds in front of the Bulgarian coast in the 1950s (Kaneva-Abadzhieva and Marinov, 1960). Based on that, according to expert evaluation, a coverage >20% is defined as good condition.

The biomass of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* is also characterised by high spatial variability due to the uneven group distribution of the species in space and may vary between 10 and 1,500 g/m².

Characteristic species

Mytilus galloprovincialis formations have a particularly important habitat-forming role, providing a hard surface in otherwise muddy areas. This attracts and supports a greater range of species including seaweeds, anemones, barnacles, molluscs, crustaceans, echinoderms, and polychaetes.

Associated species

The species composition of the accompanying fauna is variable and depends on the sediment matrix and depth. Between 20 and 106 species of macrozoobenthos are known to occur in the habitat, and the maximum number of species recorded is 131. The diverse range of epibiota and infauna within the circalittoral *Mytilus galloprovincialis* beds includes: cnidarians (*Actinithoe clavata*), sponges (*Dysidea* spp.), molluscs (*Lepidochitona cinerea*, *Abra alba*, *Calyptraea chinensis*, *Retusa truncatella*, *Nassarius nitidus*, *Gouldia minima*, *Pitar rudis*, *Acanthocardium paucicostatum*), polychaetes

(*Terebellides stroemi*, *Aonides paucibranchiata*, *Melinna palmata*, *Capitella capitata*, *C. minima*, *Eumida sanguinea*, *Glycera alba*, *Hediste diversicolor*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Nereiphylla rubiginosa*, *Pectinaria koreni*, *Polycirrus jubatus*, *Polydora* spp., *Pomatoceros triqueter*), amphipods (*Ampelisca diadema*, *Orchomene humilis*), echinoderms (*Amphiura stepanovi*, *Leptosynapta inhaerens*), tunicates (*Asciidiella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*), elasmobranchs (*Raja clavata*, *Squalus acanthias*), fish (*Acipenser gueldenstaedti*, *A. stellatus*, *Huso huso*, *Chelindonichthys lucernus*, *Mesogobius batrachocephalus*, *Psetta maeotica*).

The invasive species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation stress can lead to the destruction of mussel beds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The comparative analysis of the recent data with historical data from the called reference period shows a reduction in the coverage and a deterioration in the demographic characteristics of a *Mytilus galloprovincialis* population, which is associated with the impact of different types of pressures such as hypoxia/anoxia as a result of anthropogenic eutrophication, predation by *Rapana venosa* and physical impact from active bottom fishing gear.

Future trends include a likely reduction in the area and deterioration of mussel beds affected by two main pressures - physical damage from active bottom fishing gear and the predatory press of the invasive alien species *Rapana venosa*. Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Fishing and shell fishing (beam trawling - high pressure).
- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters disturbing bottom sediments.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Plastic micro-particles pollution can be ingested and lead to mortality of the benthic macroinvertebrate fauna.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Despite the established spatial-temporal restrictions for beam-trawling, a significant impact on the spatial extent and status of the mussel beds is observed. Therefore, conducting more detailed studies and optimizing the spatial-temporal limitations of bottom trawling is essential for the habitat protection and restoration.

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Teodorof, M., Adrian, F., Dumitrache, C., Abaza V., 2022. The macrozoobenthic species of the infralittoral and circalittoral zone from the Romanian Black Sea coast - a qualitative and quantitative assessment.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 3

MC645. Black Sea lower circalittoral mud

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC645](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore

circalittoral mud

European Red List: BLSA5.37

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Lower circalittoral mud

with *Terebellides stroemi*

>Peripheral shelf mud with

Oligochaeta

General description

This habitat occurs at depths of 50m to 130-180m. The sediment type varies between terrigenous muds, calcareous muds and biogenic detritic. There is no light influence at this depth. The benthic fauna is dominated by bean mussels *Modiolula phaseolina*, polychaetes and solitary ascidians. The polychaetes are presented by the highest number of species, among them *Terebellides stroemii* and *Aonides paucibranchiata* are registered as dominant. A total of 70 macrozoobenthic species are identified within the habitat in the Romanian Continental Shelf (Tanase et al.,2023).

As the depth increases, the species richness of the zoocenosis decreases. At a depth below 100m, the fauna is very poor, represented mainly by oligochaetes with low numbers. The conditions are characterised by a reduced content of dissolved oxygen because of the stratification of water masses.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is "Deep circalittoral (at depths of 60-100m) shelly mud with *Modiolula phaseolina*".

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Modiolula phaseolina, *Abra alba*, *Papillicardium papillosum*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*, *Phoronis psammophila*, *Terebellides stroemi*, *Notomastus profundus*, solitary ascidians (*Asciella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*, *Eugyra spp.*), hydrozoans (*Bougainvillia ramosa*), nematodes, polychaetes, and oligochaetes.

Associated species

Other species presented due to their large ecological plasticity are polychaetes *Nephtys hombergii*, *Harmothoe reticulata*, *Exogone naidina* and amphipods *Ampelisca sp.*, *Microdeutopus damnoniensis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat include nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity; and fishing with active bottom gear.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures relevant to this habitat include measures to maintain physical and biological integrity, and measures to reduce nutrient enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds).

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Tanase M., Filimon A., Dumitrache C. and Abaza V., 2023. Current Status of Zoobenthic Communities Associated with Deep Circalittoral Habitats from the Romanian Continental Shelf.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Figure 03-04, *Neopycnodonte cochlear* reef in the Adriatic Sea, with intense oyster growth and the presence of the massive-globose cf. *Petrosia* sp. and the erected sponge *Ulosa stuposa*

Source: Angeletti, Lorenzo, and Marco Taviani. 2020. "Offshore *Neopycnodonte* Oyster Reefs in the Mediterranean Sea" Diversity 12, no. 3: 92. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d12030092>

Group 3

MA1544. Facies with *Mytilus galloprovincialis* in waters enriched in organic matter

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA1544](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Littoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA1.546³⁵

General description

This habitat is characterised by a dense cover of the substrate by the bivalve mollusc *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and occurs in the lower part of the littoral zone, generally at mean sea level, on rocks washed by the waves. This facies develops on hard substrates, in calm areas with a high supply of organic matter. According to the amount of organic matter, mussel beds can extend deeper.

In absence of other dominant species of the littoral zone, *M. galloprovincialis* may settle through its byssus threads to rocks and piers, within sheltered harbours and estuaries and on rocky shores of the open coast. Due to the capacity of this species to reproduce several times over a year, *M. galloprovincialis* can determine a strong dynamic for this facies.

M. galloprovincialis is an extremely active filter feeder. As a result, this species filters the particles present in the water, contributing to the purification of water containing a high amount of suspended matter, and improving plankton supply. Mussel beds release a large quantity of nutrients into the environment, thereby contributing to the production of more plankton than what they consume.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the dominance of specimens of mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, often occurring together with the bearded horse mussel *Modiolus barbatus*. The mussels are often encrusted with barnacles and bryozoans, and their shells and byssus create interstices where cavity organisms may live. In addition to the habitat-forming species, this facies may feature gastropods such as Muricidae (e.g., *Hexaplex trunculus*, *Stramonita haemastoma*), that feed on the mussels or on the bryozoans. Copepods, various filter feeders and a large cavity fauna are additional components of the assemblage.

Associated species

The most important associated algal species belong to the order Fucales, (e.g., genus *Ericaria*, *Cystoseira*, *Gongolaria* and *Sargassum*). In addition, this facies may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges, and bryozoans. This association may host a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

In the past centuries, natural mussel beds covered a large part of the littoral zone, especially in the areas close to river mouths and sheltered bays. The intensive exploitation of the mussel beds, along with the cultivation and the

³⁵ Although MA1544 is not directly linked to habitats classified under the Barcelona Convention updated classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region (2019), it can be described within the habitat MA1.546.

introduction of non-native species for cultivation, has resulted in a dramatic historical decline. There is a lack of information on past trends in quality, but future decline is predicted in response to climate change, diseases, and competition with non-indigenous invasive species (i.e., *Branchiomma* spp.).

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Asmus, R. M., Asmus, H., 1991. Mussel beds: limiting or promoting phytoplankton? *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 148 (2), 215-232.

Bellan-Santini, D., 1965. Etude quantitative du peuplement à *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck en eau moyennement polluée. *Rapport de la Commission internationale Mer Méditerranée*, 18 (2), 85-89.

Bellan-Santini, D., 1969. Contribution à l'étude des peuplements infralittoraux sur substrat rocheux: (étude qualitative et quantitative de la frange supérieure). *Recueil de la Station Marine d'Endoume*, 47 (63), 294 p.

Boudouresque, C. F., 1990, *Livre Rouge "Gérard Vuignier" des végétaux, peuplements et paysages marins menacés de Méditerranée*, MAP Technical Reports Series N°43, UNEP, Athens, PNUE, IUCN et GIS Posidonie, 250 p.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Keklikoglou, K., Faulwetter, S., Chatzigeorgiou, G., et al., 2013. MidMedPol: Polychaetes from midlittoral rocky shores in Greece and Italy (Mediterranean Sea). *Biodiversity Data Journal* 1: e961.

La Rivière, M., et al., 2021. *Fiches descriptives des biocénoses benthiques de Méditerranée*, UMS PatriNat éd., Paris, 660 pp.

Lezzi, M., and Giangrande, A., 2018. Seasonal and bathymetric effects on macrofouling invertebrates' primary succession in a Mediterranean non-indigenous species hotspot area. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 19(3), 572-588.

Michez, N., Fourt, M., Aish, A., et al., 2014. *Typologie des biocénoses benthiques de Méditerranée Version 2*, Service du patrimoine naturel, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, SPN 33, 26 pp.

[Palomba, L., Harmelin, J.-G., Bellan-Santini, D., 2016. Descriptive sheet "III.6.1.w.-Faciès à *Mytilus galloprovincialis*" in the INVENTAIRE NATIONAL DU PATRIMOINE NATUREL'. Accessed 3 March 2023.](#)

Peres, J. M. and Picard, J., 1964. Nouveau manuel de bionomie benthique de la Méditerranée. *Rec Trav. Stat. Mar. Endoume*, 31 (47): 1-137.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfuné, A., Markovic, L., 2012. *Biocénoses des fonds durs de l'infralittoral. Sous-région marine Méditerranée occidentale. Evaluation*

initiale DCSMM, MEDDE, AAMP, Ifremer, Ref. DCSMM/EI/EE/MO/22/2012. 11 pp.

Tsuchiya, M. and Bellan-Santini, D., 1989. Vertical distribution of shallow rocky shore organisms and community structure of mussel beds (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) along the coast of Marseille, France. *Mésogée*, 49, 91-110.

Group 3

MB1514. Facies with *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB1514](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Littoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention³⁶: MB1.517a, MB1.536

General description

This facies is characterised by a dense cover of the substrate by the shells of the bivalve mollusc *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and is located at the level of the upper fringe of the infralittoral zone (between depths of 0 and 1.5m). This facies develops on hard substrates, both in calm areas and in areas with strong hydrodynamics with a low supply of organic matter. In sites where organic matter is scarce, mussels usually occupy a vertical space in the break zone, while in those rich in organic matter, mussel beds can extend deeper.

When the other dominant species of the infralittoral zone, such as *Ericaria* spp., are absent, *M. galloprovincialis* may settle through byssus threads to rocks and piers, within sheltered harbours and estuaries and on rocky shores of the open coast, sometimes also forming dense masses on soft bottoms mixed with pebbles ensuring suitable surfaces for attachment. Due to the capacity of this species to reproduce several times over a year, *M. galloprovincialis* determines a strong dynamic in this facies.

M. galloprovincialis is an extremely active filter feeder. As a result, this species filters the particles present in the water, contributing to the purification of water containing a high amount of suspended matter, improving plankton supply. Mussel beds release a large quantity of nutrients into the environment, which seems to produce more plankton than it consumes. The presence of this facies can also be a sign of disturbance, indicating that an area is polluted or that its ecological state is deteriorating.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the aggregations of the shells of mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, often in the presence of the bearded horse mussel *Modiolus barbatus*. The mussels are often encrusted with barnacles and/or bryozoans, and their shells and byssus create interstices where cavity organisms may live. In addition to the habitat-forming species, this facies may feature gastropods such as Muricidae (e.g., *Hexaplex trunculus*, *Stramonita haemastoma*), that feed on the mussels or on the bryozoans. Copepods, various filter feeders and a large cavity fauna are also elements of this assemblage.

Associated species

The most important associated algal species belong to the order Fucales, (e.g., genus *Ericaria*, *Cystoseira*, *Gongolaria* and *Sargassum*). In addition, this facies may include other erect and encrusting algae, sponges, and bryozoans. This facies may host a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, gastropods and polychaetes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

In the past centuries, natural mussel beds covered a large part of the infralittoral zone in suitable areas, especially the areas close to river mouths

³⁶ Although MB1514 is not directly linked to habitats classified under the Barcelona Convention updated classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region (2019), it can be described within the habitats MB1.517a and MB1.536.

and sheltered bays. The intensive exploitation of the mussel beds along with the cultivation and the introduction of non-native species for cultivation has resulted in dramatic historical decline. There is a lack of information on past trends in quality, but future decline is predicted in response to climate change, diseases, and competition with non-indigenous invasive species (i.e., *Branchiomma* spp.). The remaining natural beds are very few, scattered through the Mediterranean countries. In consequence, mussel beds are defined as 'endangered' by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats (Code MEDA5.6v Mediterranean infralittoral mussel beds).

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Asmus, R. M., Asmus, H., 1991. Mussel beds: limiting or promoting phytoplankton?' *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 148 (2), 215-232.

Bellan-Santini, D., 1965. Etude quantitative du peuplement à *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck en eau moyennement polluée. Rapport de la Commission internationale Mer Méditerranée, 18 (2), 85-89.

Bellan-Santini, D., 1969. Contribution à l'étude des peuplements infralittoraux sur substrat rocheux: (étude qualitative et quantitative de la frange supérieure). *Recueil de la Station Marine d'Endoume*, 47 (63), 294 p.

Boudouresque, C. F., 1990, Livre Rouge "Gérard Vuignier" des végétaux, peuplements et paysages marins menacés de Méditerranée, MAP Technical Reports Series N°43, UNEP, Athens, PNUE, IUCN et GIS Posidonie, 250 p.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Keklikoglou, K., Faulwetter, S., Chatzigeorgiou, G., et al., 2013. MidMedPol: Polychaetes from midlittoral rocky shores in Greece and Italy (Mediterranean Sea). *Biodiversity Data Journal* 1: e961.

La Rivière, M., et al., 2021. Fiches descriptives des biocénoses benthiques de Méditerranée, UMS PatriNat éd., Paris, 660 pp.

Lezzi, M., and Giangrande, A., 2018. Seasonal and bathymetric effects on macrofouling invertebrates' primary succession in a Mediterranean non-indigenous species hotspot area. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 19(3), 572-588.

Michez, N., Fourt, M., Aish, A., et al., 2014. Typologie des biocénoses benthiques de Méditerranée Version 2, Service du patrimoine naturel, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, SPN 33, 26 pp.

Palomba, L., Harmelin, J.-G., Bellan-Santini, D., 2016. Descriptive sheet "III.6.1.w.-Faciès à *Mytilus galloprovincialis*" in the INVENTAIRE NATIONAL DU PATRIMOINE NATUREL'.

Peres, J. M. and Picard, J., 1964. Nouveau manuel de bionomie benthique de la Méditerranée. *Rec Trav. Stat. Mar. Endoume*, 31 (47): 1-137.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Thibaut, T., Blanfuné, A., Markovic, L., 2012. Biocénoses des fonds durs de l'infralittoral. Sous-région marine Méditerranée occidentale. Evaluation initiale DCSMM, MEDDE, AAMP, Ifremer, Ref. DCSMM/EI/EE/MO/22/2012. 11 pp.

Tsuchiya, M. and Bellan-Santini, D., 1989. Vertical distribution of shallow rocky shore organisms and community structure of mussel beds (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) along the coast of Marseille, France. *Mésogée*, 49, 91-110.

Group 3

Mediterranean infralittoral oyster beds

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB255](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.5 or MB5.545³⁷

General description

The Mediterranean infralittoral oyster beds are bioconstructions engineered by the bivalve mollusc *Ostrea edulis*. Until the 19th century, the European flat oyster formed beds and/or banks in intertidal to very shallow (0-20m depth) waters, often close to river mouth areas or estuaries and sheltered bays. Intensive dredge fishing caused the functional extinction of the wild oysters from vast areas of the Mediterranean Sea. There is limited quantified information on the historical extent of this habitat, but they are known to have covered a large part of the coastal zone, while the known remaining natural beds are nowadays very few.

Native oyster beds provide many ecosystem services including water filtration, food and habitat for many animals (e.g., fish, crabs), shoreline stabilisation and coastal defence, also enhancing biodiversity and fisheries. In addition, shellfish reefs play an important role as habitat for other species.

Characteristic species

Infralittoral oyster beds are formed mainly by the European flat oyster *Ostrea edulis*, found as individuals or clusters attached to rock surfaces, on coarse sandy bottoms and on other shelled animals (e.g., *Pinna nobilis*). *O. edulis* is a shallower species and may be abundant down to a depth of 50m.

Associated species

The oysters are often encrusted with barnacles and/or bryozoans. In addition, this association may include erect and encrusting algae and sponges. This association may also host a very diverse assemblage of mobile invertebrates, mostly amphipods, decapods, polychaetes and gastropods, such as species of the families *Muricidae* (e.g., the European oyster driller *Ocenebra erinaceus*, the rock-shell *Stramonita haemastoma*) that feed on oysters by drilling into them and digesting their flesh.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* is a European native species that once covered vast infralittoral areas in the Mediterranean region, in particular close to river mouths and sheltered bays. All these populations have been heavily fished by dredging over the last three centuries, resulting in the local extirpation in Europe of the native flat oyster throughout much of its historical range. More recently, the development of parasitic diseases due to the emergence of *Marteilia* and *Bonamia* combined with the introduction and competition of non-native species (*Crassostrea gigas*), the predation of other species (i.e., sea stars, sea bream and oyster drills) and many other human-induced stressors (pollutants, terrestrial outputs, coastal development) have caused a dramatic decrease in the last remaining flat oyster populations.

³⁷ While this habitat is not directly linked to habitats classified under the BARCELONA CONVENTION updated classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region (2019), it can be described as a possible facies/association within the broader habitat category “MB1.5 Infralittoral rock”, “MB5.54 Habitats of transitional waters”, or “MB5.545 Facies with Bivalvia”.

Oyster reefs are considered among the most threatened marine habitats globally, having suffered losses of over 85%. There is a lack of information on past trends and on the extent of the natural mussel beds nowadays, since the remaining natural beds are very few, scattered through the Mediterranean countries. In consequence, oyster beds are defined as 'endangered' by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats (*Code MEDA5.6w Mediterranean infralittoral oyster beds*).

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist or are still subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Airoidi, L., Bacchiocchi, F., Cagliola C., et al., 2005. Impact of recreational harvesting on assemblages in artificial rocky habitats. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 299, 55-66.

Airoidi, L. and Beck, M. W., 2007. Loss, status and trends for coastal marine habitats of Europe. *Oceanography and Marine Biology Annual Review* 45, 345-405.

Beck, M. W., Brumbaugh, R. D., Airoidi, L., et al., 2011. Oyster reefs at risk and recommendations for conservation, restoration, and management. *BioScience* 61(2), 107-116.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Hughes, A., Bonačić, K., Cameron, T., Collins, K., Da costa, F., Debney, A., Van duren, L., Elzinga, J., Fariñas- franco, J.M., Gamble, C., Helmer, L., Holbrook, Z., Holden, E., Knight, K., Murphy, J.A.J., Pogoda, B., Pouvreau, S., Preston, J., Reid, A., Reuchlin-Hugenholtz, E., Sanderson, W.G., Smyth, D., Stechele, B., Strand, Å., Theodorou, J.A., Uttley, M., Wray, B & Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., 2023. Site selection for European native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) habitat restoration projects: An expert-derived consensus. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 33, 7, 721-736.

Kamermans, P., Anteau, F., Didderen, K., Ter Hofstede, R., Zhao, Y., Le Graet, A., Maas, D., Pouvreau, S., Valk, S., Wijgerde, T., Zemleni, A., Kodger, T. E., & Murk, T., 2025. Novel settlement substrates for European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) restoration. *Ecological Engineering*, 212, 107532.

Pogoda, B., Brown, J., Hancock, B., et al., 2019. The Native Oyster Restoration Alliance (NORA) and the Berlin Oyster Recommendation: bringing back a key ecosystem engineer by developing and supporting best practice in Europe. *Aquatic Living Resources* 32, 13.

Potet, M., Fabien, A., Chaudemanche, S., Sebaibi, N., Guillet, T., Gachelin, S., Cochet, H., Boutouil, M., Pouvreau, S., 2021. Which concrete substrate suits you? *Ostrea edulis* larval preferences and implications for shellfish restoration in Europe. *Ecological Engineering*, 162, 106159.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., Bonacic, K., Boudry, P., et al., 2020. Forty Questions of Importance to Policy and Practice of Oyster Restoration in Europe. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 30, 2038-2049.

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., Bos, O., Debney, A., Gamble, C., Glover, A., Pogoda, B., Pouvreau, S., Sanderson, W., Smyth, D. and Preston, J. (eds), 2021. European Native Oyster Habitat Restoration Monitoring Handbook. *The Zoological Society of London, UK.*, London, UK.

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., McCormick, H., Debney, A., Fariñas-franco, J.M., Gamble, C., Gillies, C., Hancock, B., Laugen, A.T., Pouvreau, S., Preston, J., Sanderson, W.G., Strand, Å., & Thurstan, R.H., 2024. European Native Oyster Reef Ecosystems Are Universally Collapsed. *Conservation Letters*, e13068.

Group 3

Mediterranean circalittoral oyster beds

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: MC252
EUNIS level:4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef
HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention:
MD3.511, MD4.511,
MD2.51³⁸

General description

The Mediterranean circalittoral oyster beds are bioconstructions engineered by bivalve molluscs of the Order *Ostreida*, mainly the species *Ostrea edulis* and *Neopycnodonte cochlear*. The main oyster bank builders in European shallow to intertidal waters (0-20m depth) are members of the family *Ostreidae* (*O. edulis* and the introduced species *Crassostrea gigas*), while the gryphaeid *N. cochlear* is widespread in the Mediterranean at intermediate water depths (ca. 30-150m).

There is limited quantified information on the historical extent of this habitat. Generally, this facies occurs over fragmented bedrock substrate, resulting in discrete clusters of *N. cochlear* surrounded by muddy or detritic flat bottoms. In other cases, this facies occurs on vertical rocks, where it can develop in thick pinnacles or globose formations protruding perpendicularly with respect to the cliff for 0.5-1.5m depths. These formations are often interconnected with one another to form a framework of high structural complexity. Shells from dead oysters compose most of the bioconstructions, whereas living specimens occur on the superficial layer in scattered clusters.

Native oyster beds provide many ecosystem services including water filtration, food and habitat for many animals (e.g., fish, crabs), shoreline stabilisation and coastal defence, also enhancing biodiversity and fisheries. In addition, shellfish reefs play an important role as habitat for other species.

Characteristic species

Circalittoral oyster beds are formed mainly by the European flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* and the *Gryphaeidae* *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, found as individuals or clusters attached to rock surfaces, on coarse sandy bottoms and on other shelled animals. *O. edulis* is a species found in shallower waters and may be abundant down to a depth of 50m, while *N. cochlear* forms massive aggregations on both horizontal and vertical seafloors in deeper Mediterranean waters, mainly under mesophotic conditions (40-130m, deep circalittoral, shelf edge and upper slope), with a density of up to 1,000 individuals per square meter. *N. cochlear* may also be a component of other offshore circalittoral and upper bathyal biogenic habitats and colonizes dark submarine caves.

Associated species

Several species contribute to structuring *N. cochlear* bioconstructions, such as cnidarians, serpulids, bryozoans, and sponges. Among the secondary structuring taxa, several scleractinians (e.g., *Caryophyllia* spp.) and *Corallium rubrum* (Annex III SPA/BD, Appendix III Bern, IUCN Red List EN) have been reported. Serpulid tubes encrust the outer portions of the bioconstruction as well as the reef interstices. Spirorbid polychaetes exhibit specific adaptations to the dark crevices, playing a pioneering role in the community colonisation patterns. Encrusting bryozoans (e.g., *Schizomavella* spp. and *Schizoporella* spp.) contribute to the structure by forming thin crusts on the reef surface.

³⁸ This habitat can be described as a possible facies/association within the broader habitat category "MD2.51 Offshore reefs".

Sponges are mainly represented by several encrusting species covering large portions of the substrate, binding shells together, or boring species (e.g., *Siphonodictyon infestum*) eroding the carbonate layer. The bank crevices may also be inhabited by *Hiatella* spp. bivalves, whereas red coralline algae are only sporadically reported. Fish fauna includes the species *Serranus cabrilla*, *Scorpaena scrofa* and *Conger conger*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Oyster beds are of paramount interest and have been included under different protection and management measures. However, further research is needed to expand the knowledge about the bed's spatial distribution, associated biodiversity, potential threats (e.g., direct exploitation, seafloor abrasion, anoxia and pollution) and the goods and services they may provide. In consequence, circalittoral oyster beds are defined as "unknown/data deficient" within the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats (*Code MEDAA5.6z Circalittoral biogenic habitats in the Mediterranean-oyster beds*).

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist or are still subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Airoldi, L., Bacchiocchi, F., Cagliola C., et al., 2005. Impact of recreational harvesting on assemblages in artificial rocky habitats. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 299, 55-66.

Airoldi, L. and Beck, M. W., 2007. Loss, status and trends for coastal marine habitats of Europe. *Oceanography and Marine Biology Annual Review* 45, 345-405.

Angeletti, L. and Taviani, M., 2020. Offshore *Neopycnodonte* Oyster Reefs in the Mediterranean Sea. *Diversity* 12, 3:92.

Beck, M. W., Brumbaugh, R. D., Airoldi, L., et al., 2011. Oyster reefs at risk and recommendations for conservation, restoration, and management. *BioScience* 61(2), 107-116.

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Hughes, A., Bonačić, K., Cameron, T., Collins, K., Da costa, F., Debney, A., Van duren, L., Elzinga, J., Fariñas- franco, J.M., Gamble, C., Helmer, L., Holbrook, Z., Holden, E., Knight, K., Murphy, J.A.J., Pogoda, B., Pouvreau, S., Preston, J., Reid, A., Reuchlin-Hugenholtz, E., Sanderson, W.G., Smyth, D., Stechele, B., Strand, Å., Theodorou, J.A., Uttley, M., Wray, B & Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., 2023. Site selection for European native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) habitat restoration projects: An expert-derived consensus. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 33, 7, 721-736.

Kamermans, P., Anteau, F., Didderen, K., Ter Hofstede, R., Zhao, Y., Le Graet, A., Maas, D., Pouvreau, S., Valk, S., Wijgerde, T., Zemleni, A., Kodger, T. E., &

Murk, T., 2025. Novel settlement substrates for European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) restoration. *Ecological Engineering*, 212, 107532.

Pogoda, B., Brown, J., Hancock, B., et al., 2019. The Native Oyster Restoration Alliance (NORA) and the Berlin Oyster Recommendation: bringing back a key ecosystem engineer by developing and supporting best practice in Europe. *Aquatic Living Resources* 32, 13.

Potet, M., Fabien, A., Chaudemanche, S., Sebaibi, N., Guillet, T., Gachelin, S., Cochet, H., Boutouil, M., Pouvreau, S., 2021. Which concrete substrate suits you? *Ostrea edulis* larval preferences and implications for shellfish restoration in Europe. *Ecological Engineering*, 162, 106159.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani M., Angeletti L., Cardone, F., et al., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. *Scientific Reports* 9, 12.

Thurstan, R.H., McCormick, H., Preston, J., Ashton, E.C., Bennema, F.P., Cetinić, A.B., Brown, J.H., Cameron, T.C., da Costa, F., Donnan, D.W., Ewers, C., Fortibuoni, T., Galimany, E., Giovanardi, O., Grancher, R., Grech, D., Hayden-Hughes, M., Helmer, L., Jensen, K.T., Juanes, J.A., Latchford, J., Moore, A.B., Moutopoulos, D.K., Nielsen, P., von Nordheim, H., Ondiviela, B., Peter, C., Pogoda, B., Poulsen, B., Pouvreau, S., Roberts, C.M., Scherer, C., Smaal, A.C., Smyth, D., Strand, Å., Theodorou, J.A. and Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., 2024. Records reveal the vast historical extent of European oyster reef ecosystems. *Nature Sustainability*, 1-11.

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., Bonacic, K., Boudry, P., et al., 2020. Forty Questions of Importance to Policy and Practice of Oyster Restoration in Europe. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 30, 2038-2049.

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., Bos, O., Debney, A., Gamble, C., Glover, A., Pogoda, B., Pouvreau, S., Sanderson, W., Smyth, D. and Preston, J. (eds), 2021. European Native Oyster Habitat Restoration Monitoring Handbook. *The Zoological Society of London*, UK., London, UK.

Zu Ermgassen, P.S.E., McCormick, H., Debney, A., Fariñas-franco, J.M., Gamble, C., Gillies, C., Hancock, B., Laugen, A.T., Pouvreau, S., Preston, J., Sanderson, W.G., Strand, Å., & Thurstan, R.H., 2024. European Native Oyster Reef Ecosystems Are Universally Collapsed. *Conservation Letters*, e13068.

Group 4: Maerl beds

Figure 04-01, *Phymatolithon calcareum* off Sandaig Island, Scotland

Source: *Phymatolithon calcareum* off Sandaig Island, Scotland, © Tony Gilbert, 2011

Group 4

MB421. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB421](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: #Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1160, #1170 (tbc)³⁹

European Red List: <NEAA5.51

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB4211](#)

OSPAR: <Maerl beds

IE:
<SS.SMp.Mrl
#SS.SMp.Mrl.Pcal
#SS.SMp.Mrl.Lgla
>SS.SMp.Mrl.Lcor⁴⁰

General description

Maerl is a collective term for various species of non-jointed coralline red algae (*Corallinophycidae*) that live unattached to the seabed. These species can form extensive beds, mostly on coarse clean gravel and clean sand or on muddy mixed sediments, either on the open coast, in tide-swept channels or in sheltered areas of marine inlets with weak currents. Wave and current-exposed maerl beds, where thicker depths of maerl accumulate, frequently appear as waves and ridge-and-furrow arrangements.

As maerl requires light to photosynthesize, the depth of live beds is determined by water turbidity, being recorded from the lower shore to depths of 40m or more. Water movement also appears to be a key physical environmental factor affecting the distribution of maerl and hence the formation of maerl beds.

North East Atlantic maerl beds are typically composed of both living and dead maerl of varying proportions. Extensive maerl beds formed during the late Holocene sea level rise on the west facing Atlantic coastlines of the British Isles, Scandinavia, France and Spain. Some are believed to have been tens of kilometres across and several meters in thickness. Maerl is characterised by a slow growth. Growth rates for presently existing, free living maerl in Northwest Spain and Western Ireland have been calculated to vary from 0.10 to 1.00mm/yr, and in Norway from 0.05-0.15mm/yr up to 1.0mm/yr.

Maerl has a complex three-dimensional structure with interlocking thalli providing a wide range of niches for infaunal and epifaunal invertebrates (Birkett et al., 1998). The interstitial space provided by maerl beds allows water to flow through the bed and oxygenated water to penetrate at depth, so that other species can colonize the bed at greater depths than most other sediments. Maerl-forming species are the pivotal, ecosystem engineer and biogenic reef species in maerl beds. Therefore, maerl beds fulfil ecological functions of a biogenic reef and subsequently could be considered as the HD Annex I habitat type 1170. Although currently there is no official crosslink with this habitat, this is expected as an outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

The structural complexity of maerl beds is known to provide important nursery areas for fish and shellfish species, such as cod and edible crustaceans, at a critical phase in their life histories, as well as a refuge and feeding area for commercially important shellfish brood stock (e.g., *Ensis* spp., *Pecten maximus* and *Venus verrucosa*). Some evidence suggests that coralline algae produce physical and chemical cues that encourage the settlement and recruitment of planktonic juvenile stages of many invertebrate species, while providing the prospect of higher growth potential.

³⁹ There is no official crosslink of this habitat with "1170" to date; this is expected as an outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

⁴⁰ SS.SMp.Mrl.Lcor is equal to the EUNIS subtype.

Characteristic species

Different maerl species dominate, depending on the conditions. In fully marine conditions the dominant maerl is typically *Phymatolithon calcareum*, while under variable salinity conditions, such as in some sea lochs, it can be *Lithothamnion glaciale*.

Several species are known to form maerl (or rhodoliths) in the Macaronesian region. Although *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida* is present in sparse aggregations, it may constitute the dominant maerl species in current-swept coarse sands and fine gravels in the Azores, while *Lithophyllum crouaniorum* can be found on shallow infralittoral sands at depths between 2m and 5m. Beds of *Lithothamnion corallioides* are present in the Canary Islands and Madeira from 20m down to 60m and 50m, respectively, with the Madeira beds being also characterised by the presence of *Spongites fruticulosus*. Along the Iberian Coast, *Phymatolithon lusitanicum* has been found to be the third most abundant maerl-forming species.

Associated species

The particular mix of species present will be influenced by the sediment characteristics and degree of shelter of the maerl bed. A particular characteristic of maerl is the presence of a mixture of hard and soft substrata-associated assemblages including shells and gravels or various anchored algal species such as *Gelidiella calcicola*, *Cruoria cruoriaeformis* (mostly exclusive to maerl), *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Halarachnion ligulatum*, *Ulva* spp., *Callophyllis laciniata*, *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Brongniartella byssoides*.

Phycodrys rubens and *Plocamium cartilagineum* are typical. Other organisms such as the anemones (*Anemonia viridis* and *Cerianthus lloydii*); the annelids, (*Chaetopterus variopedatus*, *Lanice conchilega*, *Kefersteinia cirrata*, *Hesione pantherina*, *Pilargis verrucosa*, *Psammolyce arenosa*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Chone dunerii*, *Parametaphoxus fultoni*, *Notomastus latericeus*, *Caulleriella alata* and *Grania* sp.); the gastropods (*Gibbula cineraria*, *Gibbula magus*, *Calyptraea chinensis*, *Alvania beani*, *Alvania cimicoides*, *Dikoleps pusilla* and *Onoba aculeus*); and crustaceans (*Liocarcinus depurator* and *Liocarcinus corrugatus*) may be present together with numerous melitid amphipod species and often large numbers of *Galathea intermedia* and/or *Pisidia longicornis*. A diverse assemblage of crustaceans is also commonly present.

In tide-swept conditions with variability salinity, the associated fauna and flora may also include species that reflect the slightly reduced salinity conditions. For example, *Psammechinus miliaris* is often present in high numbers along with other grazers such as chitons and *Tectura* spp., *Hyas araneus*, *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*. In more sheltered conditions, anemones typical of sheltered conditions may be found in close association with maerl, these may include *Anthopleura ballii*, *Cereus pedunculatus* and *Sagartiogeton undatus*. Polychaetes such as *Myxicola infundibulum* and terebellids, also characteristic of sheltered conditions, may be present as may hydroids such as *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*. Occasional *Chlamys varia* and *Thyone fusus* are present in many habitats recorded, together with red seaweeds such as *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Calliblepharis jubata* and *Chylocladia verticillata*.

In the Kattegat, fauna associated with maerl beds include crustaceans such as *Corystes cassivelaunus* and *Thia scutellata*, and echinoderms such as *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*.

Along the Iberian Coast the following associated species have been reported: *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Anemonia viridis*, *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*, *Lanice conchilega*, *Pilargis verrucosa*, *Anomia ephippium*, *Mimachlamys varia*, *Varicorbula gibba*, *Sepia officinalis*, *Gibbula magus*, *Corystes cassivelaunus*, *Galathea intermedia*, *Astropecten aranciacus*, *Thyone fusus*, *Ophiocomina nigra*, *Echinocardium cordatum*, *Diadema africanum* (only in the Madeira archipelago), and *Psammechinus miliaris*. Associated fish species in this region are *Arnoglossus thori*, *Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus*, *Serranus atricauda*, *Bodianus scrofa*, and *Scorpaena* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

In the recent past, commercial dredging has been a considerable threat to maerl beds. Extraction of both living and fossil deposits has severely depleted beds in the Fal Estuary in England, while commercial dredging of around 500,000 tonnes per annum from large beds in French waters, such as those off the Glénan Islands, has also caused irreversible damage in this and other Breton maerl beds. Apart from the direct effect of the physical removal of the maerl during extraction, there are other direct and indirect impacts from muddy plumes and sediment redistribution or suspension, caused by the dredging activity and coastal construction, which later settle out, and smother associated and surrounding communities. The impact area from this pressure may extend up to 200 times the area of the extraction zone.

Eutrophication, organic enrichment and sedimentation from domestic, industrial or agricultural discharges and from aquaculture installations are an on-going threat. In the recent past, in the Bay of Brest, maerl beds have been lost due to eutrophication, even if measures to reduce sewage discharges are likely to reduce this pressure in the future. In Galicia, Spain, mussel farming has caused a deterioration of maerl bed complexity and biodiversity through increased sedimentation. Eutrophication can indirectly cause further impacts, such as an increase in ephemeral algal biomass, smothering the maerl and sometimes resulting in the closure of the king scallop fishery, which in turn encourages an increase in the more destructive clam fishery. Moreover, an increase in algal biomass at impacted sites may promote infestation by invasive alien species such as *Crepidula fornicata*, which can degrade associated communities through competition, and reduce abundance and diversity by building up accumulations of faeces, pseudofaeces and shell drift.

Maerl thalli are fragile and inherently susceptible to physical damage from abrasion, such as that originating from mobile demersal fishing gear. Maerl beds in the Firth of Clyde, Scotland, first sampled in the 1880s, are known to have been broken up and destroyed by heavy towed fishing gear. Bivalve dredging currently remains one of the main threats to European maerl beds, with some French beds under increasing pressure from the intensification of clam (*Venus verrucosa*) fishing.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

[Birkett, D.A., Maggs, C.A. & Dring, M.J., 1998. Maerl. an overview of dynamic and sensitivity characteristics for conservation management of marine SACs. Natura 2000 report prepared by Scottish Association of Marine Science \(SAMS\) for the UK Marine SACs P.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Maerl beds.](#)

[OSPAR: Maerl Beds.](#)

[Peña, V., Bárbara, I., 2013. Non-coralline crustose algae associated with Maerl beds in Portugal: a reappraisal of their diversity in the Atlantic Iberian beds. Botanica Marina, 56.](#)

[Peña, V., Bárbara, I., Grall, J., Maggs, C.A., Hall-Spencer, J.M., 2014. The diversity of seaweeds on Maerl in the NE Atlantic. Marine Biodiversity, 44, 533-551.](#)

[Peña, V., Pardo, C., López, L., Carro, B., Hernandez-Kantun, J., Adey, W.H., Bárbara, I., Barreiro, R., Gall, L.L., 2015. Phymatolithon lusitanicum sp. nov. \(Hapalidiales, Rhodophyta\): The Third Most Abundant Maerl-Forming Species in the Atlantic Iberian Peninsula. Cryptogamie, Algologie, 36, 429-459. Peña, V.](#)

[Perry, F., Tyler-Walters, H., & Watson, A., 2024. Maerl beds. In Tyler-Walters H. Marine Life Information Network: Biology and Sensitivity Key Information Reviews. Plymouth: Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Maerl beds.](#)

Group 4

MB322. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB322](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): #Infralittoral coarse sediment

[HD](#): #1110, #1160, #1170 (tbc)⁴¹

[European Red List](#): <NEAA5.51

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB3221](#), [MB3222](#)

OSPAR: <Maerl beds

IE:
<SS.SMp.Mrl
>SS.SMp.Mrl.Pcal
>SS.SMp.Mrl.Lgla

General description

Maerl is a collective term for various species of non-jointed coralline red algae (*Corallinophycidae*) that live unattached to the seabed. These species can form extensive beds, mostly on coarse clean gravel and clean sand or on muddy mixed sediments, either on the open coast, in tide-swept channels or in sheltered areas of marine inlets with weak currents. Wave and current-exposed maerl beds, where thicker depths of maerl accumulate, frequently appear as waves and ridge-and-furrow arrangements.

As maerl requires light to photosynthesize, the depth of live beds is determined by water turbidity, being recorded from the lower shore to depths of 40m or more. Water movement also appears to be a key physical environmental factor affecting the distribution of maerl and hence the formation of maerl beds.

North East Atlantic maerl beds are typically composed of both living and dead maerl of varying proportions. Extensive maerl beds formed during the late Holocene sea level rise on the west facing Atlantic coastlines of the British Isles, Scandinavia, France and Spain. Some are believed to have been tens of kilometres across and several meters in thickness. Maerl is characterised by a slow growth. Growth rates for presently existing free living maerl in Northwest Spain and Western Ireland have been calculated to vary from 0.10 to 1.00mm/yr, and in Norway from 0.05-0.15mm/yr up to 1.0mm/yr.

Maerl has a complex three-dimensional structure with interlocking thalli providing a wide range of niches for infaunal and epifaunal invertebrates (Birkett et al., 1998). The interstitial space provided by maerl beds allow water to flow through the bed, and oxygenated water to penetrate at depth so that other species can colonize the bed at greater depths than most other sediments. Maerl forming species are the pivotal, ecosystem engineer and biogenic reef species in maerl beds. Therefore, maerl beds fulfil ecological functions of a biogenic reef and subsequently should be considered as the HD Annex I habitat type 1170. Although currently there is no official crosslink with this habitat, this is expected as an outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

The structural complexity of maerl beds is known to provide important nursery areas for fish and shellfish species, such as cod and edible crustaceans, at a critical phase in their life cycles, as well as a refuge and feeding area for commercially important shellfish brood stock (e.g., *Ensis* spp., *Pecten maximus* and *Venus verrucosa*). Some evidence suggests that coralline algae produce physical and chemical cues that encourage the settlement and recruitment of planktonic juvenile stages of many invertebrate species, while providing the prospect of higher growth potential.

⁴¹ There is no official crosslink of this habitat with 1170 to date; this is expected as an outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

Characteristic species

Different maerl species dominate, depending on the conditions. In fully marine conditions the dominant maerl is typically *Phymatolithon calcareum*, while under variable salinity conditions, such as in some sea lochs, it can be *Lithothamnion glaciale*.

Several species are known to form maerl (or rhodoliths) in the Macaronesian region. Although *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida* is present in sparse aggregations, it may constitute the dominant maerl species in current-swept coarse sands and fine gravels in the Azores, while *Lithophyllum crouaniorum* can be found on shallow infralittoral sands at depths between 2 m and 5 m. Beds of *Lithothamnion corallioides* are present in the Canary Islands and Madeira from depths of 20m down to 60m and 50m respectively, with the Madeira beds also characterised by the presence of *Spongites fruticulosus*. Along the Iberian Coast, *Phymatolithon lusitanicum* has been found to be the third most abundant maerl-forming species.

Associated species

The particular mix of species present will be influenced by the sediment characteristics and degree of shelter of the maerl bed. A particular characteristic of maerl is the presence of a mixture of hard and soft substrata-associated assemblages including shells and gravels or various anchored algal species such as *Gelidiella calcicola*, *Cruoria cruoriaeformis* (mostly exclusive to maerl), *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Halarachnion ligulatum*, *Ulva* spp., *Callophyllis laciniata*, *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Brongniartella byssoides*, *Phycodrys rubens* and *Plocamium cartilagineum*. Other organisms such as the anemones (*Anemonia viridis* and *Cerianthus lloydii*); the annelids, (*Chaetopterus variopedatus*, *Lanice conchilega*, *Kefersteinia cirrata*, *Hesione pantherina*, *Pilargis verrucosa*, *Psammolyce arenosa*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Chone duneri*, *Parametaphoxus fultoni*, *Notomastus latericeus*, *Caulleriella alata* and *Grania* sp.); the gastropods (*Gibbula cineraria*, *Gibbula magus*, *Calyptrea chinensis*, *Alvania beani*, *Alvania cimicoides*, *Dikoleps pusilla* and *Onoba aculeus*); and crustaceans (*Liocarcinus depurator* and *Liocarcinus corrugatus*) may be present together with numerous melitid amphipod species and often large numbers of *Galathea intermedia* and/or *Pisidia longicornis*. A diverse assemblage of crustaceans is also commonly present.

In tide-swept conditions with varying salinity, the associated fauna and flora may also include species that reflect the slightly reduced salinity conditions. For example, *Psammechinus miliaris* is often present in high numbers along with other grazers such as chitons and *Tectura* spp., *Hyas araneus*, *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*. In more sheltered conditions, anemones typical of sheltered conditions may be found in close association with maerl, these may include *Anthopleura ballii*, *Cereus pedunculatus* and *Sagartiogeton undatus*. Polychaetes such as *Myxicola infundibulum* and terebellids, also characteristic of sheltered conditions, may be present as may hydroids such as *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*. Occasional *Chlamys varia* and *Thyone fusus* are present in many habitats recorded, together with red seaweeds such as *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Calliblepharis jubata* and *Chylocladia verticillata*.

In the Kattegat, fauna associated with maerl beds include crustaceans such as *Corystes cassivelaunus* and *Thia scutellata*, and echinoderms such as *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*.

Along the Iberian Coast the following associated species have been reported: *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Anemonia viridis*, *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*, *Lanice conchilega*, *Pilargis verrucosa*, *Anomia ephippium*, *Mimachlamys varia*, *Varicorbula gibba*, *Sepia officinalis*, *Gibbula magus*, *Corystes cassivelaunus*, *Galathea intermedia*, *Astropecten aranciacus*, *Thyone fusus*, *Ophiocarina nigra*, *Echinocardium cordatum*, *Diadema africanum* (only in the Madeira archipelago), and *Psammechinus miliaris*. Associated fish species in this region are *Arnoglossus thori*, *Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus*, *Serranus atricauda*, *Bodianus scrofa*, and *Scorpaena* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

In the recent past, commercial dredging has been a considerable threat to maerl beds. The extraction of both living and fossil deposits has severely depleted beds in the Fal Estuary in England, while the commercial dredging of around 500,000 tonnes per annum from large beds in French waters, such as those off the Glénan Islands, has also caused irreversible damage in this and other Breton maerl beds. Apart from the direct effect of the physical removal of the maerl during extraction, there are other direct and indirect impacts from muddy plumes and sediment redistribution or suspension, caused by the dredging activity and coastal construction, which later settle out, and smother associated and surrounding communities. The impact area from this pressure may extend up to 200 times the area of the extraction zone.

Eutrophication, organic enrichment and sedimentation from domestic, industrial or agricultural discharges and from aquaculture installations are an on-going threat. In the recent past in the Bay of Brest, maerl beds have been lost due to eutrophication, even if measures to reduce sewage discharges are likely to reduce this pressure in the future. In Galicia, Spain, mussel farming has caused deterioration in maerl bed complexity and biodiversity through increased sedimentation. Eutrophication can indirectly cause further impacts, such as an increase in ephemeral algal biomass, smothering the maerl and sometimes resulting in the closure of the king scallop fishery, which in turn encourages an increase in the more destructive clam fishery. Moreover, an increase in algal biomass at impacted sites may promote infestation by invasive alien species such as *Crepidula fornicata*, which can degrade associated communities through competition, and reduce abundance and diversity by building up accumulations of faeces, pseudofaeces and shell drift.

Maerl thalli are fragile and inherently susceptible to physical damage from abrasion, such as that originating from mobile demersal fishing gear. Maerl beds in the Firth of Clyde, Scotland, first sampled in the 1880s, are known to have been broken up and destroyed by heavy towed fishing gear. Bivalve dredging currently remains one of the main threats to European maerl beds, with some French beds under increasing pressure from the intensification of clam (*Venus verrucosa*) fishing.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed but dead maerl remains then the resident community may

recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

[Birkett, D.A., Maggs, C.A. & Dring, M.J., 1998. Maerl. an overview of dynamic and sensitivity characteristics for conservation management of marine SACs. Natura 2000 report prepared by Scottish Association of Marine Science \(SAMS\) for the UK Marine SACs P.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: *Mytilus edulis* and/or barnacle communities on wave-exposed Atlantic littoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Maerl beds.](#)

[OSPAR: Maerl Beds.](#)

[Peña, V., Bárbara, I., 2013. Non-coralline crustose algae associated with Maerl beds in Portugal: a reappraisal of their diversity in the Atlantic Iberian beds. Botanica Marina, 56.](#)

[Peña, V., Bárbara, I., Grall, J., Maggs, C.A., Hall-Spencer, J.M., 2014. The diversity of seaweeds on Maerl in the NE Atlantic. Marine Biodiversity, 44, 533-551.](#)

[Peña, V., Pardo, C., López, L., Carro, B., Hernandez-Kantun, J., Adey, W.H., Bárbara, I., Barreiro, R., Gall, L.L., 2015. Phymatolithon lusitanicum sp. nov. \(Hapalidiales, Rhodophyta\): The Third Most Abundant Maerl-Forming Species in the Atlantic Iberian Peninsula. Cryptogamie, Algologie, 36, 429-459. Peña, V.](#)

[Perry, F., Tyler-Walters, H., & Watson, A., 2024. Maerl beds. In Tyler-Walters H. Marine Life Information Network: Biology and Sensitivity Key Information Reviews. Plymouth: Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Maerl beds.](#)

Group 4

MB622. Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral muddy sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB622](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: #Infralittoral mud

HD: #1110, #1160, #1170⁴²

European Red List:

<NEAA5.51

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB6221](#)

OSPAR:

<Maerl beds

IE:

<SS.SMp.Mrl

>SS.SMp.Mrl.Lcor

>SS.SMp.Mrl.Lfas

General description

Maerl is a collective term for various species of non-jointed coralline red algae (*Corallinophycidae*) that live unattached to the seabed. These species can form extensive beds, mostly on coarse clean gravel and clean sand or on muddy mixed sediments, either on the open coast, in tide-swept channels or in sheltered areas of marine inlets with weak currents. Wave and current-exposed maerl beds, where thicker depths of maerl accumulate, frequently appear as waves and ridge-and-furrow arrangements.

As maerl requires light to photosynthesize, the depth of live beds is determined by water turbidity, being recorded from the lower shore to depths of 40m or more. Water movement also appears to be a key physical environmental factor affecting the distribution of maerl and hence the formation of maerl beds.

North East Atlantic maerl beds are typically composed of both living and dead maerl of varying proportions. Extensive maerl beds formed during the late Holocene sea level rise on the west-facing Atlantic coastlines of the British Isles, Scandinavia, France and Spain. Some are believed to have been tens of kilometres across and several meters in thickness. Maerl is characterised by a slow growth. Growth rates for presently existing free living maerl in Northwest Spain and Western Ireland have been calculated to vary from 0.10 to 1.00mm/yr, and in Norway from 0.05-0.15mm/yr up to 1.0mm/yr.

Maerl has a complex three-dimensional structure with interlocking thalli providing a wide range of niches for infaunal and epifaunal invertebrates (Birkett et al., 1998). The interstitial space provided by maerl beds allow water to flow through the bed, and oxygenated water to penetrate at depth so that other species can colonize the bed at greater depths than most other sediments. Maerl forming species are the pivotal, ecosystem engineer and biogenic reef species in maerl beds. Therefore, maerl beds fulfil ecological functions of a biogenic reef and subsequently should be considered as the HD Annex I habitat type 1170. Although currently there is no official crosslink with this habitat, this is expected as outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

The structural complexity of maerl beds is known to provide important nursery areas for fish and shellfish species such as cod and edible crustaceans at a critical phase in their life cycles, as well as a refuge and feeding area for commercially important shellfish brood stock (e.g., *Ensis* spp., *Pecten maximus* and *Venus verrucosa*). Some evidence suggests that coralline algae produce physical and chemical cues that encourage the settlement and recruitment of planktonic juvenile stages of many invertebrate species, while providing the prospect of higher growth potential.

⁴² There is no official crosslink of this habitat with 1170 to date; this is expected as an outcome of the current EUNIS revision.

Characteristic species

Under sheltered silty conditions *Lithothamnion corallioides* may dominate. In more muddy, sheltered and shallow conditions, rare *Lithophyllum* spp. beds may form. An even rarer bed-forming occurrence of *Mesophyllum sphaericum* has been recorded in a single location in Galicia.

Associated species

The particular mix of species present will be influenced by the sediment characteristics and degree of shelter of the maerl bed. A particular characteristic of maerl is the presence of a mixture of hard and soft substrata-associated assemblages including shells and gravels or various anchored algal species such as *Gelidiella calcicola*, *Cruoria cruoriaeformis* (mostly exclusive to maerl), *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Halarachnion ligulatum*, *Ulva* spp., *Callophyllis laciniata*, *Cryptopleura ramosa*, *Brongniartella byssoides*, *Phycodrys rubens* and *Plocamium cartilagineum*. Other organisms such as the anemones (*Anemonia viridis* and *Cerianthus lloydii*); the annelids, (*Chaetopterus variopedatus*, *Lanice conchilega*, *Kefersteinia cirrata*, *Hesione pantherina*, *Pilargis verrucosa*, *Psammolyce arenosa*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Chone duneri*, *Parametaphoxus fultoni*, *Notomastus latericeus*, *Caulleriella alata* and *Grania* sp.); the gastropods (*Gibbula cineraria*, *Gibbula magus*, *Calyptrea chinensis*, *Alvania beani*, *Alvania cimicoides*, *Dikoleps pusilla* and *Onoba aculeus*); and crustaceans (*Liocarcinus depurator* and *Liocarcinus corrugatus*) may be present together with numerous melitid amphipod species and often large numbers of *Galathea intermedia* and/or *Pisidia longicornis*. A diverse assemblage of crustaceans is also commonly present.

In tide-swept conditions with varying salinity, the associated fauna and flora may also include species that reflect the slightly reduced salinity conditions. For example, *Psammechinus miliaris* is often present in high numbers along with other grazers such as chitons and *Tectura* spp., *Hyas araneus*, *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*. In more sheltered conditions, anemones typical of sheltered conditions may be found in close association with maerl, these may include *Anthopleura ballii*, *Cereus pedunculatus* and *Sagartiogeton undatus*. Polychaetes such as *Myxicola infundibulum* and terebellids, also characteristic of sheltered conditions, may be present as may hydroids such as *Kirchenpaueria pinnata*. Occasional *Chlamys varia* and *Thyone fusus* are present in many habitats recorded, together with red seaweeds such as *Plocamium cartilagineum*, *Calliblepharis jubata* and *Chylocladia verticillata*.

In the Kattegat, fauna associated with maerl beds include crustaceans such as *Corystes cassivelaunus* and *Thia scutellata*, and echinoderms such as *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

In the recent past, commercial dredging has been a considerable threat to maerl beds. Extraction of both living and fossil deposits has severely depleted beds in the Fal Estuary in England, while commercial dredging of around 500,000 tonnes per annum from large beds in French waters, such as those off the Glénan Islands, has also caused irreversible damaged in this and other Breton maerl beds. Apart from the direct effect of the physical removal of the maerl during extraction, there are other direct and indirect impacts from

muddy plumes and sediment redistribution or suspension, caused by the dredging activity and coastal construction, which later settle out, and smother associated and surrounding communities. The impact area from this pressure may extend up to 200 times the area of the extraction zone.

Eutrophication, organic enrichment and sedimentation from domestic, industrial or agricultural discharges and from aquaculture installations are an on-going threat. In the recent past in the Bay of Brest, maerl beds have been lost due to eutrophication, even if measures to reduce sewage discharges are likely to reduce this pressure in the future. In Galicia, Spain, mussel farming has caused deterioration in maerl bed complexity and biodiversity through increased sedimentation. Eutrophication can indirectly cause further impacts, such as an increase in ephemeral algal biomass, smothering the maerl and sometimes resulting in the closure of the king scallop fishery, which in turn encourages an increase in the more destructive clam fishery. Moreover, an increase in algal biomass at impacted sites may promote infestation by invasive alien species such as *Crepidula fornicata*, which can degrade associated communities through competition, and reduce abundance and diversity by building up accumulations of faeces, pseudofaeces and shell drift.

Maerl thalli are fragile and inherently susceptible to physical damage from abrasion, such as that originating from mobile demersal fishing gear. Maerl beds in the Firth of Clyde, Scotland, first sampled in the 1880s, are known to have been broken up and destroyed by heavy towed fishing gear. Bivalve dredging currently remains one of the main threats to European maerl beds, with some French beds under increasing pressure from the intensification of clam (*Venus verrucosa*) fishing.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

[Birkett, D.A., Maggs, C.A. & Dring, M.J., 1998. Maerl. an overview of dynamic and sensitivity characteristics for conservation management of marine SACs. Natura 2000 report prepared by Scottish Association of Marine Science \(SAMS\) for the UK Marine SACs P.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Maerl beds on Atlantic infralittoral muddy sediment.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: *Lithophyllum fasciculatum* maerl beds on infralittoral mud.](#)

[JNCC: Maerl beds.](#)

[OSPAR: Maerl Beds.](#)

[Perry, F., Tyler-Walters, H., & Watson, A., 2024. Maerl beds. In Tyler-Walters H. Marine Life Information Network: Biology and Sensitivity Key Information Reviews. Plymouth: Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Maerl beds.](#)

Figure 04-02, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, Ionian Sea

Source: © *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, Alfonso Siciliano, 2013

Group 4

MB3511. Association with rhodolithes in coarse sands and fine gravels mixed by waves

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB3511](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: <1110, <1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB3.511

General description

Rhodoliths are unattached nodules of various shapes and sizes (2-250mm mean diameter), composed by calcareous red algae that have often grown in successive layers. Scattered rhodoliths occur in many infralittoral environments and the majority of the coastal soft bottoms of the Mediterranean Sea. The association with rhodoliths of the upper infralittoral zone can occur in the open intermatte large channels of superficial meadows of thalassophytes and in particular of *Posidonia* and *Cymodocea*. The factor that determines the sediment granulometry, but also the increase due to the rolling and/or balancing of rhodoliths, is the oscillating and pulsing currents resulting from tidal motions in open lagoons.

Considering their ecological value, their role in climate regulation as carbonate production hotspots and deep benthic primary production, rhodolith beds are protected under national, European, and international conservation legislation. Rhodolith beds are also managed under the “Action Plan for Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretion” adopted during the COP15 (2008) SPA/BD Protocol meeting within the framework of the Barcelona Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Characteristic species

The species of the characterising contingent are: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida* (sometimes mistaken for *Phymatoliton calcareum*), forming rhodoliths up to 10-15cm in diameter; *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, forming rhodoliths with evident leaf-shaped lamellae up to 3-5cm in diameter; *Spongites fruticulosa*; *Phymatoliton calcareum* and *Lithophyllum racemus* in inter-matte channels. Rhodolith beds are formed by the accumulation of living and dead thalli of these species of unattached red calcareous algae.

Associated species

Rhodolith beds are characterised by a remarkably diverse community, as they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of soft bottoms by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms. Rhodoliths provide a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates can attach and feature an abundant vagile epifauna. Sessile fauna includes Alcyonacea, sponges and ascidians. The molluscan community is composed by suspension feeders, herbivores, and carnivores of both circalittoral hard and soft bottoms (e.g., *Haminoea hydatis*, *Gibberula jansseni*, and *Modiolula phaseolina*). Small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Rhodolith beds are highly threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by fishing activities with trawled gear and bivalve dredging. Other sources of impacts are the construction of structures along the coast, capable of modifying the dynamics of water masses and, thus, of bottom currents, the degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of non-indigenous invasive species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming and acidification.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

Agnesi, S., Babbini, L., Bressan, G., et al., 2011. Distribution of maerl facies and rhodolith associations in the Italian seas: current state of knowledge. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 18(1), 50-51.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Kaleb, S., et al., 2016. Monitoring deep Mediterranean rhodolith beds. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 549- 561.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., et al., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. in: Riosmena-Rodríguez, R., Nelson, W., Aguirre, J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, vol. 15, Springer, Cham.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code III.3.1.1. Association with rhodoliths: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Lithotamnium fruticosum* auct! (*Spongites fruticosus* pro parte). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 114-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tauran, A., Dubreuil, J., Guyonnet, B., et al., 2020. Impact of fishing gears and fishing intensities on maerl beds: An experimental approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 533, 151472.

Group 4

MB3521. Association with rhodolithes in coarse sands and fine gravels under the influence of bottom currents

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB3521](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: <1110, <1160⁴³

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB3.521

General description

Rhodoliths are unattached nodules of various shapes and sizes (2-250mm mean diameter), composed by calcareous red algae, often grown in successive layers. Scattered rhodoliths occur in many infralittoral environments and the majority of the coastal soft bottoms of the Mediterranean Sea. Its most favourable environment is at the base of cliffs in biotopes with laminar currents with a regular course, at depths greater than 20m (in the Western Mediterranean). Considering their ecological value, their role in climate regulation as carbonate production hotspots and deep benthic primary production, rhodolith beds are protected under national, European, and international conservation legislation. Rhodoliths beds are also managed under the “Action Plan for Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretion” adopted during the COP15 from 2008 and as a part of the Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Characteristic species

Rhodolith beds are formed by the accumulation of living and dead thalli of various species of unattached red calcareous algae (e.g., Orders Sporolithales, Corallinales, Peyssonneliales). In particular, this association with *Phymatolithon-Lithothamnietum* (Giaccone, 1965) includes the maerl beds characterised by the association of *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum* (see habitat MC3522).

The HD includes *Phymatolithon calcareum* and *Lithothamnion corallioides* in Annex V, among those species subject to exploitation and for which Member States must ensure appropriate management measures.

Associated species

Rhodolith beds are characterised by a remarkably diverse community, as they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of soft bottoms by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms. Rhodoliths provide a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates can attach and features an abundant vagile epifauna. Sessile fauna includes Alcyonacea (e.g., *Eunicella singularis*), sponges (e.g., *Haliclona fulva*, *Siphonochalina coriacea*, and *Axinella cannabina*) and ascidians (e.g., *Polycarpa mamillaris*, *Aplidium elegans*, *Ascidia mentula*). The molluscan community is composed by suspension feeders, herbivores, and carnivores of both circalittoral hard and soft bottoms (e.g., *Haminoea hydatis*, *Gibberula jansseni*, and *Modiolula phaseolina*). Small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant.

⁴³ In the Mediterranean Sea, MB3521 may be nested in the HD Annex I habitat type “Large shallow inlets and bays” (1160).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Rhodolith beds are highly threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by fishing activities with trawled gear and bivalve dredging. Other sources of impacts are the construction of structures along the coast capable of modifying the dynamics of water masses and, thus, of bottom currents, the degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of non-indigenous invasive species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming and acidification.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

Agnesi, S., Babbini, L., Bressan, G., et al., 2011. Distribution of maerl facies and rhodolith associations in the Italian seas: current state of knowledge. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 18(1), 50-51.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Kaleb, S., et al., 2016. Monitoring deep Mediterranean rhodolith beds. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 549- 561.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., et al., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. in: Riosmena-Rodríguez, R., Nelson, W., Aguirre, J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, vol. 15, Springer, Cham.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code III.3.1.1. Association with rhodoliths: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Lithotamnium fruticosum* auct! (*Spongites fruticosus* pro parte). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 114-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tauran, A., Dubreuil, J., Guyonnet, B., et al., 2020. Impact of fishing gears and fishing intensities on maerl beds: An experimental approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 533, 151472.

Group 4

MB3522. Association with maerl (= Association with *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*) on Mediterranean coarse sands and gravel

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB3522](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: 1110⁴⁴, 1160⁴⁵

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB3.511 or MB3.521

General description

Rhodoliths are unattached nodules of various shapes and sizes (2-250mm mean diameter), composed by calcareous red algae, often grown in successive layers. Maerl are rhodolith beds composed of non-nucleated, unattached, and branched coralline algae. Scattered rhodoliths occur in many infralittoral environments and the majority of the coastal soft bottoms of the Mediterranean Sea. Maerl beds are constituted only by the branching, twig-like coralline algae *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*, unattached on sediments made up of coarse sands and gravels. Maerl beds are described throughout the Mediterranean Sea, although they have a patchy distribution.

Considering their ecological value, their role in climate regulation as carbonate production hotspots and deep benthic primary production, maerl beds are protected under national, European, and international conservation legislation. Maerl beds are also managed under the “Action Plan for Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretion” adopted during the COP15 from 2008 and as a part of the Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Characteristic species

The characterising species in this association are *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*. The HD includes *Phymatolithon calcareum* and *Lithothamnion corallioides* in Annex V, among those species subject to exploitation and for which Member States must ensure appropriate management measures.

Associated species

Maerl beds are characterised by a remarkably diverse community, as they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of detritic bottoms by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms. Small *Rhodophyceae* may be present as epiphytes on the Lithothamnia. Maerl provides a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates (hydroids, bryozoans) can attach and features an abundant vagile epifauna. The molluscan community is composed by suspension feeders, herbivores, and carnivores of both circalittoral hard and soft bottom (e.g., *Haminoea hydatis*, *Gibberula jansseni*, and *Modiolula phaseolina*). Small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant in maerl beds.

⁴⁴ In the Mediterranean Sea, MB3522 may border with the HD Annex I infralittoral habitat type “Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time” (1110).

⁴⁵ In the Mediterranean Sea, MB3522 may be nested in the HD Annex I habitat type “Large shallow inlets and bays” (1160).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Maerl is highly threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by fishing activities with trawled gear and bivalve dredging. Consequently, the Council of the EU Regulation 1967/2006, concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea, established the banning of trawl nets, dredges, shore seines or similar nets on both coralligenous and maerl beds. Other sources of impacts are the construction of structures along the coast capable of modifying the dynamics of water masses and, thus, of bottom currents, the degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of non-indigenous invasive species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming and acidification.

Maerl beds are among the habitats which are to be assessed under the MSFD to achieve Good Ecological Status and they have been included in the guidelines for monitoring marine habitats in the Mediterranean, requested by the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme and related Assessment Criteria (IMAP, Barcelona Convention).

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

Agnesi, S., Babbini, L., Bressan, G., et al., 2011. Distribution of maerl facies and rhodolith associations in the Italian seas: current state of knowledge. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 18(1), 50-51.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Kaleb, S., et al., 2016. Monitoring deep Mediterranean rhodolith beds. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 549- 561.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., et al., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. in: Riosmena-Rodríguez, R., Nelson, W., Aguirre, J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, vol. 15, Springer, Cham.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code III.3.1.1. Association with rhodoliths: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Lithotamnium fruticulosum* auct! (*Spongites fruticulosus* pro parte). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 114-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tauran, A., Dubreuil, J., Guyonnet, B., et al., 2020. Impact of fishing gears and fishing intensities on maerl beds: An experimental approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 533, 151472.

Group 4

MC3521. Association with rhodolithes on coastal detritic bottoms

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC3521](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110⁴⁶

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC3.52

General description

Rhodoliths are unattached nodules of various shapes and sizes (2-250mm mean diameter), composed by calcareous red algae, often grown in successive layers. Mediterranean rhodolith beds, defined as areas of soft substrates with over 10% cover of living coralline algal nodules, are generally found at depths between 30-150m in normal marine conditions, throughout the Mediterranean Sea although they have a patchy distribution. This association occurs on circalittoral coarse detritic bottoms.

Considering their ecological value, their role in climate regulation as carbonate production hotspots and deep benthic primary production, rhodolith beds are protected under national, European, and international conservation legislation. Rhodolith beds are also managed under the “Action Plan for Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretion” adopted during the COP15 from 2008 and as a part of the Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Rhodolith beds supply provisional (as essential fish habitats), regulating (through their role as hotspots of carbonate production and deep benthic primary production) and supporting (as ecosystem engineers fostering complex ecological interactions) ecosystem services.

Characteristic species

Rhodolith beds are formed by the accumulation of living and dead thalli of various species of unattached red calcareous algae (e.g., Orders *Sporolithales*, *Corallinales*, *Peyssonneliales*). The term “rhodolith beds” includes the calcareous *Peyssonnelia* beds (species *P. heteromorpha*, *P. rosa-marina*, *P. crispata*) and the maerl beds characterised by the association of *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum* (see habitat MC3523). Different dominant species characterise the Mediterranean rhodolith beds, probably based on biogeography and local environmental conditions.

The HD includes *Phymatolithon calcareum* and *Lithothamnion corallioides* in Annex V, among those species subject to exploitation and for which Member States must ensure appropriate management measures.

Associated species

Rhodolith beds are characterised by a remarkably diverse community, as they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of detritic bottoms by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms. Rhodoliths provide a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates can attach to and features an abundant vagile epifauna. Sessile fauna includes Alcyonacea (e.g., *Eunicella singularis*), sponges (e.g., *Haliclona fulva*, *Siphonochalina coriacea*, and *Axinella cannabina*) and ascidians (e.g.,

⁴⁶ In the Mediterranean Sea, MC3521 may border with the Annex I infralittoral habitat type “Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time” (1110).

Polycarpa mamillaris, *Aplidium elegans*, *Ascidia mentula*). The mollusc community is composed of suspension feeders, herbivores, and carnivores of both circalittoral hard and soft bottoms (e.g., *Haminoea hydatis*, *Gibberula jansseni*, and *Modiolula phaseolina*). Small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Rhodolith beds are highly threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by fishing activities with trawled gear and bivalve dredging. Other sources of impacts are the degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of non-indigenous invasive species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming and acidification.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

Agnesi, S., Babbini, L., Bressan, G., et al., 2011. Distribution of maerl facies and rhodolith associations in the Italian seas: current state of knowledge. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 18(1), 50-51.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Kaleb, S., et al., 2016. Monitoring deep Mediterranean rhodolith beds. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 549- 561.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., et al., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. in: Riosmena-Rodríguez, R., Nelson, W., Aguirre, J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, vol. 15, Springer, Cham.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code III.3.1.1. Association with rhodoliths: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Lithotamnium fruticosum* auct! (*Spongites fruticosus* pro parte). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 114-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tauran, A., Dubreuil, J., Guyonnet, B., et al., 2020. Impact of fishing gears and fishing intensities on maerl beds: An experimental approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 533, 151472.

Group 4

MC3523. Association with maerl (*Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*) on coastal dendritic bottoms

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC3523](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110⁴⁷

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC3.521

General description

Maerl are rhodolith beds composed of non-nucleated, unattached, and branched coralline algae. Mediterranean rhodolith beds could be found at depths of between 20-150m under normal marine conditions. Maerl beds are constituted only by the branching, twig-like coralline algae *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*, unattached on sediments made up of circalittoral coastal coarse sands and gravels with a high proportion of detritic elements. Maerl beds are described throughout the Mediterranean Sea, although they have a patchy distribution.

Considering their ecological value, their role in climate regulation as carbonate production hotspots and deep benthic primary production, maerl beds are protected under national, European, and international conservation legislation. Since 2008, maerl beds are also managed under the “Action Plan for Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretion” adopted during the COP15, and are also a part of the Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (UNEP/MAP, 2015).

Maerl beds supply provisional (as essential fish habitats), regulating (through their role as hotspots of carbonate production and deep benthic primary production) and supporting (as ecosystem engineers fostering complex ecological interactions) ecosystem services.

Characteristic species

The characterising species in the association are *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*.

The HD includes *Phymatolithon calcareum* and *Lithothamnion corallioides* in Annex V, among those species subject to exploitation and for which Member States must ensure appropriate management measures.

Associated species

Maerl beds are characterised by a remarkably diverse community, as they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of detritic bottoms by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms. Small *Rhodophyceae* may be present as epiphytes on the Lithothamnia. Maerl provides a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates (hydroids, bryozoans) can attach to and features an abundant vagile epifauna. The mollusc community is composed of suspension feeders, herbivores and carnivores of both circalittoral hard and soft bottom (e.g., *Haminoea hydatis*, *Gibberula jansseni*, and *Modiolula phaseolina*). Small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant in maerl beds.

⁴⁷ In the Mediterranean Sea, MC3523 may border with the HD Annex I infralittoral habitat type “Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time” (1110).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Maerl beds are highly threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by fishing activities with trawled gear and bivalve dredging. Consequently, the Council of the EU Regulation 1967/2006, concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea, established the banning of trawl nets, dredges, shore seines or similar nets on both coralligenous and maerl beds. Other sources of impacts are the construction of structures along the coast capable of modifying the dynamics of water masses and, thus, of bottom currents, the degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of non-indigenous invasive species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming and acidification.

Maerl beds are among the habitats which are to be assessed under the MSFD to achieve Good Ecological Status; moreover, they have been included in the guidelines for monitoring marine habitats in the Mediterranean, requested by the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme and related Assessment Criteria (IMAP) of the Barcelona Convention.

Best practices in nature restoration

The current evidence regarding the recovery of maerl suggests that if maerl is removed, fragmented or killed, then it has almost no ability to recover. If the maerl is killed, but dead maerl remains, then the resident community may recover within 2-10 years; however, where the maerl is fragmented, species richness will probably decrease.

Management and regulation/exclusion of harmful human activities is inevitable to preserve this biotope. No active restoration measures are known.

Bibliographic sources

Agnesi, S., Babbini, L., Bressan, G., et al., 2011. Distribution of maerl facies and rhodolith associations in the Italian seas: current state of knowledge. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea* 18(1), 50-51.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Kaleb, S., et al., 2016. Monitoring deep Mediterranean rhodolith beds. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 26, 549- 561.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplá, A. A., et al., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. in: Riosmena-Rodríguez, R., Nelson, W., Aguirre, J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, vol. 15, Springer, Cham.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code III.3.1.1. Association with rhodoliths: *Neogoniolithon brassica-florida*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Lithotamnium fruticosum* auct! (*Spongites fruticosus* pro parte). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 114-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tauran, A., Dubreuil, J., Guyonnet, B., et al., 2020. Impact of fishing gears and fishing intensities on maerl beds: An experimental approach. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 533, 151472.

Group 5: Sponge, coral and coralligenous beds

Figure 05-01, *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*, NE Atlantic

Source: IFREMER (2011). Récif corallien du canyon de la Petite Sole. Ifremer.
<https://image.ifremer.fr/data/00577/68908/>

Group 5

MC121. Faunal turf communities on Atlantic circalittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC121](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

European Red List:

#NEAA4.11, #NEAA4.13

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC1211](#), [MC1212](#),

[MC1213](#), [MC1214](#), [MC1215](#),

[MC1216](#), [MC1217](#), [MC1218](#),

[MC1219](#), [MC121A](#), [MC121B](#)

DE:

>02.02.01.01.03

>02.02.01.01.04

>02.02.01.01.05

>02.02.01.01.06

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

#CR.HCR.FaT

=CR.HCR.XFa

General description

These communities occur on high-energy Atlantic circalittoral rocky substrates at a depth of about 5-30m, typically on bedrock or boulders in wave-exposed, tide-swept narrows and straits. The characteristic faunal communities are extremely diverse, and mainly consist of various hydroids, bryozoans and sponges.

Characteristic species

Hydroids: *Halecium halecinum*, *Nemertesia antennina*, *Nemertesia ramosa*.

Bryozoans: *Alcyonidium diaphanum*, *Flustra foliacea*, *Bugula flabellata*, *Bugula plumosa*.

Sponges: *Scypha ciliata*, *Pachymatisma johnstonia*, *Cliona celeta*, *Raspailia ramosa*, *Esperiopsis fucorum*, *Hemimycale columella*, *Dysidea fragilis*.

Associated species

Associated species include: *Alcyonium digitatum*, *Urticina felina*, *Sagartia elegans*, *Actinothoe sphyrodeta*, *Caryophyllia smithii*, *Pomatoceros triqueter*, *Balanus crenatus*, *Cancer pagurus*, *Necora puber*, *Asterias rubens*, *Echinus esculentus*, *Clavelina lepadiformis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is sensitive to increased siltation and smothering, as the associated biotopes are dominated by sessile filter feeders. Algal blooms have impacted circalittoral faunal turf communities in Scandinavia. Physical loss is also a major threat, as well as some effects associated with the use of towed fishing gear, such as resuspending sediment.

Best practices in nature restoration

Beneficial management and conservation measures include protection within Marine Protected Areas, the regulation of fishing methods that could damage, or disturb seabed communities, and the control of dredging activity adjacent to this habitat to avoid sedimentation. The unusual nature and rarity of occurrence of the associated biotopes need to be accounted for in the management of locations and in ecological impact assessments.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Faunal turf communities on Atlantic circalittoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: Mixed faunal turf communities.](#)

[JNCC: Very tide-swept faunal communities.](#)

Group 5

MC124. Faunal communities on variable salinity Atlantic circalittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC124](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1130, <1170

[European Red List](#):

=NEAA4.25

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC1241](#), [MC1242](#)

IE:

=CR.MCR.CFaVS

General description

These faunal communities occur in variable salinities on bedrock and cobbles from a depth of 0-30 m. They are typically found on wave-sheltered areas that are subject to weak or moderately strong tides. Typical species include sponges able to tolerate the varying salinity conditions, barnacles, sparse hydroid/bryozoan turf, as well as ascidians, anemones, starfish and crabs.

Characteristic species

Sponges: *Hymeniacidon perleve*, *Suberites ficus*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Halichondria bowerbanki*, *Cliona celata*, *Leucosolenia botryoides*. Barnacle: *Balanus crenatus*. Hydroid/bryozoans: *Nemertesia antennina*, *Nemerteis ramosa*, *Plumularia setacea*, *Alcyonidium diaphanum* and *Crisularia plumosa*.

Associated species

Ascidians: *Clavelina lepadiformis*, *Morchellium argus*, *Dendrodoa grossularia*. Anemones: *Metridium senile*, *Sagartia troglodytes*. Starfish: *Asterias rubens*. Crab: *Carcinus maenas*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is vulnerable to substratum removal and increased turbidity levels, which would result in smothering and loss of faunal populations. Interaction with mobile fishing gear is likely to damage or remove individuals from the substratum. Changes in the hydraulic conditions, for example, through the construction of tidal barrages, and the discharge of contaminants can also threaten this habitat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Beneficial management and conservation measures include protection within Marine Protected Areas, the regulation of fishing methods that could damage or disturb seabed communities, and the control of dredging activity adjacent to this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Faunal communities on variable salinity Atlantic circalittoral rock.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Circalittoral faunal communities in variable salinity.](#)

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC126](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170, <8330

[European Red List](#):

=NEAA4.71

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC1261](#)

IE:

=CR.FCR.Cv

General description

The composition and spatial extent of cave communities vary considerably, depending on the physical structure and extent of the cave system, its degree of submergence, exposure to scour and surge, and the nature of its geology. Marine caves and overhangs can support a rich and, at times, exceptional biodiversity. Some studies on marine caves and other crevicular fauna have revealed the existence of unique communities, characterised by high endemism, relict species, and other unusual characteristics. Most of the species in this biotope are long-lived. There is little complexity in the habitat, as most of the species live directly attached to the rock, and there is not much architectural complexity that would offer shelter for other species.

Characteristic species

Sponges: *Stryphnus ponderosus*, *Dercitus bucklandi*, *Chelonaplysilla noevus*, *Pseudosuberites* spp. and *Spongosorites* spp.

Anemones and anthozoans: *Parazoanthus* spp., *Corynactis viridis*, *Parerythropodium coralloides*, *Caryophyllia smithii*, *Caryophyllia inornatus*, and *Hoplangia durotrix*.

In the Southern NE Atlantic and the Macaronesian region, characteristic species can differ and include species such as *Phyllangia americana muchezii*, *Spongionella pulchella*, *Madracis* spp., *Telmatactis cricoides* and *Pajaudina atlantica*.

Associated species

Alcyonium glomeratum, *Balanophyllia regia*, *Bryozoa* and *Porifera crusts*, *Caryophyllia smithii*, *Clavelina lepadiformis*, *Corynactis viridis*, *Crisiidae*, *Leptopsammia pruvoti*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is sensitive to physical damage, for example by processes such as increased siltation, abrasion, or selective extraction of associated species. Sedimentation can be an issue where the associated biotopes are dominated by sessile filter feeders. Sport diving may produce negative effects, either directly by mechanical disturbance, or indirectly because of air-bubble accumulation that smothers those organisms that are attached to the cave roof.

Best practices in nature restoration

Few conservation and management measures exist, which are specifically directed at this habitat. These include limitations on access and on the collection of marine life, as well as general measures such as monitoring to observe deterioration. The latter may be part of a scheme of management of Marine Protected Areas.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Communities of Atlantic circalittoral caves and overhangs.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[JNCC: Circalittoral caves and overhangs.](#)

[JNCC: Sponges, cup corals and anthozoans on shaded or overhanging circalittoral rock.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Circalittoral caves and overhangs.](#)

Group 5

MC222. Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC222](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC2221](#)

OSPAR:

#*Lophelia pertusa* reefs

#Coral gardens

IE:

<SS.SBR.Crl

General description

This habitat type occurs at a depth of between 50-200m or deeper in sheltered, cold, mostly aphotic waters in areas of elevated current on silt or hard structures on the continental slope or shelf. The reef-building species at this depth is *Lophelia pertusa*. These deep-water corals lack symbiotic algae; thus, they can live in the darkness of the deep sea. The coral colonies aggregate as patches and banks to form reefs that support hundreds of other species such as sponges, polychaete worms, echinoderms (starfish, sea urchins, brittle stars) and bryozoans (sea mats). In the Southern Northeast Atlantic and the Macaronesian region, other coral species dominate.

Characteristic species

The characteristic colony-forming coral is *Lophelia pertusa*. *Dendrophyllia* spp. and *Eunicella verrucosa* are also typical species.

In the Southern NE Atlantic and Macaronesian region, characteristic species can differ, including for example *Savalia savaglia*, *Antipathella wollastoni*, *Madracis asperula*, *Anomocora fecunda* and even some species with a main distribution in the Mediterranean such as *Paramuricea grayi* and *Ellisella paraplexauroides*.

Associated species

Common species include boring sponges, anemones, bryozoans, gorgonians (*Paragorgia arborea*, *Paramuricea placomus*, *Primnoa resedaeformis*), polychaetes, barnacles, squat lobsters (*Munida sarsi*) and bivalves. Other hard corals such as *Madrepora oculata* and *Solenosmilia variabilis* may also occur. Common fish include the redfish (*Sebastes viviparous* and *Sebastes marinus*), ling (*Molva molva*) and tusk (*Brosme brosme*).

Mesophotic coral gardens off the Iberian Coast are dominated by the coral *Dendrophyllia cornigera* and are often accompanied by the following species: *Antho* spp., *Axinella* spp., *Geodia* sp., *Mycale (Mycale) lingua*, *Tethya* spp., *Polyplumaria flabellata*, *Parantipathes larix*, *Filograna implexa*, *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, sea urchins *Echinus melo* and *Gracilechinus acutus*, *Parastichopus regalis* and the sea star *Marthasterias glacialis*. Associated fish species are: *Capros aper*, *Labrus mixtus*, *Merluccius merluccius* and *Scorpaena scrofa*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The principal threat to *Lophelia pertusa* and other coral reefs is physical damage by fishing gear. There are documented instances of damage in Northwest European waters, although these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Petroleum industry developments with associated discharges of drilling mud and drill

cuttings may also negatively affect the corals. Given their slow growth rate, reefs may take centuries to recover from damage, if at all.

Global warming and the associated fast changes in temperatures, current and stratification patterns, food availability and seawater acidity may in the long run pose the most significant threat to the existing distribution of calcifying organisms, starting with those in shallower waters.

Local threats emanate from oil and gas exploration, dumping of solid waste and dredged soils.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active Ecological Restoration of cold-water corals has been reviewed by Montseny et al. (2021), who highlighted that in order to ensure the long-term viability and success of any restoration action, it is essential to include holistic and long-term monitoring programs, and to ideally combine active restoration with natural spontaneous regeneration (i.e., passive restoration) strategies such as the implementation of deep-sea Marine Protected Areas. A combination of passive and active restoration approaches with the involvement of local society would be the best optimal option to achieve and ensure cold water coral restoration success.

The possibility to restore a damaged *Lophelia pertusa* reef was successfully tested by using transplants of *L. pertusa* from a healthy reef (Dahl 2013. Jonsson et al. 2015). There seems to be a high potential for active restoration of cold-water coral habitats.

Bibliographic sources

[Dahl, M., 2012. Conservation genetics of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* \(Scleractinia\), Doctoral thesis, Gothenburg University.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic circalittoral zone.](#)

[JNCC: *Lophelia* reefs.](#)

Jonsson, L., Dahl, M., Strömberg, S., Lindegarth, M., André, C., & Lundälv, T., 2015. In situ measurement of survival and growth of genotyped transplanted fragments of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa*. Sweden: University of Gothenburg.

[Montseny, M., Linares, C., Carreiro-Silva, M., Henry, L-A., Billett, D., Cordes, E.E., Smith, C.J., Papadopoulou, N., Bilan, M., Girard, F., Burdett, H.L., Larsson, A., Strömberg, S., Viladrich, N., Barry, J.P., Baena, P., Godinho, A., Grinyó, J., Santín, A., Morato, T., Sweetman, A.K., Gili, J-M., Gori, A., 2021 Active Ecological Restoration of Cold-water corals: Techniques, Challenges, Costs and Future Directions. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8:621151.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[OSPAR: *Lophelia pertusa* reefs.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

MD121. Sponge communities on Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD121](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

European Red List:

=NEAA4.12

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MD1211](#)

OSPAR:

#Deep-Sea sponge aggregations⁴⁸

DE:

< § 30 "Riffe"

IE:

=CR.HCR.DpSp

General description

This habitat type typically occurs on deep (commonly below a depth of 30m), wave-exposed circalittoral rock subject to negligible tidal streams. The sponge component of this biotope is the most striking feature. Sponges are accompanied by e.g., bryozoans, anemones, holothurians, soft corals, hydroids, echinoderms and sea fans.

Characteristic species

The sponge community varies depending on the latitude. *Phakellia ventilabrum*, *Axinella infundibuliformis* are present in northern locations, while in southern locations *Phakellia ventilabrum* is lacking, and there is a greater diversity of axinellids (*Axinella dissimilis* and *Axinella damicornis*) and the presence of *Eunicella verrucosa*.

Other common sponges include *Artemisina* spp., *Cliona celata*, *Polymastia boletiformis*, *Haliclona viscosa*, *Pachymatisma johnstonia*, *Dysidea fragilis*, *Suberites carnosus*, *Stelligera rigida*, *Hemimycale columella* and *Tethya aurantium*.

Associated species

The cup coral *Caryophyllia smithii*, the anemone *Corynactis viridis*, the holothurian *Holothuria forskali*, soft corals (*Alcyonium digitatum*, *Alcyonium glomeratum*) and bryozoans (*Pentapora foliacea*, *Porella compressa*) are found frequently. Bryozoan crusts (*Parasmittina trispinosa*), hydroids (*Nemertesia antennina*, *Nemertesia ramosa*, *Sertularella gayi*), echinoderms (*Echinus esculentus*, *Luidia ciliaris*, *Marthasterias glacialis*, *Stichastrella rosea*, *Henricia oculata*, *Aslia lefevrei*), the sea fan *Eunicella verrucosa* and the top shell *Calliostoma zizyphinum* are found occasionally.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments that could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. The collection of sponge specimens for natural history studies and for biomedical purposes has also been identified as a potential threat in some locations. In the future, climate change may alter the composition of the species associated with this habitat.

Best practices in nature restoration

A review by Bierwirth et al. (2022) on sponge restoration shows that until now, approaches have been developed mainly on species of commercial interest. However, it seems possible to cultivate sponges to translocate them to their

⁴⁸ This OSPAR habitat type is generally located in deeper waters.

natural habitat. Looking outside European waters, sponges have successfully been restored in Florida Bay (Butler et al. 2021). However, it is not clear if these techniques are applicable in North East Atlantic offshore waters.

Beneficial management and conservation measures include protection within Marine Protected Areas and the regulation of fishing methods that could damage or disturb seabed communities.

Bibliographic sources

[Bierwirth, Jan, Torcuato Pulido Mantas, Juliette Villechanoux, and Carlo Cerrano, 2022. Restoration of Marine Sponges—What Can We Learn from over a Century of Experimental Cultivation?, *Water* 14, no. 7: 1055.](#)

[Butler, J., Sharp, W. C., Hunt, J. H., Butler IV, M. J., 2021. Setting the foundation for renewal: restoring sponge communities aids the ecological recovery of Florida Bay. *Ecosphere* 12\(12\): e03876. 1.](#)

[Dahl, M., 2013. Conservation genetics of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* \(Scleractinia\), Doctoral thesis, Gothenburg University.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Sponge communities on Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC: Deep sponge communities \(circalittoral\).](#)

[OSPAR: Deep-Sea Sponge Aggregations.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - *Natursch. Biol. Vielf.* 156, 637 S.

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

[The Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\): Deep sponge communities.](#)

Group 5

MD221. Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic offshore circalittoral zone

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD221](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD2211](#)

OSPAR:

#*Lophelia pertusa* reefs

#Coral Gardens

IE:

=SS.SBR.Crl

General description

This habitat type occurs at a depth of between 50-200m or deeper, offshore in sheltered, cold, mostly aphotic waters in areas of elevated current. The reefs are characteristically formed by *Lophelia pertusa* on silt or rock on the continental slope and on rock on the continental shelf. These deep-water corals lack symbiotic algae; thus, they can live in the darkness of the deep sea. The coral colonies aggregate as patches and banks to form reefs that support hundreds of other species such as sponges, polychaete worms, echinoderms (starfish, sea urchins, brittle stars) and bryozoans (sea mats). In southern regions and Macaronesia, other reef-forming species apart from *L. pertusa* occur.

Characteristic species

The characteristic colony-forming coral is *Lophelia pertusa*. *Dendrophyllia* spp. and *Eunicella verrucosa* are also typical species.

In the Southern NE Atlantic and Macaronesian region, characteristic species can differ, including for example *Savalia savaglia*, *Antipathella wollastoni*, *Madracis asperula*, *Anomocora fecunda* and even some species with a main distribution in the Mediterranean such as *Paramuricea grayi* and *Ellisella paraplexauroides*.

Associated species

Common species include boring sponges, anemones, bryozoans, gorgonians (*Paragorgia arborea*, *Paramuricea placomus*, *Primnoa resedaeformis*), polychaetes, barnacles, squat lobsters (*Munida sarsi*) and bivalves. Other hard corals like *Madrepora oculata* and *Solenosmilia variabilis* may also occur. Common fish include the redfish (*Sebastes viviparous* and *Sebastes marinus*), ling (*Molva molva*) and tusk (*Brosme brosme*).

Mesophotic coral gardens off the Iberian Coast are dominated by the coral *Dendrophyllia cornigera* and are often accompanied by the following species: *Antho* spp., *Axinella* spp., *Geodia* sp., *Mycale* (*Mycale*) *lingua*, *Tethya* spp. *Polyplumaria flabellata*, *Parantipathes larix*, *Filograna implexa*, *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, sea urchins *Echinus melo* and *Gracilechinus acutus*, *Parastichopus regalis* and the sea star *Marthasterias glacialis*. Associated fish species are: *Capros aper*, *Labrus mixtus*, *Merluccius merluccius* and *Scorpaena scrofa*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The principal threat is physical damage by fishing gear. There are documented instances of damage in northwest European waters, although these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Petroleum industry developments with associated discharges of drilling mud and drill cuttings may also negatively affect the corals. Given

their slow growth rate, reefs may take centuries to recover from damage, if at all.

Global warming and the associated fast changes in temperatures, current and stratification patterns, food availability and seawater acidity may in the long run pose the most significant threat to the existing distribution of calcifying organisms, starting with those in shallower waters.

Local threats emanate from oil and gas exploration, dumping of solid waste and dredged soils.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active Ecological Restoration of cold-water corals has been reviewed by Montseny et al. (2021), who highlighted that in order to ensure the long-term viability and success of any restoration action, it is essential to include holistic and long-term monitoring programs, and to ideally combine active restoration with natural spontaneous regeneration (i.e., passive restoration) strategies such as the implementation of deep-sea Marine Protected Areas. A combination of passive and active restoration approaches with the involvement of local society would be the best optimal option to achieve and ensure cold water coral restoration success.

The possibility to restore a damaged *Lophelia pertusa* reef was successfully tested by using transplants of *L. pertusa* from a healthy reef (Jonsson et al. 2015. Dahl 2013). There seems to be a high potential for active restoration of cold-water coral habitats.

Bibliographic sources

[Dahl, M., 2013. Conservation genetics of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* \(Scleractinia\), Doctoral thesis, Gothenburg University.](#)

[EUNIS factsheet: Cold water coral reefs in the Atlantic offshore circalittoral zone.](#)

[JNCC: Coral Reefs.](#)

[JNCC: *Lophelia* reefs.](#)

Jonsson, L., Dahl, M., Strömberg, S., Lindegarth, M., André, C., & Lundälv, T., 2015. In situ measurement of survival and growth of genotyped transplanted fragments of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa*. Sweden: University of Gothenburg.

[Montseny, M., Linares, C., Carreiro-Silva, M., Henry, L-A., Billett, D., Cordes, E.E., Smith, C.J., Papadopoulou, N., Bilan, M., Girard, F., Burdett, H.L., Larsson, A., Strömberg, S., Viladrich, N., Barry, J.P., Baena, P., Godinho, A., Grinyó, J., Santín, A., Morato, T., Sweetman, A.K., Gili, J-M., Gori, A., 2021 Active Ecological Restoration of Cold-water corals: Techniques, Challenges, Costs and Future Directions. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8:621151.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[OSPAR: *Lophelia pertusa* Reefs.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

[The Marine Lige Information Network \(MarLIN\): Deep sponge communities.](#)

Group 5

ME122. Sponge communities on Atlantic upper bathyal rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME122](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME1221](#), [ME1222](#)

OSPAR:
<Deep-sea sponge aggregations

IE:
=M.AtUB.Ro.DeoSpo

General description

This broad habitat type occurs approximately at depths of 200-600m on rocks and other hard substrata. The habitat can be formed by a great variety of different species, excluding only encrusting sponge morphotypes. Typically dominated by *Reteporella* and Axinellid sponges or *Lobose* sponges and stylasterids. Similar habitats can occur also on mixed, coarse and muddy sediments that have different characteristic sponges and associated species. Similar to the circalittoral sponge habitats.

Characteristic species

Frequently reported from sponge grounds on rocky substrates are *Asconema setubalense*, *Geodia* spp., *Stryphnus ponderosus*, *Stelletta* spp., *Polymastia* spp., and *Phakellia* spp. Aggregations of Axinellid or lobose sponges, cup sponges, stylasterid corals and/or the bryozoan *Reteporella* are also typical.

From the Macaronesian region, *Leiodermatium* spp. and *Corallistes* spp. are also known to be characteristic.

Associated species

Squat lobsters (*Munida*) are common.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future. Moreover, there are negative effects on sponge community composition caused by the oil and gas industry (habitat transformation, contamination by hazardous substances). Pollution from land-based activities and shipping is also a threat as well as deep-sea mining activities (ranging from exploration of mining fields to alteration of the seafloor).

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Deep sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[JNCC: Lobose sponge and stylasterid assemblage on Atlantic upper bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[JNCC: *Reteporella* and Axinellid sponges on Atlantic upper bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[OSPAR: Deep-sea sponge aggregations.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

ME123. Mixed cold water coral communities on Atlantic upper bathyal rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME123](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME1231](#)

OSPAR:

#*Lophelia pertusa* reefs, <Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtUB.Ro.MixCor

General description

This habitat type occurs on upper bathyal hard substrates at depths of 200-600m. Although this biotope is dominated by corals, these do not form a living coral reef. Several different coral types can be present, as well as sponges and ophiuroids. *Lophelia pertusa* forms distinct colonies on upper bathyal rock. Similar broad communities can occur also on upper bathyal coarse sediment and lower bathyal rocky habitats, but their associated species will differ.

Characteristic species

Lophelia pertusa, *Eunicella verrucosa*, *Dendrophyllia* spp., and the gorgonian coral (*Primnoa*) are characteristic. *Acanthogorgia* spp. and *Paragorgia* spp. can also occur.

In the Macaronesian region, *Stichopathes*, *Antipathes* and *Coenosmilia* form characteristic communities as well as *Pheronema carpenteri*, *Corallium niobe* and *Hemicorallium tricolor*.

Associated species

Madrepora oculata, Hydrozoa, Actinaraea, *Pandalus borealis*, Cerianthidae, *Cidaris cidaris*, *Phelliactis* spp., *Psolus squamatus*, *Pliobothrus* spp., *Munida* spp., Aberrantidae, *Anthomastus* spp., Anomiidae, Caryophylliidae, Porifera (massive lobose, branching, encrusting), Serpulidae, Paguridae, Ophiuroidea.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently in the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Local threats emanate from oil and gas exploration, dumping of solid waste and dredged soils.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as strictly protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited as well as all other extractive activities.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Discrete *Lophelia pertusa* colonies on Atlantic upper bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[JNCC: Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic upper bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[OSPAR: *Lophelia pertusa* Reefs.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

ME221. Atlantic upper bathyal cold water coral reef

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME221](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [ME2211](#), [ME2212](#)

OSPAR:

#*Lophelia pertusa* reefs
<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtUB.Bi.CorRee

General description

This habitat occurs in the upper bathyal zone at a depth of about 200-600m and consists of reefs formed by Scleractinian corals. In this zone, the most prominent characteristic reef forming coral is *Lophelia pertusa*. The reefs attach to hard substrate while they can also form on coarse sediment, where the corals initially attach to pebbles and cobbles. Associated species include a great variety of other corals, sponges and other fauna. In southern areas such as the Macaronesian region, other species can also be dominant.

Characteristic species

Lophelia pertusa, *Eunicella verrucosa*, *Dendrophyllia* spp., and the gorgonian coral (*Primnoa*) are characteristic. *Acanthogorgia* spp. and *Paragorgia* spp. can also occur.

Associated species

Caryophylliidae, Actiniaria, Ophiuroidea, *Phelliactis* spp., Cerianthidae, Ascidiacea, *Stichopathes gravieri*, *Antipathella* spp., *Cidaris* spp., Decapoda, *Madrepora oculata*, *Munida* spp., *Leiopathes* spp., encrusting Porifera, Serpulidae, Majidae.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened as they are found in areas which are frequently in the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat. Local threats emanate from oil and gas exploration, dumping of solid waste and dredged soils.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as strictly protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources as well as all other extractive activities are prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal cold water coral reef \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal live *Lophelia pertusa* reef \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[JNCC: Mixed coral assemblage on Atlantic upper bathyal *Lophelia pertusa* reef framework \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[OSPAR: *Lophelia pertusa* Reefs.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

ME322. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME322](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME3221](#)

OSPAR:

#*Lophelia pertusa* reefs
<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtUB.Co.MixCor

General description

The biological diversity of coral communities is typically high and often includes several species of coral belonging to different taxonomic groups, such as leather corals (*Alcyonacea*), gorgonians (*Gorgonacea*), sea pens (*Pennatulacea*), black corals (*Antipatharia*), hard corals (*Scleractinia*) and, in some places, stony hydroids (lace or hydrocorals: *Stylasteridae*). However, reef-forming hard corals (e.g., *Lophelia*, *Madrepora* and *Solenosmilia*), if present, occur only as small or scattered colonies and not as a dominating habitat component. The habitat can also include relatively large numbers of sponge species, although they are not a dominant component of the community. This habitat occurs in the upper bathyal zone at a depth of about 200-600m. *Lophelia pertusa* is the most prominent species, but also other reef forming species are characteristic. The reefs form on coarse sediment, where the corals initially attach to pebbles and cobbles.

Characteristic species

Lophelia pertusa, *Eunicella verrucosa*, *Dendrophyllia* spp., and the gorgonian coral (*Primnoa*) are also characteristic. *Acanthogorgia* spp. and *Paragorgia* spp. can also occur.

Associated species

Caryophylliidae, *Actiniaria*, *Ophiuroidea*, *Phelliactis* spp., *Cerianthidae*, *Asciadiacea*, *Stichopathes gravieri*, *Antipathella* spp., *Cidaris* spp., *Decapoda*, *Madrepora oculata*, *Munida* spp., *Acanthogorgia armata*, *Leiopathes*, encrusting *Porifera*, *Serpulidae*, *Majidae*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened as they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources (including oil and gas, deep sea mining) is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal cold water coral reef \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[OSPAR: *Lophelia pertusa* Reefs.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

ME324. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME324](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME3241](#)

OSPAR:

<Deep-sea sponge aggregations

IE:

=M.AAUB.Co.DeeSpo

General description

This habitat type occurs on upper bathyal coarse sediment at depths of 300-600m. Sponges of all morphotypes (except encrusting) dominate. *Geodia* and other massive sponge forms are common. This habitat type can also occur on mud, rock and mixed sediment with different associated infaunal species assemblages.

Characteristic species

Geodia barretti, *Geodia macandrewii*, *Geodia atlantica*, *Geodia phlegraei*, *Leiodermatium spp.*, *Macandrewia spp.*, *Neophrissospongia spp.*

Associated species

Stryphnus ponderosus, *Stelletta normani*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Deep sponge aggregation on Atlanto-Arctic upper bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[JNCC: *Geodia* and other massive sponges on Atlanto-Arctic upper bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: Deep-sea sponge aggregations.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

[Xavier, J.R., Rees, D.J., Pereira, R., Colaço, A., Pham, C.K., Carvalho, F.C., 2021. Diversity, Distribution and Phylogenetic Relationships of Deep-Sea Lithistids \(Porifera, Heteroscleromorpha\) of the Azores Archipelago. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8:600087.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME422](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME4221](#)

OSPAR:

<Deep-sea sponge aggregations

IE:

=M.AAUB.Mx.DeeSpo

ME422. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment

General description

This habitat type occurs on upper bathyal mixed sediment at depths of 300-600m. Sponges of all morphotypes (except encrusting) dominate. *Geodia* and other massive sponge forms are common. This habitat type can also occur on mud, rock and coarse sediment with different associated infaunal species assemblages.

Characteristic species

Geodia barretti, *Geodia macandrewii*, *Geodia atlantica*, *Geodia phlegraei*, *Leiodermatium spp.*, *Macandrewia spp.*, *Neophrissospongia spp.*

Associated species

Stryphnus ponderosus, *Stelletta normani*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Deep sponge aggregation on Atlanto-Arctic upper bathyal mixed sediment.](#)

[JNCC: *Geodia* and other massive sponges on Atlanto-Arctic upper bathyal mixed sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: Deep-sea sponge aggregations.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

[Xavier, J.R., Rees, D.J., Pereira, R., Colaço, A., Pham, C.K., Carvalho, F.C., 2021. Diversity, Distribution and Phylogenetic Relationships of Deep-Sea Lithistids \(Porifera, Heteroscleromorpha\) of the Azores Archipelago. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8:600087.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME623](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME6231](#)

OSPAR:

<Deep-sea sponge aggregations

IE:

=M.AtMB.Mu.DeeSpo

ME623. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic upper bathyal mud

General description

This habitat type occurs on upper bathyal muddy sediment at depths of 300-600m. It is characterised by sponges of all morphotypes (except encrusting). Aggregations of glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* are typical. This habitat type can also occur on mud, rock and coarse sediment with different associated species assemblages.

Characteristic species

Pheronema carpenteri, *Thenia muricata*

Associated species

Associated benthic communities are typically well adapted to muddy substrates. Sea pens can occur as well as ophiuroids and sometimes even corals in less dense aggregations. Crustaceans such as *Nephrops norvegicus* can be found as well as for example the gastropod *Aporrhais serresiana* or the echinoderm *Brissopsis* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future.

Best practices in nature restoration

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Deep sponge aggregation on Atlantic mid bathyal mud.](#)

[OSPAR: Deep-sea sponge aggregations.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME624](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME6241](#)

OSPAR:

<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtMB.Mu.EreCor

ME624. Erect coral field on Atlantic upper bathyal mud

General description

This habitat type occurs on upper bathyal muddy sediment. It is characterised by dense aggregations of erect soft corals, where the isidid octocoral *Acanella arbuscula* is typically the characteristic key species. The species composition otherwise depends on depth and location.

Characteristic species

Acanella arbuscula, *Radicipes gracilis*, *Kophobelemnon stelliferum*

Associated species

Ophiacantha bidentata, *Hymenaster pellucidus*, *Dytaster grandis grandis*, *Porcellanaster ceruleus*, *Echinosigra phiale*, *Ypsilothuria bitentaculata attenuata*, *Peniagone azorica*, *Ophiomusa lymani*, *Cerianthidae*, *Phelliactis robusta*, *Flabellum (Ulocyathus) alabastrum*, *Hyalonema*, *Lepidisis*

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Erect coral field on Atlantic mid bathyal mud.](#)

[JNCC: *Acanella arbuscula* assemblage on Atlantic mid bathyal mud.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral Gardens.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF121](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef
HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF1211](#)

OSPAR:

<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtLB.Ro.MixCor

MF121. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal rock

General description

This habitat type occurs on lower bathyal rock at a depth of about 1,300-2,100m. The biological diversity of coral communities is typically high and often includes several species of coral belonging to different taxonomic groups, such as leather corals (*Alcyonacea*), gorgonians (*Gorgonacea*), sea pens (*Pennatulacea*), black corals (*Antipatharia*), hard corals (*Scleractinia*) and, in some places, stony hydroids (lace or hydrocorals: *Stylasteridae*). However, reef-forming hard corals (e.g., *Lophelia*, *Madrepora* and *Solenosmilia*), if present, occur only as small or scattered colonies and not as a dominating habitat component. The habitat can also include relatively large numbers of sponge species, although they are not a dominant component of the community.

Characteristic species

Solenosmilia variabilis, *Callogorgia verticillata*, *Madrepora oculata*

Associated species

Crinoidea, *Caryophyllia*, *Porifera* (encrusting), *Bathypathes* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting

gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[Braga-Henriques, A., Porteiro, F. M., Ribeiro, P. A., de Matos, V., Sampaio, Í., Ocaña, O., and Santos, R. S., 2013. Diversity, distribution and spatial structure of the cold-water coral fauna of the Azores \(NE Atlantic\), *Biogeosciences*, 10, 4009–4036.](#)

[JNCC: Discrete *Solenosmilia variabilis* colonies on Atlantic lower bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[JNCC: Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral gardens.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF221](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MF2211](#), [MF2212](#)

OSPAR:

<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtLB.Bi.CorRee

MF221. Atlantic lower bathyal cold water coral reef

General description

This habitat type occurs on lower bathyal rock at a depth of about 1,300-2,100m and consists of reefs formed by *Scleractinian variabilis*. The reefs attach to hard substrate, but can also form on coarse sediment, where the corals initially attach to pebbles and cobbles. The reefs support a great variety of other coral species, sponges, and other fauna. This habitat type can also be found on rocky substrate.

Characteristic species

Solenosmilia variabilis, *Candidella* spp., *Acanella* spp., *Madrepora* spp., *Desmophyllum* spp.,

Associated species

Isididae, *Ophiactis*, encrusting and massive lobose *Porifera*, *Anthomastus grandiflorus*, *Zoanthidae*, *Antipathes* sp., *Leiopathes* sp., *Stichopathes* sp., *Aphrocallistes*, *Alcyonacea*, *Actiniaria*, *Munida*, Lamellate sponge, *Stichopathes gravieri*, *Acanthogorgia armata*, *Crinoidea*, *Asciacea*, *Ophiuroidea*, *Caryophylliidae*, *Hexadella dedritifera*, *Psolus squamatus*, *Pandalus*, *Echinus*. Fish include the false boarfish *Neocyttus helgae*, *Lepidion eques*, and orange roughy *Hoplostethus atlanticus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[Braga-Henriques, A., Porteiro, F. M., Ribeiro, P. A., de Matos, V., Sampaio, Í., Ocaña, O., and Santos, R. S., 2013. Diversity, distribution and spatial structure of the cold-water coral fauna of the Azores \(NE Atlantic\), *Biogeosciences*, 10, 4009–4036.](#)

[Carvalho Ferreira, M.L., Robinson, L.F., Stewart, J.A., Li, T., Chen, T., Burke, A., Kitahara, M.V., White, N.J., 2022. Spatial and temporal distribution of cold-water corals in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean over the last 150 thousand years, *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceano*.](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal cold water coral reef \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal live *Solenosmilia variabilis* reef \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[JNCC: Mixed coral assemblage on Atlantic lower bathyal *Solenosmilia* reef framework \(biogenic structure\).](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF321](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF3211](#)

OSPAR:

<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtLB.Co.MixCor

MF321. Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment

General description

This habitat type occurs on lower bathyal coarse sediment at a depth of about 1,300-2,100m. Discrete colonies of *Solenosmilia variabilis* attached to coral rubble are typical. Associated species include sponges and ophiuroids. Similar epifaunal broad communities occur also on mid and upper bathyal zones and on rocky substrates. Associated species will likely differ.

Characteristic species

Solenosmilia variabilis, *Desmophyllum* spp., *Madrepora* spp.

Associated species

Ophiuroidea, *Crinoidea*, *Caryophyllia* spp., *Porifera*, *Bathypathes* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[Carvalho Ferreira, M.L., Robinson, L.F., Stewart, J.A., Li, T., Chen, T., Burke, A., Kitahara, M.V., White, N.J., 2022. Spatial and temporal distribution of cold-water corals in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean over the last 150 thousand years, Deep Sea Resea.](#)

[JNCC: Discrete *Solenosmilia variabilis* colonies on Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[JNCC: Mixed cold water coral community on Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral gardens.](#)

[Templado, J., Ballesteros, E., Galparsoro, I., Borja, Á., Serrano, A., Martín, L., Brito, A., 2012. Guía interpretativa. Inventario español de hábitats marinos.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF622](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF6221](#)

OSPAR:
<Deep-sea sponge aggregations

IE:
=M.AtLB.Mu.DeeSpo

MF622. Sponge aggregation on Atlantic lower bathyal mud

General description

This habitat type occurs on lower bathyal mud at a depth of about 1,300-2,100m. The broad community is dominated by sponges, usually the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri*. A similar habitat can also occur on the upper and mid bathyal zone, and on rocky and mixed substrates. Associated species will differ.

Characteristic species

Pheronema carpenteri.

Associated species

Porifera (massive lobose, encrusting, massive globose), *Sabellidae*, *Cerianthidae*, *Asciacea*, *Hydrozoa*, *Ophiuroidea*, *Polynoidae/Aphroditidae*, *Syringammina fragilissima*, *Thenia muricata*, *Munida tenuimana*, *Hyalonema*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is fragile and sensitive to direct physical disturbance from demersal fishing gear. This includes trawling, dredging, bottom set nets and potting. Smothering by suspended sediments which could result from fishing activity, dredge disposal or nearby construction are other potential threats. Climate change may change the composition of species associated with this habitat in the future.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Deep sponge aggregation on Atlantic lower bathyal mud.](#)

[JNCC: *Pheronema carpenteri* field on Atlantic lower bathyal mud.](#)

Group 5

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF623](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF6231](#)

OSPAR:

<Coral gardens

IE:

=M.AtLB.Co.MixCor

MF623. Erect coral field on Atlantic lower bathyal mud

General description

This habitat type occurs on lower bathyal mud at a depth of about 1,300-2,100m and is characterised by dense aggregations of erect soft corals. The dominant species is typically the Isidid octocoral *Acanella arbuscula*. A similar community can occur in mid bathyal mud. The broad community is functionally similar to seapen fields.

Characteristic species

Acanella arbuscula.

Associated species

Ophiacantha bidentata, *Hymenaster pellucidus*, *Dytaster grandis grandis*, *Porcellanaster ceruleus*, *Echinostigma phiale*, *Ypsilothuria bitentaculata attenuata*, *Peniagone azorica*, *Ophiomusa lymani*, *Cerianthidae*, *Phelliactis robusta*, *Flabellum (Ulocyathus) alabastrum*, *Hyalonema*, *Lepidisis*, *Kophobelemnion*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold water coral reef species have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events).

The principal threat to cold water coral reefs is trawling activities, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged by bottom currents.

There are documented instances of damage in North-west European waters, but these are most likely a minute fraction of the number of instances where such reefs have been damaged. Global climate change, including acidification and warming forms an additional threat.

Best practices in nature restoration

Appointing areas where the biotope is known to occur as protected sites where bottom trawling, offshore construction work and exploitation of soil resources is prohibited.

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting

gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[JNCC: Erect coral field on Atlantic lower bathyal mud.](#)

[JNCC: *Acanella arbuscula* assemblage on Atlantic lower bathyal mud.](#)

[OSPAR: Coral gardens.](#)

Figure 05-02, *Ephydatia fluviatilis*, Bay of Bothnia, Baltic Sea

Source: Brackish water freshwater sponge (*Ephydatia fluviatilis*), Kalajoki, Lepänen, Bay of Bothnia, © Jussi-Tapio Roininen and Metsähallitus, 2011

Group 5

MB138. Baltic infralittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB138](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1150, #1160, <1170, #1180, #1650, #8330

European Red List: <BAL7

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM:
AA.A1J

DE:
#05.02.01.01.06
< § 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of rock, boulders or stones of more than 63mm in diameter. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic sponges cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. They favour areas with bottom currents, as the sponges are feeding on plankton, detritus and dissolved organic material.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all, more common in exposed areas; Depth range: photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea. As photic stony bottoms are scarce in the Southwestern and Southern Baltic Sea, this habitat is more common along the Swedish, Danish, Estonian and Finnish coastline or at some offshore reefs (HELCOM, 2013).

Characteristic species

Porifera: *Ephydatia fluviatilis*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Haliclona* (Syn: *Chalina*) *oculata*, *Halisarca dujardini*.

According to HELCOM, 2013, most of the erect and large growing sponges are marine species reaching their distribution limit in the Western Baltic Sea (Stresemann et al. 1992). The higher diversity of the sponges is found in the Southwestern Baltic Sea in zones with a higher salinity (HELCOM, 2013). Freshwater sponges occur in zones with a lower salinity to a maximum of 6 psu (Stresemann et al. 1992) in the Northern Baltic Sea or in the lagoons of the Southern Baltic Sea. The freshwater sponges form a more crust-like biotope.

Associated species

Associated species include erect growing moss animals, sea squirts, hydroids, tube-building polychaetes, echinoderms, hydrozoans, scale worms, sea spiders, brittle stars, red algae, kelp (HELCOM, 2013). As the erect sponges are more common in zones with a higher salinity, the associated invertebrate and fish species are also more diverse in those areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction

as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed substrates dominated by sponges \(Porifera\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.A1J Baltic photic rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges \(Porifera\).](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Group 5

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB43A](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral mixed sediment

[HD](#): #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

[European Red List](#): <BAL7

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM:
AA.M1J

DE:
#05.02.06.01.07
< § 30 "Riffe"

MB43A. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges (Porifera)

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with 10-90% coverage of hard (rock/boulders/stone) and 10-90% soft substrata (e.g., muddy/coarse sediment/sand). Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic sponges cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. The substrate is soft or crystalline rock, boulders or stones mixed with mobile substrates such as sand or coarse substrate.

Depth range: photic zone.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Ephydatia fluviatilis lives in the coastal waters with a salinity of up to 5ppt. Other sponge species occurring in the Southwestern Baltic Sea include *Halichondria panicea*, *Haliclona* (Syn: *Chalina*) *oculata*, *Halisarca dujardini*.

According to HELCOM, 2013, most of the erect and large growing sponges are marine species reaching their distribution limit in the Western Baltic Sea (Stresemann et al. 1992). The higher diversity of the sponges is found in the Southwestern Baltic Sea, in zones with a higher salinity (HELCOM, 2013). Freshwater sponges occur in zones with a lower salinity to a maximum of 6 psu (Stresemann et al. 1992) in the Northern Baltic Sea or in the lagoons of the Southern Baltic Sea. The freshwater sponges form a more crust-like biotope.

Associated species

Erect growing moss animals, sea squirts, hydroids, tube-building polychaetes, echinoderms, hydrozoans, scale worms, sea spiders, brittle stars, red algae, kelp (HELCOM, 2013). As the erect sponges are more common in zones with a higher salinity, the associated invertebrate and fish species are also more diverse in those areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed substrates dominated by sponges \(Porifera\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AA.M1J Baltic photic mixed substrate characterised by epibenthic sponges \(Porifera\).](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Group 5

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC133](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1150, <1170, #1180, #1650, #8330

European Red List: <BAL42

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC1331](#), [MC1332](#), [MC1333](#)

HELCOM:
AB.A1G

DE:
#05.02.01.01.05
< § 30 "Riffe"

MC133. Baltic circalittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic cnidarians

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least 90% coverage of rock, boulders or stones of more than 63mm in diameter. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic cnidarians cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Substrate is rock and boulders.

Depth: typically, 20m and deeper.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Hydroids: *Gonothyrea loveni*, *Laomedea* spp., *Cordylophora caspia* (found in the whole Baltic Sea; Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Soft corals (*Alcyonacea*): *Alcyonium digitatum* and *Swiftia rosea* (in the Kattegat and Belt Sea; HELCOM, 2013a).

Hard corals (*Scleractinida*): *Caryophylla smithii* (in the Kattegat; HELCOM, 2013b).

Sea anemones (*Actiniarida*): *Edwardsia* spp., *Metridium dianthus*, *Metridium senile*, *Urticina felina* (in the Kattegat and Belt Sea; HELCOM, 2013c).

Associated species

The nudibranch *Tritonia hombergii* is common among *Alcyonium digitatum*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by soft corals \(Alcyonacea\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by stone corals \(Scleractinida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013c. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by sea anemones \(Actiniarida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.A1G Baltic aphotic rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic cnidarians.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Group 5

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC136](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1130, #1150, <1170, #1180, #1650, #8330

European Red List: <BAL42

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM:
AB.A1J

DE:
#05.02.01.01.06
< § 30 "Riffe"

MC136. Baltic circalittoral rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least 90% coverage of rock, boulders or stones of more than 63mm in diameter. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic sponges cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Substrate is rock and boulders.

Depth: typically, 20m and deeper.

Geographic range: whole Baltic Sea; as stony bottoms are scarce in the Southwestern and Southern Baltic Sea, this habitat is more common along the Swedish, Danish, Estonian and Finnish coastline or in some offshore reefs (HELCOM, 2013).

Characteristic species

Ephydatia fluviatilis (up to 6psu). In zones with a higher salinity in the Southwestern Baltic Sea: *Halichondria panicea*, *Haliclona* (Syn: *Chalina*) *oculata*, *Halisarca dujardini*.

According to HELCOM, 2013, most of the erect and large growing sponges are marine species reaching their distribution limit in the Western Baltic Sea (Stresemann et al. 1992). The higher diversity of the sponges is found in the Southwestern Baltic Sea in zones with a higher salinity (HELCOM, 2013). Freshwater sponges occur in zones with a lower salinity to a maximum of 6 psu (Stresemann et al. 1992) in the Northern Baltic Sea or in the lagoons of the Southern Baltic Sea. The freshwater sponges form a more crust-like biotope.

Associated species

Associated species include erect growing moss animals, sea squirts, hydroids, tube-building polychaetes, echinoderms, hydrozoans, scale worms, sea spiders, brittle stars, red algae, kelp (HELCOM, 2013). As the erect sponges are more common in zones with a higher salinity, the associated invertebrate and fish species are also more diverse in those areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction

as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed substrates dominated by sponges \(Porifera\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.A1J Baltic aphotic rock and boulders characterised by epibenthic sponges \(Porifera\).](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Group 5

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC433](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mixed sediment

HD:#1110, #1130, #1170, #1180, #1650

European Red List: <BAL42

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC4331](#), [MC4332](#),

[MC4333](#)

HELCOM:

AB.M1G

DE:

#05.02.06.01.06

< § 30 "Riffe"

MC433. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least 10-90% coverage of hard (rock/boulders/stone) and 10-90% soft substrata (e.g., muddy/coarse sediment/sand). Epibenthic cnidarians cover at least 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Out of the epibenthic cnidarians, hydroids constitute at least 50% of the biomass. Substrate is soft or crystalline rock, boulders or stones mixed with mobile substrates such as sand or coarse substrate.

Depth: typically, from 20 to 100m.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

Hydroids: *Gonothyrea loveni*, *Laomedea* spp., *Cordylophora caspia* (found in the whole Baltic Sea; Kotilainen et al. 2020).

Soft corals (*Alcyonacea*): *Alcyonium digitatum* and *Swiftia rosea* (in the Kattegat and Belt Sea; HELCOM, 2013a).

Hard corals (*Scleractinida*): *Caryophylla smithii* (in the Kattegat; HELCOM, 2013b).

Sea anemones (*Actiniarida*): *Edwardsia* spp., *Metridium dianthus*, *Metridium senile*, *Urticina felina* (in the Kattegat and Belt Sea; HELCOM, 2013c).

Associated species

The nudibranch *Tritonia hombergii* is common among *Alcyonium digitatum*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013a. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by soft corals \(Alcyonacea\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013b. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by stone corals \(Scleractinida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2013c. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed hard and soft substrates dominated by sea anemones \(Actiniarida\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.M1G Baltic aphotic mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians.](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Group 5

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC436](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1180, #1650

European Red List: <BAL42, <BAL49

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

HELCOM:
AB.M1J

DE:
#05.02.06.01.07
< § 30 "Riffe"

MC436. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with 10-90% coverage of hard (rock/boulders/stone) and 10-90% soft substrata (e.g., muddy/coarse sediment/sand). Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic sponges cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Substrate is soft or crystalline rock, boulders or stones mixed with mobile substrates such as sand or coarse substrate.

Depth: typically, from 20 to 100m.

Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea; as stony bottoms are scarce in the Southwestern and Southern Baltic Sea, this habitat is more common along the Swedish, Danish, Estonian and Finnish coastline or in some offshore reefs (HELCOM, 2013).

Characteristic species

Ephydatia fluviatilis (up to 6psu).

In zones with a higher salinity in the Southwestern Baltic Sea: *Halichondria panicea*, *Haliclona* (Syn: *Chalina*) *oculata*, *Halisarca dujardini*, *Scypha ciliata*.

According to HELCOM, 2013 most of the erect and large growing sponges are marine species reaching their distribution limit in the Western Baltic Sea (Stresemann et al. 1992). The higher diversity of the sponges is found in the Southwestern Baltic Sea in zones with a higher salinity (HELCOM, 2013). Freshwater sponges occur in zones with a lower salinity to a maximum of 6 psu (Stresemann et al. 1992) in the Northern Baltic Sea or in the lagoons of the Southern Baltic Sea. The freshwater sponges form a more crust-like biotope.

Associated species

Associated species include erect growing moss animals, sea squirts, hydroids, tube-building polychaetes, echinoderms, hydrozoans, scale worms, sea spiders, brittle stars, red algae, kelp (HELCOM, 2013). As the erect sponges are more common in zones with a higher salinity, the associated invertebrate and fish species are also more diverse in those areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat are increased sedimentation caused by eutrophication, and physical pressures such as bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover and maintain its natural function, measures are e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction

as well as measures to reduce eutrophication and avoid contamination and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2013. Baltic aphotic rock and boulders or mixed substrates dominated by sponges \(Porifera\). BIOTOPE INFORMATION SHEET.](#)

[HELCOM, 2019. HELCOM underwater biotope classification. AB.M1J Baltic aphotic mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges \(Porifera\).](#)

[Kotilainen A, Kiviluoto S, Kurvinen L, Sahla M, Ehrnsten E, et al. 2020. Threatened habitat types in Finland 2018: the Baltic Sea. Red List of habitats Part II: Descriptions of habitat types. The Finnish Environment 23/2020.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Stresemann E., Hannemann H.-J., Klausnitzer B. Senglaub K. 1992. Exkursionsfauna von Deutschland. Band 1, Wirbellose (ohne Insekten). Volk und Wissen Verlag gmbH Berlin.

Figure 05-03, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* reef off the Bulgarian coasts, Black Sea

Source: *Mytilus galloprovincialis* reef off the Bulgarian coasts, Black Sea, © Janine H., 2024

Group 5

MD24. Black Sea offshore circalittoral biogenic habitats

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MD24](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

[European Red List](#):

<BLSA4.24

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

=Circalittoral rock overgrown by *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, hydrozoans, and sponges

General description

This habitat is presented by reefs formed by organisms in the circalittoral zone below the influence of wave action. It occurs in depths between 20m down to the lower limit of rock substrate distribution. The lower limit on the Northwestern Black Sea shelf is a depth of about 30-70m. In front of the Bulgarian coast, it is a depth of about 35-45m, and the most significant areas of the habitat are located on the southern shelf. The lithological varieties of the circalittoral rock substrate are limestones, sandstones, marls, clay rock complexes, volcanogenic complexes, and conglomerates.

The fauna is highly diverse, including many invertebrate and fish species. The dominant species is often the blue mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Other typical inhabitants are some species of hydrozoa and aquatic sponges, but the species composition is still insufficiently studied.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including the specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is "Circalittoral rock overgrown by *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, hydrozoans, and sponges".

In certain locations, other benthic species may dominate:

- Crusts and turfs formed by bryozoans, crust sponges (*Dysidea* spp.) or colonial tunicates *Botryllus schlosseri*.
- Vertical walls and ridges can be covered either by dense colonies of erect, branched sponges *Halichondria* sp. and *Haliclona* sp. or by solitary ascidians *Molgula manhattensis*, *Ascidella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*.
- Hydrozoans can form dense turfs or tall canopies in the case of larger species (*Obelia longissima*).

Data on the abundance and the status of typical species and communities, as well as their distribution and coverage, are incomplete.

Characteristic species

Characteristic species include *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Dysidea* spp., *Botryllus schlosseri*, *Halichondria* sp., *Haliclona* sp., *Molgula manhattensis*, *Ascidella aspersa*, *Ciona Intestinalis*, *Obelia longissima*.

Associated species

The invasive alien species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation pressure can lead to the destruction of mussel colonies.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

A significant threat is also the predatory press of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies and outcrops of the rocky bottom. Such a case was documented in 2007 in the area in front of Cherni Nos village, Bulgaria. In 2006-2010, a mass degradation of mussel growths was registered in separate areas along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast caused by the demographic expansion of *Rapana*.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Siltation, caused by trawling, dredging, and other activities in the adjacent waters, disturbing bottom sediments.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and appropriate technical and nature-based solutions in the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance.

With the aim to reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measures are planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial stimulation) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 5

ME14. Black Sea upper bathyal rock

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [ME14](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat type describes rock and other hard substrates in the upper bathyal zone of the Black Sea.

Bathyal and abyssal sediments are not subject to a status assessment or biodiversity protection measures, due to the natural anaerobic conditions at these depths in the Black Sea and the absence of aerobic biological communities. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the so-called peripheral shelf terrace (whose eastern end marks the shelf-continental slope boundary), is at a depth of 100-120m to 200m.

Concerning bathyal rocks and biogenic reefs, there is a scientific reserve regarding the presence in the Bulgarian Exclusive Economic Zone of the so-called "bubbling reefs", which are reef-like carbonate columns formed by anaerobic microbial consortia causing carbonate precipitation. Although these structures are present in the northwestern shelf of the Black Sea, they have not been observed on the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf.

Characteristic species

N/A

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 5

ME24. Black Sea upper bathyal biogenic habitat

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [ME24](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat type describes reefs formed by organisms in the upper bathyal zone of the Black Sea.

Bathyal and abyssal sediments are not subject to a status assessment or biodiversity protection measures, due to the natural anaerobic conditions at these depths in the Black Sea and the absence of aerobic biological communities. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the so-called peripheral shelf terrace (whose eastern end marks the shelf-continental slope boundary), is at a depth of 100-120m to 200m.

Concerning bathyal rocks and biogenic reefs, there is a scientific reserve regarding the presence in the Bulgarian Exclusive Economic Zone of the so-called "bubbling reefs", which are reef-like carbonate columns formed by anaerobic microbial consortia causing carbonate precipitation. These structures are present in the northwestern shelf of the Black Sea but have not been observed on the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf.

Characteristic species

N/A

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 5

MF14. Black Sea lower bathyal rock

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MF14](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat type describes rock and other hard substrates in the lower bathyal zone of the Black Sea. Bathyal and abyssal sediments are not subject to a status assessment or biodiversity protection measures, due to the natural anaerobic conditions at these depths in the Black Sea and the absence of aerobic biological communities. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the so-called peripheral shelf terrace (whose eastern end marks the shelf-continental slope boundary), is at a depth of 100-120m to 200m.

Concerning bathyal rocks and biogenic reefs, there is a scientific reserve regarding the presence in the Bulgarian Exclusive Economic Zone of the so-called "bubbling reefs", which are reef-like carbonate columns formed by anaerobic microbial consortia causing carbonate precipitation. These structures are present in the northwestern shelf of the Black Sea but have not been observed on the Bulgarian Black Sea shelf.

Characteristic species

N/A

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 - determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO₂.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the MSFD \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

Todorova, V., et al., 2021. [Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Figure 05-04, *Cladocora caespitosa* in the shallow waters of the Secche di Tor Paterno MPA (Italy), Mediterranean Sea

Source: *Cladocora caespitosa* in shallow waters of the Secche di Tor Paterno MPA (Italy), Mediterranean Sea, © Filippo Fratini 2009

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151E](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB2.53 or MB1.516a, MB1.516c⁴⁹

MB151E. Facies with *Cladocora caespitosa*

General description

This facies is characterised by the abundance of the Mediterranean zooxanthellate scleractinian coral *Cladocora caespitosa*. As a sessile invertebrate that harbours photosynthetic endosymbionts in their tissues, indirect and diffuse light is sufficient to ensure the life of the zooxanthellates of this hermatypic scleractinian. Given this, it may be able to develop successfully amidst macroalgae in well illuminated infralittoral rock, on concretion-forming calcareous algae, on artificial substrata or unattached in the *Posidonia* meadow and, also, on sandy and muddy beds. When abundant, this facies may typically occur in two main formations: beds and banks. Beds are composed by numerous small (10-30cm in diameter) sub-spherical colonies in dense populations. Banks are made up of large colonies, reaching several decimetres in height and covering areas of several square metres. Banks originate from beds under conditions of undisturbed accretion by means of three mechanisms: (i) fusion of adjacent colonies; (ii) 'pouring' of the incipient build-up due to gravity; and (iii) inclusion of satellite colonies. Mixed distributions of beds and banks can also be found, while a third formation has been recently described: free-living coral nodules or coralliths (about 5 cm in diameter). Banks are the most important bioconstructions of *C. caespitosa* and may deserve to be called reefs, as their calcification rates (up to 1.7kg CaCO₃/m² year) is comparable to the values of many tropical reef corals.

C. caespitosa reefs are the only coral bioherms native to the Mediterranean Sea. As other biogenic habitats, the reefs of *C. caespitosa* increase the topographic heterogeneity of the seafloor, thus enhancing benthic diversity by offering refuge and nursery area to many cryptic species. The role of major habitat former is not restricted to the living colonies but extends also to the accumulation of dead and subfossil corallites in the neighbouring sediments, increasing their content of coarse carbonate fractions.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the abundance of the Mediterranean zooxanthellate scleractinian coral *Cladocora caespitosa*. *C. caespitosa* is a colonial species that lives in symbiosis with algae at low depths (between depths of 6m and 20m) on rocky seabeds, also covered with photophilic algae, but can also be found at greater depths of up to 100m, in both sheltered and rough biotopes. It can withstand a slightly lower salinity, as in the Northern Adriatic, and it can also be found in both relatively warm (25°C) areas and those where the temperature of the water in the winter is under 10°C.

Associated species

Besides *Cladocora Caespitosa*, the solitary zooxanthellate scleractinians *Balanophyllia europaea* and the zooxanthellate form of the colonial *Madracis pharensis* may also participate in this habitat, while the azooxanthellate form

⁴⁹ Depending on the relative abundance of *Cladocora caespitosa*.

inhabits submarine caves. Other non-scleractinian species that can be found are the zooxanthellate sea anemone *Anemonia viridis*, the zooxanthellate paracyoniid *Maasella edwardsii*, the shallow-water zooxanthellate form of the gorgonian *Eunicella singularis* (whose azooxanthellate form lives deeper), and the zoocyanellate sponges *Chondrilla nucula* and *Petrosia ficiformis*. The associate biota may include photophilic algae (e.g., *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Padina pavonica*, *Treptacantha ballesterosii*), emiphotophilic algae (e.g., *Codium bursa*, *Dictyopteris polypoidioides*, *Sphaerococcus coronopifolius*), or antisciphilic algae (e.g., *Flabellia petiolata*, *Halimeda tuna*, *Peyssonnelia squamaria*) according to the specific situation.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are physical damage (fishing, anchoring, and diving damage), pollution, eutrophication, mucilage, excess of sedimentation, spread of alien invasive species, and climate change. *Cladocora caespitosa* exhibits a high capacity to recover from tissue injuries, nevertheless in recent decades it has suffered polyp bleaching and necrosis due to seawater warming and summer heat waves. Its slow growth dynamics makes *C. caespitosa* highly vulnerable to catastrophic events.

C. racemosa suffers the competition with invasive filamentous turf algae, while erect algal canopies have been shown to protect polyps from abrasion injuries. In consequence, alteration in species composition and abundances of mixed *C. caespitosa*-Fucales habitats may affect *C. caespitosa* populations. *C. caespitosa* is recognised as a species of conservation interest according to the Barcelona Convention and is listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Ballesteros, E., & Pons-Fita, A., 2020. Corals and macroalgae can sometimes coexist. *Frontier in Ecology and the Environment*, 18: 150.

Chefaoui, R.M., Casado-Amezúa, P., Templado, J., 2017. Environmental drivers of distribution and reef development of the Mediterranean coral *Cladocora caespitosa*. *Coral Reefs* 36 (4), 1195-1209.

Kersting, D.K., Bensoussan, N., Linares, C., 2013. Long-term responses of the endemic reef-builder *Cladocora caespitosa* to Mediterranean warming. *PLoS ONE*, 8: e70820.

Kersting, D.K., Cebrian, E., Verdura, J., Ballesteros, E., 2017. A new *Cladocora caespitosa* population with unique ecological traits. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 18 (1), 38-42.

Kersting, D.K., Teixidó, N., Linares, C., 2014. Recruitment and mortality of the temperate coral *Cladocora caespitosa*: implications for the recovery of endangered populations. *Coral Reefs* 33, 403-407.

Kružić, P., Sršen, P., Cetinić, K., Zavodnik, D., 2013. Coral tissue mortality of the coral *Cladocora caespitosa* caused by gastropod *Coralliophila meyendorffi* in the Mljet National Park (eastern Adriatic Sea). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 93 (8), 2101-2108.

López-Márquez, V., Lozano-Martín, C., Hadjioannou, L., Acevedo, I., Templado, J., Jimenez, C., Taviani, M., Machordom, A., 2021. Asexual reproduction in bad times? The case of *Cladocora caespitosa* in the eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Coral Reefs* 40, 663-677.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151Q](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.524a

MB151Q. Facies with *Astroides calycularis*

General description

This facies is characterised by the madreporian *Astroides calycularis* and is typical of the Western Mediterranean pre-coralligenous zone. *A. calycularis* form facies due to the gregarism of the crawling planulae, which favours the formation of dense monospecific stands that may cover the rock by up to 90% between just below the sea surface and at a depth of about 15m. In exposed places, the species typically exhibits massive colonies and polygonal corallites, while in sheltered places colonies tend to have a bush-shaped morphology with almost circular corallites. The species may also occur deeper down (depths up to 40-50m), but it is not as abundant as in shallow water.

This facies constitutes a “pseudo-reef”, enhances benthic diversity and may host a rich invertebrate fauna.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the abundance of the Mediterranean azooxanthellate scleractinians *Astroides calycularis* (colonial, bright orange, rarely yellow). *A. calycularis* is endemic to the Mediterranean Sea (although it extends also a little west of Gibraltar in the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf). It occurs mostly in the southwestern part of the Mediterranean basin and around Sicily, and its northern limit coincides with the February surface isotherm of 14°C; occurrences in the northern Tyrrhenian, the central Adriatic, and the Northern Ionian have been considered as linked to sea water warming and subsequent change in thermohaline circulation.

Associated species

Besides *Astroides calycularis*, the two azooxanthellate scleractinians *Balanophyllia regia* (solitary, golden yellow to orange) and *Phyllangia americana mouchezii* (colonial, rounded polyps, 35mm height, 8mm in diameter, red-orange, sometimes with whitish tentacles) may also live in shallow water, tolerating moderate light intensity, even if they do not form true facies. The colonies of *A. calycularis* host a rich invertebrate fauna, with more than 80 species, mainly crustaceans, annelids and molluscs, while the associated biota of this facies generally includes species typical of infralittoral rocky habitats.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are physical damage (fishing, illegal harvesting of date mussel, anchoring, and diving damages), pollution, eutrophication, increased levels of sedimentation and turbidity, and climate change (especially ocean acidification).

This habitat is linked to MSFD as narrower than the broad habitat type “Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef”.

A. calycularis is included in Annex II (endangered and threatened species) of the SPA/BD Protocol (Barcelona Convention) for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean, Annex II of the

Bern Convention, and Appendix II of CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of wild flora and fauna).

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Fenner, D., Riolo, F., Vittorio, M., 2013. New records of scleractinian corals from shallow waters of the Ionian coast of Italy. *Marine Biodiversity Records* 6, e136.

Grubelic, I., Antolic, B., Despalatovic, M., Grbec, B., Beg Paklar, G., 2004. Effect of climatic fluctuations on the distribution of warm-water coral *Astroides calycularis* in the Adriatic Sea new records and review. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 84, 599-602.

Ingrosso, G., Abbiati M., Badalamenti F., Bavestrello G., Belmonte G., Cannas R., Benedetti-Cecchi L., Bertolino, M., Bevilacqua S., Bianchi C.N., Bo M., Boscarì E., Cardone F., Cattaneoovietti R., Cau A., Cerrano C., Chemello, R., Chimienti, G., Congiu, L., Corriero, G., Costantini, F., De Leo, F., Donnarumma, L., Falace, A., Fraschetti, S., Giangrande, A., Gravina, M. F., Guarnieri, G., Mastrototaro, F., Milazzo, M., Morri, C., Musco, L., Pezзолesi, L., Piraino, S., Prada, F., Ponti, M., Rindi, F., Russo, G. F., Sandulli, R., Villamor, A., Zane, L., Boero, F., 2018. Mediterranean bioconstructions along the Italian coast. *Advances in Marine Biology* 79 (3), 61-136.

Kružić, P., Zibrowius, H., Požar-Domac, A., 2002. Actinaria and Scleractinia (Cnidaria, Anthozoa) from the Adriatic Sea (Croatia): first records, confirmed occurrences and significant range extensions of certain species. *Italian Journal of Zoology* 69, 345-353.

Parravicini, V., Mangialajo, L., Mousseau, L., Peirano, A., Morri, C., Montefalcone, M., Francour, P., Kulbicki, M., Bianchi, C.N., 2015. Climate change and warm-water species at the northwestern boundary of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Ecology* 36, 897-909.

Prada F., Musco L., Alagna A., Agnetta D., Beccari E., D'anna G., Giacalone V.M., Pipitone C., Vega Fernández T., Goffredo S., Badalamenti F., 2019. Anthropogenic impact is negatively related to coral health in Sicily (Mediterranean Sea). *Scientific Reports* 9 (1), 1-14.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Teixidó, N., Caroselli, E., Alliouane, S., Ceccarelli, C., Comeau, S., Gattuso, J. P., Fici, P., Micheli, F., Mirasole, A, Monismith, S.G., Munari, M., Palumbi, S.R., Sheets, E., Urbini, L., De Vittor, C., Goffredo, S., Gambi, M.C., 2020. Ocean

acidification causes variable trait-shifts in a coral species. *Global Change Biology* 26 (12), 6813-6830.

Terrón-Sigler, A., León-Muez, D., Peñalver-Duque, P., Espinosa Torre, F., 2016. The effects of SCUBA diving on the endemic Mediterranean coral *Astroides calycularis*. *Ocean Coastal Management* 122, 1-8.

Terrón-Sigler, A., León-Muez, D., Peñalver-Duque, P., Gálvez-César, R., Espinosa Torre, F., 2016. Geographic distribution of *Astroides calycularis* (Scleractinia: Dendrophylliidae) as a baseline to assess future human impacts on the Southern Iberian Peninsula. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 96, 1181-1189.

Terrón-Sigler, A., Peñalver-Duque, P., León-Muez, D., Espinosa Torre, F., 2014. Spatio-temporal macrofaunal assemblages associated with the endangered orange coral *Astroides calycularis* (Scleractinia: Dendrophylliidae). *Aquatic Biology* 21 (2), 143-154.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB151α](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB1.55

MB151α. Facies and association of coralligenous biocenosis (in enclave)

General description

Coralligenous is a biogenic origin habitat built by calcareous thalli of coralline algae growing in dim light conditions and in relatively calm waters. Normally, coralligenous assemblages are present in the circalittoral zone; however, in conditions where the light is sufficiently dim (e.g., cavities in the infralittoral rocks, below rock shelves, in cavities in dense *Posidonia oceanica* meadow and algal beds), coralline algae may form discontinuous calcareous structures on the infralittoral hard bottoms, even if in some cases coralline algae constitute conspicuous structures (several decimetres thick), forming peculiar habitats. This “coralligenous in enclave” means that the habitat is found in the infralittoral zone, while it normally lives in the circalittoral zone. The infralittoral coralligenous assemblages support biodiversity by providing habitat, feeding grounds, recruitment, refuge and nursery sites for many invertebrates and fishes both at the juvenile and adult stages. This habitat provides numerous ecosystem services, and is of great interest to tourists, especially for diving.

Characteristic species

Coralline algae are the primary habitat builders (i.e., *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, encrusting *Peyssonnelia* species), while the assemblages may feature species of invertebrates such as sponges, anthozoans (e.g., *Eunicella singularis* and *Cladocora caespitosa*), bryozoans (e.g., *Pentapora fascialis*, *Myriapora truncata*) and ascidians (e.g., *Halocynthia papillosa*).

Associated species

Associated species are mainly sciaphilous algae, such as the Chlorophyta *Halimeda tuna*, *Codium bursa* and *Flabellia petiolata*, the Ochrophyta *Halopteris filicina*, *Sargassum hornschurchii*, and *Cystoseira montagnei*, and the Rhodophyta *Sphaerococcus coronopifolius*, *Laurencia chondrioides*, and *Tricleocarpa fragilis*. Because of the depth at which the habitat develops, less sciaphilic algae can also be found, such as *Dictyota* spp. and *Padina pavonica*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are mechanical destruction (fishing, anchoring, and diving damages), pollution, sedimentation, spread of alien invasive species, bloom of benthic mucilage, and climate change. In particular, this habitat is threatened by thermal anomalies and physical destruction.

The inclusion of this habitat type within the HD, its recognition as a habitat of conservation interest according to the Barcelona Convention and its inclusion in the Action Plan for the conservation of the coralligenous and other calcareous bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea (UNEP/MAP 2017), highlight its need of protection and monitoring. Several Coralligenous species, belonging to Porifera, Cnidaria, Bryozoa, Mollusca, Crustacea and

Echinodermata are listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol, and in Appendix I “Strictly protected flora species” of the Bern Convention.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Action Plan for the Conservation of the Coralligenous and Other Calcareous Bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea, UN Environment/MAP Athens, Greece 2017

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Bevilacqua, S., Guarnieri G., Farella G., et al., 2018. A regional assessment of cumulative impact mapping on Mediterranean coralligenous outcrops. *Scientific Reports* 8, 1757.

Casoli, E., Raschetti, S., Mouquet, N., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Penna, M., Belluscio, A. and Ardizzone, G., 2025. Assessing the ecological and aesthetic effectiveness of restoration interventions on coralligenous reefs. *Restoration Ecology*, e70092.

Ingresso, G., Abbiati M., Badalamenti F., Bavestrello G., Belmonte G., Cannas R., Benedetti-Cecchi L., Bertolino, M., Bevilacqua S., Bianchi C.N., Bo M., Boscarì E., Cardone F., Cattaneo Vietti R., Cau A., Cerrano C., Chemello, R., Chimienti, G., Congiu, L., Corriero, G., Costantini, F., De Leo, F., Donnarumma, L., Falace, A., Frascchetti, S., Giangrande, A., Gravina, M. F., Guarnieri, G., Mastrototaro, F., Milazzo, M., Morri, C., Musco, L., Pezolesi, L., Piraino, S., Prada, F., Ponti, M., Rindi, F., Russo, G. F., Sandulli, R., Villamor, A., Zane, L., Boero, F., 2018. Mediterranean bioconstructions along the Italian coast. *Advances in Marine Biology* 79 (3), 61-136.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Coralligenous biocenosis Priority habitat IV,3.1 (EUR 27: 1170). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 213-218.

Piazzì, L., Gennaro, P., Balata, D., 2012. Threats to macroalgal coralligenous assemblages in the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 64, 2623-2629.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Zentner, Y., Garrabou, J., Margarit, N., Rovira, G., Gómez-Gras, D., Linares, C., 2025. Active restoration of a long-lived octocoral drives rapid functional recovery in a temperate reef. *Science Advances* 11: eado5249.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1519](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.514b, MC1.514c

MC1519. Facies with *Eunicella cavolini*

General description

This facies constitute one of the most typical facies of the upper layer of the coralligenous seascape. This facies can potentially be distributed wherever in the circalittoral zone where coralligenous reefs, rocky and coastal detritic bottoms are present. It mainly develops in the circalittoral zone with dim light conditions and at depths corresponding to those of the coralligenous, between 25m to about 120m, where alcyonaceans usually grow on vertical slopes or on overhanging faces, but they can also develop on sub-vertical slopes or horizontal substrates being able to withstand a slight sedimentary deposit. In the circalittoral zone this habitat can also be found on coralligenous outcrops and platforms, while at shallower depths on moderately illuminated lower infralittoral rock, both algal and invertebrate-dominated.

Characteristic species

This facies is dominated by the arborescent and long-lived alcyonacean sea fan *Eunicella cavolini*. This yellow (rarely light pink) gorgonian has colonies up to 40-50cm high, with fan-shaped cylindrical branches largely growing in a single plane and smooth and short branches.

Associated species

This facies is an invertebrate-dominated coralligenous assemblage belonging to the group of 'animal forests' growing on a basal layer built by encrusting coralline algae (e.g., *Lithophyllum stictaeforme*, *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Peyssonnelia* spp.).

Sponges (e.g., *Agelas oroides*, *Ircinia* spp., *Sarcotragus* spp.), serpulids, other cnidarians, bryozoans (e.g., *Schizomavella* spp., *Smittina cervicornis*, *Myriapora truncata*), tunicates (e.g., *Halocynthia papillosa*, *Microcosmus sabatieri*) are all typical associated species. Epibionts are very abundant on sea fan's branches: algae, serpulids, bryozoans (e.g., *Adeonella calveti*, *Turbicellepora avicularis*, *Reteporella* spp., *Pentapora fascialis*), colonial tunicates, and molluscs (i.e., *Pteria hirundo* and *Anomia ephippium*). Many other vagile invertebrates can find in branched alcyonaceans a refuge and a suitable habitat.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are a long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species, and display a low resilience to human pressures. Assemblages are particularly damaged by fishing gear, bottom trawling, anchoring, and by diving activities; moreover, they are sensitive to entanglement by mucilage filaments and suffer for thermal anomalies. Severe diseases are triggered by a complex combination of pathogenic microbial and abnormally high seawater temperatures, and several mass mortality events have been recorded in the Mediterranean in coincidence with summer heat waves and the ongoing seawater warming trend. Gorgonians are still often collected for use in aquariums and as souvenirs. No specific protection measures have been

implemented to date for all the other *Alcyonacea* species, with the significant exception of *Corallium rubrum*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Cánovas-Molina, A., Montefalcone, M., Bavestrello, G., Billah Masmoudi, M., Haguenaer, A., Hammami, P., Chaoui, L., Hichem Kara, M., Aurelle D., 2018. Connectivity patterns of the yellow gorgonian: *Eunicella cavolini* in the NW Mediterranean. *Comptes Rendus Biologies* 341 (9-10), 421-432.

Casoli, E., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Cardone, S., Farina, F., Donnini, L., Pace, D.S., Shaul, R., Belluscio, A., & Ardizzone, G., 2021. Rehabilitation of Mediterranean animal forests using gorgonians from fisheries by-catch. *Restoration Ecology*, 30.

Casoli, E., Raschetti, S., Mouquet, N., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Penna, M., Belluscio, A. and Ardizzone, G., 2025. Assessing the ecological and aesthetic effectiveness of restoration interventions on coralligenous reefs. *Restoration Ecology*, e70092.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots*, 207-233.

Grinyó, J., Gori, A., Ambroso, S., Purroy, A., Calatayud, C., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Coppari, M., Lo Iacono, C., Lòpez-González, P.J., Gili, J.M., 2016. Diversity, distribution and population size structure of deep Mediterranean gorgonian assemblages (Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea). *Prog. Oceanogr.* 145, 42-56.

Iborra, L., Leduc, M., Fullgrabe, L., Cuny, P., Gobert, S., 2022. Temporal trends of two iconic Mediterranean gorgonians (*Paramuricea clavata* and *Eunicella cavolini*) in the climate change context. *Journal of Sea Research*, 186, 102241.

Sini, M., Kipson, S., Linares, C., Koutsoubas, D., Garrabou, J., 2015. The yellow gorgonian *Eunicella cavolini*: demography and disturbance levels across the Mediterranean Sea' *Plos One* 10, e0126253.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC151A](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.514b, MC1.514c

MC151A. Facies with *Eunicella singularis*

General description

This facies constitute one of the most typical facies of the upper layer of the coralligenous seascape. This facies can potentially be distributed wherever in the circalittoral zone where coralligenous reefs, rocky and coastal detritic bottoms are present: it mainly develops in the circalittoral zone with dim light conditions and at depths corresponding to those of the coralligenous, between 25m to about 120m, where alcyonaceans usually grow on vertical slopes or on overhanging faces, but they can also develop on sub-vertical slopes or horizontal substrates being able to withstand a slight sedimentary deposit. In the circalittoral zone, this habitat can also be found on coralligenous outcrops and platforms, while at shallower depths it can be found on moderately illuminated lower infralittoral rock, both algal and invertebrate-dominated.

Characteristic species

This facies is dominated by the Mediterranean arborescent and long-lived alcyonacean sea fan *Eunicella singularis*. The white gorgonian *E. singularis* has a branching structure with a small number of nearly vertical branches and a few side branches, all smooth. The occurrence of symbiotic zooxanthellae in this sea fan causes the greenish coloration of its coenosarc.

Associated species

This facies is an invertebrate-dominated coralligenous community characterised by 'animal forests' growing on a basal layer built by encrusting coralline algae (e.g., *Lithophyllum stictaeforme*, *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Peyssonnelia* spp.).

Sponges (e.g., *Agelas oroides*, *Ircinia* spp., *Sarcotragus* spp.), serpulids, other cnidarians, bryozoans (e.g., *Schizomavella* spp., *Smittina cervicornis*, *Myriapora truncata*), tunicates (e.g., *Halocynthia papillosa*, *Microcosmus sabatieri*) are all typical species associated with this facies. The gastropod *Simnia spelta* mimics *E. singularis* and feeds and lays its eggs on its branches. Epibionts are very abundant on sea fan's branches: algae, serpulids, bryozoans (e.g., *Adeonella calveti*, *Turbicellepora avicularis*, *Reteporella* spp., *Pentapora fascialis*), colonial tunicates, and molluscs (i.e., *Pteria hirundo* and *Anomia ephippium*). Many other vagile invertebrates can find a refuge or suitable habitat in branched alcyonaceans.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are a long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species and display a low resilience to human pressures. Assemblages are particularly damaged by fishing gear, bottom trawling, anchoring, and by diving activities, are sensitive to entanglement by mucilage filaments and suffer for thermal anomalies. Severe diseases are triggered by a complex combination of pathogenic microbial and abnormally high seawater temperatures, and several mass mortality events have been recorded in the Mediterranean in coincidence with summer heat waves and the ongoing seawater warming

trend. Gorgonians are still often collected for use in aquariums and as souvenirs. No specific protection measures have been yet implemented for all the other *Alcyonacea* species, with the significant exception of *Corallium rubrum*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Ezzat, L., Merlep, L., Furla, P., Buttler, A., Ferrier-Pagès, C., 2013. The response of the Mediterranean gorgonian *Eunicella singularis* to thermal stress is independent of its nutritional regime. *Plos One* 8, e64370.

Casoli, E., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Cardone, S., Farina, F., Donnini, L., Pace, D.S., Shaul, R., Belluscio, A., & Ardizzone, G., 2021. Rehabilitation of Mediterranean animal forests using gorgonians from fisheries by-catch. *Restoration Ecology*, 30.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots*, 207-233.

Grinyó, J., Gori, A., Ambroso, S., Purroy, A., Calatayud, C., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Coppari, M., Lo Iacono, C., Lòpez-González, P.J., Gili, J.M., 2016. Diversity, distribution and population size structure of deep Mediterranean gorgonian assemblages (Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea). *Prog. Oceanogr.* 145, 42-56.

Sarda, J., Gori, A., Doñate-Ordóñez, R., Viladrich, N., Costantini, F., Garrabou, J., Linares, C., 2025. Recurrent marine heatwaves compromise the reproduction success and long-term viability of shallow populations of the Mediterranean gorgonian *Eunicella singularis*, *Marine Environmental Research*, 203,106822.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC151B](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.514b, MC1.514c

MC151B. Facies with *Paramuricea clavata*

General description

This facies is one of the most typical facies of the coralligenous seascape. It is widely distributed within the Mediterranean Sea basin in the circalittoral zone where coralligenous reefs and rocky bottoms are present. It mainly develops in the circalittoral zone with dim light conditions and at depths corresponding to those of the coralligenous, between 25m to about 120m, where alcyonaceans usually grow on vertical slopes or on overhanging faces, but they can also develop on sub-vertical slopes or horizontal substrates being able to withstand a slight sedimentary deposit. In the circalittoral zone, this habitat can also be found on coralligenous outcrops and platforms, while at shallower depths on moderately illuminated lower infralittoral rock, both algal and invertebrate-dominated.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by a high density of colonies of the gorgonian (red sea-fan) *Paramuricea clavata*, endemic in the Mediterranean Sea. *P. clavata* is among the biggest Mediterranean Sea fans (up to 1m high), with a typical purple-red colour and a single plane colony. Under certain conditions (i.e., in deep or turbid waters), some colonies may be yellow coloured. The species settles on horizontal rocky bottoms or, more commonly, on vertical walls with low sedimentation. Growth in height is about 4-5cm per year in the first years of life, then the speed decreases until it disappears when reaching the maximum sustainable size which rarely exceeds 1m. The generation time is <10 years and the average life cycle is 60 years. The species reproduces annually during the late spring-summer period by releasing eggs agglutinated inside mucous filaments. Only at the larval stage will they move away from the mother colony. An erroneous classification could occur with *P. macrospina*, that can live in sympatry with *P. clavata* and shows a morphological similarity, while they differ for the number of rows of spindles in the collaret of the polyps.

Associated species

This facies is an invertebrate-dominated coralligenous assemblage creating 'animal forests' growing on a basal layer built by encrusting coralline algae (e.g., *Lithophyllum stictaeforme*, *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Peyssonnelia* spp.).

This facies could be very rich: typical associated species are the cnidarians *Caryophyllia smithii*, *Hoplangia durotrix*, *Leptopsammia pruvoti*, *Corallium rubrum*, the bryozoans *Celleporina caminata*, *Schizomavella mamillata*, *Smittina cervicornis*, *Myriapora truncata*, Serpulidae, the sponges *Ircinia variabilis*, *Spongia officinalis*, *Sarcotragus spinosulus*, *Scalariispongia scalaris*, *Aplysina cavernicola*, *Penares euastrum* and *Agelas oroides*, and the molluscs *Thylacodes arenarius* and *Lithophaga lithophaga*. Other invertebrates colonize parts of the branches, such as the cnidarian *Alcyonium coralloides*, the bryozoans *Adeonella calveti*, *Turbicellepora avicularis*, *Reteporella* spp. and *Pentapora fascialis*, and the molluscs *Pteria hirundo* and *Anomia ephippium*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are a long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species and display a low resilience to human pressures. Assemblages are particularly damaged by fishing gear, bottom trawling, anchoring, and by diving activities, are sensitive to entanglement by mucilage filaments and suffer for thermal anomalies. Severe diseases are triggered by a complex combination of pathogenic microbial, possible seasonal impact of mucilage and abnormally high seawater temperatures, and *P. clavata* suffered several mass mortalities (e.g., in the Ligurian Sea, 1999 and 2006) due to thermal stress at low depths in coincidence with summer thermocline anomalies. In consequence of the ongoing seawater warming trend, a decline of more than 30% has been recorded in the last 20-30 years for surface populations, while the deep forests are still very dense. Gorgonians are still often collected for use in aquariums and as souvenirs. No specific protection measures have been yet implemented for all the other *Alcyonacea* species, with the significant exception of *Corallium rubrum*. The species are however already partially protected within protection being present in numerous Mediterranean MPAs.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Casoli, E., Raschetti, S., Mouquet, N., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Penna, M., Belluscio, A. and Ardizzone, G., 2025. Assessing the ecological and aesthetic effectiveness of restoration interventions on coralligenous reefs. *Restoration Ecology*, e70092.

Cerrano, C., Bavestrello, G., Bianchi, C.N., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Bava, S., Morganti, C., Morri, C., Picco, P., Sara, G., Schiaparelli, S., Siccardi, A., Sponga, F., 2000. A catastrophic mass-mortality episode of gorgonians and other organisms in the Liguria Sea (North-Western Mediterranean), summer 1999. *Ecology Letters*, 3: 284-293.

Cerrano, C., Arillo, A., Azzini, F., Calcinai, B., Castellano, L., Muti, C., Valisano, L., Zega, G., Bavestrello, G., 2005. Gorgonian population recovery after a mass mortality event. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, pp. 147-157.

Chimienti, G., Maiorca, M., Digenis, M., Poursanidis, D., 2023. Conservation status of upper-mesophotic octocoral habitats at Sporades Archipelago (Aegean Sea), *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 190, 114868.

Casoli, E., Ventura, D., Mancini, G., Cardone, S., Farina, F., Donnini, L., Pace, D.S., Shaul, R., Belluscio, A., & Ardizzone, G., 2021. Rehabilitation of

Mediterranean animal forests using gorgonians from fisheries by-catch. *Restoration Ecology*, 30.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots*, 207-233.

Grinyó, J., Gori, A., Ambroso, S., Purroy, A., Calatayud, C., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Coppari, M., Lo Iacono, C., López-González, P.J., Gili, J.M., 2016. Diversity, distribution and population size structure of deep Mediterranean gorgonian assemblages (Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea). *Prog. Oceanogr.* 145, 42-56.

Iborra, L., Leduc, M., Fullgrabe, L., Cuny, P., Gobert, S., 2022. Temporal trends of two iconic Mediterranean gorgonians (*Paramuricea clavata* and *Eunicella cavolini*) in the climate change context. *Journal of Sea Research*, 186, 102241.

Mokhtar-Jamal, K., Coma, R., Wang, J., Zuberer, F., Feral, J-P., Aurelle, D., 2013. Role of evolutionary and ecological factors in the reproductive success and the spatial genetic structure of the temperate gorgonian *Paramuricea clavata*. *Ecology and Evolution* 3 (6), 1765-1779.

Pica, D., Calcinai, B., Polisenò, A., Trainito, E., Cerrano, C., 2018. Distribution and phenotypic variability of the Mediterranean gorgonian *Paramuricea macrospina* (Cnidaria: Octocorallia). *The European Zoological Journal* 85 (1), 392-408.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC151E](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef
HD: #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.514b, MC1.514c

MC151E. Facies with *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*

General description

This facies is one of the most typical facies of the upper layer of the coralligenous seascape. It is widely distributed within the Mediterranean Sea basin in the circalittoral zone where coralligenous reefs, rocky and coastal detritic bottoms are present. It mainly develops in the circalittoral zone with dim light conditions and at depths corresponding to those of the coralligenous, between 25m to about 120m, where alcyonaceans usually grow on vertical slopes or on overhanging faces, but they can also develop on sub-vertical slopes or horizontal substrates being able to withstand a slight sedimentary deposit. In the circalittoral zone, this habitat can also be found on coralligenous outcrops and platforms, while at shallower depths on moderately illuminated lower infralittoral rock, both algal and invertebrate-dominated.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by a high density of colonies of the gorgonian (sea-fan) *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*. Species able to tolerate high sedimentation rates, it settles on detrital or muddy seabeds, even inside ports. Most present between 15 and 40m, *L. sarmentosa* can be found from depths of up to 6m to 300m. It can also colonize anthropic substrates such as wrecks. It is a gonochoric species with a greater abundance of females. The growth is rapid (2-3cm per year), male colonies reach maturity only when they are over 20cm tall, while female colonies are fertile even at smaller sizes (1-10cm). Among *Leptogorgia* species, *L. sarmentosa* is the most widely distributed in the circalittoral. It has a bushy aspect, with thin branches (straighter, slenderer and with smaller polyps with respect to other sea fans) that are usually developed at several levels, and can vary its colour from pale yellow to brick-red.

Associated species

This facies is an invertebrate-dominated coralligenous community characterised by 'animal forests' growing on a basal layer built by encrusting coralline algae (e.g., *Lithophyllum stictaeforme*, *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Peyssonnelia* spp.).

Sponges (e.g., *Agelas oroides*, *Ircinia* spp., *Sarcotragus* spp.), serpulids, other cnidarians, bryozoans (e.g., *Schizomavella* spp., *Smittina cervicornis*, *Myriapora truncata*), tunicates (e.g., *Halocynthia papillosa*, *Microcosmus sabatieri*) are all typical species associated with this facies. Epibionts are very abundant on sea fan's branches: algae, serpulids, bryozoans (e.g., *Adeonella calveti*, *Turbicellepora avicularis*, *Reteporella* spp., *Pentapora fascialis*), colonial tunicates, and molluscs (i.e., *Pteria hirundo* and *Anomia ephippium*). Many other vagile invertebrates can find a refuge or suitable habitat in branched alcyonaceans.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species and display a low resilience to human pressures. Assemblages are particularly damaged by fishing gear, bottom trawling, anchoring, and by diving activities, are sensitive to entanglement by mucilage filaments and suffer for thermal anomalies. Severe diseases are triggered by a complex combination of pathogenic microbial, possible seasonal impact of mucilage and abnormally high seawater temperatures. In consequence of the ongoing seawater warming trend, a decline may affect surface populations, while the deep forests are still very dense. Gorgonians are still often collected for use in aquariums and as souvenirs. No specific protection measures have been yet implemented for all the other *Alcyonacea* species, with the significant exception of *Corallium rubrum*. The species are however already partially protected within protection being present in numerous Mediterranean MPAs.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Cerrano, C., Bavestrello, G., Bianchi, C.N., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Bava, S., Morganti, C., Morri, C., Picco, P., Sara, G., Schiaparelli, S., Siccardi, A., Sponga, F., 2000. A catastrophic mass-mortality episode of gorgonians and other organisms in the Liguria Sea (North-Western Mediterranean), summer 1999. *Ecology Letters*, 3: 284-293.

Cerrano, C., Arillo, A., Azzini, F., Calcinaï, B., Castellano, L., Muti, C., Valisano, L., Zega, G., Bavestrello, G., 2005. Gorgonian population recovery after a mass mortality event. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* pp. 147-157.

Chimienti, G., Maiorca, M., Digenis, M., Poursanidis, D., 2023. Conservation status of upper-mesophotic octocoral habitats at Sporades Archipelago (Aegean Sea), *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 190, 114868.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots*, 207-233.

Rossi, S., Ribes, M., Coma, R., Gili, J.M., 2004. Temporal variability in zooplankton prey capture rate of the passive suspension feeder *Leptogorgia sarmentosa* (Cnidaria: Octocorallia), a case study' *Marine Biology* 144, 89-99.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC151F](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.524a, MC1.524b

MC151F. Facies with *Antipathella subpinnata* and sparse red algae

General description

This facies is dominated by the arborescent black coral *Antipathella subpinnata*; it occurs mainly on sub-horizontal or gently sloping hardgrounds (2-30°, rarely sub-vertical). In the shallower portion of its distribution, it can be found on rocks with coralline algae cover. This species occurs as small, isolated patches or dense forests, monospecific or intermixed with other habitat-forming alcyonaceans and antipatharians. The largest forests are generally found on elevated rocky reliefs (e.g., pinnacles, outcrops, boulders) exposed to moderate or strong currents. Forests are known from the Alboran Sea, North African coasts, Balearic Sea, Gulf of Lion, Ligurian and Tyrrhenian seas, Sicily Channel, Adriatic and Ionian Seas, and the Aegean Sea. Overall, is considered one of the most common facies of the Western Mediterranean mesophotic zone, because this assemblage would be typical of the lower circalittoral zone, but the presence of macro-algae means that it can be ascribed to the upper circalittoral, both along the continental platform, canyons and seamounts' summits. Dense populations have been reported also on iron wrecks. Isolated colonies can be found on other materials (e.g., concrete).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by a high density of colonies of the large arborescent (up to 1.5m high), white, branched antipatharian *Antipathella subpinnata*. *A. subpinnata* is an Atlanto-Mediterranean species. The greatest part of the global population is found in the Mediterranean basin, where this species is found throughout the area from depths of about 50m to about 600m, but mainly between depths of 60-150m. It is a stenothermal species living between 13-15°C, with the shallower populations able to withstand plumes of summer water at 16°C. The main factors driving the distribution and the structure of *A. subpinnata* forests are the availability of rock, dim light or darkness, currents (minimum of 0.08m/sec), moderate to light inclination, low to moderate silting, trophic supply, biotic interactions with other habitat formers, and fishing intensity.

It settles on rocky seabeds with poor sedimentation. In highly sedimented environments the colonies are smaller. It typically forms dense aggregations of even over 30,000 colonies. *A. subpinnata* is considered a long-lived species, with slow growth rates, reproductive capacity linked to the late summer period, low larval dispersion and generation times of about 30 years. Besides larvae, *A. subpinnata* may potentially rely also on fragmentation and polyp bail-out as dispersal strategies, which probably explains its colonisation success in the basin.

Associated species

Within the coralligenous habitat, *Antipathella subpinnata* has been recorded within dense forests of *Paramuricea clavata* and *Eunicella cavolinii* together with sponges (for example *Axinellae* spp., *Haliclona mediterranea*, *Aplysina aerophoba*) and bryozoans (e.g., *Myriapora truncata*) on a basal layer built by

encrusting coralline algae. At deeper depths, this facies has been recorded on rocky outcrops together with *Antipathes dichotoma*, *Parantipathes larix*, *Leiopathes glaberrima*, the scleractinian *Dendrophyllia cornigera*, large-sized gorgonians and various small-sized alcyonaceans (e.g., *Corallium rubrum*, *Villogorgia bebrycoides*, *Bebryce mollis*, *Muriceides lepida*). Intermixed forests usually show a higher abundance of alcyonaceans with respect to black corals. Other filter-feeders that are also reported include *Pachastrella monilifera*, *Poecillastra compressa*, *Diazona violacea*, *Halocynthia papillosa*, and *Sabella pavonina*.

The dense canopy forms a highly three-dimensional environment and can host a rich associated fauna, showing a variability depending on the local environmental conditions and the season. The colonies host several species of epibionts generally organised in large masses settled on the dead branches. The most common species are the serpulids *Filograna* spp., hydroids, the bivalve *Pteria hirundo*, the bryozoans *Schizoporella* spp., *Turbicellepora avicularis* and *Pentapora fascialis*, the ascidian *Clavelina dellavallei*, and, occasionally, some macroalgae. *Ectopleura* hydroids, crabs and pycnogonids, as well as the cryptic polyclad *Anthoplana antipathellae* laying circular cocoons of eggs on the ramifications, are often associated to the living portions. Large vagile species may move in the forest, such as *Octopus vulgaris*, *Neomaja goltziana*, *Palinurus elephas*, *Homarus gammarus*, *Holothuria* spp., *Echinus melo*, together with a rich fish community (e.g., *Anthias anthias*, *Capros aper*, *Phycis phycis*, *Labrus mixtus*, *Serranus cabrilla*, *Conger conger*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fishing activities represent the main source of decline for Mediterranean populations of *Antipathella subpinnata*. Longlines and deep benthic nets (trammel and gillnets) set in the proximity of the hardgrounds may result in coral bycatch, entanglement, mechanical damage, sediment resuspension and clogging, finally leading to a reduction of tridimensionality, alteration of biogeochemical cycles, and ultimately loss of biodiversity. Their resistant skeleton enhances the entanglement of the colony, that could be uprooted, broken or entrapped. Wounds increase the chances for the epibiosis to turn into necrosis and eventually mortality.

These species may potentially be subjected to mass mortality events possibly related to deep bottom turbid currents, thermal anomalies or land pollution, but they can also be threatened by trawling silt resuspension, seafloor drilling activities for oil exploration or mining.

Several Mediterranean SCIs/SACs (HD, N2000 Network) host black corals. Black corals are included in CITES Appendix II, Annex III of the Bern Convention, and Annex II of Barcelona Convention. They have been assessed by the IUCN in the Anthozoan Red List, and the Mediterranean Action Plan of the Barcelona Convention included black corals-dominated habitats as part of the so-called "Dark Habitats", which deserve protection. Coral aggregations have been internationally identified as special ecological features that require protection under the Convention of Biological Diversity. More specifically, "Coral Garden" habitats, as those formed by black corals on hardgrounds, are considered sensitive habitats, contributing to the formation of Vulnerable

Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) potentially impacted by deep-sea fisheries. This is the reason why it has been recommended to establish Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) where such VMEs are known to be or likely to occur, so as to put into action an ecosystem-based fishery management of deep ecosystems.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Tazioli, S., Spanò, N., Bavestrello, G., 2008. *Antipathella subpinnata* (Antipatharia, Myriopathidae) in Italian seas. Italian Journal of Zoology 75, 185-195.

Bo, M., Bavestrello, G., Canese, S., Giusti, M., Salvati, E., Angiolillo, M., Greco, S., 2009. Characteristics of a black coral meadow in the twilight zone of the central Mediterranean Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 397, 53-61.

Bo, M., Bava, S., Canese, S., Angiolillo, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Bavestrello, G., 2014. Fishing impact on deep Mediterranean rocky habitats as revealed by ROV investigation. Biological Conservation 171, 167-176.

Bo, M., Montgomery, A.D., Opresko, D.M., Wagner, D., Bavestrello, G., 2019. Antipatharians of the mesophotic zone: four case studies. In: Mesophotic Coral Ecosystems. Springer, Cham, pp. 683-708.

Chimienti, G., De Padova, D., Mossa, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2020. A mesophotic black coral forest in the Adriatic Sea. Scientific Reports 10, 1-15.

Coppari, M., Mestice, F., Betti, F., Bavestrello, G., Castellano, L., Bo, M., 2019. Fragmentation, reattachment ability and growth rate of the Mediterranean black coral *Antipathella subpinnata*. Coral Reefs 38, 1-14.

Gaino, E., Bavestrello, G., Boyer, M., Scoccia, F., Bo M., 2013. Biological and ecological relevance of black corals (Antipatharia) in the benthic environment. NOVA Science Publishers, Inc., New York.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyo, J., Dominguez-Carrio, C., Ambroso, S., Bo, M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots. Springer, 207-233.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC151G](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): #1160, <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.512b, MC1.512c

MC151G. Facies with massive sponges and sparse red algae

General description

This facies is a component of the invertebrate-dominated coralligenous community, also covered by sediment, and is dominated by massive sponges, typically *Sarcotragus foetidus* or *Spongia (Spongia) lamella*, but also other large and/or erect long-lived species (e.g., *Geodia cydonium*, *Agelas oroides*, *Axinella cannabina*, *A. polypoides*, *Ircinia* spp., *S. (S.) officinalis*, *Cacospongia mollior*, and *Aplysina cavernicola*). This facies develops in the upper layer of coralligenous assemblages, usually where gorgonians are absent or scarce. The habitat develops in the circalittoral zone under dim light conditions and at depths corresponding to those of the Coralligenous community, between 25m to about 130m, or even deeper (down to 180-200m) in the Eastern Mediterranean basin, often in high productivity areas.

Characteristic species

This facies is dominated by large/erect and long-lived sponges on a basal layer built by encrusting coralline algae. Typical massive sponges characterising the habitat are the large sponges *Sarcotragus foetidus* and *Spongia (Spongia) lamella*, together with *Sarcotragus spinosulus*, *Ircinia oros*, *S. (S.) officinalis*, and *Cacospongia mollior*. This group of sponges can be identified for their massive shape, conulose surface and usually dark and grey colours. *S. (S.) lamella* is recognised by its typical vase/fan shape. *Geodia cydonium* presents a globose shape and lobate surface, while *Aplysina cavernicola* is characterised by a digitate body with each process bearing one osculum, and both display a typical yellow colour. The massive orange sponge *Agelas oroides* can be very abundant in the Aegean and Levantine Seas.

Erect sponges may also dominate this facies, such as *Axinella cannabina* and *A. polypoides*. They can be easily recognised based on their erect shape: *A. polypoides* has a stalk and dichotomous and, occasionally, coalescent branches circular or oval in cross-section, yellow-orange, smooth surface and stellate oscula. *A. cannabina*, typically orange, has a very particular erect shape, often with one or, at most, two main stalks and few branches.

Associated species

Many other invertebrates and vertebrates (e.g., fish) can find refuge and a suitable habitat on branched sponges. Epibionts (e.g., algae) often cover the wide surface of massive sponges. The gastropod *Tyrodina perversa* is often found feeding on the sponge *Aplysina cavernicola*. *Geodia cydonium* usually hosts several species of polychaetes. Demosponges, in general, host a rich symbiotic community of eubacteria and sometimes of *Archaea*. The nudibranch *Phyllidia flava* and the epibiotic zoantharian *Parazoanthus axinellae* are often associated with *Axinella* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Their large and erect growth form makes the massive sponges highly sensitive to mechanical damage caused by human activities such as anchoring, fishing and derelict fishing gear, collection or involuntary damage from diving activities, and entanglement by mucilage filaments. Mortality events of sponges have been recorded in coincidence with recent summer heat waves and the ongoing seawater warming trend.

Geodia cydonium, *Axinella cannabina*, *A. polypoides*, *Sarcotragus foetidus*, and *Aplysina cavernicola* are listed in Annex II “Endangered or threatened species”, whilst *Spongia (Spongia) officinalis* and *S. (S.) lamella* in Annex III “Species whose exploitation is regulated” of the SPA/BD Protocol. *A. polypoides* and *Aplysina cavernicola* are also listed in Annex II “Strictly protected fauna species” of the Bern Convention, *Spongia (Spongia) officinalis* and *S. (S.) lamella* in Annex III “Protected fauna species” of the same convention. All these species are defined as ‘Endangered’ in many regional IUCN Red lists (e.g., Italy, France, Montenegro). However, further information is needed to improve knowledge about the conservation status of these sponges in the Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Azzola, A., Bertolino, M., Bianchi, C.N., Enrichetti, F., Morri, C., Oprandi, A., Toma, M., Montefalcone, M., 2021. Ecology and protection status of a marine endangered invertebrate: the sponge *Axinella polypoides* in the Ligurian Sea (Italy). *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*.

Bertolino, M., Cerrano, C., Bavestrello, G., Carella, M., Pansini, M. Calcinai, B., 2013. Diversity of Porifera in the Mediterranean coralligenous accretions, with description of a new species. *Zookeys* 336, 1-37.

Bianchi, C.N., Cocito, S., Diviacco, G., Dondi, N., Fratangeli, F., Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., Rovere, A., Sgorbini, S., Vacchi, M., Morri, C., 2018. The park never born: Outcome of a quarter of a century of inaction on the sea-floor integrity of a proposed but not established Marine Protected Area. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 28 (5),1209-1228.

Enrichetti, F., Bavestrello, G., Betti, F., Coppari, M., Toma, M., Pronzato, R., Canese, S., Bertolino, M., Costa, G., Pansini, M., Bo, M., 2020. Keratose-dominated sponge grounds from temperate mesophotic ecosystems (NW Mediterranean Sea). *Marine Ecology*, e12620.

Gerovasileiou, V., Dailianis, T., Sini, M., Otero, M., Numa, C., Katsanevakis, S., Voultsiadou, E., 2018. Assessing the regional conservation status of sponges (Porifera): The case of the Aegean ecoregion. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 19, 526-537.

Idan, T., Shefer, S., Feldstein, T., Yahel, R., Huchon, D., Ilan, M., 2018. Shedding light on an East-Mediterranean mesophotic sponge ground community and the regional sponge fauna. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 19, 84-106.

Piazzì, L., Kaleb, S., Ceccherelli, G., Montefalcone, M., Falace, A., 2019. Deep coralligenous outcrops of the Apulian continental shelf: biodiversity and spatial variability of sediment-regulated assemblages. *Continental Shelf Research* 172, 50-56.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1522](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170, <8330

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.533a, MC1.533b

MC1522. Facies with *Corallium rubrum*

General description

This facies is characterised by the high presence of the cnidarian (red coral) *Corallium rubrum*; it occurs on walls of caves and/or cavities with coralligenous concretions and semi-dark overhangs. The species is found at a depth from 5m (in caves) to 600m, with significant banks between 30 m and 150 m.

Two situations can be distinguished: (i) coastal populations, down to a depth of 50m, characterised by high density (up to 1,000 colonies/m²) and small colony size (height <5cm); (ii) deeper populations, down to a depth of more than 200m, characterised by low density (<100 colonies/m²) and large colony size. Colonies taller than 20cm and thicker than 2cm in basal diameter have become very rare because of intensive harvesting. This facies is distributed throughout the Mediterranean Sea, and especially in the western basin; in the eastern basin, it is rarer and occurs at greater depths. This sheet relates to the assemblages living in the upper circalittoral zone.

Characteristic species

The red coral *Corallium rubrum* (dark red colonies and white polyps), among the alcyonacean species that can colonize semi-dark caves (especially near the entrance, e.g., *Alcyonium acaule*, *Eunicella cavolini*, *Paramuricea clavata*), is the only species able to form true facies, with dense monospecific stands especially on the cave roof. *C. rubrum* is a long-lived species exhibiting an arborescent growth form, which can reach 50cm in height (weight >2kg). The average annual growth rate of young colonies is about 1mm/year for the basal diameter, and 10mm/year for the height; growth rate decreases with colony age: after 5 years it becomes 0.2-0.5mm/year for the basal diameter and 1-2.5mm/year for the height. Being a passive suspension feeder, *C. rubrum* contributes to the energy transfer from the water column to the cave community.

Associated species

Corallium rubrum provides a biogenic three-dimensional space for many mobile invertebrates. The solitary scleractinian *Leptopsammia pruvoti* is frequently found abundant amidst the colonies of red coral. The small pontonine shrimp *Balssia gasti* lives associated with the red coral, while the gastropod *Pseudosimnia carnea* is known to feed on the polyps. The sponge *Delectona ciconiae* bores in the scleraxis and may cause the detachment of the colony.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Intensive harvesting has caused a severe depletion of most commercial stocks of *Corallium rubrum*, especially shallow populations, living at depths <50m. Low fecundity and recruitment and slow growth rate raise concern about the resilience of overexploited populations. Recovery takes a long time, and the populations of several areas might be unable to re-colonize old and overexploited sites. The minimum harvestable size (7mm basal diameter) is

reached in 30-40 years, and the larvae have poor dispersal capacity. The few historical data series available indicate a dramatic shift in the size structure of over-harvested populations in recent decades. Besides harvesting, other human impacts can be relevant: colonies are fragile and can be easily broken by the contact of scuba divers, and lost fishing lines can entangle and break the branches of the colonies. Other main sources of mortality of red coral include dislodgement from the substrate due to the action of boring species or seismic movements, and sedimentation increase. Mass mortality events have been recorded in coincidence with recent summer heat waves and the ongoing seawater warming trend.

The red coral *Corallium rubrum* is listed as 'Endangered' in the IUCN Red List of threatened species, and is included in Annex II (List of endangered or threatened species) of the Bern Convention, in Annex III (List of species whose exploitation is regulated) of the SPA/BD Protocol of the Barcelona Convention, and in Annex V (Animal and plant species of Community interest whose taking in the wild and exploitation may be subject to management measures) of the HD. Today, harvesting is allowed only by scuba divers and regulated by specific laws. Prohibition of coral harvesting in overexploited areas has been adopted by several countries. International concern for conservation motivated attempts to regulate the trade of the red coral by including all the species of the genus *Corallium* in the lists of the CITES; such attempts have failed due to insufficient information to meet CITES criteria.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bavestrello, G., Bo, M., Canese, S., Sandulli, R., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2015. Long-term comparison of structure and dynamics of the red coral metapopulation of the Portofino Promontory (Ligurian Sea): a case-study for a Marine Protected Area in the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Ecology* 36 (4), 1354-1363.

Bavestrello, G., Bo, M., Canese, S., Sandulli, R., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2014. The red coral populations of the gulfs of Naples and Salerno: human impact and deep mass mortalities. *Italian Journal of Zoology* 81 (4), 552-563.

Bavestrello, G., Cerrano, C., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2009. Biological interactions affecting the growth rates of red coral (*Corallium rubrum*) colonies' In Proceedings of the 1st Mediterranean symposium on the conservation of the coralligenous and other calcareous bio-concretions, (Tabarka, 15-16 January 2009) pp. 53-58

Betti, F., Bavestrello, G., Fravega, L., Bo, M., Coppari, M., Enrichetti, F., Cappanera, V., Venturini, S., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., 2019. On the effects of recreational SCUBA diving on fragile benthic species: the Portofino MPA (NW Mediterranean Sea) case study. *Ocean and Coastal Management* 182, 104926.

Bramanti, L., Vielmini, I., Rossi, S., Tsounis, G., Iannelli, M., Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Priori, C., Santangelo, G., 2014. Demographic parameters of two populations

of red coral (*Corallium rubrum* L. 1758) in the North Western Mediterranean. *Marine Biology* 161 (5), 1015-1026.

Cattaneo-Vietti, R., Bo, M., Cannas, R., Cau, A., Follesa, C., Meliadó, E., Russo, G.F., Sandulli, R., Santangelo, G., Bavestrello, G., 2016. An overexploited Italian treasure: past and present distribution and exploitation of the precious red coral *Corallium rubrum* (L., 1758; Cnidaria: Anthozoa). *Italian Journal of Zoology* 83 (4), 443-455.

Gallmetzer, I., Haselmair, A., Velimirov, B., 2010. Slow growth and early sexual maturity: Bane and boon for the red coral *Corallium rubrum*. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* pp. 1-10

Ouerghi, A., Gerovasileiou, V., Bianchi, C.N., 2019. Mediterranean marine caves: a synthesis of current knowledge and the Mediterranean Action Plan for the conservation of “dark habitats”. in: ÖZTÜRK B. (ed.), *Marine caves of the eastern Mediterranean Sea: biodiversity, threats and conservation*. Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV) Publication no. 53, Istanbul, 1-13.

Santangelo, G., Carletti, E., Maggi, E., Bramanti, L., 2003. Reproduction and population sexual structure of the overexploited Mediterranean red coral *Corallium rubrum*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* pp. 99-108

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, OCEANA, 2017. Guidelines for inventorying and monitoring of dark habitats in the Mediterranean Sea. By Gerovasileiou V., Aguilar R., Marin P. SPA/RAC-Deep Sea Lebanon Project, Tunis, 40 pp (+ Annexes).

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

SPA/RAC-UNEP/MAP, 2020. Mediterranean marine caves: remarkable habitats in need of protection. By Gerovasileiou V., Bianchi C.N. SPA/RAC, Tunis, 63 pp (+ Annexes).

Zentner, Y., Garrabou, J., Margarit, N., Rovira, G., Gómez-Gras, D., Linares, C., 2025. Active restoration of a long-lived octocoral drives rapid functional recovery in a temperate reef. *Science Advances* 11: eado5249.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC1523](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170, <8330

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.534a, MC1.534b

MC1523. Facies with *Leptopsammia pruvoti*

General description

This facies with the madreporian (yellow coral) *Leptopsammia pruvoti* occurs on hard substrata at the entrance to caves and under overhangs. Such facies develops mainly on the roof of semi-dark zones, where the solitary bright yellow *L. pruvoti* may reach a density of over 700 individuals/m². Facies with scleractinians have been reported from all over the Mediterranean Sea, at various depths. In particular, the facies with *L. pruvoti* are highly distributed in, especially on walls and overhangs in the NW Mediterranean.

Characteristic species

Leptopsammia pruvoti is a sciaphilic species; therefore, it is present along vertical rocky walls, in overhangs, in ravines with little sedimentation. Also present in the cave, it does not live inside deep cavities as it requires good exposure to currents. Gonochoric and viviparous species with a 1:1 sex ratio. Sexual maturity is reached at 3mm in diameter of the calyx, very long gametogenesis (from 12 to 24 months) with release of the larvae in late spring. It has a potentially high larval dispersal.

Associated species

Common in marine circalittoral caves, *Leptopsammia pruvoti* can dominate visually in more or less dense monospecific or polyspecific facies with other scleractinian corals: the azooxanthellate form of the colonial *Madracis pharensis*, *Dendrophyllia ramea*, the colonial *Polycyathus muelleriae*, *Caryophyllia inornata*, *Hoplangia durotrix*, *Cladopsammia rolandi* and the colonial bright orange *Astroides calycularis*. Species less frequently recorded in caves include: *Balanophyllia regia*, *Monomyces pygmaea*, *Phyllangia americana mouchezii*, and *Thalamophyllia gasti*, while *Ceratotrochus magnaghii*, *Guynia annulata* (in areas with freshwater seepage), and *Paracyathus pulchellus* may be comparatively more abundant in the darker zones.

This facies host a diverse community of either sessile or mobile associated fauna. Many bryozoans, sponges and serpulids encrust and may overgrow the corallites; the bryozoan *Cribrilaria radiata* shows preference for the coral substrate. The sponge *Delectona madreporica* and the bivalve *Hiatella arctica* bore into the coral skeleton and may cause detachment from the substrate. The sponge *Haliclona fulva* is often found together with *L. pruvoti* on vertical walls. The small barnacle *Adna anglica* lives in association with scleractinian corals where it attaches to their calcareous skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Slow population turnover (over 10 years), high juvenile mortality, and low growth rate made scleractinian corals poorly resilient. They are threatened by pollution, sedimentation, sea water warming and contact by scuba divers.

This facies is protected by the 'Action plan for the conservation of the coralligenous and other calcareous bio-concretions' of the Barcelona Convention, which also integrates semi-dark cave communities. All

scleractinian coral species are listed in Appendix II of CITES. Mediterranean cave-dwelling species are included in the IUCN Red List.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bussotti, S., Terlizzi, A., Frascchetti, S., Belmonte, G., & Boero, F., 2006. Spatial and temporal variability of sessile benthos in shallow Mediterranean marine caves. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, pp. 109-119

Caroselli, E., Zaccanti, F., Mattioli, G., Falini, G., Levy, O., Dubinsky, Z., Goffredo, S., 2012. Growth and demography of the solitary scleractinian coral *Leptopsammia pruvoti* along a sea surface temperature gradient in the Mediterranean Sea. *PLoS One* 6.

Fenner, D., Riolo, F., Vittorio, M., 2013. New records of scleractinian corals from shallow waters of the Ionian coast of Italy. *Marine Biodiversity Records* pp. e136.

Goffredo, S., Airi, V., Radetic, J., Zaccanti, F., 2006. Sexual reproduction of the solitary sunset cup coral *Leptopsammia pruvoti* (Scleractinia, Dendrophylliidae) in the Mediterranean. 2. Quantitative aspects of the annual reproductive cycle. *Marine Biology* 5: 923-931.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, OCEANA, 2017. Guidelines for inventorying and monitoring of dark habitats in the Mediterranean Sea. By Gerovasileiou V., Aguilar R., Marin P. SPA/RAC-Deep Sea Lebanon Project, Tunis, 40 pp (+ Annexes).

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

SPA/RAC-UNEP/MAP, 2020. Mediterranean marine caves: remarkable habitats in need of protection. By Gerovasileiou V., Bianchi C.N. SPA/RAC, Tunis, 63 pp (+ Annexes).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC251](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:
MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef
HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention:
MC2.51, MC1.52a or
MC1.52b⁵⁰

MC251. Coralligenous platforms

General description

Coralligenous platforms are biogenic structures mostly constructed by coralline algae on sedimentary bottoms that are subject to currents. They are mainly built on horizontal substrates and may have a very complex morphology often leading to a very typical cavernous structure, with a variable thickness ranging from a few centimetres to several meters (3-4 m). Coralligenous platforms are not usually built on rock substrata but result from the active development of bioconstructors from scattered elements on loose beds, shells, stones, and gravel occurring over sedimentary substrates (i.e., may develop from the coalescence of rhodoliths). Calcified species of the *Peyssonnelia* genus play an important role in the aggregation of the components of the coralligenous platforms. The planimetric geometry of this habitat is also highly variable and may cover from a few square meters to tens of square kilometres. Coralligenous platforms may also develop on rocky outcrops and consist of individual structures, occupying an area of about 1-10m² and an elevation up to 2m. These structures are recognizable individually, although they may appear clustered in tens or hundreds.

Coralligenous platforms are distributed around all the Mediterranean coasts, in specific environmental conditions of the circalittoral zone (i.e., dim light, low and constant temperature, moderate rate of sedimentation). The depth distribution of the habitat ranges from about 40m to 150m on the continental shelf.

Coralligenous platforms support biodiversity by providing habitat, feeding grounds, recruitment, refuge and nursery sites for many invertebrates and fishes both at the juvenile and adult stages. The habitat provides provisional (i.e., food, raw materials), regulating (i.e., carbon sequestration, nutrient recycling), and cultural ecosystem services.

Characteristic species

Coralligenous platforms may exhibit a complex and stratified structure and, therefore, feature remarkably diverse species structuring the assemblages. The basal layer may include encrusting algae (i.e., *Lithophyllum stictaeforme*, *Neogoniolithon mamillosum*, *Mesophyllum lichenoides*, *Peyssonnelia* spp.), sponges, bryozoans, scleractinians, and ascidians. The intermediate layer is usually characterised by small erect macroalgae and invertebrates. The erect layer hosts large and erect sponges (e.g., *Axinella cannabina*, *A. polypoides*, *Sarcotragus* spp., *Haliclona mediterranea*), cnidarians (e.g., *Corallium rubrum*, *Eunicella cavolini*, *E. verrucosa*, *E. singularis*, *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*, *Leptopsammia pruvoti*, *Paramuricea clavata*, *Alcyonum acaule*, *Parazoanthus axinellae*, *Savalia savaglia*), bryozoans (e.g., *Pentapora fascialis*, *Myriapora truncata*), depending on depth and geographical distribution.

⁵⁰ According to the Barcelona Convention updated classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region (2019), the coralligenous assemblages on large tabular buildups are described as “MC2.51 Coralligenous platforms”. On the other hand, if the coralligenous develops on rocky outcrops, defined as individual structures surrounded by mobile substrates on the continental shelf, the habitat is defined, within the Barcelona Convention updated classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types (2019) as “MC1.52a Coralligenous outcrops” or “MC1.52b Coralligenous outcrops covered by sediment”.

Associated species

The facies developing on the coralline algae that constitute the coralligenous platform, exhibit a differentiated composition, depending on depth, hydrodynamics and geographical distribution, and they are important secondary substrates that increase the structural complexity of seabeds by providing suitable habitats for many epiphytic and mobile organisms.

Frequent associated species may be:

- Algae: Fucales (i.e., *Cystoseira usneoides*, *C. zosteroides*), Laminariales, *Codium* spp.
- Bryozoa: *Hornera lichenoides*.
- Polychaeta: *Sabella spallanzani*, *Serpula vermicularis*.
- Mollusca: *Hiatella arctica*, *Lithophaga lithophaga*, *Pteria hirundo*, *Serpulorbis arenaria*, *Spondylus gaederopus*.
- Crustacea: *Homarus gammarus*, *Palinurus elephas*, *Scyllarides latus*.
- Echinodermata: *Asterina pancerii*, *Centrostephanus longispinus*, *Echinus melo*, *Ophidiaster ophidianus*, *Paracentrotus lividus*.
- Vertebrates (fish species): *Anthias anthias*, *Acantholabrus palloni*, *Conger conger*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Gobius auratus*, *Hippocampus guttulatus*, *Labrus mixtus*, *Lappanella fasciata*, *Phycis phycis*, *Sciaena umbra*, *Scorpaena scrofa*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are mechanical destruction (fishing, anchoring, and diving damage), pollution, sedimentation, spread of alien invasive species, blooms of benthic mucilage, and climate change. In particular, the habitat is threatened by fishing activities and sedimentation.

The coralligenous platforms are included in the habitat 1170 “Reefs”, listed among the priority habitats defined by the HD, that should also be monitored under the MSFD. The inclusion of this habitat type within the HD, its recognition as a habitat of conservation interest according to the Barcelona Convention (many characteristic species are also listed in Annex II of the SPA/BD Protocol) and its inclusion in the Action Plan for the conservation of the coralligenous and other calcareous bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea (UNEP/MAP 2017), highlight its protection and monitoring value. EU Regulation 1967/2006, concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea, established the banning of trawl nets, dredges, shore seines or similar nets on both coralligenous and maerl beds.

Best practices in nature restoration

Active restoration measures for this habitat exist and are subject to various research activities. Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Action Plan for the Conservation of the Coralligenous and Other Calcareous Bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea, UN Environment/MAP Athens, Greece 2017.

Appolloni, L., Ferrigno, F., Russo, G. F., et al., 2020. β -Diversity of morphological groups as indicator of coralligenous community quality status. *Ecological Indicators* 109, 105840.

Ballesteros, E., 2006. Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages: a synthesis of present knowledge. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review* 44, 123-195.

Bevilacqua, S., Guarnieri G., Farella G., et al., 2018. A regional assessment of cumulative impact mapping on Mediterranean coralligenous outcrops. *Scientific Reports* 8, 1757.

Bracchi, V. A., Basso, D., Marchese, F., et al., 2017. Coralligenous morphotypes on subhorizontal substrate: A new categorization. *Continental Shelf Research* 144, 10-20.

Enrichetti, F., Dominguez-Carriò, C., Toma, M., et al., 2019. Megabenthic communities of the Ligurian deep continental shelf and shelf break (NW Mediterranean Sea). *Plos One* 14 (10), e0223949.

Enrichetti, F., Bo, M., Morri, C., et al., 2019. Assessing the environmental status of temperate mesophotic reefs: A new, integrated methodological approach. *Ecological Indicators* 102, 218-229.

Ferrigno, F., Russo, G. F., Sandulli, R., 2017. Coralligenous bioconstructions Quality Index (CBQI): a synthetic indicator to assess the status of different types of coralligenous habitats. *Ecological Indicators* 82, 271-279.

Ferrigno F., Appolloni L., Russo G.F., Sandulli R., 2018. Impact of fishing activities on different coralligenous assemblages of Gulf of Naples (Italy). *Journal of Marine Biology Association of U.K.* 98, 41-50.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Coralligenous biocenosis Priority habitat IV,3.1 (EUR 27: 1170). in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 213-218.

Giaccone, G., Giaccone, T., Catra, M., 2009. Habitat identification code IV.3.1.15. Coralligenous platforms: vegetal association of the coralligenous biocenosis: Lithophyllo-Halimedetum tunae Giaccone 1965. in: Relini, G. and Giaccone, G. Priority habitats according to the SPA/BIO protocol (Barcelona Convention) present in Italy. Identification sheets. *Biologia Marina Mediterranea*, 16 (Suppl. 1), 213-218.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyo, J., et al., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. in: Rossi, S., Bramanti, L., Gori, A., Orejas, C. (eds), *Marine Animal Forests: The Ecology of Benthic Biodiversity Hotspots*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, Switzerland, 207-233.

Grinyó, J., Gori, A., Ambroso, S., et al., 2016. Diversity, distribution and population size structure of deep Mediterranean gorgonian assemblages

(Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea). Progress in Oceanography 145, 42-56.

Grinyó, J., Gori, A., Greenacre, M., et al., 2018. Megabenthic assemblages in the continental shelf edge and upper slope of the Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea. Progress in Oceanography 162, 40-51.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC6514](#)
EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention:
MC6.511

MC6514. Facies of sticky muds with *Alcyonium palmatum* and *Parastichopus regalis* on circalittoral mud

General description

This facies occurs in coastal terrigenous mud and in muddy detritic bottoms and is dominated by the arborescent and long-lived alcyoniid *Alcyonium palmatum* associated with the *Holoturoidea Parastichopus regalis*. The habitat develops in the circalittoral zone at depths between 25m to about 150 m on bottoms characterised by mud or mixed sediment, is a typical habitat of muddy detritic bottoms and of coastal terrigenous mud and can be associated with all the other typical facies, i.e., facies with Hydrozoa, Pennatulacea, Polychaeta, Ophiuroidea, Ascidiacea, Gastropoda.

Sea cucumbers have an important ecological role, since they reduce the organic load while excreting inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus, playing major roles in nutrient recycling and enhancing the productivity of the ecosystem.

Characteristic species

In the Mediterranean Sea, *Alcyonium palmatum* (together with *A. acaule*) can be considered the most abundant soft coral species. *A. palmatum* forms clumps of pink, brown-red to brown-orange fleshy masses of finger-like lobes (usually named “dead man’s fingers”) and is found on soft bottoms at depths from 20m to 200m, fixed to the ground with its sterile stalk preferably on shells, pebbles, or small stones. *A. palmatum* shows broadcast spawning, so its gametes are directly released into the water column where fertilisation takes place. This facies can be dominated by other arborescent and long-lived alcyonacean species also, such as the gorgonians *Spinimuricea* spp. and the alcyoniid *Paralcyonium spinulosum*.

A typical holothurian species is *Parastichopus regalis*, typically found on sand or other soft substrates at depths down to about 800m, most frequently in the 100m to 300m depth range colour variable: from brown with nuance of yellow to red, the sides being constellated with maculae possible blanches, up to 35cm in length. *Oestergrenia digitata* (its colour is pink or red-brown, sometimes purple, up to 30cm in length), *Holothuria tubulosa* (its general colour is a shade of brown, and the surface is covered with numerous dark-coloured, conical, thorn-like papillae, up to 45cm in length) may also be considered characteristic species.

Associated species

Long-lived erect *Alcyonacea* act as marine ecosystem engineers and habitat formers, as they play a significant role in benthic-pelagic coupling and generate three-dimensional space and habitat for many mobile invertebrates, thus enhancing biodiversity. Due to the heterogeneous nature of the seabed (mud, sand, gravel, organogenic detritus), rich communities can develop, which are often very diverse. The associated community includes infaunal polychaetes, sipunculids, echinoderms, bivalves, and burrowing anemones such as *Cerianthus* spp. When hard substrates are available (shell debris and

stones), the surface enables epifaunal species to become established, particularly hydroids. Pennatulaceans, ophiurans, ascidians, molluscs, and crustaceans are also commonly associated elements of this habitat.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species and display a low resilience to human pressures. Assemblages are particularly damaged by fishing gear, trawling and anchoring and are sensitive to entanglement by mucilage filaments. Sea cucumbers are used for food in some countries and are object of commercial fishery, and they are also often collected by divers. The harvesting of sea cucumbers (resources mainly intended for commercialisation and consumption in non-EU markets) has taken on an ever-increasing dimension, in consequence some Mediterranean countries (such as Italy) have introduced temporary bans on fishing or landing sea cucumbers.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Canese, S., Spaggiari, C., Pusceddu, A., Bertolino, M., Angiolillo, M., Giusti, M., Loreto, M.F., Salvati, E., Greco, S., Bavestrello, G., 2012. Deep coral oases in the South Tyrrhenian Sea' Plos One 7, e49870.

Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Kaschner, K., Lasram, F.B.R., Aguzzi, J., Ballesteros, E., Bianchi, C. N., Corbera, J., Dailianis, T., Danovaro, R., Estrada, M., Froglia, C., Galil, B. S., Gasol, J. M., Gertwagen, R., Gil, J., Guilhaumon, F., Kesner-Reyes, K., Kitsos, M-S., Koukouras, A., Lampariadou, N., Laxamana, E., López-Fé de la Cuadra, C. M., Lotze, H. K., Martin, D., Mouillot, D., Oro, D., Raicevich, S., Rius-Barile, J., Saiz-Salinas, J. I., San Vicente, C., Somot, S., Templado, J., Turon, X., Vafidis, D., Villanueva, R., Voultsiadou E., 2010. The biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: estimates, patterns, and threats. Plos One 5 (8), e11842.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo, M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots, 207-233.

Mangano, M.C., Kaiser, M.J., Porporato, E.M.D., Spanò, N., 2013. Evidence of trawl disturbance on megaepibenthic communities in the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 475, 101-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Terribile, K., Evans, J., Knittweis, L., Schembri, P.J., 2016. Maximising MEDITS: Using data collected from trawl surveys to Characterise the benthic and demersal assemblages of the circalittoral and deeper waters around the

Maltese Islands (Central Mediterranean). *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 3, 163-175.

Topçu, N.E., Öztürk, B., 2015. Composition and abundance of octocorals in the Sea of Marmara, where the Mediterranean meets the Black Sea. *Scientia Marina* 79, 125-135.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD151](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC1.51, MD1.52

MD151. Biocenosis of Mediterranean shelf-edge rock

General description

The biocoenoses of the deep circalittoral rocky bottoms occur near the border of the rocky continental shelf, mainly on sub-horizontal or gently sloping hardgrounds, rarely sub-vertical. These biocoenoses, dwelling at a depth of up to 250m, usually occupy rough bottoms where current and turbidity are reasonably important. In these habitats, the progressively lower light conditions have a profound influence on the biocoenoses composition mostly because of reduced primary production, but this zone continues to be characterised by high biodiversity and biomass levels, at times comparable to those found in shallow waters.

Characteristic species

The offshore circalittoral rock is invertebrate-dominated by sponges, anthozoans, bryozoans and brachiopods while macroscopic plant life is absent, even if in the shallower portion of its distribution it can be found also on rocks with coralline-cover. This species occurs as small, isolated patches or dense aggregations, monospecific or intermixed, with habitat-forming species able to form specific facies, such as facies with small sponges, with large and erect sponges (e.g., *Axinellae* spp.), with *Alcyonacea* (e.g., *Corallium rubrum*, *Villogorgia bebyricoides*, *Bebryce mollis*, *Muriceides lepida*, *Chironephytia mediterranea*), with *Antipatharia* (*Antipathella subpinnata*, *Parantipathes larix*), with *Scleractinia* (*Dendrophyllia cornigera* and *D. ramea*), with *Ceriantharia*, with *Zoantharia*, with *Polychaeta*, with *Bivalvia*, with *Brachiopoda*, with *Bryozoa* (e.g., *Myriapora truncata*).

Associated species

The various facies that may occur on the shelf-edge rocky bottoms may host rich and diverse assemblages, showing a variability depending on the local environmental conditions and the dominant species. The most common species are the serpulids *Filograna* spp., hydroids, the bivalve *Pteria hirundo*, the bryozoans *Schizoporella* spp., *Turbicellepora avicularis* and *Pentapora fascialis*, the ascidian *Clavelina dellavallei*, and, occasionally, some macroalgae. Large vagile species (e.g., *Octopus vulgaris*, *Neomaja goltziana*, *Palinurus elephas*, *Homarus gammarus*, cidarids, *Holothuria* spp., *Hacelia attenuata*, *Peltaster placenta*, *Echinus melo*) and a rich fish community (e.g., *Anthias anthias*, *Capros aper*, *Phycis phycis*, *Labrus mixtus*, *Serranus cabrilla*, *Conger conger*, *Lappanella fasciata*, *Acantholabrus palloni*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Mola mola*, *Zeus faber*, sharks such as *Scyliorhinus* spp. and *Galeus melastomus*) are frequently observed.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

With respect to anthropogenic threats, fishing activities represent the main source of impacts for massive and erected invertebrates characterising the biocenosis. These species may potentially be subjected to mass mortality events possibly related to deep bottom turbid currents, thermal anomalies or

land pollution, but they can also be threatened by trawling silt resuspension, seafloor drilling activities for oil exploration or mining. Coral aggregations have been internationally identified as special ecological features that require protection under the Convention of Biological Diversity.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Canese, S., Spaggiari, C., Pusceddu, A., Bertolino, M., Angiolillo, M., Giusti, M., Loreto, M.F., Salvati, E., Greco, S., Bavestrello, G., 2012. Deep coral oases in the South Tyrrhenian Sea' Plos One 7, e49870.

Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Kaschner, K., Lasram, F.B.R., Aguzzi, J., Ballesteros, E., Bianchi, C. N., Corbera, J., Dailianis, T., Danovaro, R., Estrada, M., Frogli, C., Galil, B. S., Gasol, J. M., Gertwagen, R., Gil, J., Guilhaumon, F., Kesner-Reyes, K., Kitsos, M-S., Koukouras, A., Lampariadou, N., Laxamana, E., López-Fé de la Cuadra, C. M., Lotze, H. K., Martin, D., Mouillot, D., Oro, D., Raicevich, S., Rius-Barile, J., Saiz-Salinas, J. I., San Vicente, C., Somot, S., Templado, J., Turon, X., Vafidis, D., Villanueva, R., Voultsiadou E., 2010. The biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: estimates, patterns, and threats. Plos One 5 (8), e11842.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo, M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots, 207-233.

Mangano, M.C., Kaiser, M.J., Porporato, E.M.D., Spanò, N., 2013. Evidence of trawl disturbance on megaepibenthic communities in the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 475, 101-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Terribile, K., Evans, J., Knittweis, L., Schembri, P.J., 2016. Maximising MEDITS: Using data collected from trawl surveys to Characterise the benthic and demersal assemblages of the circalittoral and deeper waters around the Maltese Islands (Central Mediterranean). Regional Studies in Marine Science 3, 163-175.

Topçu, N.E., Öztürk, B., 2015. Composition and abundance of octocorals in the Sea of Marmara, where the Mediterranean meets the Black Sea. Scientia Marina 79, 125-135.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD25](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MD2.5

MD25. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral biogenic habitats

General description

Mediterranean offshore circalittoral biogenic habitats are built by invertebrates with calcareous skeleton arising both from hard and soft bottoms and able to create biodiversity hotspots. The biogenic habitats are edified by different invertebrate taxa, such as scleractinians, bivalves, vermetids, and serpulids. Although they are mostly described for bathyal habitats, they have been also found on the continental shelf until the shelf edge arising from soft bottoms at depths ranging from 40m to the limit of the photic zone. This habitat may have a complex morphology hosting high biodiversity. Offshore reefs are reported on much of the Mediterranean continental shelf, although they are considered quite rare.

Characteristic species

Offshore biogenic reefs may be built by different organisms, such as the scleractinians *Phyllangia americana mouchezii* and *Polycyathus muelleriae*, *Vermetidae*, bivalves (*Neopycnodonte cochlear*) and *Serpulidae* (*Hydroides pseudo uncinata*, *Janita fimbriata*, *Serpula massiliensis*). Three additional scleractinian species, *Leptopsammia pruvoti*, *Caryophyllia inornata*, and *Hoplanguia durotrix*, and the serpulids *Vermiliopsis infundibulum* and *V. labiata* may contribute to the reef construction.

Associated species

The offshore reefs support biodiversity by providing habitats, feeding grounds, recruitment, refuges and nursery sites for many invertebrates and fishes both at the juvenile and adult stages. The associated assemblages mostly include *Porifera*, *Bryozoa* (e.g., *Schizomavella* spp., *Pentapora fascialis*, *Myriapora truncata*, *Adeonella calveti*, and *Chartella papyrea*), and *Mollusca*, while encrusting coralline algae may be present but to a lesser extent.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are mechanical destruction (e.g., fishing, anchoring, and diving damage), pollution, sedimentation, spread of alien invasive species, blooms of benthic mucilage, and climate change. The habitat has been included among the “special habitat types” according to the HD that should be monitored under the MSFD. Recently, the Action Plan for the conservation of the coralligenous and other calcareous bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea promoted protection and monitoring activities (UNEP/MAP).

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., 2020. Off-shore Neopycnodonte oyster reefs in the Mediterranean Sea. *Diversity* 12, 92.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2018. Know the distribution to assess the changes: Mediterranean cold-water coral bioconstructions. *Rendiconti Lincei, Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 583-588.

Chimienti, G., Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., 2019. Mesophotic and deep-sea vulnerable coral habitats of the Mediterranean Sea: Overview and Conservation Perspectives. *Advances in the Studies of the Benthic Zone*, 20.

Corriero, G., Pierri, C., Mercurio, M., Nonnis Marzano, C., Tarantini, S.O., Gravina, M.F., Lisco, S., Moretti, M., De Gioia, F., Valenzano, E., Giangrande, A., Mastrodonato, M., Longo, C., Cardone, F.A., 2019. Mediterranean mesophotic coral reef built by non-symbiotic scleractinians. *Scientific Reports* 9, 3601.

Enrichetti, F., Dominguez-Carriò, C., Toma, M., Bavestrello, G., Betti, F., Canese, S., Bo, M., 2019. Megabenthic communities of the Ligurian deep continental shelf and shelf break (NW Mediterranean Sea). *Plos One* 14 (10), e0223949.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD6512](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MD6.51

MD6512. Facies of sticky muds with *Alcyonium palmatum* and *Parastichopus regalis* on lower circalittoral mud

General description

This facies occurs on the furthest part of the continental shelf, canyons and offshore banks and it is dominated by arborescent and long-lived alcyoniids (mainly *Alcyonium palmatum*) associated with *Holoturoidea* (such as *Parastichopus regalis*). The habitat develops on bottoms characterised by soft bottoms with muddy sediments, and can be associated with other typical facies, such as facies with *Pennatulacea*, *Polychaeta*, *Bivalvia*, *Brachiopoda*, and *Ceriantharia*.

Characteristic species

In the Mediterranean Sea, *Alcyonium palmatum* (together with *A. acaule*) can be considered the most abundant soft coral species. *A. palmatum* forms clumps of pink, brown-red to brown-orange fleshy masses of finger-like lobes (usually named “dead man’s fingers”) and is found on soft bottoms from depths of up to 20m to 200m, fixed to the ground with its sterile stalk preferably on shells, pebbles, or small stones. *A. palmatum* shows broadcast spawning, so its gametes are directly released into the water column where fertilisation takes place. These facies can also be dominated by other arborescent and long-lived alcyonacean species, such as the gorgonians *Spinimuricea* spp. and the alcyoniid *Paralcyonium spinulosum*.

Typical holothurian species is *Parastichopus regalis*, typically found on sand or other soft substrates at depths down to about 800 m, most frequently in the 100m to 300m depth range colour variable; from brown with nuance of yellow to red, the sides being constellated with maculae possible blanches, up to 35cm in length.

Associated species

Long-lived erect Alcyonacea act as marine ecosystem engineers and habitat formers, as they play a significant role in benthic-pelagic coupling and generate three-dimensional space and habitat for many mobile invertebrates, thus enhancing biodiversity. The habitat is characterised by organisms of muddy, soft bottoms. Many taxa are considered as typical of this habitat, such as *Pennatulacea* (e.g., *Pennatula* spp., *Virgularia mirabilis*), *Polychaeta*, *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Neopycnodonte* spp.), *Brachiopoda*, *Ceriantharia* (e.g., *Cerianthus* spp., *Arachnanthus* spp.). Offshore muddy bottoms host highly diversified fish assemblages also of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lophius budegassa*, *Lepidorhombus boscii*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Erect *Alcyonacea* are long-lived, slow growing and slow recruiting species and display a low resilience to human pressures. The mixed detritic bottoms may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act

directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Canese, S., Spaggiari, C., Pusceddu, A., Bertolino, M., Angiolillo, M., Giusti, M., Loreto, M.F., Salvati, E., Greco, S., Bavestrello, G., 2012. Deep coral oases in the South Tyrrhenian Sea' Plos One 7, e49870.

Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Kaschner, K., Lasram, F.B.R., Aguzzi, J., Ballesteros, E., Bianchi, C. N., Corbera, J., Dailianis, T., Danovaro, R., Estrada, M., Frogli, C., Galil, B. S., Gasol, J. M., Gertwagen, R., Gil, J., Guilhaumon, F., Kesner-Reyes, K., Kitsos, M-S., Koukouras, A., Lampariadou, N., Laxamana, E., López-Fé de la Cuadra, C. M., Lotze, H. K., Martin, D., Mouillot, D., Oro, D., Raicevich, S., Rius-Barile, J., Saiz-Salinas, J. I., San Vicente, C., Somot, S., Templado, J., Turon, X., Vafidis, D., Villanueva, R., Voultsiadou E., 2010. The biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: estimates, patterns, and threats. Plos One 5 (8), e11842.

Gori, A., Bavestrello, G., Grinyó, J., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Ambroso, S., Bo, M., 2017. Animal forests in deep coastal bottoms and continental shelf of the Mediterranean Sea. Marine Animal Forests: the ecology of benthic biodiversity hotspots, 207-233.

Mangano, M.C., Kaiser, M.J., Porporato, E.M.D., Spanò, N., 2013. Evidence of trawl disturbance on megaepibenthic communities in the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea. Marine Ecology Progress Series 475, 101-117.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Terribile, K., Evans, J., Knittweis, L., Schembri, P.J., 2016. Maximising MEDITS: Using data collected from trawl surveys to Characterise the benthic and demersal assemblages of the circalittoral and deeper waters around the Maltese Islands (Central Mediterranean). Regional Studies in Marine Science 3, 163-175.

Topçu, N.E., Öztürk, B., 2015. Composition and abundance of octocorals in the Sea of Marmara, where the Mediterranean meets the Black Sea. Scientia Marina 79, 125-135.

Group 5

ME1511. Mediterranean upper bathyal *Lophelia pertusa* reefs

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME1511](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME2.513, ME1.51 (partially)

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony corals), found below depths of about 200m, forming bioconstructions. These species can create single facies or may variously co-exist. Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. dianthus*. The white coral clumps are only found at depths between 300m and 700m, on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side. The live portions of *D. pertusum* rarely exceed 20cm in size. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians. *D. pertusum* is more frequent in the lower bathyal depth range.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often with a width of many tens of square km) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence:

- the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province.
- the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province.
- the Sicily Channel CWC Province.
- the South Sardinia CWC Province.
- the Corsica Channel CWC Province.
- the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces.
- the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

Occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*, antipatharians (Leiopathes), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (Dendrophyllia). They provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth, adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denuded skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospections, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Polisenò, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The "Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province" (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Gheerardyn, H., King, N. J., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D'Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean). *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Pairaud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Gori, A., Ferrier-Pagès, C., Hennige, S.J., Murray, F., Rottier, C., Wicks, L.C., Roberts, J.M., 2016. Physiological response of the cold-water coral *Desmophyllum dianthus* to thermal stress and ocean acidification. *PeerJ* 4, e1606.

Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., Taviani, M., 2019. Cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. *Plos One* 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. *Cold-water corals and ecosystems*, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 145, 61-78.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME1512](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME2.513, ME1.51 (partially)

ME1512. Mediterranean upper bathyal *Madrepora oculata* reefs

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by Cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony corals), found below depths of about 200m, forming bioconstructions. These species can create single facies or may variously co-exist. Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Madrepora oculata*. The white coral clumps are only found between depths of 300m and 700m, on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side.

The living *M. oculata* canopy has a height of up to 70cm and a width of up to 50cm. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians. In terms of occurrence, *M. oculata* is usually dominant in the upper bathyal frameworks and seems to exhibit a greater ability to grow in warmer waters.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often many tens of square km wide) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence:

- the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province.
- the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province.
- the Sicily Channel CWC Province.
- the South Sardinia CWC Province.
- the Corsica Channel CWC Province.
- the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces.
- the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

Occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Madrepora oculata*, accompanied by antipatharians (Leiopathes), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (Dendrophyllia). They provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth, adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denudated skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened, because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospections, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Poliseo, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The "Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province" (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D'Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean), *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Paireud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. *Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral* (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., Taviani, M., 2019. Cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. *Plos One* 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. *Cold-water corals and ecosystems*, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 145, 61-78.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Cardone, F., Montagna, P., Danovaro, R., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. *Scientific reports* 9, 1-12.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Fogliini, F., Corselli, C., Nasto, I., Pons-Branchu, E., Montagna, P., 2019. U/Th dating records of cold-water coral colonization in submarine canyons and adjacent sectors of the southern Adriatic Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 300-308.

Tunesi L., Diviacco G., Mo G., 2001. Observations by submersible on the biocoenosis of the deep-sea corals off Portofino Promontory (Northwestern Mediterranean Sea). In: *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Deep-Sea Corals*, Ecology Action Centre and Nova Scotia Museum, Halifax, Nova Scotia, J.H. Martin Willison et al. (eds): 76-87.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME1513](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Upper bathyal rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME2.513, ME1.51 (partially)

ME1513. Mediterranean upper bathyal *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa* reefs

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by Cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony) corals), found below depths of about 200 m, forming bioconstructions. These species can create single facies or may variously co-exist. Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. This facies is characterised by the framework-building corals *Madrepora oculata* and *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*. The white coral clumps are only found between depths of 300 m and 700 m, on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150 m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side.

The living coral canopy has a height of up to 70cm and a width of up to 50cm for *M. oculata*, while the live portions of *D. pertusum* rarely exceed 20cm in size. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians.

In terms of occurrence, *M. oculata* and *D. dianthus* are usually dominant in the upper bathyal frameworks, *D. pertusum* is more frequent in the lower bathyal depth range, despite they all show almost the same bathymetric range within the basin. *M. oculata* seems to exhibit a greater ability to grow in warmer waters.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often many tens of square km wide) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence:

- the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province.
- the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province.
- the Sicily Channel CWC Province.
- the South Sardinia CWC Province.
- the Corsica Channel CWC Province.
- the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces.
- the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

Occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building corals *Madrepora oculata* and *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*, antipatharians (Leiopathes), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (*Dendrophyllia*). They provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth, adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denuded skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospections, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Trincardi, F., Bakran-Petricioli, T., Ceregato, A., Chimienti, G., Macic, V., Polisenò, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The "Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province" (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Gheerardyn, H., King, N. J., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Aguilar, R., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D'Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean), *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Pairaud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Gori, A., Ferrier-Pagès, C., Hennige, S.J., Murray, F., Rottier, C., Wicks, L.C., Roberts, J.M., 2016. Physiological response of the cold-water coral

Desmophyllum dianthus to thermal stress and ocean acidification. PeerJ 4, e1606.

Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Gherardi, M., Longo, C., Rosso, A., Sciuto, F., Sanfilippo, R., Gravili, C., Boero, F., Taviani, M., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., González-Duarte, M. M., López, E., Madurell, T., Maldonado, M., Mateo-Ramírez, A., Megina, C., Moreira, J., Moya, F., Ramalho, L. V., Rosso, A., Sitjà, C., Taviani, M., 2019. 29 cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. Plos One 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. Cold-water corals and ecosystems, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Cau, A. B., Follesa, M. C., Marchese, F., Montagna, P., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography 145, 61-78.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Cardone, F., Montagna, P., Danovaro, R., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. Scientific reports 9, 1-12.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Foglini, F., Corselli, C., Nasto, I., Pons-Branchu, E., Montagna, P., 2019. U/Th dating records of cold-water coral colonization in submarine canyons and adjacent sectors of the southern Adriatic Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. Progress in Oceanography 175, 300-308.

Tunesi L., Diviacco G., Mo G., 2001. Observations by submersible on the biocoenosis of the deep-sea corals off Portofino Promontory (Northwestern Mediterranean Sea). In: *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Deep-Sea Corals*, Ecology Action Centre and Nova Scotia Museum, Halifax, Nova Scotia, J.H. Martin Willison et al. (eds): 76-87.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME6514](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME6.511

ME6514. Mediterranean upper bathyal facies of with *Pheronema carpenteri*

General description

This facies is characterised by the presence of the sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* forming highly structured and dense habitats (i.e., aggregations), which contribute to the increase of nearby biodiversity on the upper bathyal noncohesive seafloor (e.g., clayey mud, not compact and containing sandy components). This species can be found as scattered individual but may also form dense aggregations (up to 20ind./m²) in some areas, especially in the Western Mediterranean basin at a depth of between 500m and 1,600m.

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the birds' nest sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* (Thomson, 1869), a globular to subcylindrical sponge, possessing a wide and deep atrial cavity with a large apical osculum, and is usually covered with mud. *P. carpenteri* needs bottoms of fine sediment or mud, anchoring itself to soft substrate by means of a basal tuft of spicules.

Associated species

The upper bathyal zone shows a high species richness, hosting abundant meiofauna (dominated by Nematoda), together with infaunal macro and megabenthos. Macrofauna is generally dominated by polychaetes. Epimegafauna tends to be sparse and constituted mainly by mobile species such as crustacean, fishes and echinoderms. Cnidarians are among the most common sessile and sedentary organisms, together with sponges. Aggregations of giant foraminiferans and bryozoans are also present. This habitat can host gorgonians (*Isidella elongata*), aggregations of ceriantharians and sea pens such as *Pennatula* spp., *Funiculina quadrangularis*, *Protoptilum carpenteri*, *Kophobelemnion stelliferum* and *Virgularia mirabilis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Vulnerable marine ecosystems, such as those formed by *P. carpenteri*, are affected by climate change and other anthropogenic activities (especially demersal fishing) since they are formed by sensitive species with slow growth rates and limited dispersal capability, which can hinder their adaptive capability and recovery after disturbance. The impact that climate change will have on *P. carpenteri* is still unclear, although it is expected to influence the species' suitable habitat availability and distribution range.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Bertolino, M., Bavestrello, G., Canese, S., Giusti, M., Angiolillo, M., Pansini, M., Taviani, M., 2012. Role of deep sponge grounds in the Mediterranean Sea: a case study in southern Italy. *Hydrobiologia*, 687:163-177.

Gregório, I., Xavier, J.R., Davies, A.J., 2024. Present and future distribution of the deep-sea habitat-forming sponge - *Pheronema carpenteri* (Thomson, 1869) in a changing ocean, *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*: 213, 104390.

Vieira, R.P., Bett, B.J., Jones, D.O.B., Durden, J.M., Morris, K.J., Cunha, M.R., Trueman, C.N., Ruhl, H.A., 2020. Deep-sea sponge aggregations (*Pheronema carpenteri*) in the Porcupine Seabight (NE Atlantic) potentially degraded by demersal fishing. *Progress in Oceanography*, 183, 102189.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF1511](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MF2.511, MF1.513 (partially)

MF1511. Mediterranean lower bathyal *Lophelia pertusa* reefs

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by Cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony corals), forming bioconstructions. The distinction between Upper bathyal reefs (below a depth of about 200m) and Lower bathyal reefs (below a depth of about 400m to 1,300m) is fundamentally based on bathymetry, since the structure, a large part of the associated fauna and the functioning is very similar (even if with a higher occurrence in the upper bathyal). Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. The white coral clumps are found on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side. The live portions of *D. pertusum* rarely exceed 20cm in size. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians. *D. pertusum* is more frequent in the lower bathyal depth range.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often many tens of square km wide) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence: the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province, the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province, the Sicily Channel CWC Province, the South Sardinia CWC Province, the Corsica Channel CWC Province, the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces, and the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

Occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*, antipatharians (Leiopathes), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (Dendrophyllia). They provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth,

adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denuded skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospections, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced global climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Trincardi, F., Bakran-Petricioli, T., Ceregato, A., Chimienti, G., Macic, V., Poliseo, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The “Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province” (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Gheerardyn, H., King, N. J., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Aguilar, R., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D’Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean), *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Pairaud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Gori, A., Ferrier-Pagès, C., Hennige, S.J., Murray, F., Rottier, C., Wicks, L.C., Roberts, J.M., 2016. Physiological response of the cold-water coral *Desmophyllum dianthus* to thermal stress and ocean acidification. *PeerJ* 4, e1606.

Mastrototaro, F., D’Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Gherardi, M., Longo, C., Rosso, A., Sciuto, F., Sanfilippo, R., Gravili, C., Boero, F., Taviani, M., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. *Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral* (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., González-Duarte, M. M., López, E., Madurell, T., Maldonado, M., Mateo-Ramírez, A., Megina, C., Moreira, J., Moya, F., Ramalho, L. V., Rosso, A., Sitjà, C., Taviani, M., 2019. 29 cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. *Plos One* 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. *Cold-water corals and ecosystems*, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Cau, A. B., Follesa, M. C., Marchese, F., Montagna, P., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 145, 61-78.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Cardone, F., Montagna, P., Danovaro, R., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. *Scientific reports* 9, 1-12.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Fogliani, F., Corselli, C., Nasto, I., Pons-Branchu, E., Montagna, P., 2019. U/Th dating records of cold-water coral colonization in submarine canyons and adjacent sectors of the southern Adriatic Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 300-308.

Tunesi L., Diviacco G., Mo G., 2001. Observations by submersible on the biocoenosis of the deep-sea corals off Portofino Promontory (Northwestern Mediterranean Sea). In: *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Deep-Sea Corals*, Ecology Action Centre and Nova Scotia Museum, Halifax, Nova Scotia, J.H. Martin Willison et al. (eds): 76-87.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF1512](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MF2.511, MF1.513 (partially)

MF1512. Mediterranean lower bathyal *Madrepora oculata* reefs

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by Cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony corals), forming bioconstructions. The distinction between upper bathyal reefs (below a depth of about 200m) and lower bathyal reefs (at depths below about 400m to 1,300m) is fundamentally based on bathymetry, since the structure, a large part of the associated fauna and the functioning is very similar (even if with a higher occurrence in the upper bathyal). Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Madrepora oculata*. The white coral clumps are only found on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side.

The living *M. oculata* canopy has a height of up to 70cm and a width of up to 50 cm. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians. In terms of occurrence, *M. oculata* is usually dominant in the upper bathyal frameworks and seems to exhibit a greater ability to grow in warmer waters.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often many tens square km wide) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence: the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province, the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province, the Sicily Channel CWC Province, the South Sardinia CWC Province, the Corsica Channel CWC Province, the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces, and the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

The occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building coral *Madrepora oculata*, accompanied by antipatharians (Leiopathes), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (Dendrophyllia). They

provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth, adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denudated skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened because they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospections, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged along by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Trincardi, F., Bakran-Petricioli, T., Ceregato, A., Chimienti, G., Macic, V.,

Poliseno, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The "Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province" (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Gheerardyn, H., King, N. J., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Aguilar, R., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D'Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean), *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Paireud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Gherardi, M., Longo, C., Rosso, A., Sciuto, F., Sanfilippo, R., Gravili, C., Boero, F., Taviani, M., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. *Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral* (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., González-Duarte, M. M., López, E., Madurell, T., Maldonado, M., Mateo-Ramírez, A.,

Megina, C., Moreira, J., Moya, F., Ramalho, L. V., Rosso, A., Sitjà, C., Taviani, M., 2019. 29 cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. *Plos One* 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. *Cold-water corals and ecosystems*, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Cau, A. B., Follesa, M. C., Marchese, F., Montagna, P., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 145, 61-78.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Cardone, F., Montagna, P., Danovaro, R., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. *Scientific reports* 9, 1-12.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Foglini, F., Corselli, C., Nasto, I., Pons-Branchu, E., Montagna, P., 2019. U/Th dating records of cold-water coral colonization in submarine canyons and adjacent sectors of the southern Adriatic Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 300-308.

Tunesi L., Diviacco G., Mo G., 2001. Observations by submersible on the biocoenosis of the deep-sea corals off Portofino Promontory (Northwestern Mediterranean Sea). In: *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Deep-Sea Corals*, Ecology Action Centre and Nova Scotia Museum, Halifax, Nova Scotia, J.H. Martin Willison et al. (eds): 76-87.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF1513](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MF2.511, MF1.513 (partially)

MF1513. Mediterranean lower bathyal *Madrepora oculata* and *Lophelia pertusa* reefs

General description

Deep-sea biogenic habitats, thriving in the upper and lower bathyal depth range, are a common source of biological heterogeneity both on hardgrounds and soft seafloors, where they increase the complexity of the primary substrate. The most representative of these biogenic habitats, at times extending for km and arising for various dozens of meters, is that formed by Cold-water corals (CWC) *sensu stricto* (deep-water azooxanthellate scleractinian (stony) corals), forming bioconstructions. The distinction between upper bathyal reefs (at depths below about 200 m) and lower bathyal reefs (below depths of about 400 m to 1,300 m) is fundamentally based on bathymetry, since the structure, a large part of the associated fauna and the functioning is very similar (even if with a higher occurrence in the upper bathyal). Mediterranean CWC habitats are structurally complex deep-sea ecosystems that form an intricate network of biogenic frames and interstices, providing trophic niches, spawning, nursery or shelter grounds for a large variety of organisms, including commercially important and threatened species. This facies is characterised by the framework-building corals *Madrepora oculata* and *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*. The white coral clumps are found on hard substrata along the edges of canyons or over topographic reliefs, where slope and seafloor heterogeneity sustain a significant hydrodynamic flux. Corals may form scattered colonies, reefs (ridge structures with a length of up to 20km and a height of up to 150m) or, more often in the Mediterranean context, carbonate mounds (elongated structures 25-50m in height and 100-800m across, often occurring in large numbers), with the most intense coral growth observed on the up-current, exposed side.

The living coral canopy has a height of up to 70cm and a width of up to 50cm for *M. oculata*, while the live portions of *D. pertusum* rarely exceed 20cm in size. Apart from rocks and thanatocoenoses, living colonies may settle on the denudated skeleton of persistent habitat-formers such as antipatharians.

In terms of occurrence, *M. oculata* and *D. dianthus* are usually dominant in the upper bathyal frameworks, *D. pertusum* is more frequent in the lower bathyal depth range, despite they all show almost the same bathymetric range within the basin. *M. oculata* seems to exhibit a greater ability to grow in warmer waters.

Major areas have been identified in the basin, referring to geographically discrete areas (often many tens of square km wide) with an important deep-sea scleractinian presence:

- the Santa Maria di Leuca CWC Province.
- the Southern Adriatic Sea CWC Province.
- the Sicily Channel CWC Province.
- the South Sardinia CWC Province.
- the Corsica Channel CWC Province.
- the Gulf of Lion CWC Provinces.

- the Alboran Sea CWC Province.

The occurrence, distribution and abundance of CWC species are strongly influenced by several abiotic factors (aragonite saturation, hydrodynamism, food supply, availability of suitable substrata, temperature, oxygen concentration).

Characteristic species

This facies is characterised by the framework-building corals *Madrepora oculata* and *Desmophyllum pertusum* (formerly known as *Lophelia pertusa*), accompanied by the solitary coral *D. Dianthus*, antipatharians (*Leiopathes*), octocorals (the calcified gorgonacean *Corallium rubrum*) and yellow corals (*Dendrophyllia*). They provide a suitable substrate both for larval settlement and adult growth, adding to the number of available secondary hard substrates and increasing the overall tridimensionality of the habitat.

Associated species

Facies dominated by scleractinian frameworks are recognised as a key component of Mediterranean deep-sea ecosystems. The bioconstructions act as poles of attraction for the fauna, increasing the quantity and nutritional quality of the available organic matter and increasing the deposition of biogenic detritus also in the adjacent soft bottoms, which host a higher faunal diversity. With respect to the various taxonomic components, the assemblage features small and encrusting sponges (*Desmacella inornata*, *Sceptrella insignis*, and, occasionally, large, massive species such as *Calthropella pathologica*), hydrozoans and especially anthozoans (including scleractinians, black corals, actinarians, and alcyonaceans), polychaetes, bryozoans, and vagile species such as crustaceans, molluscs, fishes, echinoderms, and brachiopods. Most species are not exclusively associated to this facies, but they benefit from the complex and diverse microhabitats provided by the bioconstruction. The dead portions of the bioconstructions that are not covered by mud are biodiversity hotspots thanks to the occurrence of numerous cavities and the availability of inert denudated skeletons.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Most cold-water coral species, and specifically white corals, have been listed as vulnerable (due to their fragility, slow growth rates, low resilience and ecological role), as well as threatened as they are found in areas which are frequently the focus of resource exploitation (e.g., deep-sea fisheries, oil and gas prospecting, mining) or are affected directly by other human activities (e.g., seafloor litter, pollution events). With respect to fishing practices impacting the coral frameworks, trawling activities are a major threat, since they may both mechanically impact the structures compromising their integrity and increase silting levels enhancing the clogging of the filtering structures. Similarly, longlines have a high chance of entanglement on these branched species. In addition, when lost or discarded, the gear (similarly to other plastic litter) collapses on the seafloor and may be dragged by bottom currents. The effects of anthropogenically-induced climate change, including acidification, warming and salinification, are expected to have strong impacts on Mediterranean marine ecosystems and biodiversity also at great depths.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., Canese, S., Foglini, F., Mastrototaro, F., Argnani, A., Trincardi, F., Bakran-Petricioli, T., Ceregato, A., Chimienti, G., Macic, V., Polisenò, A., 2014. New deep-water cnidarian sites in the southern Adriatic Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 15, 263-273.

Angeletti, L., Castellan, G., Montagna, P., Remia, A., Taviani, M., 2020. The “Corsica Channel Cold- Water Coral Province” (Mediterranean Sea). *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 661.

Buhl-Mortensen, L., Vanreusel, A., Gooday, A.J., Levin, L.A., Priede, I.G., Buhl-Mortensen, P., Gheerardyn, H., King, N. J., Raes, M., 2010. Biological structures as a source of habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity on the deep ocean margins. *Marine Ecology* 3, 21-50.

Chimienti, G., Bo, M., Taviani, M., Mastrototaro, F., 2019. Occurrence and Biogeography of Mediterranean Cold-water corals. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: Past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 213-243.

Corbera, G., Iacono, C.L., Gràcia, E., Grinyó, J., Pierdomenico, M., Huvenne, V.A., Aguilar, R., Gili, J.M., 2019. Ecological Characterisation of a Mediterranean cold-water coral reef: Cabliers Coral Mound Province (Alboran Sea, western Mediterranean). *Progress in Oceanography* 175, 245-262.

De La Torriente, A., González-Irusta, J.M., Aguilar, R., Fernández-Salas, L.M., Punzón, A., Serrano, A., 2019. Benthic habitat modelling and mapping as a conservation tool for Marine Protected Areas: A seamount in the western Mediterranean. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, 732-750.

D’Onghia, G., Sion, L., Capezzuto, F., 2019. Cold-water coral habitats benefit adjacent fisheries along the Apulian margin (central Mediterranean), *Fisheries Research* 213, 172-179.

Fabri, M.C., Bargain, A., Pairaud, I., Pedel, L., Taupier-Letage, I., 2017. Cold-water coral ecosystems in Cassidaigne Canyon: an assessment of their environmental living conditions. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137, 436-453.

Fabri, M.C., Vinha, B., Allais, A.G., Bouhier, M.E., Dugornay, O., Gaillot, A., Arnaubec, A., 2019. Evaluating the ecological status of cold-water coral habitats using non-invasive methods: an example from Cassidaigne canyon, northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 178, 102172.

Fanelli, E., Delbono, I., Ivaldi, R., Pratellesi, M., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., 2017. Cold-water coral *Madrepora oculata* in the eastern Ligurian Sea (NW Mediterranean): Historical and recent findings. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27, 965-975.

Gori, A., Ferrier-Pagès, C., Hennige, S.J., Murray, F., Rottier, C., Wicks, L.C., Roberts, J.M., 2016. Physiological response of the cold-water coral

Desmophyllum dianthus to thermal stress and ocean acidification. PeerJ 4, e1606.

Mastrototaro, F., D'Onghia, G., Corriero, G., Matarrese, A., Maiorano, P., Panetta, P., Gherardi, M., Longo, C., Rosso, A., Sciuto, F., Sanfilippo, R., Gravili, C., Boero, F., Taviani, M., Tursi A., 2010. Biodiversity of the white coral bank off Cape Santa Maria di Leuca (Mediterranean Sea): An update. Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography 57, 412-430.

Orejas C., Jiménez C. (eds), 2019. Mediterranean Cold-water corals: Past, Present and Future: Understanding the Deep-Sea Realms of Coral (Vol. 9). Springer.

Rueda, J.L., Urra, J., Aguilar, R., Angeletti, L., Bo, M., García-Ruiz, C., González-Duarte, M. M., López, E., Madurell, T., Maldonado, M., Mateo-Ramírez, A., Megina, C., Moreira, J., Moya, F., Ramalho, L. V., Rosso, A., Sitjà, C., Taviani, M., 2019. 29 cold-water coral associated fauna in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas. In: *Mediterranean cold-water corals: past, present and future*, Springer, Cham, 295-333.

Savini, A., Vertino, A., Marchese, F., Beuck, L., Freiwald, A., 2014. Mapping cold-water coral habitats at different scales within the Northern Ionian Sea (Central Mediterranean): an assessment of coral coverage and associated vulnerability. Plos One 9, e87108.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Taviani, M., Freiwald, A., Zibrowius, H., 2005. Deep coral growth in the Mediterranean Sea: an overview'. Cold-water corals and ecosystems, 137-156.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cardone, F., Cau, A., Cau, A. B., Follesa, M. C., Marchese, F., Montagna, P., Tessarolo, C., 2017. The "Sardinian cold-water coral province" in the context of the Mediterranean coral ecosystems. Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography 145, 61-78.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Cardone, F., Montagna, P., Danovaro, R., 2019. A unique and threatened deep water coral-bivalve biotope new to the Mediterranean Sea offshore the Naples megalopolis. Scientific reports 9, 1-12.

Taviani, M., Angeletti, L., Foglini, F., Corselli, C., Nasto, I., Pons-Branchu, E., Montagna, P., 2019. U/Th dating records of cold-water coral colonization in submarine canyons and adjacent sectors of the southern Adriatic Sea since the Last Glacial Maximum. Progress in Oceanography 175, 300-308.

Tunesi L., Diviacco G., Mo G., 2001. Observations by submersible on the biocoenosis of the deep-sea corals off Portofino Promontory (Northwestern Mediterranean Sea). In: *Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Deep-Sea Corals*, Ecology Action Centre and Nova Scotia Museum, Halifax, Nova Scotia, J.H. Martin Willison et al. (eds): 76-87.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF6511](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MF6.511

MF6511. Mediterranean lower bathyal facies of sandy muds with *Thenea muricata*

General description

This facies is characterised by sandy muds populated by the sponge *Thenea muricata*. This species can be found as scattered individuals, but may also form dense monospecific aggregations on sandy muds between depths of 300m and 2,000m.

Characteristic species

Thenea muricata is a globular/egg-shaped sponge, sized up to 5-6cm in height/diameter with rooting structures and one or few apical oscula. It is characterised by a distinct groove around the mid-section of the body, where inhalant pores are located, and root-like structures projecting from the base, by means of which they attach to soft substrate. Consistency is slightly compressible, and texture is smooth. Colour is white to brownish/greyish.

Associated species

The upper bathyal zone shows a high species richness, hosting abundant meiofauna (dominated by Nematoda), together with infaunal macro and mega-benthos. Macrofauna is generally dominated by polychaetes. Epimegafauna tends to be sparse and constituted mainly by mobile species such as crustacean, fishes and echinoderms. Cnidarians are among the most common sessile and sedentary organisms, together with sponges. Aggregations of giant foraminiferans and bryozoans are also present. This habitat can host gorgonians (*Isidella elongata*), aggregations of ceriantharians and sea pens such as *Pennatula* spp., *Funiculina quadrangularis*, *Protoptilum carpenteri*, *Kophobelemnion stelliferum* and *Virgularia mirabilis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Vulnerable marine ecosystems such as those formed by *P. carpenteri* are affected by climate change and other anthropogenic activities (especially demersal fishing), as they are formed by sensitive species with slow growth rates and limited dispersal capability, which can hinder their adaptive capability and recovery after disturbance. The impact that climate change will have on *P. carpenteri* is still unclear, although it is expected to influence the species' suitable habitat availability and distribution range.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Bo, M., Bertolino, M., Bavestrello, G., Canese, S., Giusti, M., Angiolillo, M., Pansini, M., Taviani, M., 2012. Role of deep sponge grounds in the

Mediterranean Sea: a case study in southern Italy. *Hydrobiologia*, 687:163-177.

Santín, A., Grinyó, J., Ambroso, S., Uriz, M.J., Gori, A., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Gili, J.M. Sponge assemblages on the deep Mediterranean continental shelf and slope (Menorca Channel, Western Mediterranean Sea). *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 131, 75-86.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Stamouli, C., Gerovasileiou, V., Voultsiadou, E., 2023. Sponge Community Patterns in Mesophotic and Deep-Sea Habitats in the Aegean and Ionian Seas. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng*, 11, 2204.

Group 5

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF6513](#)

EUNIS level: 5

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MF6.512, ME6.513

MF6513. Mediterranean lower bathyal facies of compact muds with *Isidella elongata*

General description

This facies is present on the lower bathyal plain (down to a depth of 1,850m) and is considered the most representative habitat with alcyonaceans of the bathyal mud, characterised by compact muds in which the cnidarian *Isidella elongata* is present. The colonies penetrate the mud thanks to a large basal root. The density of the aggregations and the abundance of the associated fauna is lower when the mud habitat fade into sandy mud. This facies is present both in open bathyal plain areas and in the soft bottom near rocky elevations or dead coral mounds, also along the offshore circalittoral, the continental slope and the upper bathyal mud. Bioturbation produced by large shrimps is an important phenomenon in this habitat. Due to heavy trawling activities, bathyal meadows of *I. elongata* are now considered very rare, except for areas made difficult for trawling activities (e.g., small enclaves of colonies in shallow-water refuge areas protected by hardgrounds, areas nearby submarine cables, canyons, areas near cold-water coral reefs) and poorly exploited bathyal fishing grounds (e.g., Otranto Channel, Balearic Sea, Southwestern Sardinia, Northeast of Lipari).

Characteristic species

I. elongata is a large-sized Mediterranean isidid, or bamboo coral, that may reach 70cm in height and significant densities (up to 2,300-2,683 colonies/hectare; up to 7 colonies/m²) on compact mud covered by a film of fluid mud with little or no slope (3-20°). *I. elongata* is widespread in the Mediterranean region between 113-115m (Malta, Southwestern Sardinia) and at a depth of 1,819m depth (France), but vast populations are traditionally reported at depths of around 400-700m, and it is considered the most important habitat-forming species of the Mediterranean bathyal mud.

Associated species

The *Isidella elongata* bathyal facies is a biodiversity hotspot. The colonies host numerous non-exclusive epibionts, including hydrozoans, the anemone *Amphianthus dohrnii*, the lepas *Scalpellum scalpellum*, the crab *Anamathia rissoana*, *Chlamys* bivalves, and polychaetes. Numerous sessile or vagile epifaunal invertebrates are observed between the colonies or nearby the forest, such as large foraminifera, sponges (*Rhizaxinella pyrifer* and *Thenea muricata*), the large hydrozoan *Lytocarpia myriophyllum*, pennatulaceans (*Funiculina quadrangularis* and *Kophobelemnon stelliferum*), bryozoans, decapods (*Munida* spp. and *Dorhynchus thomsonis*), echinoderms. The mud surrounding the colonies hosts a rich infauna and is a favourable area for many mud-stirring deep shrimps (e.g., *Aristeus antennatus*, *Aristaeomorpha foliacea*, *Nephrops norvegicus*, *Parapenaeus longirostris*, and *Plesionika* spp.), cephalopods and fishes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The patchy aggregation, the size and fragility of the colonies, the long recovery times (from a few decades to one century), and the fact that it cannot bend, does not retract into the sediments and is not able to re-settle when swept away, make *I. elongata* highly vulnerable. The main threat is represented by bottom trawling damaging and uprooting of the colonies. Beside habitat alteration, trawling also alters the silting rates causing the clogging of the non-retractile polyps and a disturbance in the zooplankton feeding activity, and influences the benthic trophic web. Also bottom long line fishing is known to cause damage to the *I. elongata* facies. In addition to fishing impact, pollution and litter dumping on these facies are other important threats as well as other human activities, such as mineral extraction that favours, together with trawling activities and the alteration of river run off, high silting levels. The GFCM identified the mud facies with the *I. elongata*, as a sensitive habitat and indicative of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) as well as Essential Fish Habitats (EFHs) based on the functional significance, fragility, and structural complexity of this facies, as well its life history traits that limit the probability of recovery. *I. elongata* has been assessed by the IUCN in the Anthozoan Red List as critically endangered, it has been included in Annex II of the Barcelona Convention.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angiolillo, M., Di Lorenzo, B., Izzi, A., Giusti, M., Nonnis, O., Pazzini, A., Trabucco, B., Tunesi, L., 2024. Healthy assemblages of *Isidella elongata* unintentionally protected from trawling offshore of Asinara Island (northwestern Sardinia, NW Mediterranean Sea). *Scientific Reports*, 14:12813.

Bo, M., Bavestrello, G., Angiolillo, M., Calcagnile, L., Canese, S., Cannas, R., Cau, A., D'Elia, M., D'Oriano, F., Follesa, M.C., Quarta, G., Cau, A., 2015. Persistence of pristine deep-sea coral gardens in the Mediterranean Sea (Southwestern Sardinia). *Plos One* 10, e0119393.

Carbonara, P., Zupa, W., Follesa, M.C., Cau, A., Capezzuto, F., ..., Maiorano, P., 2020. Exploring a deep-sea vulnerable marine ecosystem: *Isidella elongata* (Esper, 1788) species assemblages in the Western and Central Mediterranean. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers* 166, 103406.

Cartes, J.E., Loiacono, C., Mamouridis, V., Lopez-Perez, C., Rodriguez, P., 2013. Geomorphological, trophic and human influences on the bamboo coral *Isidella elongata* assemblages in the deep Mediterranean: To what extent does *Isidella* form habitat for fish and invertebrates? *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers* 76, 52-65.

De La Torriente, A., Serrano, A., Fernandez-Salas, L.M., Garcia, M., Aguilar, R., 2018. Identifying epibenthic habitats on the Seco de los Olivos Seamount:

Species assemblages and environmental characteristics. Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers 135, 9-22.

D'Onghia, G., Mastrototaro, F., Matarrese, A., Politou, C., Mytilineou, C., 2003. Biodiversity of the upper slope demersal community in the eastern Mediterranean: preliminary comparison between two areas with and without trawl fishing. Journal of Northwest Atlantic Fishery Science 31, 263.

Evans, J., Aguilar, R., Alvarez, H., Borg, J.A., Garcia, S., Knittweis, L., Schembri P.J., 2016. Recent evidence that the deep sea around Malta is a biodiversity hotspot. Rapports de la Commission internationale pour la Mer Méditerranée 41, 463.

Fabri, M.C., Pedel, L., Beuck, L., Galgani, F., Hebbeln, D., Freiwald A., 2014. Megafauna of vulnerable marine ecosystems in French Mediterranean submarine canyons: spatial distribution and anthropogenic impacts. Deep-Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography 104, 184-207.

Gerovasileiou V., Smith C.J., Kiparissis S., Stamouli C., Dounas C., Mytilineou C., 2019. Updating the distribution status of the critically endangered bamboo coral *Isidella elongata* (Esper, 1788) in the deep Eastern Mediterranean Sea. Regional Studies in Marine Science 28, 100610.

Ingrassia, M., Martorelli, E., Bosman, A., Chiocci, F.L., 2019. *Isidella elongata* (Cnidaria: Alcyonacea): First report in the Ventotene Basin (Pontine Islands, western Mediterranean Sea). Regional Studies in Marine Science 25, 100494.

Lauria, V., Garofalo, G., Fiorentino, F., Massi, D., Milisenda, G., Piraino, S., Russo, T., Gristina, M., 2017. Species distribution models of two critically endangered deep-sea octocorals reveal fishing impacts on vulnerable marine ecosystems in central Mediterranean Sea. Scientific Reports 7, 1-14.

Mastrototaro, F., Chimienti, G., Acosta, J., Blanco, J., Garcia, S., Rivera, J., Aguilar, R., 2017. *Isidella elongata* (Cnidaria: Alcyonacea) facies in the western Mediterranean Sea: visual surveys and descriptions of its ecological role. The European Zoological Journal 84, 209-225.

Pierdomenico, M., Russo, T., Ambroso, S., Gori, A., Martorelli, E., D'Andrea, L., Gili, J.M., Chiocci, F.L., 2018. Effects of trawling activity on the bamboo-coral *Isidella elongata* and the sea pen *Funiculina quadrangularis* along the Gioia Canyon (Western Mediterranean, southern Tyrrhenian Sea). Progress in Oceanography 169, 214-226.

Sartoretto, S., Zibrowius, H., 2017. Note on new records of living Scleractinia and Gorgonaria between 1700 and 2200 m depth in the western Mediterranean Sea. Marine Biodiversity 48, 689-694.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 6: Vents and seeps

Figure 06-01, Cold seep with mussels (*Bathymodiolus aff. boomerang*) off the French Coast, NE Atlantic

Source: IFREMER (2011). Affleurement d'hydrates de gaz et moules (*Bathymodiolus boomerang*). Ifremer.
<https://image.ifremer.fr/data/00575/68748/>

Group 6

MB128. Vents and seeps in Atlantic infralittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB128](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: #1160, <1170, #1180

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB1281](#), [MB1282](#), [MB1283](#), [MB1284](#), [MB12841](#), [MB12842](#)

OSPAR:

Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents⁵¹

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, although some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist: submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to a reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are also less toxic to organisms.

The Atlantic infralittoral rock habitat encompasses seabed substrates such as bedrock, boulders, and cobbles, occurring in the shallow subtidal zone. The main factor delimiting the boundaries between infralittoral, upper and lower circalittoral, is light availability. The upper boundary of the infralittoral is defined by the top of the kelp zone, while the lower boundary is set by the deepest extent of kelp growth or dense seaweed growth. Infralittoral rock typically features dense kelp forest in its upper zone and a sparse kelp growth in its lower zone, both accompanied by an underlayer of seaweeds.

The HD habitat 1180 is known to occur in at least OSPAR regions II-IV, especially in the Kattegat area, where it is characterised by so-called bubbling reef structures. Bubbling reefs consist of chalk that binds sand, gravel and shells. At one certain location, small stones also contribute significantly to the structure alongside the chalk. These reef formations are predominantly found in the Danish section of the Kattegat, though they are also documented in the Swedish part of the Kattegat and in the Danish part of Skagerrak (figure 2.1). All known reefs, apart from one west of the island Læsø in the Kattegat, are located between the shoreline and at a depth of 20 metres within the infralittoral zone. The ecological characteristics of these reefs vary significantly depending on the depth, location on the reef structure (in MB12841 vertical or down-facing) and local environmental conditions. Salinity gradients from the northern to southern parts of the Kattegat influence species composition as this region serves as a transition zone between the brackish Baltic Sea and the more saline Greater North Sea. Additionally, salinity differs vertically, with lower salinity in surface waters compared to the bottom layers.

⁵¹ In its Decision IG.24/7 (2019), the SPA/RAC adopted an updated classification of benthic marine habitat types for the Mediterranean region, in which certain geomorphologic and hydrologic features were excluded from the habitat type list, due to their independence from depth zones and substrate types, as well as them forming habitat complexes. The excluded habitats included hydrothermal vents and cold seeps.

Characteristic species

Photophilic species generally inhabit the upper parts, and the shadier areas are vegetated by sciaphilic species/communities. Commonly, brown algae (such as Laminariales) dominate. In exposed environments, species such as *Laminaria hyperborea* dominate, whereas in more sheltered areas, e.g., *Saccharina latissima* is more common. Other kelp species may prevail under specific conditions. On the extreme lower shore and in very shallow subtidal zones, a narrow band of *Alaria esculenta* can be found on exposed coasts, while *L. digitata* is typical in moderately exposed coasts, and *L. saccharina* in very sheltered ones. In areas with mixed substrates that lack stable rock, kelps may be absent, but seaweed communities can still thrive. In estuaries and other turbid waters, the shallow subtidal zone may be dominated by animal communities, with poorly developed seaweed growth.

For bubbling reefs, the two most abundant red algal species are *Phycodrys rubens* and *Phyllophora pseudoceranoides*. *Delesseria sanguinea*, *L. digitata* and *L. hyperborea*, as well as *Saccharina latissimi*, can also be found, although their occurrence is variable between sites. *Alcyonium digitatum*, *Electra pilosa* and *Metridium senile* are also characteristic as are *Bonnemaisonia hamifera*, *Coccotylus* spp. and *Vertebrata byssoides*.

Associated species

In the photic zone, the areas tend to be vegetated by marine macroalgae, such as *Laminariales*, and other foliose and filamentous brown and red algae. The animal communities can consist of Porifera, Cnidarians, bryozoans, Anthozoa, Polychaeta, Gastropoda, Decapoda, Echinodermata, as well as some fish and bacterial (e.g., Beggiatoa) species.

At vent sites, the number of species toward the vent commonly decline, due to the increasing temperature and acidity of the environment. The dominant species, however, usually increase in both numbers and biomass toward the vent. These species usually do not occur in the surrounding areas.

The species compositions at shallow-water seeps are commonly a sub-set of the species in the surrounding environment, but there may be differences in the substrate as well as higher sulphide concentrations, affecting the communities.

Colonisation of both vent and seep sites are commonly limited by the toxicity of sulphide, especially hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g., debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Bubbling reefs face significant threats from dredged bottom-contact fishing activities, which can cause irreversible damage. Other fishing methods in-

volving seabed contact, anchoring and sand or gravel extraction pose additional risks. Eutrophication represents a reversible but harmful impact.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), mining activities, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[Dahl, K., Göke, C., 2025. Bubbling reef habitats - Input to the interpretation manual of the marine EUNIS habitats in the Nature Restoration Regulation. Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, 18 pp. Technical Report No. 340.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Atlantic infralittoral rock.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Infralittoral rock \(and other hard substrata\).](#)

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region.](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

Group 6

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB627](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB6271](#), [MB6272](#)

OSPAR:

Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents

MB627. Vents and seeps in Atlantic infralittoral mud

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, but some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist, e.g., submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are also less toxic to organisms.

The Atlantic infralittoral mud habitat encompasses seabed substrates such as silt and clay, with sandy substrates at lower concentrations, dominated by very fine-grained substrate. This habitat occurs predominantly in the lower shore to about 15-20m in depth, in very sheltered areas with weak tidal currents. Some areas may be periodically or permanently anoxic.

Characteristic species

Typically, rich varieties of polychaetes (e.g., *Melinna palmata*), tube-building amphipods (e.g., *Ampelisca* spp.), and bivalves (e.g., *Macoma balthica*, *Mysella bidentata*) occur in the infralittoral mud. Sea pens (e.g., *Virgularia mirabilis*) and brittlestars (e.g., *Amphiura* spp.) may be scarcely present. In some areas, lugworm (*Arenicola marina*) with anemones, opisthobranch (*Philine aperta*) as well as synaptid holothurians, are common.

Associated species

Various faunal-dominated communities are supported, especially polychaetes, bivalves, and urchins (e.g., *Echinocardium cordatum*). Bacterial mats may form in anoxic areas.

At vent sites, the number of species toward the vent commonly decline, due to the increasing temperature and acidity of the environment. The dominant species, however, usually increase in both numbers and biomass toward the vent. These species usually do not occur in the surrounding areas.

The species compositions at shallow-water seeps are commonly a sub-set of the species in the surrounding environment, but there may be differences in the substrate as well as higher sulphide concentrations, affecting the communities.

Colonisation of both vent and seep sites are commonly limited by the toxicity of sulphide, especially hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g., debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

Dando, P. R. 2010. Chapter 11 Biological communities at Marine Shallow-Water Vent and Seep Sites. In: Kiel, S. (ed.) 2010. The Vent and Seep Biota-Aspects from Microbes to Ecosystems. Topics in Geobiology, 33. Springer.

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Atlantic infralittoral mud.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Infralittoral muddy sand.](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents.](#)

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region.](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

Group 6

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC127](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

HD: <1170, #1180

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC1271](#), [MC1272](#), [MC1273](#), [MC1274](#), [MC1275](#)

OSPAR:

Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents

MC127. Vents and seeps in Atlantic circalittoral rock

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, but some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist, e.g., submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are also less toxic to organisms.

The Atlantic circalittoral rock habitats are wave-exposed and characterised by strong tidal streams and are typically found in tidal straits and narrows. The circalittoral zone is dependent on light conditions. The circalittoral zone continues from the lower limit of the infralittoral down to where light intensity is so low that photosynthesis is no longer possible, in general, at a depth of approximately 200m. The circalittoral can be further divided into the upper and lower circalittoral, the former where foliose red algae can be present, and the latter where they are not. The communities are generally dominated by animal species, but may greatly vary due to the environmental conditions, such as wave action, tidal stream strength, turbidity, salinity, degree of scouring, and rock topography.

The HD habitat 1180 is known to occur in (at least) OSPAR regions II-IV, especially in the Kattegat area, where it is characterised by so-called bubbling reef structures. Bubbling reefs consist of chalk that binds sand, gravel and shells. These reef formations are predominantly found in the Danish section of the Kattegat, though they are also documented in the Swedish part of the Kattegat and in the Danish part of Skagerrak (figure 2.1). Circalittoral bubbling reef formations have been identified at one site. The ecological characteristics of these reefs vary significantly depending on the depth, location on the reef structure and local environmental conditions.

Characteristic species

The communities reflect the energy levels in the circalittoral rock type habitat. Species tend to be of the attaching kind, e.g., algae, tubeworms, bryozoans, sponges and corals, and usually only one species does not dominate.

Sponges may include *Pachymatisma johnstonia*, *Halichondria panicea*, *Esperiopsis fucorum* and/or *Myxilla incrustans*. The hydroid *Tubularia indivisa* may be present in densely populated plots, and the barnacle *Balanus crenatus* may be present in high abundances on hard substrates. The soft coral *Alcyonium digitatum* is often present.

For bubbling reefs in the circalittoral zone, there is currently no documented information on the biological communities. It is highly probable that these communities mirror those observed on offshore circalittoral bubbling reefs.

Associated species

The species communities reflect the individual characteristics of the area, and may, therefore, vary between habitats. Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g., debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Bubbling reefs face significant threats from dredged bottom-contact fishing activities, which can cause irreversible damage. Other fishing methods involving seabed contact, anchoring and sand or gravel extraction pose additional risks. Eutrophication represents a reversible but harmful impact.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

[Dahl, K., Göke, C., 2025. Bubbling reef habitats - Input to the interpretation manual of the marine EUNIS habitats in the Nature Restoration Regulation. Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, 18 pp. Technical Report No. 340.](#)

Dando, P. R. 2010. Chapter 11 Biological communities at Marine Shallow-Water Vent and Seep Sites. In: Kiel, S. (ed.) 2010. The Vent and Seep Biota-Aspects from Microbes to Ecosystems. Topics in Geobiology, 33. Springer.

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Circalittoral rock and other hard substrata.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Circalittoral rock.](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents.](#)

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region.](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC622](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral mud

HD: #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC6221](#), [MC6222](#)

OSPAR:

Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, but some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist, e.g., submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are thus also less toxic to organisms.

The Atlantic circalittoral (sandy) mud habitat is generally encountered in areas with little tidal action, at depths greater than 10 m. This type of habitat can generally be found in deeper parts of bays and marine inlets, or offshore from areas of weak wave action.

Characteristic species

Cnidarians such as the sea pens *Virgularia mirabilis* or *Pennatula phosphorea*, anemones such as *Cerianthus lloydii*, and brittlestars such as *Amphiura* spp. are characteristic in circalittoral mud habitats. Infauna may include tube-building polychaetes such as *Lagis koreni* and *Owenia fusiformis*, and deposit feeding bivalves such as *Mysella bidentata* and *Abra* spp.

Associated species

As a result of the relatively stable conditions, megafaunal species such as the lobster *Nephrops norvegicus* may form communities in circalittoral mud type habitats. Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g., debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Best practices in nature restoration

Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

Dando, P. R. 2010. Chapter 11 Biological communities at Marine Shallow-Water Vent and Seep Sites. In: Kiel, S. (ed.) 2010. The Vent and Seep Biota-Aspects from Microbes to Ecosystems. Topics in Geobiology, 33. Springer.

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Atlantic circalittoral mud.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Circalittoral rock.](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents.](#)

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region.](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

Group 6

MD122. Vents and seeps on Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD122](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef

[HD](#): <1170, #1180

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD1221](#)

OSPAR:

Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, but some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist, e.g., submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are thus also less toxic to organisms.

The circalittoral offshore generally occurs at depths deeper than 50-70 m, and deeper than the influence of wave action. The area is aphotic, with faunal communities in stable steno-thermal or stenohaline conditions. Little data exists from the habitat.

Bubbling reefs belong to HD type 1180 and can also occur in offshore waters. They consist of chalk that binds sand, gravel and shells. Most documented offshore circalittoral bubbling reef structures are located in the Skagerrak, at depths ranging from 36 to 64m.

Characteristic species

The species are associated with hard bottoms (rock, boulders, bedrock), and may include hydroids, bryozoans, echinoderms, sponges, anthozoans, or ascidians.

In bubbling reefs, the soft coral *Alcyonium digitatum* is the dominant species.

Associated species

Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

In bubbling reefs, additional species observed included the sea stars *Asterias rubens* and *Marthasterias glacialis*, the sea urchin *Echinus esculentus* and the sea anemone *Metridium senile*. Gadoid fish, including cod (*Gadus morhua*) and saithe (*Pollachius virens*), can also be abundant around these structures.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g.,

debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Offshore circalittoral bubbling reefs face significant threats from dredged bottom-contact fishing gear that can cause irreversible structural damage. Other bottom-contact fishing practices, anchoring and sand or gravel extraction also pose risks. Eutrophication represents a reversible but harmful impact.

Best practices in nature restoration

Restoration is challenging, because baselines regarding, e.g., original species communities in a disturbed area may not be known. Connectivity, e.g., between intra or inter-vent fields, or the relationship with the rest of the marine realm, is also obscure. Passive restoration measures such as inclusion in marine protected areas and preservation measures such as precautionary regulation or even the exclusion of harmful activities or activities with unknown impacts still should be in order.

Bibliographic sources

[Dahl, K., Göke, C., 2025. Bubbling reef habitats - Input to the interpretation manual of the marine EUNIS habitats in the Nature Restoration Regulation. Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, 18 pp. Technical Report No. 340.](#)

Dando, P. R. 2010. Chapter 11 Biological communities at Marine Shallow-Water Vent and Seep Sites. In: Kiel, S. (ed.) 2010. The Vent and Seep Biota-Aspects from Microbes to Ecosystems. Topics in Geobiology, 33. Springer.

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Circalittoral rock.](#)

[Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\). Seeps and vents in sublittoral sediments.](#)

[MIDAS project Consortium \(Managing Impacts of Deep-Sea Resource Exploitation\).](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents.](#)

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

Group 6

MD622. Vents and seeps in Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD622](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD6221](#), [MD6222](#)

OSPAR:
Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents

General description

Vents and seeps are dynamic, heterogenous, and essentially ephemeral environments. Vents in shallow environments generally occur near volcanically active areas, but some occur along mid-ocean-ridges (such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge). Shallow cold seepage sites are distributed more widely, occurring on both shelves and slopes. Different types of seepage sites exist, e.g., submarine groundwater seeps, hydrocarbon seeps, and cold brine seeps.

Physical and chemical factors, such as surface type and topography, or sulphide concentrations, affect the organisms present. The amount and frequency of gas released at shallower sites is higher than at deep sites, due to reduced solubility of gases at lower pressures. At shallow vent sites, heavy metal and sulphide concentrations tend to be lower due to temperature and are thus also less toxic to organisms.

The circalittoral offshore zone generally occurs at a depth deeper than 50-70m, deeper than the influence of wave action. The habitats may occur on open coasts or in marine inlets, such a sea lochs (tidal inlets). The area is aphotic, with faunal communities in stable stenothermal or stenohaline conditions. Little data exists from the habitat.

In some areas, the methane seeps create pockmarks in deeper muddy sediments. However, so far there is no scientific proof that chimney structures inside pockmarks consists of carbonate cement. Therefore, these pockmarks with EUNIS type MD622 are not verified as a HD type 1180.

Characteristic species

The fauna depends on the levels of silt and clay and organic matter in the sediment. Typically, the communities are dominated by polychaetes, along with high numbers of bivalves (e.g., *Thyasira* spp.), echinoderms and foraminifera.

Associated species

Species encountered are adapted to softer bottom substrates, and may include e.g., crustaceans, worms, sea peans and anemones, but relatively little data exists. Microbes may inhabit and dominate the gas outlets.

Species may include the polychaetes *Capitella capitata* and *Levinsea gracilis*, and sea pens *Funiculina quadrangularis* and *Pennatula phosphorea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic pressures to this habitat type are represented by unregulated scientific research, potential bioprospecting, potential seabed mining and natural resource material extraction (e.g., oil, gas, hydrates), fishing activities, especially demersal gear, tourism, shipping, pollution (e.g.,

debris, waste disposal in oceans), introduction of new species, and removal of existing species.

Best practices in nature restoration

Restoration is challenging, because baselines regarding, e.g., original species communities in a disturbed area may not be known. Restoration of inaccessible areas, such as vents and seeps, is likely costly. Passive restoration measures that allow the biotope to recover, e.g., regulation/limitation/ban of fisheries (especially regarding bottom contacting gear), deep-sea-mining, construction as well as measures to reduce and avoid contamination of sediments, sediment alteration and abrasion.

Bibliographic sources

Dando, P. R. 2010. Chapter 11 Biological communities at Marine Shallow-Water Vent and Seep Sites. In: Kiel, S. (ed.) 2010. The Vent and Seep Biota-Aspects from Microbes to Ecosystems. Topics in Geobiology, 33. Springer.

[Danish Environmental Protection Agency, 2019. Kortlægning af Natura 2000-områder Marin habitatkortlægning i Skagerrak og Nordsøen 2017-2018.](#)

[EUNIS habitat classification: Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[JNCC. Description of biotope or habitat type: Offshore circalittoral mud.](#)

[Marine Life Information Network \(MarLIN\). Seeps and vents in sublittoral sediments.](#)

[MIDAS project Consortium \(Managing Impacts of Deep-Sea Resource Exploitation\).](#)

OSPAR, 2008. Descriptions of habitats on the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. OSPAR Agreement: 2008-07.

OSPAR, 2010. Background Document for Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields. Biodiversity series.

[OSPAR, 2022. Status Assessment 2022-Oceanic Ridges with hydrothermal vents.](#)

[SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region.](#)

[Van Dover, C. L., 2014. Impacts of anthropogenic disturbances at deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems: a review. Mar Environ Res, 102, 59-72.](#)

Group 7: Soft sediments (not deeper than 1.000 metres of depth)

Figure 07-01, *Virgularia mirabilis*, NE Atlantic

Source: *Virgularia mirabilis*, © Bernard Picton 2021

Group 7

MA32. Atlantic littoral coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA32](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA321](#), [MA3211](#),

[MA3212](#), [MA322](#)

IE:

=LS.LCS

General description

Atlantic littoral coarse sediments include shores of mobile pebbles, cobbles and gravel, sometimes with varying amounts of coarse sand. The sediment is highly mobile and subject to high degrees of drying between tides. As a result, few species can survive in this environment. Beaches of mobile cobbles and pebbles tend to be devoid of macroinfauna, while gravelly shores may support limited numbers of crustaceans, such as *Pectenogammarus planicrurus*.

Littoral coarse sediments are found along relatively exposed open shores, where wave action prevents finer sediments from settling. Coarse sediments may also be present on the upper parts of shores where there are more stable, sandy biotopes on the lower and mid shore.

The sediment particle size structure may vary seasonally, with relatively finer sediments able to settle during calmer conditions in summer. Where the sediment grain size is very large (at the interface between sediment and boulder shores), cobbles may be mobile during exposed winter conditions, but stable enough during summer months to support limited juvenile rocky shore epifauna (e.g., juvenile barnacles).

MA321: Shores of shingle (mobile cobbles and pebbles) or coarse gravel typically deposited because of onshore wave action and long-shore drift. The particle size tends to increase along the shore in the direction of the long-shore drift.

MA322: Shores of coarse sediments (shingle, gravels and coarse sand) in the upper reaches of estuaries and other inlets (e.g., sea lochs) which are subject to variable and reduced salinity conditions. The outflow of riverine freshwater at the heads of the inlets results in the washing out of fine particulate matter, leaving coarse sediments.

Characteristic species

MA321: As the sediment is very coarse and often quite mobile, it typically supports little marine life, other than opportunist amphipods and oligochaete worms. Summer growths of ephemeral green algae (*Enteromorpha* spp. or *Ulva* spp.) may develop. As for MA3211, the few individuals that may be found are those washed into the habitat by the ebbing tide, including the occasional amphipod or small polychaete.

MA3212: Shores of well-sorted gravel with a predominant particle size of 4 mm, but ranging between 3 and 6 mm, support dense populations of the amphipod *Pectenogammarus planicrurus*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Group 7

MA42. Atlantic littoral mixed sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA42](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment
HD: #1130, #1140, #1160, #1170

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA421](#), [MA4211](#),
[MA422](#), [MA4221](#), [MA423](#),
[MA4231](#), [MA4232](#),
[MA42321](#), [MA42322](#),
[MA42323](#), [MA42324](#),
[MA42325](#), [MA4233](#)

IE:

=LS.LMx

DE:

#02.01.01

#§ 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes shores of mixed sediments, ranging from muds with gravel and sand components to mixed sediments with pebbles, gravels, sands and mud in more even proportions. By definition, mixed sediments are poorly sorted. Stable large cobbles or boulders may be present, which support epibiota, e.g., fucoids and green seaweeds more commonly found on rocky and boulder shores. Depending on the features present (e.g., scattered stones, boulders with epifauna) and regional characteristics, mixed sediments can also be considered as reef structures (e.g., German Bight). Mixed sediments which are predominantly muddy tend to support infaunal communities which are similar to those of mud and sandy mud shores.

It is probable that there are broad transition areas between areas of mudflat or sandy mudflat, and mixed sediment biotopes where the sediment consists principally of mud but has significant proportions of gravel and sand mixed in. Gravelly mud may occur in patches on mudflats. Similarly, there is unlikely to be an easily defined boundary between areas of mixed sediment with stable cobbles and boulders, and boulder fields which fall into the rocky shore category.

Characteristic species

This biotope has a low species diversity. The relatively high number of species described below is due to a variation in the species composition from site to site, and not to high species richness on individual sites.

MA4211: The main species present are *Ulva intestinalis*, *Ulva lactuca* and *Porphyra* spp., along with colonial diatoms covering the surface of the substratum. Small numbers of other species such as barnacles *Semibalanus balanoides* and *Elminius modestus* are confined to any larger cobbles and pebbles or on the shells of larger individuals of the mussel *Mytilus edulis*. The crab *Carcinus maenas* and the winkle *Littorina littorea* can be present among the boulders, cobbles and seaweeds, while gammarids can be found in patches underneath the cobbles. In common with the other biotopes found on mixed substrata, patches of sediment are typically characterised by infaunal species including bivalves, for example, *Cerastoderma edule* and the polychaete *Arenicola marina* and the polychaete *Lanice conchilega*.

MA422: The ephemeral bands of seaweed often shelter communities of sandhoppers. A fauna of dense juvenile mussels may be found in sheltered firths, attached to algae on shores of pebbles, gravel, sand, mud and shell debris with a strandline of fucoid algae.

MA4232: Sheltered gravelly sandy mud, subject to reduced salinity, mainly on the mid and lower shore. The infaunal community is dominated by abundant ragworms *Hediste diversicolor*. Other species of the infauna vary for the sub-biotopes described. They include polychaetes such as *Pygospio elegans*, *Streblospio shrubsolii*, and *Manayunkia aestuarina*, oligochaetes such as *Heterochaeta costata* and *Tubificoides* spp., the mud shrimp *Corophium volutator*, the spire shell *Peringia ulvae*, the Baltic tellin *Limecola balthica* (*Macoma balthica*) and the peppery furrow shell *Scrobicularia plana*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

MA52. Atlantic littoral sand

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA52](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MA522](#) in this

report; [MA521](#), [MA5211](#),

[MA523](#), [MA5231](#), [MA5232](#),

[MA52321](#), [MA52322](#),

[MA5233](#), [MA52331](#),

[MA52332](#), [MA52333](#),

[MA524](#), [MA5241](#), [MA52411](#),

[MA52412](#), [MA52413](#),

[MA525](#), [MA5251](#), [MA5252](#),

[MA5253](#), [MA5254](#), [MA5255](#)

DE:

#02.01.04

#§ 30 "Wattflächen im Küstenbereich"

IE:

=LS.LSa

General description

This habitat type describes shores comprising clean sands (coarse, medium or fine-grained) and muddy sands with up to a 25% silt and clay fraction. Shells and stones may occasionally be present on the surface. The sand may be duned or rippled because of wave action or tidal currents. Littoral sands exhibit varying degrees of drying at low tide depending on the steepness of the shore, the sediment grade and the height on the shore. The more mobile sand shores are relatively impoverished (MA523), with more species-rich communities of amphipods, polychaetes and, on the lower shore, bivalves developing with increasing stability in finer sand habitats (MA524). Muddy sands (MA525), the most stable within this habitat complex, contain the highest proportion of bivalves.

A strandline of talitrid amphipods (MA5211) typically develops at the top of the shore where decaying seaweed accumulates. Fully marine sandy shores occur along stretches of open coast, while muddy sands are often present in more sheltered lower estuarine conditions and may be subject to some freshwater influence.

Littoral sandy shore environments can change markedly over seasonal cycles, with sediment being eroded during winter storms and accreted during calmer summer months. The particle size structure of the sediment may change from finer to coarser during winter months, as finer sediment gets resuspended in seasonal exposed conditions. This may affect the sediment infauna, with some species only present in summer when sediments are more stable. More sheltered muddy sand shores are likely to be more stable throughout the year, but may have a seasonal cover of green seaweeds during the summer period, particularly in nutrient enriched areas or where there is a freshwater inflow.

Characteristic species

MA521: A strandline of talitrid amphipods (*Talorchestia deshayesii*, MA5211) typically develops at the top of the shore where decaying seaweed accumulates. A fauna of dense juvenile mussels may be found in sheltered firths, attached to algae on the shores of pebbles, gravel, sand, mud and shell debris with a strandline of fucoid algae. Oligochaetes, mainly enchytraeids, can occur within damp stranded debris.

MA522: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MA523: Clean mobile sands (coarse, medium and some fine-grained), with little very fine sand, and no mud support a limited range of species: communities of isopods, amphipods and a limited range of polychaetes (*Scolelepis squamata*, *Pontocrates arenarius*, *Bathyporeia pelagica*, *B. pilosa*, *Haustorius arenarius* and *Eurydice pulchra*).

MA524: Fine sand communities. In the lower shore, and where sediments are stable, bivalves such as *Angulus tenuis* may be present in large numbers. Species recorded include *Anaitides maculata*, *Hediste diversicolor*, *Scoloplos armiger*, *Pygospio elegans*, *Tharyx killariensis*, oligochaetes, *Gammarus locusta*, *Peringia ulvae*, *Cerastoderma edule* and *Mya truncata*.

MA525: Muddy sand or fine sand, often occurring as extensive intertidal flats on open coasts and in marine inlets. The infauna consists of a diverse range of amphipods, polychaetes, bivalves and gastropods.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Scophthalmus maximus* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biototypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

MA62. Atlantic littoral mud

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MA62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral mud

HD: #1130, #1140, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See MA623 in this report; [MA621](#), [MA622](#), [MA6221](#), [M6222](#), [MA62221](#), [MA6223](#), [MA6224](#), [MA6225](#), [MA6226](#), [MA6227](#), [MA62271](#), [MA62272](#), [MA62273](#), [MA6228](#), [MA624](#), [MA6241](#)

DE:

#02.01.05

#§ 30 "Wattflächen im Küstenbereich"

IE:

=LS.LMu

General description

This habitat type describes shores of fine particulate sediment, mostly in the silt and clay fraction (particle size less than 0.063mm in diameter), though sandy mud may contain up to 40% sand (mostly very fine and fine sand). Littoral mud typically forms extensive mudflats, though dry compacted mud can form steep and even vertical structures, particularly at the top of the shore adjacent to saltmarshes. Little oxygen penetrates these cohesive sediments, and an anoxic layer is often present within millimetres of the sediment surface. Littoral mud can support communities characterised by polychaetes, bivalves and oligochaetes. Most muddy shores are subject to some freshwater influence, as most of them occur along the shores of estuaries. Mudflats on sheltered lower estuarine shores can support a rich infauna, whereas muddy shores at the extreme upper end of estuaries and which are subject to very low salinity often support very little infauna.

Characteristic species

MA621: Intertidal mudflats in the fully marine open sea (coast) only develop under macrotidal conditions such as those found in the German Bight and Mont Saint Michel, France. Low species diversity but huge overall invertebrate productivity, resulting in an important and perpetually exploited food source for waders, waterfowl and fish as well as resting, pupping and feeding areas for seals and their young.

MA622: Upper estuarine sandy mud and mud shores, in areas with significant freshwater influence are characterised by a restricted range of polychaetes and oligochaetes.

MA623: See the description of this habitat in this report.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

MB32. Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB32](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB321](#) and [MB322](#) in this report; [MB323](#), [MB3231](#), [MB3232](#), [MB3233](#), [MB3234](#), [MB3235](#), [MB3236](#), [MB3237](#), [MB3238](#)

IE:
=SS.SCS.ICS

DE:
#02.02.07, #02.02.08
#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand-, und Schillgründe"

General description

This habitat type describes moderately exposed habitats with coarse sand, gravelly sand, shingle and gravel in the infralittoral, which are subject to disturbance by tidal steams and wave action.

Characteristic species

MB321: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB322: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB323: The habitats found on the open coast or in tide-swept marine inlets are characterised by a robust fauna of infaunal polychaetes such as *Chaetozone setosa* and *Lanice conchilega*, cumacean crustacea such as *Iphinoe trispinosa* and *Diastylis bradyi*, and venerid bivalves. Habitats with the lancelet *Branchiostoma lanceolatum* may also occur.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Ammodytes tobianus* and/or *Hyperoplus lanceolatus* (depending on specific grain size).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017.-Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

MB42. Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB42](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1170

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB421](#) in this report; [MB422](#), [MB4221](#), [MB4222](#), [MB4223](#), [MB423](#), [MB4231](#), [MB4232](#), [MB4233](#), [MB424](#), [MB4241](#), [MB4242](#)

IE:
=SS.SMx.IMx

DE:
#02.02.06
#§ 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes shallow mixed (heterogeneous) sediments in fully marine or near fully marine conditions, supporting various animal-dominated communities, with relatively low proportions of seaweeds. This habitat may include well mixed muddy gravelly sands or very poorly sorted mosaics of shell, cobbles and pebbles embedded in mud, sand or gravel. Depending on the features present (e.g., scattered stones, boulders with epifauna) and regional characteristics, mixed sediments can also be considered as reef structures (e.g., German Bight).

Characteristic species

Due to the quite variable nature of the sediment type, a widely variable array of communities may be found, including those characterised by bivalves (MB4233, MB4231), polychaetes (MB4232) and file shells (MB2221). This has resulted in many species being described as characteristic of this biotope complex all contributing only a small percentage to the overall similarity. This biotope is characterised by an undescribed *Chaetopterus* sp. and small *Lanice conchilega*.

MB421: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB422: Low-salinity seaweed communities typically include the kelp *Laminaria saccharina*, the bootlace weed *Chorda filum* and various red and brown seaweeds, particularly filamentous types. The generally sheltered nature of these habitats enables the seaweeds to grow on shells and small stones which lie on the sediment surface; some communities develop as loose-lying mats on the sediment surface. Beds of submerged or slightly emergent vascular vegetation of brackish seas, sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of mud or sand flats, and coastal lagoons (*Lamprothamnium papulosum*, *Chara aspera*, *Myriophyllum* spp.). Among the filamentous green algae, grazing molluscs and solitary ascidians may be present. Infauna may typically include *Corophium volutator*, *Heterochaeta costata*, *Tubificoides benedeni* and other taxa suited for low/variable salinity environments.

MB423: Fully or near fully marine animal-dominated communities of polychaetes, bivalves and file shells, with relatively low proportions of seaweeds. Also, sponges (*Esperiopsis fucorum*, *Haliclona oculata* and *Halichondria panicea*) and anemones (*Sagartia elegans*, *Cerianthus lloydii* and *Urticina felina*) and hydroids (*Hydrallmania falcata*) and the encrusting polychaete *Pomatoceros triqueter* are important. There is an extremely diverse epifaunal community.

MB424: Estuarine conditions, often with surface shells or stones, enabling the development of diverse epifaunal communities, e.g., *Crepidula fornicata* as well as infaunal communities. This habitat is rich in species, compared to purer sediments.

Associated species

Venerupis senegalensis, *Amphipholis squamata*, *Apseudes latreilli*, *Crepidula fornicata*. Associated fish species are *Ciliata mustela*, *Gadus morhua*, *Liparis*

liparis, Myoxocephalus scorpius, Pholis gunnellus, Scopthalmus maximus and Trisopterus luscus.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB52](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB521](#) and [MB522](#) in this report;

[MB523](#), [MB5231](#), [MB5232](#), [MB5233](#), [MB5234](#), [MB5235](#), [MB5236](#), [MB5237](#), [MB5238](#), [MB5239](#), [MB523A](#), [MB524](#), [MB5241](#), [MB5242](#), [MB5243](#)

IE:

=SS.SSa

DE:

#02.02.09

#02.02.10

#§ 30 "Sublitorale Sandbank"

MB52. Atlantic infralittoral sand

General description

This habitat type describes sands that occur in shallow water, either on the open coast or in tide-swept channels of marine inlets.

Characteristic species

MB521: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB522: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB523: Clean sands typically lack a significant seaweed component and is characterised by robust fauna, particularly amphipods (*Bathyporeia*) and robust polychaetes including *Nephtys cirrosa* and *Lanice conchilega*. Non-cohesive muddy sand (with 5% to 20% silt/clay) supports a variety of animal-dominated communities, particularly polychaetes (*Magelona mirabilis*, *Spiophanes bombyx* and *Chaetozone setosa*), bivalves (*Fabulina fibula* and *Chamelea gallina*) and the urchin *Echinocardium cordatum*.

MB524: Clean sands that occur in the upper reaches of marine inlets, especially estuaries, where water movement is moderately strong, allowing the sedimentation of sand but not the finer silt fraction. The habitat typically lacks a significant seaweed component and is characterised by brackish-water tolerant fauna, particularly amphipods, polychaetes and mysid shrimps.

Associated species

The polychaete *Capitella capitata* may occur frequently in some areas. Other taxa, such as the polychaetes *Eteone* spp. and *Arenicola marina*, the mysid *Neomysis integer* and the amphipods *Bathyporeia* spp. and *Haustorius arenarius*. *N. integer*, will most likely be found on the sediment surface or just above it, while *Gammarus* may be found under loose weed, stones or other detritus on the sediment surface.

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Raja clavate*, *Raja montagui*, *Scophthalmus maximus*, *Scophthalmus rhombus* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MB62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mud

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MB621](#) and

[MB622](#) in this report;

[MB623](#), [MB6231](#), [MB6232](#),

[MB624](#), [MB6241](#), [MB6242](#),

[MB6243](#), [MB6244](#), [MB6245](#),

[MB6246](#), [MB6247](#), [MB6248](#),

[MB6249](#), [MB624A](#), [MB624B](#),

[MB624C](#), [MB625](#), [MB6251](#),

[MB6252](#), [MB6253](#), [MB6254](#),

[MB6255](#), [MB6256](#), [MB6257](#),

[MB626](#), [MB627](#), [MB6271](#),

[MB6272](#)

OSPAR:

#Seapen and burrowing

megafauna

IE:

>SS.SMu.ISaMu

>SS.SMu.IFiMu

DE:

#02.02.11

#§ 30 "Schlickgründe mit

bohrender

Bodenmegafauna"

MB62. Atlantic infralittoral mud

General description

This habitat type describes shallow sublittoral muds, extending from the extreme lower shore to a depth of about 15-20m in fully marine or near marine conditions, predominantly in extremely sheltered areas with very weak tidal currents. Such habitats are found for example in sea lochs and some rias.

Characteristic species

MB621: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB622: See the description of this habitat in this report.

MB623: Beds of submerged or slightly emergent vascular vegetation of brackish seas, sea inlets, estuaries, permanent pools of mud or sand flats, and coastal lagoons (*Phragmites australis* reed beds, filamentous green algae and charophytes such as *Lamprothamnium papulosum* and *Chara aspera*, the freshwater quillwort *Myriophyllum* spp., *Stuckenia pectinata*).

MB624: Full salinity habitat in sheltered bays or marine inlets and along sheltered areas of open coast. Infralittoral, cohesive sandy mud, typically with over 20% silt/clay, have a rich variety of polychaetes including *Melinna palmata*, tube building amphipods (*Ampelisca* spp.) and deposit feeding bivalves such as *Macoma balthica* and *Mysella bidentata*. Sea pens such as *Virgularia mirabilis* and brittlestars such as *Amphiura* spp. may be present but not in the same abundances as found in deeper circalittoral waters. Mud with minimal sand content have populations of the lugworm *Arenicola marina* may be dense, with anemones, the opisthobranch *Philine aperta* and synaptid holothurians also characteristic in some areas. The extent of the oxidised layer may be shallow with some areas being periodically or permanently anoxic. In these areas bacterial mats may develop on the sediment surface. Infaunal records for this biotope complex are limited encompassing only one biotope. They are therefore not representative of the full suite of infaunal species found in this biotope.

MB625: Variable or reduced salinity habitat extending from the extreme lower shore into the subtidal in variable salinity (estuarine) conditions. Fauna: *Polydora ciliata*, *Corophium volutator*, *Pygospio elegans*, *Hediste diversicolor*, *Streblospio shrubsolii*, *Tubificoides benedii*, *Aphelochaeta* species, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Capitella capitata*, *Melinna palmata*, *Caulleriella zetlandica*, *Tharyx* spp., *Marenzelleria* sp., *Limecola balthica* (*Macoma balthica*), *Arenicola marina*, *Eteone longa*, *Gammarus zaddachi*, *Paranais litoralis*, *Heterochaeta costata*, *Arenicola marina* and *Carcinus maenas*.

Associated species

Associated fish species are: *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Raja clavate* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[OSPAR: Sea pen and burrowing megafauna.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC32](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral coarse sediment

[HD](#): #1110, #1160

[European Red List](#):

NEAA5.14 (vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC321](#), [MC3211](#), [MC3212](#), [MC3213](#), [MC3214](#), [MC3215](#), [MC3216](#)

IE:

=SS.SCS.CCS

DE:

#02.02.07, #02.02.08

#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

MC32. Atlantic circalittoral coarse sediment

General description

This habitat type describes tide-swept circalittoral coarse sands, gravel and shingle generally in depths of over 15-20m. This habitat may be found in tidal channels of marine inlets, along exposed coasts and offshore.

As with shallower coarse sediments, this habitat may be characterised by robust infaunal polychaetes, mobile crustacea and bivalves. Certain species of sea cucumber (e.g., *Neopentadactyla*) may also be prevalent in these areas along with the lancelet *Branchiostoma lanceolatum*.

Characteristic species

[MC3211](#): This biotope is characterised by a few ubiquitous robust and/or fast-growing ephemeral species which can colonise pebbles and unstable cobbles and slates which are regularly moved by wave and tidal action. The main cover organisms tend to be restricted to calcareous tube worms such as *Pomatoceros triqueter* (or *P. lamarcki*), small barnacles including *Balanus crenatus* and *Balanus balanus*, and a few bryozoan and coralline algal crusts. Scour action from the mobile substratum prevents colonisation by more delicate species. Occasionally in tide-swept conditions tufts of hydroids such as *Sertularia argentea* and *Hydrallmania falcata* are present. This biotope often grades into MC4214 which is characterised by large amounts of the above hydroids on stones also covered in *Pomatoceros* and barnacles. The main difference here is that MC4214, seems to develop on more stable, consolidated cobbles and pebbles or larger stones set in sediment in moderate tides. These stones may be disturbed in the winter and therefore long-lived and fragile species are not found. This biotope is found on exposed open coasts as well as at the entrance to marine inlets.

[MC3212](#): Circalittoral gravels, coarse to medium sands, and shell gravels, sometimes with a small amount of silt and generally in relatively deep water (generally over 15-20m deep), may be characterised by polychaetes such as *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Lumbrineris* spp., *Glycera lapidum* with the pea urchin *Echinocyamus pusillus*. Other taxa may include *Nemertea* spp., *Protodorvillea kefersteini*, *Owenia fusiformis*, *Spiophanes bombyx* and *Amphipholis squamata* along with amphipods such as *Ampelisca spinipes*. This biotope may also be characterised by the presence of conspicuous venerid bivalves, particularly *Timoclea ovata*. Other robust bivalve species such as *Moerella* spp., *Glycymeris glycymeris* and *Astarte sulcata* may also be found in this biotope. *Spatangus purpureus* may be present especially where the interstices of the gravel are filled by finer particles, in which case, *Gari tellinella* may also be prevalent (Glemarec 1973). Venerid bivalves are often under-sampled in benthic grab surveys and as such may not be conspicuous in many infaunal datasets. Such communities in gravelly sediments may be relatively species-rich, and they may also contain epifauna such as *Hydroides norvegicus* and *Pomatoceros lamarcki*. In sand wave areas this biotope may also contain elements of the MB5236 biotope, particularly *Magelona* species. This biotope has previously been described as the 'Deep Venus Community' and the 'Boreal Off-Shore Gravel Association' by other workers (Ford 1923; Jones 1950) and may also be part of the Venus community described by Thorson (1957) and in

the infralittoral étage described by Glemarec (1973). MC3212 may be quite variable over time and in fact may be closer to a biotope complex in which several biotopes or sub-biotopes may yet be defined. For example, Ford (1923) describes a 'Series A' and a 'Series B' characterised by *Echinocardium cordatum-Chamelea gallina* and *Spatangus purpurea-Clausinella fasciata*. Furthermore, mosaics of cobble and lag gravel often contain ridges of coarse gravelly sand, and these localised patches are also characterised by robust veneriid and similar bivalves including *Arcopagia crassa*, *Laevicardium crassum* et al. including *Glycymeris glycymeris* (E.I.S. Rees pers. comm. 2002). This high porosity fine gravel or coarse sand may be a separate biotope.

This biotope, and variants of it, make up a significant proportion of the offshore Irish Sea benthos (Mackie, Oliver & Rees 1995). Also, MC3212 may be quite variable over time.

MC3213: In coarse gravelly or shelly sand sometimes with a slight mud content, along open coasts in depths of 10 m to 30 m, and in shallower offshore areas, an impoverished community characterised by *Protodorvillea kefersteini* may be found. This biotope has several other species associated with it including *Nemertea* spp., *Caulleriella zetlandica*, *Minuspio cirrifera*, *Glycera lapidum*, *Ampelisca spinipes* and numerous other polychaete species all occurring at low abundances. The polychaete *Sabellaria spinulosa* is also found in low numbers in this biotope.

This biotope has been reported in the North Sea along the Norfolk/Lincolnshire coast, located in and around marine aggregate dredging areas (IECS, 1999). This biotope may be quite variable both spatially and temporally in terms of community structure and sediment type, which is often borderline between coarse sediments (and subunits) and mixed sediments (and subunits).

MC3214: Sublittoral plains of clean, shell, maerl and/or stone gravels or sometimes coarse sands, with frequent *Neopentadactyla mixta*. *Pecten maximus* may occur occasionally along with *Lanice conchilega*. Other epifaunal species may include *Ophiura albida*, *Pagurus* spp. and *Callionymus* spp. These sediments may be thrown into dunes by wave action or tidal streams. Widespread species such as *Cerianthus lloydii* and *Chaetopterus variopedatus* are present in many examples of this biotope. Scarcely recorded species such as *Molgula oculata*, *Ophiopsila annulosa* and *Amphiura securigera* may also be found. *O. annulosa* only occurs in records from the south-west of the British Isles. It should be noted that *Neopentadactyla* may exhibit periodicity in its projection out of, and retraction into, the sediment (Picton, 1993). This biotope may be an epibiotic overlay of unit MC3212.

This biotope may occur adjacent to maerl beds and, to some extent, in the lower infralittoral zone, where some seaweeds may occur in low abundances.

MC3215: Gravel and coarse sand with shell gravel often includes communities of robust venerid bivalves (MC3212). Shallower examples, such as the biotope presented here, may support a significant population of *Branchiostoma lanceolatum*. Other conspicuous infauna may include *Echinocyamus pusillus*, *Glycera lapidum*, *Polygordius*, *Pisone remota* and *Arcopagia crassa* (in the South of the UK). Sessile epifauna are typically a minor component of this community. This biotope has been described from a limited number of records and as such may need revising when further data become available.

This biotope is related to the 'Boreal Offshore Gravel Association' and 'Deep Venus Community' described by other workers (Ford 1923; Jones 1951) and may also be closely allied (the same?) as the ' *Venus fasciata* ' community of Cabioch (Glemarec 1973). This biotope may be an epibiotic overlay of the biotope MB3233 or MC3212.

MC3216: Scallops on Atlantic circalittoral shell gravel and sand with some sand scour.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Ammodytes marinus*, *Ammodytes tobianus* and/or *Hyperoplus lanceolatus* (dependent on specific grain size).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries, gravel extraction.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004. The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC42](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1160, #1170

European Red List:

>NEAAS.44, >NEAAS.45

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC421](#), [MC4211](#), [MC4212](#), [MC4213](#), [MC4214](#), [MC4215](#), [MC4216](#)

IE:

=SS.SMx.CMx

DE:

#02.02.06

#§ 30 "Riffe"

MC42. Atlantic circalittoral mixed sediment

General description

This habitat type describes mixed (heterogeneous) sediment habitats in the circalittoral zone (generally at depths below 15-20m) including well mixed muddy gravelly sands or very poorly sorted mosaics of shell, cobbles and pebbles embedded in or lying upon mud, sand or gravel. Circalittoral mixed sediments may be constituents of natural geogenic reefs with 5-90% coverage of hard substrata, such as rocks, blocks, solidified soft substrata (boulder clay, peat), or shell debris.

Due to the variable nature of the seabed, a variety of communities can develop, which are often very diverse. A wide range of infaunal polychaetes, bivalves, and amphipods are often present in such habitat and the presence of hard substrata (shells and stones) on the surface facilitates the establishment of epifaunal species, particularly turf-forming hydroids and bryozoans as well as anthozoans, such as *Metridium senile* and *Alcyonium digitatum*. In coastal waters, the sediment may be covered by epibenthic bivalves, such as *Mytilus edulis* and the non-indigenous *Magallana gigas*. In the absence of physical disturbance, reefs of the European oyster *Ostrea edulis* or the Ross worm *Sabellaria spinulosa* may develop. The combination of epifauna and infauna can lead to species-rich communities. However, mechanical disturbance may result in the absence of epifauna. Coarser mixed-sediment communities may show a strong resemblance, in terms of infauna, to biotopes within the sublittoral coarse sediment complex.

Characteristic species

The infauna species in mixed sediments are representatives of a variety of different sediment types covering the whole range from mud to gravel. Accordingly, no characterising infauna species of mixed sediments can be identified. Therefore, infauna species are listed as members of the typical communities only.

Depending on the specific composition of the mixed sediments and the combination of other habitat characteristic, the epibenthic bivalves *Magallana gigas*, *Mytilus edulis*, and *Ostrea edulis* as well as the Ross worm *Sabellaria spinulosa* may form biogenic reefs. On geogenic reef structures, species typically depending on hard substrata, such as the sponges *Halichondria panicea*, *Halisarca dujardini*, *Sycon ciliatum*, the calcareous tube-building polychaete *Spirobranchus triqueter*, as well as erect species, such as bryozoans (*Flustra foliacea*, *Alcyonidium diaphanum*), hydrozoans (*Kirchenpaueria pinnata*, *Plumularia setacea*, *Sertularia cupressina*), actinians (*Metridium senile*, *Urticina felina*, *Alcyonium digitatum*), and ascidians (*Ciona intestinalis*, *Clavelina lepadiformis*, *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Molgula* spp., *Styela* spp.) are characterising sessile species. When the mixed sediments are constituents of geogenic reefs, characterising mobile species are *Echinus esculentus*, *Cancer pagurus*, and *Necora pube*.

Associated species

The infaunal community depends largely on the dominant sand fraction. Mixed sediments are often dominated by coarse sediments and therefore species of the *Goniadella-Spisula* association such as *Aonides paucibranchiata*, *Branchiostoma lanceolatum*, *Spisula elliptica*, etc. are characterising. Also, medium sands to fine sands occur, and typical species may also be those species preferring those grain sizes (e.g., *Goodallia triangularis*, *Nephtys cirrosa* or *Scoloplos armiger*, *Magelona johnstoni*, *Fabulina fabula*, *Cerianthus lloydii*).

A typical epifauna community consists of decapod crustaceans (*Liocarcinus* spp., *Pagurus bernhardus*) and ascidians (*Ascidella aspersa*).

Fish species typically occurring on mixed sediments with scattered geogenic reef structures are the goldsinny wrasse (*Ctenolabrus rupestris*), cod (*Gadus morhua*), Shorthorn sculpin (*Myoxocephalus scorpius*), five-bearded rockling (*Ciliata mustela*), turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*) and the common seasnail (*Liparis liparis*).

Because of the considerable water depth, benthic feeding by seabirds is negligible on circalittoral mixed sediments.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat may be threatened by:

- Physical loss (due to permanent change of seabed substrate or morphology and to extraction of seabed substrate) because of the extraction of minerals (rock, metal ores, gravel, sand, shell).
- Temporary or reversible physical disturbance to the seabed due to restructuring of the seabed morphology, including dredging and the depositing of materials.
- Extraction of, or mortality/injury to, wild species by commercial and recreational fishing and other activities.
- Changes to hydrological conditions.
- Input or spread of non-indigenous species.
- Input of litter (solid waste matter, including micro-sized litter), carbohydrates and other pollutants.
- Input of nutrients — diffuse sources, point sources, atmospheric deposition.
- Climate change.
- Input of anthropogenic sound (impulsive, continuous) from renewable energy generation (wind, wave and tidal power), including infrastructure and shipping.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EEA, 2022c. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Red List in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[JNCC: Circalittoral mixed sediment.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC52](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

NEAA5.25 (endangered)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC521](#), [MC5211](#),

[MC5212](#), [MC5213](#), [MC5214](#),

[MC5215](#)

IE:

>SS.SSa.CFiSa

>SS.SSa.CMuSa

DE:

#02.02.10, #02.02.09

#§ 30 "Sublitorale

Sandbank"

MC52. Atlantic circalittoral sand

General description

This habitat type includes sand and muddy sand in the Atlantic circalittoral zone. It includes clean fine sands with less than 5% silt/clay in deeper water which is characterised by a wide range of echinoderms (in some areas including the pea urchin *Echinocyamus pusillus*), polychaetes and bivalves. This habitat is generally more stable than shallower, infralittoral sands and consequently supports a more diverse community.

Also, circalittoral non-cohesive muddy sands with the silt content of the substratum typically ranging from 5% to 20% supports animal-dominated communities characterised by a wide variety of polychaetes, bivalves such as *Abra alba* and *Nucula nitidosa*, and echinoderms such as *Amphiura* spp. and *Ophiura* spp., and *Astropecten irregularis*. These circalittoral habitats tend to be more stable than their infralittoral counterparts and as such support a richer infaunal community.

Clean fine sands with less than 5% silt/clay in deeper water is characterised by a wide range of echinoderms (in some areas including the pea urchin *Echinocyamus pusillus*), polychaetes and bivalves. This habitat is generally more stable than shallower, infralittoral sands and consequently supports a more diverse community.

Circalittoral non-cohesive muddy sands with the silt content of the substratum typically ranging from 5% to 20% supports animal-dominated communities characterised by a wide variety of polychaetes, bivalves such as *Abra alba* and *Nucula nitidosa*, and echinoderms such as *Amphiura* spp. and *Ophiura* spp., and *Astropecten irregularis*. These circalittoral habitats tend to be more stable than their infralittoral counterparts and as such support a richer infaunal community.

Characteristic species

MC5211: Circalittoral and offshore medium to fine sand (from depths of 40 m to 140 m) is characterised by the pea urchin *Echinocyamus pusillus*, the polychaete *Ophelia borealis* and the bivalve *Abra prismatica*. Other species may include the polychaetes *Spiophanes bombyx*, *Pholoe* sp., *Exogone* spp., *Sphaerosyllis bulbosa*, *Goniada maculata*, *Chaetozone setosa*, *Owenia fusiformis*, *Glycera lapidum*, *Lumbrineris latreilli* and *Aricidea cerrutii* and the bivalves *Thracia phaseolina* and *Moerella pygmaea* and to a lesser extent *Spisula elliptica* and *Timoclea ovata*. This biotope has been found in the central and Northern North Sea.

MC5212: In circalittoral and offshore medium to fine sands at depths of between 25 m and 100 m, a community characterised by the bivalve *Abra prismatica*, the amphipod *Bathyporeia elegans* and polychaetes such as *Scoloplos armiger*, *Spiophanes bombyx*, *Aonides paucibranchiata*, *Chaetozone setosa*, *Ophelia borealis* and *Nephtys longosetosa* may be found. Crustacea such as the cumacean *Eudorellopsis deformis* and the opheliid polychaetes such as *Ophelia borealis*, *Travisia forbesii* or *Ophelina neglecta* are often present in this biotope and the brittlestar *Amphiura filiformis* may also be

common at some sites. This biotope has been reported in the central and Northern North Sea (Basford and Eleftheriou, 1989; Kunitzer et al., 1992).

MC5213: Medium to very fine sand, at a depth of 100-120 m, with polychaetes *Spiophanes kroyeri*, *Amphipectene auricoma*, *Myriochele* sp., *Aricidea wassi* and amphipods *Harpinia antennaria*.

MC5214: Non-cohesive muddy sands or slightly shelly/gravelly muddy sand characterised by the bivalves *Abra alba* and *Nucula nitidosa*. Other important taxa include *Nephtys* spp., *Chaetozone setosa* and *Spiophanes bombyx* with *Fabulina fabula* also common in many areas. The echinoderms *Ophiura albida* and *Asterias rubens* may also be present. The epibiotic biotope MB5235 may overlap this biotope. This biotope is part of the *Abra* community defined by Thorson (1957) and the infralittoral étage described by Glemarec (1973).

MC5215: In shallow, circalittoral non-cohesive muddy sand (typically less than 20% silt/clay), abundant populations of the brittlestar *Amphiura brachiata* may occur with other echinoderms such as *Astropecten irregularis*, *Asterias rubens*, *Ophiura ophiura* and *Echinocardium cordatum*. Other infaunal species typically include *Mysella bidentata*, *Lanice conchilega* and *Magelona filiformis*. This biotope is likely to form part of the non-cohesive/cohesive muddy sand communities, which make up the 'offshore muddy sand association' described by other workers (Jones 1951; Mackie 1990). It is possible that in some areas this biotope forms an epifaunal overlay which may cover a range of biotopes in years of good recruitment but does not develop into a settled or established community.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Raja clavate*, *Raja montagui*, *Scophthalmus maximus*, *Scophthalmus rhombus* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries, sand extraction.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MC62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mud

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

NEAA5.35 (endangered),

NEAA5.36 (endangered)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MC622](#) in this

report; [MC621](#), [MC6211](#),

[MC6212](#), [MC6213](#), [MC6214](#),

[MC62141](#), [MC6215](#),

[MC6216](#), [MC62161](#),

[MC6217](#), [MC6218](#), [MC6219](#)

OSPAR:

>Sea Pen and burrowing
megafauna communities

IE:

>SS.SMu.CSaMu

>SS.SMu.CFiMu

DE:

#02.02.11

#§ 30 "Schlickgründe mit
bohrender Megafauna"

MC62. Atlantic circalittoral mud

General description

This habitat type includes circalittoral, cohesive sandy mud, typically with over 20% silt/clay, generally in water depths of over 10m, with weak or very weak tidal streams. This habitat is generally found in deeper areas of bays and marine inlets or offshore from less wave exposed coasts. Sea pens such as *Virgularia mirabilis* and brittlestars such as *Amphiura* spp. are particularly characteristic of this habitat while infaunal species include the tube building polychaetes *Lagis koreni* and *Owenia fusiformis*, and deposit feeding bivalves such as *Mysella bidentata* and *Abra* spp.

Characteristic species

The sea pens *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea* occur in this biotope complex, together with the burrowing anemone *Cerianthus lloydii* and the ophiuroid *Amphiura* spp. The relatively stable conditions often lead to the establishment of communities of burrowing megafaunal species, such as *Nephrops norvegicus*.

MC621: Sublittoral muds, occurring below moderate depths of 15-20m, either on the open coast or in marine inlets such as sea lochs. The seapens *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea* are characteristic of this habitat type together with the burrowing anemone *Cerianthus lloydii* and the ophiuroid *Amphiura* spp. The relatively stable conditions often lead to the establishment of communities of burrowing megafaunal species, such as *Nephrops norvegicus*.

MC6211: Cohesive sandy mud off wave exposed coasts with weak tidal streams can be characterised by super-abundant *Amphiura filiformis* with *Mysella bidentata* and *Abra nitida*. This community occurs in muddy sands in moderately deep water (Hiscock 1984; Picton et al. 1994) and may be related to the 'offshore muddy sand association' described by other workers (Jones 1951; Thorson 1957; Mackie 1990) and is part of the infralittoral étage described by Glemarec. This community is also characterised by the sipunculid *Thysanocardia procera* and the polychaetes *Nephtys incisa*, *Phoronis* sp. and *Pholoe* sp., with cirratulids also common in some areas. Other taxa, such as *Nephtys hombergii*, *Echinocardium cordatum*, *Nucula nitidosa*, *Callianassa subterranea* and *Eudorella truncatula*, may also occur in offshore examples of this biotope (e.g., Künitzer et al. 1992).

MC6212: Circalittoral cohesive sandy muds with small quantities of gravel, off sheltered or moderately exposed coasts may support populations characterised by *Thyasira* spp. and in particular *Thyasira flexuosa*. Other characteristic taxa may include *Nuculoma tenuis*, *Goniada maculate* and in some areas *Rhodine gracilior*. *Mysella bidentata*, *Abra alba*, *Harpinia antennaria* and *Amphiura filiformis* may be abundant in some examples of this biotope. While moderately diverse, animal abundances are often low and it is possible that the biotope is the result of sedimentary disturbance e.g., from trawling and is possibly an impoverished version of MC6213. Collectively the biotopes MB6248, MC6212, MC6213 and MD5212, may form the *Amphiura* dominated components of the 'offshore muddy sand association' described

by other workers (Jones 1951; Thorson 1957; Mackie 1990) and the infralittoral étage described by Glemarec (1973).

MC6213: In cohesive and non-cohesive sandy mud, off moderately exposed coasts in deep water dense populations of *Amphiura filiformis* with the bivalve *Nuculoma tenuis* may occur. This biotope together with MB6248, MC6212 and MD5212 may be part of the *Amphiura filiformis* dominated infralittoral étage described by Glemarec (1973) and part of the 'offshore muddy sand association' described by other workers (Jones 1951; Mackie 1990). Other species characteristic of this biotope may include the echinoderms *Ophiura albida* and *Echinocardium flavescens* and the bivalve *Mysella bidentata*. *Phaxas pellucidus*, *Owenia fusiformis* and *Virgularia mirabilis* may also be present. At the sediment surface the hydroid *Sertularia argentea* may be present although only at very low abundances. Variations of this biotope exist in the Northern North Sea, and it is possible that more than one entity exists for this biotope.

MC6214: Circalittoral fine sandy mud may contain *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Ophiura* spp. A variety of species may occur, and species composition at a particular site may relate, to some extent, to the proportions of the major sediment size fractions. Several species are common to most sites including *Virgularia mirabilis* which is present in moderate numbers, *Ophiura albida* and *Ophiura ophiura* which are often quite common, and *Pecten maximus* which is usually only present in low numbers. *Virgularia mirabilis* is usually accompanied by occasional *Cerianthus lloydii*, *Liocarcinus depurator* and *Pagurus bernhardus*. *Amphiura chiajei* and *Amphiura filiformis* may occur in some examples of this biotope. Polychaetes and bivalves are generally the main components of the infauna, although the nemerteans, *Edwardsia claparedii*, *Phoronis muelleri* and *Labidoplax buski* may also be widespread. Of the polychaetes *Goniada maculata*, *Nephtys incisa*, *Minuspio cirrifera*, *Chaetozone setosa*, *Notomastus latericeus* and *Owenia fusiformis* are often the most widespread species while *Myrtea spinifera*, *Lucinoma borealis*, *Mysella bidentata*, *Abra alba* and *Corbula gibba* are typical bivalves in this biotope. This biotope is primarily identified on the basis of its epifauna and may be an epibiotic overlay over other closely related biotopes such as MC6216, MB6248 and MC6213. Such sediments are very common in sea lochs, often occurring shallower than the finest mud or in somewhat more exposed parts of the lochs.

MC6215: In stable circalittoral sandy mud, dense populations of the tube building polychaete *Lagis koreni* may occur. Other species found in this habitat typically include bivalves such as *Phaxas pellucidus*, *Mysella bidentata* and *Abra alba* and polychaetes such as *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Spiophanes bombyx*, *Owenia fusiformis* and *Scalibregma inflatum*. At the sediment surface, easily visible fauna includes *Lagis koreni* and *Ophiura ophiura*. *Lagis koreni* is an important source of food for commercially important demersal fish, especially dab and plaice (Macer, 1967; Lockwood, 1980 and Basimi & Grove, 1985).

As for temporal variation, in some areas, e.g., Liverpool Bay, MC5214 and MC6215 have exhibited cyclical behaviour with the community periodically switching from one biotope to another-possibly in relation to dredge spoil disposal (Rees et al. 1992) along with other environmental and biological factors. Both *Lagis koreni* and *Phaxas pellucidus*, can tolerate sudden increases in the deposition of sediment and often dominate such areas following such an event. Indeed, it is likely that the two biotopes are merely

different aspects of the same community as *Lagis koreni* is often recorded with high densities of *Abra alba* (Eagle 1975; Rees and Walker 1983). Densities of mature populations of *L. koreni* may exceed 1,000 per square metre.

MC6217: In circalittoral stable mud distinctive populations of megafauna may be found. These typically include *Nephrops norvegicus*, *Calocaris macandreae* and *Callianassa subterranea*. Large mounds formed by the echinuran *Maxmuelleria lankesteri* are also frequent in this biotope. The seapen *Virgularia mirabilis* may occur occasionally in this biotope but not in the same abundance as MC6216 to which MC6217 is closely allied. Infaunal species may include *Nephtys hystricis*, *Chaetozone setosa*, *Amphiura chiajei* and *Abra alba*.

MC6218: Mud in deep offshore, or shallower stable nearshore, waters can be characterised by the urchin *Brissopsis lyrifera* and the brittle star *Amphiura chiajei*. Where intense benthic dredge fishing activity occurs, populations of the indicator species, *Brissopsis lyrifera* may be depressed, although broken tests may still remain (E.I.S. Rees pers. comm. 1997; M. Costello pers. comm. 1997). Low numbers of the seapen *Virgularia mirabilis* may be found in many examples of this biotope. In addition, in certain areas of the UK, such as the Northern Irish Sea, this community may also contain *Nephrops norvegicus* and can consequently be the focus for fishing activity (Mackie, Oliver & Rees 1995). Infaunal species in this community are similar to those found in MC6216 and include the polychaetes *Nephtys hystricis*, *Pectinaria belgica*, *Glycera* spp. and *Lagis koreni* and the bivalves *Myrtea spinifera* and *Nucula sulcata*. This community is the 'Boreal Offshore Mud Association' and 'Brissopsis-Chiajei' communities described by other workers (Petersen 1918; Jones 1950).

MC6219: Sublittoral soft anoxic mud, often in areas with poor water exchange with the open sea, can have a conspicuous bacterial mat covering of *Beggiatoa* spp. The anoxia may be a result of natural conditions of poor water exchange in some sea lochs (and many Scandinavian fjords) or artificially under fish farm cages from nutrient enrichment. The fauna is normally impoverished at such sites, with few elements of the infaunal communities present in other muddy biotopes. Scavenging species such as *Asterias rubens* and *Carcinus maenas* are typically present where the habitat is not too anoxic along with occasional *Arenicola marina*, but in extreme conditions of anoxia little survives other than the *Beggiatoa*. The polychaete *Ophiodromus flexuosus* occurs in high densities at the interface between oxygenated and deoxygenated sediments (in Norwegian fjords).

Associated species

MC62161: Seapens, including *Funiculina quadrangularis*, and burrowing megafauna in undisturbed Atlantic circalittoral fine mud.

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Enchelyopus cimbrius*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Raja clavate* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[OSPAR: Sea pen burrowing megafauna.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD32](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment
[European Red List](#):
NEA5.15 (vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD321](#), [MD3211](#), [MD3212](#)

OSPAR: #*Modiolus modiolus* beds

IE:
=SS.SCS.OCS

DE:
#02.02.07
#02.02.08
#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

MD32. Atlantic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

General description

This habitat type describes offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with coarse sands and gravel or shell. This habitat may cover large areas of the offshore continental shelf although there is relatively little quantitative data available. Such habitats are quite diverse compared to shallower versions of this habitat and generally characterised by robust infaunal polychaete and bivalve species. Animal communities in this habitat are closely related to offshore mixed sediments and, in some areas, settlements of *Modiolus modiolus* larvae may occur; consequently, these habitats may occasionally have large numbers of juvenile *M. modiolus*. In areas where the mussels reach maturity their byssus threads bind the sediment together, increasing stability and allowing an increased deposition of silt.

Characteristic species

[MD3211](#): Offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with coarse sands and gravel, stone or shell and, occasionally, a little silt (<5%) may be characterised by the polychaetes *Glycera lapidum* and *Amythasides macroglossus* with the bivalve *Thyasira* spp. (particularly *Thyasira succisa*). Other taxa include polychaetes such as *Exogone verugera*, *Notomastus latericeus*, *Spiophanes kroyeri*, *Aphelochaeta marioni* (*Tharyx marioni*) and *Lumbrineris gracilis* and occasional numbers of the bivalve *Timoclea ovata*. This biotope bears some resemblance to the shallow MB3235 and to the circalittoral and offshore venerid biotopes (units MC3212 and MD4211) but differs by the range of polychaete and bivalve fauna present. This biotope is notable for the presence of the rarely recorded ampharetid polychaete *Amythasides macroglossus* and for the small ear file clam *Limatula subauriculata* which is common in some examples of this biotope.

[MD3212](#): Offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with coarse sand may support populations of the interstitial polychaete *Hesionura elongata* with *Protodorvillea kefersteini*. Other notable species include the phyllodocid polychaete *Protomystides limbata* and the bivalve *Moerella pygmaea*.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Ammodytes marinus* and/or *Hyperoplus lanceolatus* (dependent on specific grain size) and *Scophthalmus maximus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries, seabed mining.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[OSPAR: *Modiolus modiolus* beds.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD42](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment
HD: #1170

[European Red List](#):
NEAA5.45 (vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD421](#), [MD4211](#)

IE:
=SS.SMx.OMx

DE:
#02.02.06
#§ 30 "Riffe"

MD42. Atlantic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

General description

This habitat type describes offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with slightly muddy mixed gravelly sand and stones or shell. This habitat may cover large areas of the offshore continental shelf, although there is relatively little data available. Such habitats are often highly diverse, with a high number of infaunal polychaete and bivalve species. Depending on the features present (e.g., scattered stones, boulders with epifauna) and regional characteristics, offshore mixed sediments can also be considered as reef structures (e.g., German Bight).

Characteristic species

[MD421](#): Such habitats are often highly diverse, with a high number of infaunal polychaete and bivalve species. Animal communities in this habitat are closely related to offshore gravels and coarse sands and, in some areas, populations of the horse mussel *Modiolus modiolus* may develop in these habitats

[MD4211](#): In offshore circalittoral slightly muddy mixed sediments, a diverse community particularly rich in polychaetes, with a significant venerid bivalve component, may be found. Typical species include the polychaetes *Glycera lapidum*, *Aonides paucibranchiata*, *Laonice bahusiensis*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Lumbrineris gracilis*, *Pseudomystides limbata*, *Protomystides bidentata* and syllid species and bivalves such as *Timoclea ovata*, *Glycymeris glycymeris*, *Spisula elliptica* and *Goodallia triangularis*. This biotope has been recorded on surveys of the Lambay and Codling Deeps and other areas of the Irish Sea and collectively with MC3212 comprise the 'Deep Venus Community' and the 'Boreal Off-Shore Gravel Association' as defined by other workers (Ford 1923; Jones 1950). Some examples of this biotope may have abundant juvenile *Modiolus modiolus*.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Gadus morhua*, *Myoxocephalus Scorpius*, *Scophthalmus maximus* and *Trisopterus luscus*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries, seabed mining.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD52](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore circalittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

NEAAS.25 (endangered)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MD521](#), [MD5211](#),

[MD5212](#)

IE:

=SS.SSa.OSa

DE:

#02.02.10, #02.02.09

#§ 30 "Sublitorale

Sandbank"

MD52. Atlantic offshore circalittoral sand

General description

This habitat type describes Atlantic offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with fine sands or non-cohesive muddy sands. Although very little data are available on these habitats, they are likely to be more stable than their shallower counterparts, and to be characterised by a diverse range of polychaetes, amphipods, bivalves and echinoderms.

Characteristic species

MD5211: In deep offshore sand or non-cohesive muddy sand, dense populations of maldanid polychaetes such as *Maldane sarsi* and the cumacean *Eudorellopsis deformis* may be found. Accompanying these species are abundant ophiuroids including *Amphiura filiformis*, polychaetes such as *Terebellidae* sp., *Chaetozone setosa*, *Levinsenia gracilis*, *Scoloplos armiger*, the amphipod *Harpinia antennaria* and the bivalves *Nuculoma tenuis* and *Parvicardium minimum*. This biotope is similar to the *Maldane sarsi*-*Ophiura sarsi* community defined by Glemarec (1973).

MD5212: Areas of slightly muddy sand (generally <20% mud) in offshore waters may be characterised by high numbers of the tube building polychaete *Owenia fusiformis* often with the brittlestar *Amphiura filiformis*. While *O. fusiformis* is also found in other circalittoral or offshore biotopes it usually occurs in lower abundances than in MD5212. Other species found in this community are the polychaetes *Goniada maculata*, *Pholoe inornata*, *Diplocirrus glaucus*, *Chaetozone setosa* and *Spiophanes kroyeri* with occasional bivalves such as *Timoclea ovata* and *Thyasira equalis*. The sea cucumber *Labidoplax buski* and the cumacean *Eudorella truncatula* are also commonly often found in this biotope.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Raja clavate*, *Raja montagui*, *Scophthalmus maximus*, *Scophthalmus rhombus* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries, seabed mining.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MD62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Offshore circalittoral mud

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List:

NEAAS.25 (endangered)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MD621](#), [MD6211](#),

[MD6212](#), [MD6213](#),

[MD6214](#), [MD6215](#),

[MD6216](#), [MD62161](#),

[MD6217](#), [MD6218](#),

[MD6219](#), [MD621A](#)

OSPAR:

#Sea Pen and burrowing megafauna

IE:

=SS.SMu.OMu

DE:

#02.02.11

#§ 30 "Schlickgründe mit bohrender Megafauna"

MD62. Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud

General description

This habitat type describes Atlantic sublittoral muds, occurring below moderate depths of 15-20m, either on the open coast or in marine inlets such as sea lochs.

MD621: The seapens *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea* occur in this habitat type, together with the burrowing anemone *Cerianthus lloydii* and the ophiuroid *Amphiura* spp. The relatively stable conditions often lead to the establishment of communities of burrowing megafaunal species, such as *Nephrops norvegicus*.

Characteristic species

MD6211: *Lumbrineris fragilis*, *Levinsenia gracilis* and *Eriopisa elongata*.

MD6212: *Macoma calcarean*.

MD6213: *Ampharete falcata* turf with *Parvicardium ovale* near margins of deep stratified seas.

MD6214: Foraminiferans and *Thyasira* spp.

MD6215: *Styela gelatinosa*, *Pseudamussium septemradiatum* and solitary ascidians e.g., *Ascidia conchilega*, *Corella parallelogramma* and *Ascidiella* spp.

MD6216: *Capitella capitata* and *Thyasira* spp. and sometimes *Pholoe inornata*, *Lagis koreni*, *Philine scabra*, *Anaitides groenlandica*, *Mediomastus fragilis* and *Paramphinome jeffreysii*.

MD6217: *Levinsenia gracilis* and *Heteromastus filiformis*. Other important taxa may include *Paramphinome jeffreysii*, *Nephtys hystericis* and *N. incisa*, *Spiophanes kroyeri*, *Orbinia norvegica*, *Terebellides stroemi*, *Thyasira gouldi* and *Thyasira equalis*. Burrowing megafauna such as *Calocaris macandreae* may also be found in this biotope. This biotope has been found in the central and Northern North Sea. A similar community, dominated by *L. gracilis* but accompanied by *Glycera* spp. (particularly *Glycera rouxii*) and *Monticellina dorsobranchialis*, has also been reported from the Irish Sea. This Irish community also includes *Calocaris macandreae*, *Mediomastus fragilis*, *Tubificoides amplivasatus*, *Nephtys incisa*, *Ancistrosyllis groenlandica*, *Nucula sulcata*, *Litocorsa stremma* and *Minuspio* sp., and it is not known at present whether this represents a separate biotope or whether it is a geographic variant of a wider *Levinsenia* biotope.

MD6218: *Paramphinome jeffreysii*, *Thyasira* spp. and *Amphiura filiformis*. Other taxa may include *Laonice cirrata*, the sea cucumber *Labidoplax buski* and the polychaetes *Goniada maculata*, *Spiophanes kroyeri* and *Aricidea catherinae*. *Amphiura chiajei* may be occasional in this biotope, as may *Philine scabra*, *Levinsenia gracilis* and *Pholoe inornata*.

MD6219: *Myrtea spinifera* and polychaetes. Polychaetes typically include *Chaetozone setosa*, *Paramphinome jeffreysii*, *Levinsenia gracilis*, *Aricidea catherinae* and *Prionospio malmgreni*. The bivalves *Thyasira* spp. and *Abra nitida* may also be found as may seapens, such as *Pennatula phosphorea*.

MD621A: Sublittoral soft anoxic mud, often in areas with poor water exchange with the open sea, can have a conspicuous bacterial mat covering of *Beggiatoa* spp.

Associated species

Associated fish species are *Agonus cataphractus*, *Arnoglossus laterna*, *Buglossidium luteum*, *Callionymus lyra*, *Chelidonichthys lucerna*, *Enchelyopus cimbrius*, *Eutrigla gurnardus*, *Limanda limanda*, *Merlangius merlangus*, *Raja clavate* and *Solea solea*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Bottom trawling fisheries.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[OSPAR: Sea pen burrowing megafauna.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME32](#)
EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
MSFD: <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [ME322](#) in this report; [ME321](#), [ME3211](#), [ME3212](#), [ME3213](#), [ME3214](#), [ME3215](#)

IE:
=M.AtUB.Co

ME32. Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment

General description

Little is currently known about the infaunal community structure of this habitat type. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse mobile species or burrowing fauna such as anemones visible at the surface.

In the absence of ecological data, coarse sediment habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between coarse sediment and mixed sediment using video data only. Note that mixed sediment has a greater mud content than coarse sediment. If sediment particles are large enough to be classed as gravel using the Folk classification, then sediment would be classed as coarse sediment rather than sand. If sand contains a high enough percentage of gravel, it is also classed as coarse sediment. Coral rubble is classed as coarse sediment. Stable pebbles, cobbles and boulders are classed as rock; any rock present on coarse sediment is considered a separate habitat within a mosaic.

Characteristic species

[ME321](#) and [ME3211](#): Crinoid assemblages (e.g., *Leptometra celtica*) are found typically in areas with higher current speeds that facilitate filter feeding, such as the shelf edge and heads of canyons.

[ME3212](#): Biotope comprising cup coral *Caryophyllia smithii* and anemone *Actinauge richardi* attached to small pieces of hard material in the sediment. This assemblage is observed on the shallow parts of Rockall Bank on sand with some gravel/pebble component.

[ME3213](#): Pale encrusting sponge and serpulid assemblages.

[ME3214](#): Squat lobster assemblage. This biotope describes the fringing rubble apron of cold-water coral mounds or accumulations of gravel size *Lophelia pertusa* skeleton.

[ME3215](#): Cidarid urchin assemblage.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME42](#)
EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME421](#), [ME4211](#), [ME422](#), [ME4221](#)

IE:
=M.AtUB.Mx

ME42. Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment

General description

Little is currently known about the infaunal community structure of this habitat type. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse mobile species.

In the absence of ecological data, mixed sediment habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. Note that only small amounts of gravel are required to move the habitat from mud to mixed sediment and only small amounts of mud can move the habitat from coarse to mixed sediment. In the absence of particle size data, it can be difficult to reliably distinguish between coarse sediment and mixed sediment. Note that stable pebbles, cobbles and boulders are classed as rock; any rock present on mixed sediment is considered a separate habitat within a mosaic.

Characteristic species

[ME421](#) and [ME4211](#): This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of xenophyophores (*Syringamina fragilissima*). Associated species will vary with depth and sediment type but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges and sediment dwelling anemones.

[ME422](#): This broad community includes assemblages where sponges dominate sediment habitats. Sponges can be of all morphotypes except encrusting. Aggregations of the *Geodia* species with other massive forms are typical of Atlanto-Arctic upper bathyal coarse or mixed sediment. Associated species are likely to differ on different sediment types.

[ME4221](#): This biotope has been found at approximately 500m on the eastern slopes of the Faroe-Shetland Channel, it principally consists of rather small sponge specimens but that practically carpet the seafloor. Large sponges (tens of centimetres in diameter) are however common (*Geodia* spp.). The area where the community is observed experiences temperature fluctuations between <0°C to >8°C and heightened current speeds as a result of internal tides between the Arctic and Atlantic. This assemblage is also known as Boreal Ostur. The same assemblage was recorded on sand substrate, but associated infaunal species are likely to differ.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME52](#)
EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
MSFD: <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME521](#), [ME5211](#), [ME5212](#), [ME5213](#), [ME522](#)

IE:
=M.AtUB.Sa

ME52. Atlantic upper bathyal sand

General description

In this habitat type, deep-sea sand sediments have a diverse infaunal community dominated by polychaetes. Epifauna tends to be sparse and include mobile species or burrowing fauna such as anemones and brittlestars visible at the surface.

In the absence of ecological data, sand habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between mud and sand using video data only. Note that muddy sand sediments are classed as mud if the mud content is great enough. If sediment particles are large enough to be classed as gravel using the Folk classification, then sediment would be classed as coarse sediment rather than sand. If sand contains a high enough percentage of gravel, it is also classed as coarse sediment.

Characteristic species

ME5211: This biotope consists of dense aggregations of the crinoid *Leptometra celtica* on sand in the upper bathyal. It occurs at the shelf edge and in the heads of canyons. It is likely that the fast currents associated with the heads of canyon systems provide a favourable habitat for suspension feeding organisms such as crinoids. The same assemblage has been recorded in the mid bathyal on various substrate types; however, any associated species are likely to differ. The characterising species listed refer to all *Leptometra celtica* assemblages, and not to just those found associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

ME5212: This biotope is characterised by sparse and, occasionally, aggregated Cidarid urchins on sand substrates. The same epifaunal assemblage is also found on coarse sediment and in the mid bathyal but associated infauna are likely to differ. The characterising species listed refer to all Cidarid urchins' assemblages, and not to just those found associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

ME5213: This biotope consists of aggregations of *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* (previously *Echinus acutus norvegicus*) on sand substrate. The same epifaunal assemblage is also found on mud and sand in the mid and lower bathyal but associated infauna are likely to differ. Gage (1986) reports this assemblage from depths of 700m to 1,400m on the pelagic ooze, and suggests that it is present in a ribbon-like distribution around the continental margin of Europe down to a depth of about 1,400m. Le Danois also describes this assemblage from a depth of 150m to more than 500m, but emphasises that, in areas with a depth shallower than 500 m, *Spatangus raschi* dominates, while at depths below 500m *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* dominates. The characterising species listed refer to all *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* assemblages, and not to just those found to be associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

Associated species

All infaunal communities in the deep-sea are dominated by polychaete species with a diverse range of other taxa including bivalves, amphipods and sipunculids.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal sand.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [ME62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [ME621](#), [ME6211](#),

[ME6212](#), [ME622](#), [ME6221](#),

[ME623](#), [ME6231](#), [ME624](#),

[ME6241](#), [ME625](#), [ME6251](#),

[ME626](#)

IE:

=M.AtUB.Mu

ME62. Atlantic upper bathyal mud

General description

Deep-sea mud sediments have a diverse infaunal community dominated by polychaetes. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse, mobile species, but aggregations of erect fauna such as glass sponges, sea pens and soft corals can occur.

In the absence of ecological data, mud habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between mud and sand using video data only. Note that muddy sand sediments are classed as mud if the mud content is great enough.

Characteristic species

ME621: This broad community consisting of assemblages characterised by brittle stars (ophiuroids) that bury into soft sediments with the tips of the arms visible at the surface. Species may differ with depth and sediment type, but it was not possible to identify to species level using the video data available.

ME6211: This biotope is characterised by burrowing anemones (*Cerianthidae*), unidentified hydroids (*Hydrozoa*) and unidentified tube worms (*Sabellidae*) on bioturbated mud with phytodetritus. Video observations suggest there are many large burrows supporting associated unknown megafauna, the rare occurrence of sea pens (*Virgularia mirabilis*) and stalked sponges (*Hyalonema*) associated with this biotope.

ME6212: This biotope consists of aggregations of *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* (previously *Echinus acutus norvegicus*) on mud substrate. Gage (1986) reports this assemblage from depths of 700 m to 1,400 m on the pelagic ooze, and suggests it is present in a ribbon-like distribution around the continental margin of Europe down to depths of about 1,400 m. Le Danois also describes this assemblage from depths of 150 m to more than 500m, but emphasises that in areas that are shallower than 500 m *Spatangus raschi* dominates, while *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* dominates depths below 500 m. The same epifaunal assemblage is also found on sand and in the lower bathyal zone, but associated infauna is likely to differ. The characterising species listed refer to all *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* assemblages, and not to just those found associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

ME622 and ME6221: Dense aggregations of sea pens on fine sediments. The species composition will vary with depth and location. The seapens *Kophobelemnon* spp. (*Kophobelemnon stelliferum*) has been recorded in the Atlantic upper and mid bathyal mud and sand, but associated species are likely to differ with zone and substrate type.

ME623 and ME6231: This broad community includes assemblages where sponges dominate sediment habitats (e.g., *Pheronema carpenteri*). Sponges can be of all morphotypes except encrusting. Aggregations of the glass sponge

Pheronema carpenleri have been recorded on the Atlantic mid to lower bathyal mud. Associated species are likely to differ with depth.

ME624 and ME6241: Dense aggregations of erect soft corals occurring on fine sediments (e.g., Isidid octocoral *Acanella arbuscula* on sandy silts and fine-grained oozes). The species composition (e.g., *Acanella arbuscula*) will vary with depth and location. This broad community is functionally similar to sea pen fields.

ME625 and ME6251: This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of xenophyophores (e.g., *Syringammina fragilissima*). Associated species will vary with depth and sediment type, but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges and sediment dwelling anemones.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic upper bathyal mud.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF32](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF321](#), [MF3211](#), [MF322](#), [MF323](#), [MF3231](#)

IE:
=M.AtLB.Co

MF32. Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment

General description

Deep-sea coarse sediment has not been sampled widely for infauna; therefore, little is currently known about infaunal community structure. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse, mobile species or burrowing fauna such as anemones visible at the surface.

In the absence of ecological data, coarse sediment habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between coarse sediment and mixed sediment using video data only. Note that mixed sediment has a greater mud content than coarse sediment. If sediment particles are large enough to be classed as gravel using the Folk classification, then sediment would be classed as coarse sediment rather than sand. If sand contains a high enough percentage of gravel, it is also classed as coarse sediment. Coral rubble is classed as coarse sediment. Stable pebbles, cobbles and boulders are classed as rock; any rock present on coarse sediment is considered a separate habitat within a mosaic.

Characteristic species

[MF321](#) and [MF3211](#): This broad community includes those biotopes where corals dominate but do not form a living coral reef. A mixture of different coral types can be present (e.g., *Solenosmilia variabilis*). Associated species are similar to 'sparse encrusting community', including sponges and ophiuroids. On the Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment, discrete colonies of *Solenosmilia* attach to coral rubble.

[MF322](#): This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of solitary cup corals (*Caryophylliidae* and/or *Flabellidae*) on sediments including mud and sandy mud and coarse sediments. The species composition of the biotopes belonging to this broad community will vary with depth and location, and associated species will vary with sediment type.

[MF323](#) and [MF3231](#): This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of xenophyophores (e.g., *Syringammina fragilissima*). Associated species will vary with depth and sediment type but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges and sediment dwelling anemones.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal coarse sediment.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF42](#)
EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF421](#), [MF4211](#), [MF422](#), [MF4221](#)

IE:
=M.AtLB.Mx

MF42. Atlantic lower bathyal mixed sediment

General description

[MF421](#): This broad community consisting of assemblages characterised by brittle stars (ophiuroids) which lie on the surface of the seabed. They can occur in isolation or be overlain onto other broad communities such as 'sparse encrusting fauna' and 'mixed cold-water coral'. Brittle star beds comprised of *Ophiomusium lymani* have been recorded on Atlantic lower bathyal mixed sediment.

[MF422](#): This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of xenophyophores. Associated species will vary with depth and sediment type, but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges and sediment dwelling anemones.

Characteristic species

[MF4211](#): Brittle star *Ophiomusium lymani* and associated species on mixed sediments. This may be found overlain on top of another assemblage.

[MF4212](#): This biotope is characterised by dense aggregations of the xenophyophore *Syringammina fragilissima* on mixed sediment. Associated species will vary with depth but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges (yellow, white, grey, cream, pink) and sediment dwelling anemones. The same epifaunal assemblage is also found in the mid bathyal zone and on other sediments, but associated infauna is likely to differ. The Characterising species listed refer to all *Syringammina fragilissima* assemblages, and not to just those found associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal mixed sediment.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF52](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF521](#), [MF5211](#)

IE:
=M.AtLB.Sa

MF52. Atlantic lower bathyal sand

General description

Deep-sea sand sediments have a diverse infaunal community dominated by polychaetes. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse, mobile species, or burrowing fauna such as anemones and brittlestars visible at the surface. Long (2006), describes these broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between mud and sand using video data only. Note that muddy sand sediments are classed as mud if the mud content is great enough. If sediment particles are large enough to be classed as gravel using the Folk classification, then sediment would be classed as coarse sediment rather than sand. If sand contains a high enough percentage of gravel, it is also classed as coarse sediment.

Characteristic species

[MF521](#) and [MF5211](#): This broad community consisting of assemblages characterised by brittle stars (ophiuroids, e.g., *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus*, previously *Echinus acutus norvegicus*) that bury into soft sediments with the tips of the arms visible at the surface. Species may differ with depth and sediment type; however, it was not possible to identify to species level using the video data available.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal sand.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Group 7

NE Atlantic

EUNIS code: [MF62](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MF621](#), [MF6211](#),

[MF6212](#), [MF622](#), [MF6221](#),

[MF623](#), [MF6231](#), [MF624](#),

[MF6241](#), [MF625](#)

IE:

=M.AtLB.Mu

MF62. Atlantic lower bathyal mud

General description

Deep-sea mud sediments have a diverse infaunal community dominated by polychaetes. Epifauna tend to consist in sparse, mobile species, but aggregations of erect fauna such as glass sponges, sea pens and soft corals can occur.

In the absence of ecological data, mud habitat can be defined according to Long (2006), which describes the classification's broad sediment types according to the relative proportion of mud, sand and gravel. It can be difficult to reliably distinguish between mud and sand using video data only. Note that muddy sand sediments are classed as mud if the mud content is great enough.

Characteristic species

MF621 and MF6211: This broad community consisting of assemblages characterised by brittle stars (ophiuroids, *Gracilechinus acutus norvegicus* previously *Echinus acutus norvegicus*) that bury into soft sediments with the tips of the arms visible at the surface. Species may differ with depth and sediment type; however, it was not possible to identify to species level using video data available.

MF6212: Urchin *Gracilechinus alexandri* with sea stars on mud substrate. Gage (1986) describes an assemblage from the continental slope west of the Hebrides (Rockall Trough) between depths of 1,400 and 2,500m on the pelagic ooze and terbidite dominated by echinoderms. The same epifaunal assemblage is also found in the upper abyssal but associated infauna are likely to differ. The characterising species listed refer to all *Gracilechinus alexandri*, *Psilaster* and *Plinthaster* assemblages, and not to just those found associated with the zone and substrate specified in this biotope.

MF622: This broad community includes assemblages where sponges dominate sediment habitats. Sponges can be of all morphotypes except encrusting. Aggregations of the glass sponge *Pheronema carpenteri* have been recorded on the Atlantic mid to lower bathyal mud. Associated species are likely to differ with depth.

MF623: Dense aggregations of erect soft corals (e.g., Isidid octocoral *Acanella arbuscula*) occurring on fine sediments. The species composition will vary with depth and location. This broad community is functionally similar to sea pen fields.

MF624 and MF4241: This broad community is characterised by dense aggregations of xenophyophores (e.g., *Syringamina fragilissima*). Associated species will vary with depth and sediment type but may include squat lobsters (Munida), Ophiuroids, Majid crabs, pale encrusting sponges and sediment dwelling anemones.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

N/A

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

[Connor, D.W., Allen, J.H., Golding, N., Howell, K.L., Lieberknecht L.M., Northen, K.O., Reker, J.B., 2004 The Marine Habitat Classification for Britain and Ireland, Version 04.05.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows](#)

[JNCC: Atlantic lower bathyal mud.](#)

[McBreen, F., Askew, N., 2011. UKSeaMap 2010 technical report 3.](#)

Figure 07-02, *Phragmites australis*, Baltic Sea

Source: Lake reed (*Phragmites australis*), Pyhtää, The Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea. © Juho Lappalainen and Metsähallitus, 2012

Group 7

MA33. Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA33](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1610, #1620, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MA332](#) in this report; [MA331](#), [MA3311](#), [MA3312](#), [MA333](#), [MA3334](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I

DE:

=05.01.04

#§ 30 "Riffe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate to high.

Characteristic species

MA331: Baltic hydrolittoral littoral coarse sediment characterised by emergent vegetation. MA3311: common reed; MA3312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MA332: Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged vegetation. MA3321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*. MA3322: *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*. MA3323: *Chara aspera*, *C. baltica*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*. MA3324: *Ranunculus* spp. MA3325: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*. MA3326: *Zostera marina*.

MA333: Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment characterised by sparse or no macrocommunity (meiofauna, bacteria).

MA334: Baltic hydrolittoral coarse sediment characterised by sparse or no macroscopic biotic structures. No macrovegetation, no macro-epi- or infauna.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-](#)

[detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MA43. Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA43](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1610, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MA432](#) in this report; [MA431](#), [MA4311](#), [MA4312](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I

DE:

=05.01.03

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with less than 90% coverage of a certain substrate type. Mixed substrates comprise any proportion of the mix of any substrate type of soft/mobile and/or hard/non-mobile substrates.

Characteristic species

MA431: Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment characterised by emergent vegetation. MA4311: *Phragmites australis*; MA4312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MA432: Baltic hydrolittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged vegetation. MA4321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*. MA4322: *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*. MA4323: *Chara aspera*, *C. baltica*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*. MA4324: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*. MA4325: *Zostera marina*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MA53. Baltic hydrolittoral sand

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA53](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1140,

#1150, #1160, #1180,

#1610, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MA532](#) in this

report; [MA531](#), [MA5311](#),

[MA5312](#), [MA533](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I

DE:

=05.01.05

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63 µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all.

Characteristic species

MA531: Baltic hydrolittoral sandy substrata characterised by emergent vegetation. MA5311: *Phragmites australis*; MA5312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MA532: Baltic hydrolittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants. MA5321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*. MA5322: *Zannichellia* spp., *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera noltii*. MA5323: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*; MA5324: *Chara aspera*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. baltica*; MA5325: *Najas marina*, *P. perfoliatus*, *S. pectinata*; MA5326: *Ranunculus* spp.; MA5327: *Zostera marina*. MA5328: *Eleocharis acicularis*, *E. parvula*, *E. uniglumis*.

MA533: Baltic hydrolittoral sand characterised by sparse or no macrocommunity.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Rath, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-](#)

[detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MA63. Baltic hydrolittoral mud

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MA63](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150,

#1160, #1180, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MA632](#) in this

report; [MA631](#), [MA6311](#),

[MA6312](#), [MA633](#)

HELCOM:

AA.H

DE:

=05.01.06

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic hydrolittoral bottoms (with level fluctuations due to tide or weather) in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm).

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: sheltered.

Characteristic species

MA631: Baltic hydrolittoral mud characterised by emergent vegetation. MA6311: *Phragmites australis*. MA6312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MA632: Baltic hydrolittoral mud characterised by submerged rooted plants. MA6321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*; MA6322: *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*. MA6323: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*; MA6324: *Chara aspera*, *C. tomentosa*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*; MA6325: *Najas marina*; MA6326: *Ranunculus peltatus* subsp. *baudotii*; MA6327: *Zostera marina*; MA6328: *Eleocharis acicularis*, *E. parvula*, *E. uniglumis*.

MA633: Baltic hydrolittoral mud characterised by sparse or no macroscopic communities.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure and construction works.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-](#)

[detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MB33. Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB33](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB332](#) and [MB333](#) in this report; [MB331](#), [MB3311](#), [MB3312](#), [MB334](#), [MB335](#), [MB336](#), [MB3361](#), [MB3362](#), [MB3363](#), [MB337](#), [MB3371](#), [MB338](#), [MB339](#), [MB3391](#), [MB3392](#), [MB33A](#), [MB33A1](#), [MB33A2](#), [MB33B](#), [MB33C](#), [MB33C1](#), [MB33D](#), [MB33E](#), [MB33E1](#)

HELCOM:

AA.I

DE:

#05.02.07, #05.02.08

#§ 30 "Sublitorale

Sandbank"

#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-,

Grobsand- und

Schillgründe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: moderate to high; Depth range: photic zone. Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

MB331: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by emergent vegetation. MB3311: common reed; MB3312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MB332: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants. MB3321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*. MB3322: *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*. MB3323: *Chara aspera*, *C. baltica* *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*. MB3324: *Ranunculus* spp. MB3325: *Zostera marina*.

MB333: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by perennial algae. MB3331: *Fucus* spp. MB3332: *Furcellaria lumbricalis*. MB3333: *Coccotylus truncatus*, *Phyllophora* spp. MB3334: *Saccharina latissima*.

MB334: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by aquatic moss (*Fontinalis* spp.).

MB335: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves (*Mytilus* spp.).

MB336: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by stable aggregations of unattached perennial vegetation. MB3361: *Fucus vesiculosus* (typical form), *F. radicans*; MB3362: *Fucus vesiculosus* dwarf form (synonym *f. pygmaea*); MB3363: *Furcellaria lumbricalis*.

MB337: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by annual algae. MB3371: *Chorda filum*, *Halosiphon tomentosus*.

MB338: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity. No perennial attached erect group, perennial unattached algae or annual algae have ≥ 10% coverage.

MB339: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised sparse macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures. MB3391: *Hydrobiidae*, *Theodoxus* spp., *Bithynia* spp., *Radix* spp. MB3392: *Mytilus* spp., Hydroids, *Amphibalanus improvisus*.

MB33A: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal bivalves. MB33A1: *Macoma calcarea*, *Mya truncata*, *Astarte* spp., *Spisula* spp. MB33A2: *Ophelia* spp., *Tanaissus* spp., *Streptosyllis* spp.

MB33B: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal polychaetes. (*Ophelia* spp.)

MB33C: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal crustaceans. MB33C1: *Amphiura* spp., *Ophiura* spp., *Brissopsis lyrifera*, *Echinocardium* spp.

MB33D: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment dominated by infaunal insect larvae.

MB33E: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment dominated by no macroscopic biotic structures. MB33E1: *Oligochaeta*, *Ostracoda*, *Nematoda*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works, inputs of organic matter and nutrients, and sedimentation from physical seabed disturbance such as dredging and maritime traffic.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MB43. Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB43](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB432](#) and [MB433](#) in this report; [MB431](#), [MB4311](#), [MB4312](#), [MB434](#), [MB435](#), [MB4351](#), [MB4352](#), [MB436](#), [MB437](#), [MB438](#), [MB4381](#), [MB4382](#), [MB439](#), [MB43A](#), [MB43B](#), [MB43B1](#), [MB43B2](#), [MB43B3](#), [MB43B4](#), [MB43C](#), [MB43D](#), [MB43D1](#), [MB43D2](#), [MB43E](#), [MB43F](#), [MB43G](#), [MB43H](#)

HELCOM:
AA.I

DE:
<05.02.06
#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with less than 90% coverage of a certain substrate type. Mixed substrates comprise any proportion of the mix of any substrate type of soft/mobile and/or hard/non-mobile substrates.

Salinity range: All; Exposure range: All; Depth range: Photic zone.

Geographical coverage: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

MB431: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by emergent vegetation. MB4311: Common reed; MB4312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MB432: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants. MB4321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*. MB4322: *Zannichellia palustris*, *Ruppia maritima*, *Zostera noltii*. MB4323: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*. MB4324: *Chara aspera*, *C. tomentosa*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*, *C. baltica*. MB4325: *Zostera marina*.

MB433: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by perennial algae. MB4331: *Fucus vesiculosus*, *F. radicans*, *F. serratus maritimus*. MB4332: *Furcellaria lumbricalis*. MB4333: *Coccytulus truncatus*, *Phyllophora* spp., *Delesseria sanguinea*. MB4334: *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria digitata*. MB4335: *Polysiphonia fucooides*, *Aegagrophila linnaei*, *Cladophora rupestris*, *Rhodomela confervoides*.

MB434: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by aquatic moss (*Fontinalis* spp.).

MB435: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves. MB4351: *Mytilus* spp., *Modiolus modiolus*. MB4352: *Dreissena polymorpha*.

MB436: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic chordates (sea squirts (Ascidiacea, *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Molgula* ssp.)).

MB437: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians (hydroids, sea anemones, corals).

MB438: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic Bryozoa. MB4381: *Einhornia (Electra) crustulenta*. MB4382: *Flustra foliacea*.

MB439: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic crustacea. *Balanidae* (*Amphibalanus improvisus*, *Balanus crenatus*, *Semibalanus balanoides*).

MB43A: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges (Porifera, *Ephydatia fluviatilis*).

MB43B: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by stable aggregations of unattached perennial vegetation. MB43B1: *Fucus vesiculosus*,

Fucus radicans. MB43B2: *Fucus vesiculosus* dwarf form (synonym f. *pygmaea*).
MB43B3: *Furcellaria lumbricalis*. MB43B4: *Ceratophyllum demersum*.

MB43C: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by soft crustose algae.

MB43D: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by annual algae.
MB43D1: *Cladophora glomerata*, *Ceramium tenuicorne*, *Ulva* spp., *Pilayella littoralis*, *Dictyosiphon* spp. MB43D2: *Chorda filum*, *Halosiphon tomentosus*.

MB43E: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity. No perennial attached erect group, perennial unattached algae, soft crustose algae or annual algae cover more than 10% of the seabed.

MB43F: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by microphytobenthic organisms and grazing snails (e.g., *Hydrobiidae*, *Theodoxus*, *Bithynia*, *Radix*).

MB43G: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic macrocommunity. Sessile/semi-sessile macroscopic epibenthic fauna and flora is present but has less than 10% coverage.

MB43H: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment characterised by no macrocommunity. No macrovegetation, no macro- epi- or infauna.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works, inputs of organic matter and nutrients, and sedimentation from physical seabed disturbance such as dredging and maritime traffic.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MB53. Baltic infralittoral sand

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB53](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): Infralittoral sand

[HD](#): #1110, #1130, #1140, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

[European Red List](#): BAL26 (least concern), BAL27 (least concern), BAL28 (near threatened), BAL29 (least concern), BAL30 (data deficient), BAL31 (near threatened), BAL32 (least concern), BAL33 (least concern)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MA532](#) in this report; [MA531](#), [MA5311](#), [MA5312](#), [MA533](#)

HELCOM:

AA.J

DE:

#05.02.09

#05.02.10

#§ 30 "Sublitorale Sandbank"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all; Depth range: photic zone.

Characteristic species

[MB531](#): Baltic infralittoral sandy substrata characterised by emergent vegetation. [MB5311](#): *Phragmites australis*; [MB5312](#): *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

[MB532](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by submerged rooted plants. [MB5321](#): *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*; [MB5322](#): *Zannichellia* spp., *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera noltii*; [MB5323](#): *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *M. sibiricum*; [MB5324](#): *Chara aspera*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. baltica*; [MB5325](#): *Najas marina*; [MB5326](#): *Ranunculus peltatus* subsp. *baudotii*; [MB5327](#): *Zostera marina*; [MB5328](#): *Eleocharis acicularis*, *E. parvula*, *E. uniglumis*.

[MB533](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves (*Mytilus* sp.).

[MB534](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by stable aggregations of unattached perennial vegetation. [MB5341](#): *Fucus vesiculosus* (typical form). [MB5342](#): *Fucus vesiculosus* dwarf form (synonym *f. pygmaea*). [MB5343](#): *Furcellaria lumbricalis*.

[MB535](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by annual algae. [MB5351](#): *Chorda filum*, *Halosiphon tomentosus*. [MB5352](#): *Vaucheria* spp.

[MB536](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity.

[MB537](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by infaunal bivalves. [MB5371](#): *Limecola (Macoma) balthica*. [MB5372](#): *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *C. edule*. [MB5373](#): *Arctica islandica*. [MB5374](#): *Mya arenaria*. [MB5375](#): *Cerastoderma* spp., *Mya arenaria*, *Astarte borealis*, *Arctica islandica*, *Limecola balthica (Macoma balthica)*. [MB5376](#): *Macoma calcarea*, *Mya truncata*, *Astarte* spp., *Spisula* spp.

[MB538](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by infaunal polychaetes. [MB5381](#): *Ophelia* spp., *Travisia forbesii*, *Tanaissus* spp., *Streptosyllis* spp. [MB5382](#): *Arenicola marina*, *Mya arenaria*, *Cerastoderma* sp. [MB5383](#): *Pygospio elegans*, *Marenzelleria* spp. and *Hediste diversicolor* constitute at least 50% of the biomass.

[MB539](#): Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by infaunal crustacea (*Monoporeia affinis*, *Bathyporeia pilosa*, *Oligochaeta*, *Haustorius arenarius*, *Cyathura carinata*, *Hediste diversicolor*).

MB53A: Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by infaunal insect larvae (*Chironomidae*).

MB53B: Baltic infralittoral sand characterised by no macrocommunity. No macro- or microvegetation, no macro- epi- or infauna.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works and inputs of organic matter and nutrients.

Best practices in nature restoration

Revegetation of eelgrass on sites not impacted by eutrophication or sedimentation.

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MB63. Baltic infralittoral mud

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MB63](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Infralittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150, #1160, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL34

(least concern), BAL35 (least concern), BAL36 near threatened), BAL37 (least concern), BAL38 (least concern), BAL39 (near threatened), BAL40 (least concern), BAL41 (least concern)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MB632](#) in this report; [MB631](#), [MB6311](#), [MB6312](#), [MB633](#), [MB6331](#), [MB6332](#), [MB6333](#), [MB634](#), [MB6341](#), [MB635](#), [MB6351](#), [MB6352](#), [MB6353](#), [MB6354](#), [MB6355](#), [MB636](#), [MB637](#), [MB638](#), [MB6381](#), [MB6382](#), [MB6383](#), [MB6384](#), [MB639](#), [MB63A](#), [MB63A1](#), [MB63A2](#), [MB63B](#), [MB63C](#), [MB63D](#), [MB63D1](#), [MB63E](#)

HELCOM:

AA.H

DE:

#05.02.11

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic infralittoral bottoms in the photic zone with at least 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm).

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: sheltered; Depth range: photic zone. Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

MB631: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by emergent vegetation. MB6311: *Phragmites australis*; MB6312: *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Bolbaschoenus maritimus*.

MB632: Baltic infralittoral mud sediment characterised by submerged rooted plants. MB6321: *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Stuckenia pectinata*; MB6322: *Zannichellia* spp., *Ruppia* spp., *Zostera noltii*; MB6323: *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Myriophyllum sibiricum*; MB6324: *Chara aspera*, *C. tomentosa*, *Tolipella nidifica*, *C. horrida*; MB6325: *Najas marina*; MB6326: *Ranunculus peltatus* subsp. *baudotii*; MB6327: *Zostera marina*; MB6328: spike-rush (*Eleocharis* spp.) constitutes at least 50% of the biovolume.

MB633: Baltic infralittoral mud sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves. MB6321: *Mytilus* sp.; MB6322: the epibenthic bivalve zebra mussel (*Dreissena polymorpha*) constitutes at least 50% of the biovolume; MB6333: the epibenthic bivalve valve snails (*Valvata* spp.) constitutes at least 50% of the biovolume.

MB634: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by epibenthic polychaetes (*Maldanidae* and *Terebellida*).

MB635: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by stable aggregations of unattached perennial vegetation MB6351: *Fucus vesiculosus* (typical form), *F. radicans*. MB6352: *Fucus vesiculosus dwarf form* (synonym *f. pygmaea*). MB6353: *Furcellaria lumbricalis*. MB6354: *Ceratophyllum demersum*. MB6355: *Aegagropila linnaei*.

MB636: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by annual algae. Annual algae cover at least 10% of the seabed. such as *Vaucheria* spp.

MB637: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by mixed epibenthic. No perennial attached erect group; perennial unattached algae or annual algae have ≥ 10% coverage.

MB638: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by infaunal bivalves. MB6381: *Limecola balthica* (*Macoma balthica*). MB6382: *Arctica islandica*. MB6383: Unionidae. MB6384: *Abra* spp.

MB639: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by infaunal polychaetes. MB6391: *Marenzelleria arctica*, *Marenzelleria viridis*, *Marenzelleria neglecta*. MB6392: *Polydora ciliata*, *Pectinaria koreni*, *Capitella capitata*, *Scoloplos*.

MB63A: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by infaunal crustacea. MB63A1: *Monoporeia affinis*, *Saduria entomon*. MB63A2: *Corophium volutator*, *Apocorophium lacustre*.

MB63B: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by infaunal echinoderms (*Amphiura* spp., *Ophiura* spp., *Brissopsis lyrifera*, *Echinocardium* spp.)

MB63C: Baltic infralittoral mud characterised by infaunal insect larvae.

MB63D: Baltic infralittoral mud without characteristic macroscopic communities (*Oligochaeta*, *Ostracoda*, *Nematoda*).

MB63E: Baltic infralittoral soft anthropogenically created substrates.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works, inputs of organic matter and nutrients, and sedimentation from physical seabed disturbance such as dredging and maritime traffic.

Best practices in nature restoration

Revegetation of eelgrass on sites not impacted by eutrophication or sedimentation.

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MC33. Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC33](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Circalittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL45 (near threatened), BAL46 (vulnerable), BAL47 (least concern), BAL48 (least concern)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC331](#), [MC332](#), [MC333](#), [MC3331](#), [MC3332](#), [MC334](#), [MC335](#), [MC336](#), [MC3361](#)

HELCOM:

AB.I

DE:

#05.02.07

#05.02.08

#§ 30 "Sublitorale Sandbank"

#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: All; Exposure range: All; Depth range: Below photic zone - more common in the shallow.

Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

MC331: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic bivalves cover 10% or less of the seabed and more than other attached erect groups.

MC332: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity. No perennial attached erect group has ≥ 10% coverage.

MC333: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal bivalves. MC3331: *Macoma calcaria*, *Mya truncata*, *Astarte* spp., *Spisula* spp.; MC3332: *Ophelia* spp., *Travisia forbesii*, *Tanaissus* spp., *Streptosyllis* spp.

MC334: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal polychaetes.

MC335: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by infaunal crustaceans. (*Bathyporeia pilosa*).

MC336: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment characterised by no macrocommunity. *Oligochaeta*, *Ostracoda*, *Nematoda*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works, inputs of organic matter and nutrients, bottom-trawling fisheries, and sedimentation from physical seabed disturbance such as dredging and maritime traffic

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MC43. Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC43](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Circalittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL42 (near threatened), BAL43 (least concern), BAL49 (near threatened), BAL50 (data deficient), BAL51 (least concern)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MC433](#) and [MC436](#) in this report; [MC431](#), [MC432](#), [MC4321](#), [MC434](#), [MC4341](#), [MC4342](#), [MC435](#), [MC437](#), [MC438](#), [MC439](#), [MC43A](#)

HELCOM:

AB.M

DE:

<05.02.06

#§ 30 "Artenreiche Kies-, Grobsand- und Schillgründe"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with less than 90% coverage of a certain substrate type. Mixed substrates comprise any proportion of a mix of any substrate type of soft/mobile and/or hard/non-mobile substrates.

Salinity range: All; Exposure range: All; Depth range: Below photic zone - more common on elevations.

Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

MC431: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic bivalves (*Mytilus* sp.).

MC432: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic chordates (Ascidiacea: *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Molgula* spp.)

MC433: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians. MC4331: *Laomedea* spp., *Cordylophora caspia*. MC4332: *Edwardsia* spp., *Metridium dianthus*. MC4333: *Alcyonium digitatum*, *Swiftia rosea*.

MC434: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic Bryozoa (*Einhornia (Electra) crustulenta*, *Flustra foliaceae*).

MC435: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic crustacea (*Amphibalanus improvisus*, *Balanus crenatus*, *Semibalanus balanoides*).

MC436: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by epibenthic sponges (*Haliclona oculata* rarely other species such as *Halichondria panicea*, *Halisarca dujardini*, *Scypha ciliata*. In the Northern Baltic Sea, only *Ephydatia fluviatilis*).

MC437: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity. No perennial attached erect group (not epibenthic bivalves) has $\geq 10\%$ coverage.

MC438: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic fauna (not epibenthic bivalves).

MC439: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by infaunal communities.

MC43A: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment characterised by no macrocommunity.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Infrastructure, construction works, inputs of organic matter and nutrients, bottom-trawling fisheries, and sedimentation from physical seabed disturbance such as dredging and maritime traffic.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM HUB, 2013. HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MC53. Baltic circalittoral sand

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC53](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: Circalittoral sand
HD: #1110, #1130, #1140, #1150, #1180, #1650

European Red List: BAL52 (least concern), BAL53 (near threatened), BAL54 (least concern), BAL55 (least concern)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC531](#), [MC5311](#), [MC532](#), [MC533](#), [MC5331](#), [MC5332](#), [MC5333](#), [MC5334](#), [MC5335](#), [MC5336](#), [MC534](#), [MC5341](#), [MC535](#), [MC5351](#), [MC536](#), [MC537](#), [MC5371](#)

HELCOM:
AB.J3L

DE:
#05.02.09
#05.02.10
#§ 30 "Sublitorale Sandbank"

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction. The depth range is below the photic zone. This habitat is generally more stable than shallower, infralittoral sands and consequently supports a more diverse community.

The habitat is defined by at least 10% infaunal bivalves. No microvegetation or epibenthic macrofauna are present.

Typical taxa that describe the habitat include polychaetes, bivalve molluscs and amphipod crustacea.

This habitat is common throughout the Baltic Sea, occurring in all the sub-basins, although some of the associated biotopes have a more restricted distribution.

Characteristic species

Mya arenaria, *Macoma baltica*, *Arctica islandica*, *Pygospio elegans*, *Marenzelleria* spp., *Hediste diversicolor*, *Monoporeia affinis*, *Chironomidae*.

Associated species

A typical sparse or no macrofaunal community consists of *Oligochaeta*, *Ostracoda*, *Nematoda*, *Copepoda*. In the Gulf of Bothnia, nektobenthic *Mysidae* can be associated with the habitat.

A typical epifaunal community consist of *Mytilus* spp., *Hediste diversicolor*.

A typical infaunal community not dominated by bivalves consists of *Pygospio elegans*, *Marenzelleria* spp., *Hediste diversicolor*, *Ophelia* spp., *Travisia forbesii*, *Monoporeia affinis*, *Saduria entomon* and the insect larvae (*Chironomidae*).

A typical infaunal community dominated by bivalves consists of *Arctica islandica*, *Macoma balthica*, *Macoma calcarea*, *Cerastoderma* spp., *Mya arenaria*, *Mya truncata*, *Astarte* spp., *Spisula* spp., *Thracia* spp., *Phaxas pellucidus* or polychaete species such as *Ophelia rathkei*, *Ophelia limacina*, *Travisia forbesii* and *Streptosyllis* spp.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is threatened by eutrophication (increase in N, P and organic matter) and contaminant pollution, as well as by activities that cause direct damage to the seabed. These include sand extraction, oil and gas exploration and extraction and bottom trawling. All of these are also envisaged to be future threats.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.

[HELCOM, 2020. HELCOM underwater biotope classification](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MC63. Baltic circalittoral mud

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MC63](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150, #1180, #1650

European Red List⁵²: BAL59

(endangered), BAL57

(vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC631](#), [MC6311](#),

[MC632](#), [MC633](#), [MC6331](#),

[MC634](#), [MC6341](#), [MC635](#),

[MC636](#), [MC6361](#), [MC637](#),

[MC6371](#), [MC6372](#), [MC6373](#),

[MC638](#), [MC6381](#), [MC6382](#),

[MC6383](#), [MC639](#), [MC6391](#),

[MC63A](#), [MC63A1](#), [MC63A2](#),

[MC63B](#), [MC63C](#), [MC63C1](#),

[MC63C2](#), [MC63D](#)

HELCOM:

AB.H⁵³

DE:

<05.02.11

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm).

Salinity range: All; Exposure range: All; Depth range: Below the photic zone; more common in deeper areas. Characteristic species: *Macoma balthica*, *Marenzelleria* spp. Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Correspondence with the European Red List biotope BAL59 “Sparse epibenthic community of Baltic upper circalittoral muddy sediment” (endangered):

- This Baltic Sea benthic habitat occurs in the aphotic zone where there is at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment according to the HELCOM HUB classification. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic fauna is present but covers less than 10% of the seabed. One associated biotope has been identified: ‘Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by seapens’ (AB.H2T1). This is characterised by conspicuous populations of seapens that usually live scattered over the sea floor but usually cover less than 10% of the muddy surface. It occurs typically from depths of 15 to 200m in low to moderate energy exposure classes in the highest salinity regions of the Baltic (up to 23psu in the Sound). These deep-water communities are crucially important to the function of the ecosystem. They provide food and shelter for many other species, including commercially important fish.
- MC63 subtype MC636 “Baltic circalittoral mud characterised by sparse epibenthic macrocommunity” is more or less equal.
- MC63 subtype MC6361 “Baltic circalittoral mud dominated by seapens” is wider.

Correspondence with the European Red List biotope BAL57 “Infaunal communities of Baltic upper circalittoral muddy sediment dominated by bivalves” (vulnerable):

- This habitat occurs on Baltic Sea aphotic bottoms with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment according to the HELCOM HUB classification. Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic macrofauna is not present and the biomass of infaunal bivalves dominates. The habitat generally occurs below a depth of approximately 20m in locations of energy exposure.
- MC63 subtype MC637 “Baltic circalittoral muds characterised by infaunal bivalves” is more or less equal.
- MC63 subtype MC6371 “Baltic circalittoral mud dominated by *Limecola balthica*” is narrower.
- MC63 subtype MC6372 “Baltic circalittoral mud dominated by *Arctica islandica*” is narrower.

⁵² See “General description” for more information on the correspondence of this habitat type with European Red List habitats.

⁵³ See “General description” for more information on the correspondence of this habitat type with HELCOM subtype.

- MC63 subtype MC6373 “Baltic circalittoral mud dominated by *Astarte* spp.” is narrower.

Correspondence with the HELCOM HUB AB.H “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment” (equal), containing:

- AB.H1E “AB.H1E Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by epibenthic bivalves” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC631).
- AB.H1E1 “AB.H1E1 Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by *Mytilidae*” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6311).
- AB.H1G “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by epibenthic cnidarians” (corresponds to MC632).
- AB.H1I “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by epibenthic crustaceans” (corresponds to MC633):
 - Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic crustacean cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. The substrate is a muddy sediment. Depth below approximately 20m. Appears in all energy exposure classes. Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.
- AB.H1K “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by epibenthic polychaetes” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC634).
- AB.H1K1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by various tube-building polychaetes” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6341).
- AB.H1V “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC635):
 - Baltic aphotic bottoms with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). No perennial attached erect group has ≥10% coverage. Substrate is muddy sediment. Depth below approximately 20m. Appears in all energy exposure classes. Geographic range: Southern part of the Baltic Sea.
- AB.H2T “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by sparse epibenthic macrocommunity” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC636).
- AB.H2T1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by sea pens” (corresponds to MC6361).
- AB.H3 “Aphotic muddy sediments dominated by macroscopic infauna biotic structures”:
 - Baltic bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Macroscopic infauna present, no epibenthic macrofauna.
- AB.H3L “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by infaunal bivalves”:
 - Corresponds to MC63 subtype MC637 “Baltic circalittoral muds characterised by infaunal bivalves” (equal).
 - Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic macrofauna is not present. Biomass of infaunal

bivalves dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Substrate is muddy sediment. Depth below approximately 20m. Appears in all energy exposure classes. Characteristic species: *Macoma balthica*, *Arctica islandica*, *Astarte* spp. Geographic range: Whole Baltic Sea.

- AB.H3L1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by Baltic tellin (*Macoma balthica*)” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6371).
- AB.H3L3 “Aphotic muddy sediment dominated by the ocean quahog (*Arctica islandica*)”:
 - Corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6372 “Baltic circalittoral mud dominated by *Arctica islandica*” (equal).
 - Listed on HELCOM Red List as critically endangered.
 - Defined as MSFD Other Habitat Type (OHT).
 - Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm). Biomass of infaunal bivalves dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Out of the infaunal bivalves, Ocean quahog (*Arctica islandica*) constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. The substrate is a muddy sediment. Appears in low to moderate energy exposure classes. Characteristic species: *Arctica islandica*. Geographic range: Western Baltic Sea.
- AB.H3L5 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by *Astarte* spp.” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6373).
- AB.H3M “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by infaunal polychaetes”:
 - Corresponds to MC638 “Baltic circalittoral mud characterised by infaunal polychaetes”.
 - Baltic circalittoral bottoms in the aphotic zone with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63 µm). Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic macrofauna is not present. Biomass of infaunal polychaetes dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Substrate is muddy sediment. Depth below approximately 20m. Appears in all energy exposure classes.
- AB.H3M1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by *Scoloplos (Scoloplos) armiger*” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6381).
- AB.H3M3 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by *Marenzelleria* spp.” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6382).
- AB.H3M5 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by various opportunistic polychaetes” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6383).
- AB.H3N “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by infaunal crustaceans” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC639).
- AB.H3N1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by *Monoporeia affinis* and/or *Pontoporeia femorata*” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC6391).
- AB.H3O “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by infaunal echinoderms” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC63A).
- AB.H3P “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by infaunal insect larvae” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC63B).

- AB.H3P1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by midge larvae (Chironomidae)”.
- AB.H4U “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment characterised by no macrocommunity” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC63C).
- AB.H4U1 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by meiofauna” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC63C1).
- AB.H4U2 “Baltic aphotic muddy sediment dominated by anaerobic organisms” (corresponds to MC63 subtype MC63C2).

Characteristic species

Macoma balthica, *Marenzelleria* spp.

Germany’s national biotope list (Finck et al. 2017): *Macoma balthica*, *Mya arenaria*, *Anodonta anatina*, *Arctica islandica*, *Astarte borealis*, *Macoma calcarea*, *Priapulida*, *Corophium volutator*, *Diastylis rathkei*, *Leptocheirus pilosus*, *Pontoporeia femorata*, *Arenicola marina*, *Hediste diversicolor*, *Lagis koreni*, *Marenzelleria* spp., *Alitta succinea*, *Nephtys ciliata*, *Scoloplos armiger*, *Chironomidae*, *Mytilus* spp.

For AB.H3L3 (corresponds to EUNIS MC6372): *Arctica islandica*.

For BAL57 (European Red List, contains MC6373): *Astarte* spp.

From Natura2000 habitat type 1160:

- Plants/Algae: *Ceramium virgatum*, *Delesseria sanguinea*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Fucus serratus*, *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, *Laminaria saccharina*, *Ulva lactuca*, *Zanichellia palustris*, *Zostera marina*, *Zostera noltii*, *Chara baltica*, *C. aspera*, *C. canescens*, *C. tomentosa*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, *P. pectinatus*, *Ruppia cirrhosa*, *R. maritima*, *Tolipella nidifica*.
- Macrozoobenthos: *Abra alba*, *Anaitides mucosa*, *Arctica islandica*, *Arenicola marina*.
- *Bylgides sarsi*, *Capitella capitata*, *Cerastoderma lamarckii*, *Ciona intestinalis*, *Corophium crassicorne*, *Cyathura carinata*, *Diastylis rathkei*, *Dipolydora quadrilobata*, *Eteone cf. longa*, *Gastrosaccus spinifer*, *Halicryptus spinulosus*, *Hediste diversicolor*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Hydrobia ventrosa*, *Hydrobia Ulva*, *Lagis koreni*, *Macoma balthica*, *Manayunkia aestuarina*, *Microdeutopus gryllotalpa*, *Mya arenaria*, *Mya truncata*, *Mysella bidentata*, *Mytilus edulis*, *Nemertea indet.*, *Nephtys caeca*, *Nephtys ciliata*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Parvicardium ovale*, *Polydora ciliata*, *Pygospio elegans*, *Scoloplos armiger*, *Scrobicularia plana*, *Streblospio shrubsoli*, *Terebellides stroemi*, *Trochochaeta multisetosa*, *Tubificoides benedenii*, *Varicorbula gibba*, *Corophium volutator*, *Cyathura cyathura*, *Marenzelleria viridis*, *Sphaeroma hookeri*, *Tubifex costatus*.
- Fish: *Pholis gunellus*, *Gasterosteus aculeatus*, *Platichthys flesus*, *Perca fluviatilis*, *Liparis liparis*, *Esox lucius*, *Clupea harengus*, *Gadus morhua*, *Nerophis ophidion*, *Ctenolabrus rupestris*, *Pomatoschistus minutus*, *Pleuronectes platessa*, *Cyclopterus lumpus*, *Spinachia spinachia*, *Pomatoschistus microps*, *Stizostedion lucioperca*, *Gobiusculus flavescens*.

- Birds/Mammals: *Aythya marila*, *Anser albifrons*, *Somateria mollissima*, *Clangula hyemalis*, *Mergus merganser*, *Anser anser*, *Podiceps cristatus*, *Cygnus olor*, *Mergus serrator*, *Aythya fuligula*, *Podiceps grisegena*, *Anser fabilis*, *Bucephala clangula*, *Cygnus cygnus*, *Melanitta nigra*.

From HELCOM HUB corresponding biotopes: *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Mytilus* spp., *Haploids* spp., *Maldanidae* spp., *Terebellida* spp., *Macoma baltica*, *Arctica islandica*, *Astarte* spp., *Marenzelleria* spp., *Hediste diversicolor*, *Nephtys* spp. *Balanidae*, *Virgularia mirabilis*, *Pennatula phosphorea*, *Polydora ciliata*, *Lagis koreni*, *Capitella capitata*, *Scoloplos (Scoloplos) armiger*, *Monoporeia affinis*, *Pontoporeia femorata*, *Saduria entomon*, *Amphiura* spp., *Amphiura filiformis*, *Amphiura chiajei*, *Ophiura* spp., *Brissopsis lyrifera*, *Echinocardium* spp., *Chironomidae*, *Oligochaeta*, *Nematoda*, *Ostracoda*.

Associated species

Baltic circalittoral mud (MC63) does typically not contain any plant or macroalgal communities, as it occurs in the aphotic zone. However, it is also assigned to the Natura 2000 habitat type “1160” (Large shallow inlets and bays), which also comprises the photic zone. In this case, typical community-forming species are listed under this habitat type in the section “Characterising species”.

In general, Baltic circalittoral mud is characterised by long-living bivalves such as *Arctica islandica* or *Astarte* spp., and opportunistic polychaetes such as *Capitella capitata*, *Nephtys* spp. and *Polydora ciliata*. The species composition depends on the salinity gradient in the Baltic.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Physical pressures include change of seabed substrate or morphology (~physical loss), disturbance or damage to seabed, and major activities such as mobile bottom-contacting fishing gear (dredging), laying of cables and pipelines. Also, pressures from chemicals and other pollutants include the input of nutrients and organic matter (eutrophication), and major activities such as nutrient loads from rivers (agriculture).

In combination with climate change (rising sea water temperature), eutrophication can lead to an increase of oxygen depletion in this biotope (spatio-temporal), resulting in higher mortalities of characterising species such as long-living bivalves.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[EEA, 2022c. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Red List in separate rows.](#)

[EU Marine Habitat Fact Sheets \(Baltic Sea\), reviewed 2016.](#)

Finck, P., Heinze, S., Raths, U., Riecken, U. & Ssymank, A., 2017. Rote Liste der gefährdeten Biotoptypen Deutschlands. Dritte fortgeschriebene Fassung 2017. - -Natursch. Biol. Vielf. 156, 637 S.)

[Interpretation Manual of EU Habitats, version EUR 28.](#)

[Martin, G., Torn, K., Nyström Sandman, A. & Nygård, H. 2020. A practical guidance how different hierarchical levels of habitats \(e.g., broader and more-detailed HELCOM underwater biotopes\) can be tackled within the same assessment. Deliverable 4.1.2 of HELCOM SPICE project.](#)

Group 7

MD33. Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD33](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MD331](#), [MD332](#), [MD3321](#), [MD3322](#), [MD333](#)

HELCOM:

AB.I

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below halocline/pycnocline with at least a 90% coverage of coarse sediment. Coarse sediment has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of gravel and pebbles (grain size 2-63mm) exceeds 30% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Characteristic species

[MD331](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse habitat characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures. Coverage of sessile macroscopic epifauna is ≥10%.

[MC332](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse bottoms characterised by macroscopic infaunal biotic structures (polychaetes and crustaceans).

[MC333](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse bottoms characterised by no macroscopic biotic structures. No macro- epi- or infauna.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Inputs of nutrients and hazardous substances.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[HELCOM HUB, 2013 HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

Group 7

MD43. Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD43](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MC431](#) in this report

HELCOM:

AB.M

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with less than a 90% coverage of a certain substrate type. Mixed substrates comprise any proportion of a mix of any substrate type of soft/mobile and/or hard/non-mobile substrates.

Characteristic species

[MD431](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed bottoms macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures. [MD4311](#): Sessile/semi-sessile *Mytilidae* cover less than 10% of the seabed but more than other perennial attached erect groups. [MD4312](#): Sessile/semi-sessile epibenthic chordates cover at least 10% of the seabed and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Depth is typically from 20m to 100m. Characteristic species *Ascidacea*: *Dendrodoa grossularia*, *Molgula* spp. [MD4313](#): Epibenthic Bryozoa (*Einhornia (Electra) crustulenta*) cover at least 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Out of the epibenthic Bryozoa, corticated Bryozoa constitute at least 50% of the biomass.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Inputs of nutrients and hazardous substances.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[HELCOM HUB, 2013 HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

Group 7

MD53. Baltic offshore circalittoral sand

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD53](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Offshore

circalittoral sand

[European Red List](#): BAL61

(vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: See [MD531](#) in this report; [MD532](#)

HELCOM:

AB.J3L

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with at least a 90% coverage of sand. Sand has less than 20% of mud/silt/clay fraction (<63µm), and the proportion of sand (grain size 0.063-2mm) exceeds 70% of the combined gravel and sand fraction.

Salinity range: all; Exposure range: all; Depth range: below photic zone - more common in the shallow.

Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

[MD531](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral sand characterised by macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures. [MD5311](#): Epibenthic bivalves/cover less than 10% of the seabed, and more than other perennial attached erect groups. Out of the epibenthic bivalves, *Mytilidae* constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD5312](#): No perennial attached erect group has ≥ 10% coverage.

[MD532](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral sand characterised by macroscopic infaunal biotic structures. [MD5321](#): Biomass of infaunal bivalves dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Out of the infaunal bivalves, *Limecola (Macoma) balthica* constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD5322](#): Biomass of infaunal bivalves dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Out of the infaunal bivalves, *Arctica islandica* constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD5323](#): Biomass of infaunal bivalves dominates and is highest in the group that includes infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/echinoderms/insect larvae. Constitute at least 50% of the biomass. [MD5324](#): Biomass of infaunal polychaetes dominates and is the highest in the group infaunal bivalves/polychaetes/crustaceans/insect larvae. [MD5325](#): *Monoporeia affinis* and *Saduria entomon*. [MD5326](#): Chironomidae.

[MD533](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral sand characterised by no macroscopic biotic structures.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is threatened by eutrophication (increase in N, P and organic matter) and contaminant pollution as well as activities which cause direct damage to the seabed. These include sand extraction, oil and gas exploration and extraction and bottom trawling. All of these are also envisaged to be future threats.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[HELCOM, 2020. HELCOM underwater biotope classification.](#)

Group 7

MD63. Baltic offshore circalittoral mud

Baltic Sea

EUNIS code: [MD63](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Offshore

circalittoral mud

[European Red List](#): BAL61

(vulnerable)

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MD631](#) in this

report; [MD632](#)

HELCOM:

AB.H

General description

This habitat type describes Baltic offshore bottoms in the aphotic zone, below the halocline/pycnocline with at least a 90% coverage of muddy sediment. The sediment must contain at least 20% of mud, silt or clay (grain size less than 63µm).

Salinity range: All; Exposure range: All; Depth range: Below photic zone - more common in deeper areas.

Geographical range: Whole Baltic Sea.

Characteristic species

[MD631](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic bivalves (*Mytilus* sp.).

[MD632](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic cnidarians: hydroids, sea anemones, corals.

[MD633](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic Crustaceans. [MD6331](#): Where there is sufficient oxygen and elevated salinity - Copepods (Harpacticoida) e.g., *Laophonte baltica*, *Amphiascoides dispar* and *Kliopsyllus constrictus*.

[MD634](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by epibenthic polychaetes. In the depths around Gotland the polychaetes *Scoloplos armiger* and where the substrate is predominantly clay *Pontoporeia femorata* and *Terebellides stroemi*.

[MD635](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by mixed epibenthic macrocommunity.

[MD636](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by sparse macroscopic epibenthic biotic structures: *Limecola balthica* (*Macoma balthica*), *Saduria entomon*, *Marenzelleria* spp., *Monoporeia affinis*, *Virgularia mirabilis*, *Pennatula phosphorea*.

[MD637](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by macroscopic infaunal biotic structures. [MD6371](#): Out of the infaunal bivalves, *Limecola balthica* (*Macoma balthica*) constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6372](#): Out of the infaunal bivalves, Ocean quahog (*Arctica islandica*) constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6373](#): Out of the infaunal polychaetes, *Scoloplos armiger* constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6374](#): Out of the infaunal polychaetes, *Marenzelleria* spp. constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6375](#): Out of the infaunal polychaetes, various opportunistic polychaetes. constitutes at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6376](#): Out of the infaunal crustaceans, *Monoporeia affinis* and/or *Pontoporeia femorata* constitute at least 50% of the biomass. [MD6377](#): *Amphiura* spp., *Ophiura* spp., *Brissopsis lyrifera*, *Echinocardium* spp. [MD6378](#): *Chironomidae*.

[MD638](#): Baltic offshore circalittoral mud characterised by no macroscopic biotic structures: meiofauna, bacteria.

MD639: Baltic offshore circalittoral soft anthropogenically created substrates.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Inputs of nutrients and hazardous substances.

Best practices in nature restoration

Reduction of external inputs of nutrients and organic matter as well as management of internal nutrient reserves.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA 2002b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalk to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[HELCOM HUB, 2013 HELCOM Underwater Biotopes.](#)

Group 7

MA34. Black Sea littoral coarse sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MA34](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA2.132

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA341](#)

BG:

>Littoral gravels

General description

Littoral coarse sediments are presented by mobile pebbles, cobbles, gravel, shells, sometimes with varying amounts of coarse sand, exposed to currents or wave action. As the sediment is quite coarse it typically does not support large volumes of marine life. There may be accumulations of shell hash, for example *Cerastoderma*, *Mya*, and other molluscs.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is "Mediolittoral coarse sediment (cobbles, gravel, shell hash) typically with or without poor fauna (e.g., *Janua pagenstecheri*)".

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

This habitat is characterised by poor fauna. A typical species is the polychaete *Janua pagenstecheri*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main anthropogenic risk to this habitat is represented by coastal developments, including the construction of marinas and slipways, sediment extraction, the widening and dredging of channels, creation of artificial beaches, road building, and construction of coastal hydrotechnical facilities. These activities may alter the hydrological regime, which will in turn affect the character and viability of the habitat. Other potential threats are sealing and smothering due to waste pollution.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to the application of nature-based solutions for construction of hydro-technical facilities, establishment of protected areas, and prevention of waste pollution are of importance for the protection and restoration of this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to](#)

[Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators](#)").

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MA44](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130,#1140, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MA441](#)

General description

The extent of the distribution of littoral sediments is determined by morphometric parameters: width of the inundation of the above-water shore, height of wave inundation, width of the underwater surf zone, and depth. This habitat is presented by diverse mixed sediment fractions, ranging from muds with gravel and sand components to mixed sediments with pebbles, gravels, sands, and mud in more even proportions.

Characteristic species

Stable large cobbles or boulders may be present, supporting epibiota such as fucoids and green seaweeds, more commonly found on rocky and boulder shores. Mixed sediments, which are predominantly muddy, tend to support infaunal communities that are similar to those of mud and sandy mud shores.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- The construction of coastal hydro-technical facilities leads to permanent changes in the hydrodynamic and lithodynamic regimes, with subsequent silting and damage to a significant percentage of the habitat area.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and application of nature-based solutions for the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO₂

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MA54](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1160

European Red List:

=BLSA2.2x

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA541](#)

BG:

>Coarse and medium mediolittoral sands exposed to wave action with *Donacilla cornea* and *Ophelia bicornis*

General description

The extent of distribution of littoral sediments is determined by morphometric parameters: width of inundation of the above-water shore, height of wave inundation, width of the underwater surf zone, and depth. The habitat is presented by coarse, medium, and fine sands, or muddy sands with up to 25% of silt and clay fraction, in areas, typically exposed, moderately exposed or sheltered from wave action. Shells and stones may occasionally be present on the surface. This is the dominant biotope in the habitat of mediolittoral sediments of the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast, while the gravelly and muddy mediolittoral are very limited distributed. The dominant environmental conditions defining the sediment characteristic and species composition are high levels of physical disturbance from wave action, wide temperature variability, and periods of desiccation. In the microtidal Black Sea environment (tidal range of about 0.3m) this habitat is limited to narrow beach strip according to the swash.

Inhabiting community composition depends on grain size and the origin of sand (siliceous/calcareous, biogenic/abiogenic) with three associated biotopes distinguished. Diversity is usually low due to high physical disturbance from wave action, but abundances may be high.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Mediolittoral (0-1m) coarse or medium clean sand with *Donacilla cornea* (and *Ophelia bicornis*)”, and “Mediolittoral (0-1m) fine sand with *Pontogammarus maeoticus*”.

Characteristic species

The biotope associated with coarse and medium sands of exposed to moderately exposed coasts is inhabited by the burrowing wedge clam *Donacilla cornea*, whose distribution is strictly limited to the beach strip covered by the swash, and only exceptionally may extend towards the infralittoral at a depth of up to about 3m – an area usually inhabited by *Donax trunculus*.

Other characteristic species are the infaunal polychaete *Ophelia bicornis*, which occupies the upper swash zone, and the mysid shrimp *Gastrosaccus sanctus*. Typical interstitial species are the crustaceans *Eurydice dolfusi*, *G. sanctus*, and the polychaetes *Nerine cirratulus*, *Saccocirrus papillocercus*, *Pisione remota*, *Hesionides arenaria*.

The second biotope occurs on the sheltered shores of lagoons and estuaries from the Crimea and the Taman Peninsula, where *Donacilla* occurs in a very narrow swash zone in muddy sands with significant organic load, together with polychaetes such as *Hediste diversicolor* and *Alitta succinea*.

The third biotope occurs in fine siliceous sands (freshwater-influenced), where the amphipod *Pontogammarus maeoticus* is highly abundant, while *Donacilla* and *Ophelia* disappear. Other species include *Zostera marina*, *Z. noltii*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- The construction of coastal hydrotechnical facilities, which leads to permanent changes in the hydrodynamic and lithodynamic regimes, with subsequent silting and damage to a significant percentage of the habitat area.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and application of nature-based solutions for the construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MA64. Black Sea littoral mud

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MA64](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA2.32

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MA641](#)

BG:

>Mediolittoral mud

General description

The extent of the distribution of littoral sediments is determined by morphometric parameters: width of inundation of the above-water shore, height of wave inundation, width of the underwater surf zone, and depth. The Black Sea fine particulate sediments are presented by mostly silt and clay fraction (particle size less than 0.063mm in diameter), though sandy mud may contain up to 40% fine sand. Littoral mud typically forms extensive mudflats. These cohesive sediments contain low oxygen, and an anoxic layer is often present within millimetres of the sediment surface. Most muddy shores are subject to some freshwater influence, as they typically occur in the area of, or impacted by, estuaries. Littoral mud can support communities characterised by polychaetes, bivalves, and oligochaetes. Mudflats on sheltered lower estuarine shores can support a rich infauna.

Information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is scarce.

Characteristic species

MA641: Upper estuarine mud communities support few infaunal species and are principally characterised by a restricted range of polychaetes and oligochaetes. Chironomids are present in the upper estuary where freshwater conditions are prevalent.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Construction works at the area of ports and *marinas*, or construction of hydro-technical facilities, causing siltation, and smothering.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and application of nature-based solutions for construction of hydro-technical facilities are of high importance for this habitat.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MB34. Black Sea infralittoral coarse sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB34](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1160

European Red List: ≈BLSA5.a

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB341](#)

BG:

>Infralittoral gravels

General description

This habitat type describes coarse sediments in the Black Sea including coarse sand, gravel, pebbles, shingle, and cobbles which are often unstable due to wave action. They typically have a low silt content and a lack of a significant seaweed component. This habitat is characterised by a robust fauna including venerid bivalves.

MB341: Coarse sediments in sheltered areas, presented by pebbles, cobbles, fine gravels, coarse sands, and shell hash. This habitat comprises a diverse range of communities, including sparse fauna on pebbles and gravels; cobbles and gravels, and shell hash with well-defined characteristic species (*Branchiostoma lanceolatum* - *Protodorvillea kefersteini* - *Ophelia limacina*). This biotope is spread in coastal surge zones, on wave-exposed bottoms along open coasts, and deposits affected by unidirectional currents. Typical species inhabiting coarse sand and shell gravel environment are the lancelet *B. lanceolatum* and polychaetes *P. kefersteini* and *O. limacina*.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is “Infralittoral coarse sediments (including pebbles, cobbles, fine gravels, coarse sands and shell”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Spirobranchus triqueter, *Branchiostoma lanceolatum*, *Protodorvillea kefersteini*, *Ophelia limacina*, *Flexopecten glaber ponticus* and *Polititapes aureus*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling, which causes habitat destruction; trawling, which causes deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic communities both directly and indirectly through effects, such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB44](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Infralittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1160, #1170

European Red List:

≈BLSA5.13

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

In this habitat, the substrate is often patchy and is comprised of a mix of cobbles, pebbles, shelly gravels, and silted cobbles. The effects of currents and wave action are varied and influence the type of substrate present and whether it is overlain by silt. These different substrates can support a diverse range of faunal communities.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is “Infralittoral mixed sediment with varied fauna”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Biological communities are represented by encrusting spirorbid worms, *Amphibalanus improvisus*, *Actinia aequina*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Pisidia longicornis*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling, which causes habitat destruction; trawling, which causes deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic communities both directly and indirectly through effects such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MB54. Black Sea infralittoral sands

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB54](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA5.22, <BLSA5.237,

<BLSA5.24, <BLSA5.bb,

<BLSA5.aa, <BLSA5.53,

<BLSA5.5z, <BLSA5.5w

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: See [MB546](#),

[MB547](#), and [MB548](#) in this

report; [MB541](#), [MB542](#),

[MB543](#), [MB544](#), [MB545](#)

BG:

>Underwater seagrass meadows

>Coarse and medium shallow sand with *Donax trunculus*

>Fine and medium sand with *Lentidium mediterraneum*

>Clean sand with *Arenicollina marina* and *Callianassa* spp.

>Sand with *Chamelea gallina*

>Muddy sand with *Upogebia pusilla*

RO:

>Habitat with *Zostera noltii*

General description

Infralittoral sands occur in shallow waters at depths of up to 20m on open coasts, offshore or in estuaries and marine inlets. Such habitats are often subject to a degree of wave action or currents which restrict the silt and clay content to less than 15%. Depending on the grain size composition, the sands are coarse-grained, medium-grained, fine-grained, and sandy mud. The habitat of the shallow sandy bottom is characterised by a significant biodiversity of species and biological communities.

MB541: Estuarine infralittoral sands are found in front of the large rivers in the Northwest Black Sea; they form an important habitat type, often with underwater dunes. This habitat also occurs in association with smaller rivers.

MB542: Sandy habitats dominated by faunal species occurring in the infralittoral zone down to 20m in depth with a lot of variations. These range from medium to coarse grained sands on exposed beaches to offshore infralittoral fine sand banks and include many types of surface features at different scales (banks, ripples, mounds and burrows of infauna). The depth and waves or current exposure are important elements in defining the species composition.

MB543: Non-cohesive muddy sand (with 5% to 20% silt/clay) in the lower infralittoral zone. This habitat is dominated by faunal species including ghost shrimps and bivalves.

MB544: This habitat is typically found in sheltered environments close to the coast, most commonly in deltas, bays, estuaries or lagoons. Due to the low energy environments, algal species are able to form stands on the sediment surface. These algal stands are typically characterised by lamina green algae species of the genera *Ulva* and *Cladophora*.

MB545: Infralittoral sands and muddy sands with unattached forms of macroalgae, in particular the ball-like form of the red algae species *Phyllophora crispa* var. *sphaerica*. The classic example of this habitat is the Small *Phyllophora* field (SPF) National Botanical Reserve, which lies in shallow waters (less than 16m) on sand with shells in the Karkinitsky Bay, Ukraine.

MB546: See the description in this report.

MB547: See the description in this report.

MB548: See the description in this report.

Characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are:

- *Zostera noltii* meadows (1-3m).
- *Zostera marina* meadows (4-7m).
- Mixed meadows with *Zostera noltii*-*Zannichellia palustris*-*Zostera marina* meadows (2-4m).
- *Stuckenia pectinata* - *Zannichellia palustris* meadows in man-made sheltered areas.

- Upper-infralittoral (1-7m) medium and fine sand dominated by *Donax trunculus*.
- Infralittoral (at depths of 5-15m) fine and medium sand, dominated by *Chamelea gallina*; other typical species include *Lentidium mediterraneum*, *Macomangulus tenuis*, *Lucinella divaricata*;
- Lower infralittoral (at depths of 13-24m) coarse and medium sand, dominated by *Upogebia pusilla*.

Characteristic species

MB541: This habitat is characterised mainly by euryhaline species: *Gammarus marinus*, *Idothea tricuspidata*, *Dikerogammarus haemobaphes*, *Palaemon adspersus*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Bittium reticulatum* are common. The biocenosis of sands with *Cerastoderma* and *Monodacna* is typical for the Grigorievsky, Tiligulsky, and Berezansky estuaries.

MB542: *Donax trunculus*, *Upogebia pusilla*, *Lentidium mediterraneum*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Mya arenaria*, *Chamelea gallina*, *Tellina tenuis*, *Anadara inaequalis*, *Cyclope neritea*, *Arenicola marina*, *Callianassidae*, *Gouldia minima*, *Donax semistriatus*, *Modiolus adriaticus*, *Solen marginatus* amphipods and *Aonides ornatus*.

MB543: *Upogebia pusilla*, *Mya arenaria*, *Anadara inaequalis*, *Abra alba*, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Pitar rudis*.

MB544: *Ulva* spp. and *Cladophora* spp.

MB545: Macrophyte species diversity is not high, comprising about 20 species, chiefly *Zostera noltii* and *Phyllophora crispa*.

MB546: See the description in this report.

MB547: See the description in this report.

MB548: See the description in this report.

Associated species

Within this habitat, seagrasses are edifiers that create a habitat for diverse epiphytic algal flora (Chlorophyta: *Cladophora* sp., *Ulva* sp.; Rhodophyta: *Ceramium* sp., *Chondria* sp.; Phaeophyta: *Ectocarpus siliquosus*, Heterokontophyta: *Polysiphonia subulifera*; *Gongolaria barbata*) and invertebrate fauna (*Botryllus schlosseri*, gastropods *Hydrobia acuta*, *Rissoa membranacea*, *Bittium reticulatum*, *Cyclope pellucida*, *Cytherea costulata*; crustaceans *Dexamine spinosa*, *Diogenes pugilator*, *Gammarus* sp.; polychaetes *Capitella capitata*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Lagis koreni*, *Nephtys* sp., *Prionospio* sp., *Syllis gracilis*) and the growth of the larvae of various fish and mollusc species.

The *Phyllophora* beds support a specialised fauna of more than 110 species of invertebrates and 47 species of fish, which use the alga for breeding, food and shelter. In 2000, the main groups of macrozoobenthos recorded from the Small *Phyllophora* Field in terms of number of species, abundance and biomass were molluscs, polychaetes and crustaceans; the most common species (with an occurrence of 60%) were *Mytilaster linneatus*, *Bittium reticulatum*, *Harmothoe reticulata*, *Nereis zonata* and *Synisoma capito*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication from nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure (between the 1970s and early 2000s), affecting the status and distribution of this habitat, resulting in a decrease in water transparency, opportunistic green and red algal blooms, as well as bottom hypoxia, and which led to a degradation of phytobenthic communities. Since the 1990s, this pressure has reduced due to the reduced inflow of pollutants into the catchment, especially in the northwestern and western part of the Black Sea.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Dredging activities and construction works at the area of ports and *marinas*, or construction of hydrotechnical facilities, causing siltation, and smothering.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling causes habitat destruction; trawling causes deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic communities both directly and indirectly through effects such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics).
- Extraction of seafloor and subsoil minerals (e.g., sand, gravel, oil, gas).
- Hydrological changes, caused by changes to freshwater inputs.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter) remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.

This habitat has a low resilience towards climate change and related effects, such as global warming and sea level rise, as well as to flood events causing the input of suspended solids and leading to siltation and reduced light penetration. At the same time, this habitat is essential for climate change mitigation, due to its capacity to capture carbon.

Best practices in nature restoration

This habitat shows good potential of recovering naturally when the water quality is improved and the hydrological regime is stable. Therefore, conservation and management measures related to the regulation of fisheries, reducing the nutrients enrichment (waste water treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) and reduction in suspended sediments are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MB64. Black Sea infralittoral mud

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MB64](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Infralittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA5.33, <BLSA5.34

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB641](#), [MB642](#)

BG:

>Infralittoral mud with

Melinna palmata

General description

Infralittoral muds are predominantly found in sheltered harbours, bays, marine inlets and estuaries, and stable deeper areas where the reduced influence of wave action allow fine sediments to settle. Two habitat subtypes are distinguished:

MB641: Fine muddy habitats situated in the lower infralittoral zone in front of the estuaries of the large rivers (Danube, Dnepr, Bug) discharging into the Northwestern Black Sea shelf. These fine muds mixed with terrestrial and freshwater detritus form soft, unstable deposits. Where the sediment content is lower in detritic organic particles, terrigenous muds are more stable and stickier. This habitat is populated by bivalve molluscs and polychaetes adapted to living in very soft substrata with high organic content.

MB642: This habitat is presented by mud and sandy mud substrates, mixed with terrestrial and freshwater detritus, and is inhabited by bivalve molluscs and polychaete worms.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Infralittoral mud (7-18m) with *Mya arenaria*, *Anadara kagoshimensis*, *Upogebia pussila*, *Nephtys* sp., *Melinna palmata* and other polychaetes” (Romania), and “Infralittoral mud (9-25 m) dominated by *Aricidea claudiae*, *Prionospio maciolekae*, *Melinna palmata* and *Lucinella*” (Türkiye).

Detailed information on the abundance and extent of the habitat is scarce.

Characteristic species

MB641: *Neanthes succinea*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Abra prismatica*, *Mysella bidentata*, *Abra alba*, *Acanthocardium paucicostatum*.

MB642: *Melinna palmata*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Pitar rudis*, *Terebellides stroemii*, *Aricidea claudiae*, *Abra* sp., *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus*.

Associated species

The invasive species *Rapana venosa* is essential for habitat status and distribution, as *Rapana* predation pressure can lead to the destruction of mussel beds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

A significant threat is also the predatory pressure of the invasive species *Rapana venosa*, which can lead to the destruction of black mussel colonies.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Bottom trawling and dredging, which cause habitat destruction and reduction in the extent and quality.
- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Plastic micro-particles pollution can be ingested and lead to mortality of the benthic macroinvertebrate fauna.
- The predatory press of the invasive species *R. venosa*.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices within the adjacent watersheds) are of high importance.

To reduce the predatory press of *Rapana venosa*, in the Marine Strategies of Bulgaria and Romania, coordinated measure is planned for the promotion and stimulation (including financial) of environmentally friendly methods for *Rapana* and shellfish extraction.

Strengthening research to assess and monitor changes in distribution, habitat fragmentation and the state, composition, and structure of the communities, will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[Biserkov, V., et al. \(Eds.\) 2015. Red Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 3. Natural habitats.](#)

[BLSA5.33 Pontic infralittoral terrigenous muds.](#)

[BLSA5.34 Pontic infralittoral fine mud.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[Information system for protected areas from the Natura 2000 ecological network \(BG\).](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Teodorof, M., Adrian, F., Dumitrache, C., Abaza V., 2022. The macrozoobenthic species of the infralittoral and circalittoral zone from the Romanian Black Sea coast – a qualitative and quantitative assessment.](#)

Todorova, V., et al., 2021. [Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MC34. Black Sea circalittoral coarse sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC34](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Circalittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Shelly sands and gravels with *Modiolus adriaticus* and *Gouldia minima*

General description

This habitat type describes circalittoral coarse sands, gravel, and shingle generally in depths of over 15-20m. This habitat may be found in tidal channels of marine inlets, along exposed coasts and offshore. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, this habitat is more broadly distributed in the central and southern parts, characterised by spatial heterogeneity represented by variously grained sands (detailed stratigraphy is missing); in the northern part, this habitat is represented by clean shell debris deposited at the edge of the rocky bottoms. The central part of the Northwestern Black Sea shelf area is characterised by very low rates of sediment accumulation. Shelly sediments occasionally mixed with a small amount of muddy material are widespread here. The top layers are usually shells covered with carbonate and thin Fe-Mn crusts.

This habitat may be characterised by robust infaunal polychaetes, mobile crustacea, and bivalves.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Shallow circalittoral (at depths of 17-35m) shelly gravel and coarse sand with varied infauna (typical *Modiolus adriaticus*, *Gouldia minima*)”, and “Shallow circalittoral shelly organogenic sand with *Mytilus* biogenic reefs and filamentous/folious algae (*Phyllophora* field of Zernov; Ukraine)”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Depending on the prevailing substrate, biological communities are represented by the bivalves *Modiolus adriaticus*, *Gouldia minima*; *Mytilus* biogenic reefs and filamentous/folious algae; polychaetes *Prionospio maciolekae*, *Magelona longicornis* and *Heteromastus filiformis*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling, which causes habitat destruction; trawling, which causes

deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic communities both directly and indirectly through effects such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[Begun, T., Teacă A. et al. 2022. Habitat and Macrozoobenthic Diversity in Marine Protected Areas of the Southern Romanian Black Sea Coast.](#)

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

[Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.](#)

[Oaie, G., Secieru, D., Shimkus, K., 2004. Black Sea Basin: Sediment types and distribution, sedimentation processes.](#)

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MC44. Black Sea circalittoral mixed sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC44](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Circalittoral mixed sediment

HD: #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Shelly sands and gravels with *Modiolus adriaticus* and *Gouldia minima*

>Sands and muddy sands with *Chamelea gallina*

>Muddy sands with *Upogebia pusilla*

General description

This habitat type describes mixed (heterogeneous) sediment habitats in the circalittoral zone at a depth of 20m to 40m including well-mixed muddy gravelly sands or very poorly sorted mosaics of shells, cobbles, and pebbles embedded in or lying upon mud, sand, or gravel. Due to the variable nature of the seabed, a variety of communities can develop, which are often very diverse. It is expected that this habitat is most widespread in the north and west of the Black Sea.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Shallow circalittoral shelly muddy sand/sandy mud with *Upogebia pusilla*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Aricidea claudiae*, *Chamelea gallina*, *Anadara inaequalis*, *Mya arenaria*”, and “Shallow circalittoral (at depths of 20-40m) shelly sandy mud/mud with *Pitar rudis*, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Paphia aurea*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Abra* spp., *Cardiidae*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Heteromastus filiformis*”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Depending on the prevailing substrate, biological communities are represented by:

- Shallow circalittoral shelly muddy sand/sandy mud: *Upogebia pusilla*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Aricidea claudiae*, *Chamelea gallina*, *Anadara inaequalis*, *Mya arenaria*.
- Shallow circalittoral shelly sandy mud/mud: *Pitar rudis*, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Paphia aurea*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Abra* spp., *Cardiidae*, *Nephtys hombergii*, *Heteromastus filiformis*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling, which causes habitat destruction; trawling, which causes deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic

communities both directly and indirectly through effects such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MC54. Black Sea circalittoral sand

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC54](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Circalittoral sand

HD: #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA5.26

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC541](#)

BG:

>Shelly sands and gravels with *Modiolus adriaticus* and *Gouldia minima*

>Sands and muddy sands with *Chamelea gallina*

>Muddy sands with *Upogebia pusilla*

General description

Circalittoral sands and muddy sands with animal dominated communities are widespread in the shelf zone at a depth of 20m to 40m. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the habitat is more broadly distributed in the central and southern parts, represented by variously grained sands (detailed stratigraphy is missing).

MC541: Non-cohesive muddy sand (with 20% to 80% of silt/clay) in the circalittoral zone. This habitat is characterised by low light and low energy conditions. Species include bivalve and polychaete worms.

Characteristic species

Modiolus adriaticus, *Gouldia minima*, *Chamelea gallina*, *Upogebia pusilla*.

MC541: *Mya arenaria*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Abra alba*, *Parvicardium exiguum*, *Spisula subtruncatna*, *Pitar rudis* and *Aricidea claudiae*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear: mobile demersal dredging and trawling, which causes habitat destruction; trawling, which causes deterioration and habitat destruction by damaging benthic communities both directly and indirectly through effects such as smothering and altering the sediment characteristics.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MC64. Black Sea circalittoral mud

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MC64](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Circalittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1160

European Red List:

<BLSA5.xZ, <BLSA5.35,

<BLSA5.36 Pontic upper

circalittoral fine mud,

<BLSA5.37

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MC641](#), [MC643](#),

[MC644](#), [MC645](#)

BG:

>Upper circalittoral muds with *Nephtys*, *Pitar*, *Spisula*, *Abra*, etc.

>Lower circalittoral mud with *Terebellides stroemi*

>Peripheral shelf mud with *Oligochaeta*

General description

The circalittoral mud and cohesive sandy mud are predominantly found in sheltered harbours, bays, marine inlets, estuaries, and stable deeper/offshore areas where the reduced influence of wave action and currents allows settlement of the fine sediments. The sediment type varies between terrigenous muds, calcareous muds, and biogenic detritic. The muds themselves are heterogeneous, with variable structural characteristics.

Terrigenous muds are the predominant substrate in the Bulgarian shelf, occasionally mixed with shell sediments. Mud, silty mud, and sandy silt dominate in the Kerch area, between the Ukraine and Russia. In the Coruh Polygon area (Georgia), the sediments are represented mainly by mud and silt, and are greatly disturbed by biological activity. Similar sediment types, with the local addition of a significant sandy fraction, are present in the Sinop area (Türkiye). Shell detritus is a constant component of the sediments.

MC641: Terrigenous sediments (with terrestrial origin) generally consist of sand, mud and silt carried to the sea by watercourses, and their composition is usually related to their source material. Terrigenous muds are most abundant in the shelf zone.

MC643: Sandy muds occur in the upper circalittoral zone below the photic zone at depths between 20m and 50m. The habitat is characterised by faunal communities dominated by bivalve molluscs and polychaete worms.

MC644: Fine muds in the upper circalittoral zone. There is no light influence. This habitat is characterised by faunal communities dominated by bivalves and polychaete worms.

MC645: This habitat occurs at depths of 50m to 130-180m. The benthic fauna is dominated by bean mussels *Modiolula phaseolina*, polychaetes, and solitary ascidians. The polychaetes are presented by the highest number of species, among them *Terebellides stroemii* and *Aonides paucibranchiata* are registered as dominant. A total of 70 macrozoobenthic species are identified within the habitat of the Romanian continental shelf (Tanase and Filimon, 2023).

As the depth increases, the species richness of the zoocenosis decreases. At a depth below 100m, the fauna is very poor, represented mainly by nematodes, oligochaetes, and rarely polychaetes. The conditions are characterised by a reduced content of dissolved oxygen as a result of the stratification of water masses.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Shallow circalittoral mud dominated by *Melinna palmata*”, “Shallow circalittoral mud and organogenic sandy mud with *Gouldia minima*, *Pitar rudis*, *Aricidea claudiae*”, and “Deep circalittoral (depths of 60-100 m) shelly mud with *Modiolula phaseolina*”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

MC641: *Abra alba*, *Acanthocardium paucicostatum*, *Plagiocardium papillosum*.

MC643: *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Dipolydora quadrilobata*, *Nephtys hombergii* and *Spisula subtruncata*.

MC644: *Mya arenaria*, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Melinna palmata*, *Heteromastus filiformis* and *Aricidea claudiae*.

MC645: *Modiolula phaseolina*, *Abra alba*, *Papillicardium papillosum*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*, *Phoronis psammophila*, *Terebellides stroemi*, *Notomastus profundus*, solitary ascidians (*Ascidella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*, *Eugyra*), hydrozoans (*Bougainvillia ramosa*), nematodes, polychaetes, and oligochaetes.

Associated species

Other species presented in the lower circalittoral zone, due to their large ecological plasticity, are polychaetes *Nephtys hombergii*, *Harmothoe reticulata*, *Exogone naidina* and amphipods *Ampelisca* sp., *Microdeutopus damnoniensis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear in the shallower zone.
- Sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures relevant to this habitat include measures to maintain physical and biological integrity, and to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance.

Strengthening the research activity to establish and follow-up the changes in the distribution of the habitat, and monitoring the state, composition, and structure of the communities will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Oaie, G., Secieru, D., Shimkus, K., 2004. Black Sea Basin: Sediment types and distribution, sedimentation processes.](#)

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Tanase M., Filimon A., Dumitrache C. and Abaza V., 2023. Current Status of Zoobenthic Communities Associated with Deep Circalittoral Habitats from the Romanian Continental Shelf.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MD34. Black Sea offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MD34](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): =Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

Offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with coarse sands and gravel or shell are quite diverse, depending on the local hydrodynamic regime and geological and geomorphological characteristics and sources of nourishment. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the offshore circalittoral coarse sediments occur at depths of 60-90m to 100-120m. Unevenly distributed, significant accumulations of biogenic shell detritus, represented by whole shells and detritus of *Dreissena*, are observed among the muddy deposits. The muds themselves are heterogeneous, with variable structural characteristics. The fauna is generally characterised by robust infaunal polychaete and bivalve species.

Characteristic species

Typical inhabitants are some infaunal polychaete and bivalve species.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Given that the distribution and status of the habitat and the inhabiting communities are insufficiently studied, it is difficult to assess the degree of impact of human activities and the necessary mitigation measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MD44. Black Sea offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MD44](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): =Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Shelly muds with *Modiolula phaseolina*

General description

Offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with slightly muddy mixed gravelly sand and stones or shell are diverse, depending on the local hydrodynamic regime and geological and geomorphological characteristics and sources of nourishment. Along the western coastline of the Black Sea, the offshore circalittoral mixed sediments occur at depths of 60-90m to 100-130m, with a predominant distribution in the northern part of the shelf.

The benthic fauna is dominated by bean mussels *Modiolula phaseolina*, polychaetes and solitary ascidians. As the depth increases, the species richness of the zoocenosis decreases. At a depth below 100m, the fauna is very poor, represented mainly by nematodes, oligochaetes and rarely polychaetes. The conditions are characterised by a reduced content of dissolved oxygen as a result of the stratification of water masses.

The characteristic habitat subtype, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD is "Deep circalittoral (60-100m) shelly mud with *Modiolula phaseolina*".

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Typical species are *Modiolula phaseolina*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, *Notomastus profundus*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local Character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Given that the distribution and status of the habitat and the inhabiting communities are insufficiently studied, it is difficult to assess the degree of impact of human activities and the necessary mitigation measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MD54. Black Sea offshore circalittoral sand

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MD54](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Offshore circalittoral sand

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat type describes offshore (deep) circalittoral habitats with fine sands or non-cohesive muddy sands. Although very little data is available on the occurrence, distribution, and specific characteristics of these habitats, they are likely to be more stable than their shallower counterparts, and to be characterised by a diverse range of polychaetes, amphipods, bivalves and echinoderms.

Characteristic species

No specific information is available.

Associated species

N/A

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions affect the extent and the status of the habitat.

Another potential threat is the sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures related to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance for this habitat.

Given that the distribution and status of the habitat and the inhabiting communities are insufficiently studied, it is difficult to assess the degree of impact of human activities and the necessary mitigation measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

Group 7

MD64. Black Sea offshore circalittoral mud

Black Sea

EUNIS code: [MD64](#)

EUNIS level: 4

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: =Offshore circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

BG:

>Lower circalittoral mud with *Terebellides stroemi*,
>Peripheral shelf mud with Oligochaeta

General description

The habitat occurs at depths of 50m to 130-180m. The sediment type varies between terrigenous muds, calcareous muds and biogenic detritic. Terrigenous muds are most abundant in the shelf zone. The muds themselves are heterogeneous, with variable structural characteristics.

The benthic fauna is dominated by bean mussels *Modiolula phaseolina*, polychaetes, and solitary ascidians. The polychaetes are presented by the highest number of species, among them *Terebellides stroemii* and *Aonides paucibranchiata* are registered as dominant. A total of 70 macrozoobenthic species are identified within the habitat of the Romanian continental shelf (Tanase et al.,2023).

As the depth increases, the species richness of the zoocenosis decreases. At a depth below 100m, the fauna is very poor, represented mainly by nematodes, oligochaetes and rarely polychaetes. The conditions are characterised by a reduced content of dissolved oxygen as a result of the stratification of water masses.

The characteristic habitat subtypes, including specific biological communities, identified to be assessed at the national and regional level under the criteria of the MSFD are “Deep circalittoral mud (at depths of 40-90m) with *Terebellides stroemi*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*”, and “Deep circalittoral suboxic muds”.

Detailed information on the distribution, and specific habitat characteristics, including historical or recent trends, is lacking.

Characteristic species

Modiolula phaseolina, *Abra alba*, *Papillicardium papillosum*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*, *Phoronis psammophila*, *Terebellides stroemi*, *Notomastus profundus*, solitary ascidians (*Asciella aspersa*, *Ciona intestinalis*, *Eugyra*), hydrozoans (*Bougainvillia ramosa*), nematodes, polychaetes, and oligochaetes.

Associated species

Other species presented, due to their large ecological plasticity, are polychaetes *Nephtys hombergii*, *Harmothoe reticulata*, *Exogone naidina* and amphipods *Ampelisca* sp., *Microdeutopus damnoniensis*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Eutrophication because of nutrient enrichment (N, P) is the most significant historic pressure affecting the habitat status and distribution. Anoxic and hypoxic conditions caused mass mortalities of the macroinvertebrate fauna.

Pressures and threats of current and future importance affecting the habitat are:

- Nutrient enrichment (N, P, organic matter), which remains a current pressure, even at a lower intensity.
- Fishing with active bottom gear in the shallower zone.
- Sealing and smothering of habitats due to the accumulation of waste on the seabed of a local character, according to the relief of the seabed and the hydrodynamic conditions.

Best practices in nature restoration

Conservation and management measures relevant to this habitat include measures to maintain physical and biological integrity, and to reducing nutrients enrichment (wastewater treatment, good agricultural practices), and prevention of waste pollution at the marine region level are of high importance.

Strengthening the research activity to establish and follow-up the changes in the distribution of the habitat, and monitoring the state, composition, and structure of the communities will allow the most effective planning of the necessary specific measures.

Bibliographic sources

[EEA, 2022a. EUNIS marine habitat classification 2022 including crosswalks.](#)

[EEA, 2022b. EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows.](#)

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

[IO-BAS, 2021. Bulgaria, Updated assessment of the state of the marine environment. \("Update of the first part of the Marine Strategy, according to Art. 8 on the state of the marine environment, Art. 9 on the GES definition and Art. 10 – determination of environmental targets and related indicators"\).](#)

Moncheva, S., et al., 2013. IO-BAS Initial assessment of the state of the marine environment, according to Art. 8 of MSFD 2008/56/EO.

[Romania, National report on the ecological state of the Black Sea marine ecosystem according to the requirements of art. 17 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive \(2008/56/EC\), 2018.](#)

[Todorova, V., et al., 2021. Black Sea monitoring and assessment guideline. ANEMONE Deliverable 1.3, Ed. CD PRESS, 190 pp. ISBN 978-606-528-527-9.](#)

[Tanase M., Filimon A., Dumitrache C. and Abaza V., 2023. Current Status of Zoobenthic Communities Associated with Deep Circalittoral Habitats from the Romanian Continental Shelf.](#)

Figure 07-03, *Talitrus saltator* on Mediterranean sand

Source: *Talitrus saltator*, © faluke, 2023

Group 7

MA35. Mediterranean littoral coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA3.5

General description

Mediterranean littoral coarse sediments include shores of mobile pebbles, cobbles and gravel, with varying amounts of coarse sand. The sediment is extremely mobile and subject to high degrees of drying between tides.

This habitat may feature supralittoral associations with macrophytes (and related deposits of dead leaves and slowly drying wracks). Wracks and banks made by marine phanerogams, leaves, algae and other debris can be washed up and deposited in this zone.

Characteristic species

Few species can survive in this environment, as the rapid drainage and the instability of the substrate limit the characteristic species to a small number of highly adapted macrophytes. In the supralittoral portion, this habitat may host associations characterised by halophytic vegetation, strongly influenced by sand mobility, soil salinity, water availability, nutrient status, and temperature.

The fauna of the upper mediolittoral beaches with stones and pebbles is basically made up of scavengers (e.g., the amphipod *Pectenogammarus olivii* and the isopod *Sphaeroma serratum*) of detritus and their predators; therefore, it is essentially unstable as it is highly dependent on the quality and quantity of detritus and sediment retained by the sediment.

Associated species

The common reed *Phragmites australis*, the spiny rush *Juncus acutus* and *Carex arenaria*, and other sand grasses and sedges can be abundant.

The fauna associated to banks of dead leaves of macrophytes (and to deposits and wracks) is temporary and is mainly composed of detritivores, scavenging species and their predators (such as sea birds). The main macrofaunal taxa are represented by insects, *Araneae* dwelling spiders, crustaceans *Amphipoda* (e.g., *Orchestia* spp.), *Isopoda* (e.g., *Halophiloscia couchii*, *Tylos ponticus*) and *Decapoda*, molluscs (Gastropoda, e.g., *Truncatella subcylindrica*) and *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Abra alba*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Loripes orbiculatus*), *Polychaeta*, *Oligochaeta*, and *Sipuncula*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is highly vulnerable to various anthropogenic pressures along the coast, such as trampling and waste. The main threats are linked to coastal development and urban activities (direct destruction for land reclaim, dredging, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, pollution, eutrophication), living resources exploitation, global warming and sea-level rise.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Acosta, A.T.R., Ercole, S., Stanisci, A., De Patta, Pillar, V., Blasi C., 2007b. Coastal vegetation zonation and dune morphology in some mediterranean ecosystems. *Journal of Coastal Research* 23 (6), 1518-1524.

Farris, E., Pisanu, S., Ceccherelli, G., Filigheddu, R., 2013. Human trampling effects on Mediterranean coastal dune plants. *Plant Biosystems* 147 (4), 1043-1051.

Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Acosta, A.T.R., 2013. The fate of threatened coastal dune habitats in Italy under climate change scenarios. *PLOS ONE* 8 (7), e68850.

Santoro, R., Jucker, T., Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Battisti, C., Acosta, A.T.R., 2012. Effects of trampling limitation on coastal dune plant communities, *Environmental Management* 49, 534-542.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MA45. Mediterranean littoral mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA45](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1140, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA4.5

General description

This habitat type describes Mediterranean shores of poorly sorted mixed sediments, ranging from muds with gravel and sand components to mixed sediments with pebbles, gravels, sands and mud in more even proportions. Gravel mud may occur in patches on mudflats, with broad transition areas between areas of mudflat or sandy mudflat. Similarly, there is no easily defined boundary between areas of mixed sediment with stable large cobbles or boulders.

This habitat may feature supralittoral associations with macrophytes (and related deposits of dead leaves and slowly drying wracks). The littoral pioneer vegetation enhances particle trapping and organic matter accumulation, contributing to the development of the dune systems, reducing turbulence and, thus, sediment erosion. Wracks and banks made by marine phanerogams, leaves, algae and other debris can be washed up and deposited in this zone.

Characteristic species

In the supralittoral portion, this habitat may host associations characterised by halophytic vegetation, dominated by psammophilous-halophilous species (e.g., *Cakile maritima*, *Salsola* spp., *Thinopyrum junceum*, *Euphorbia peplis* and *Calamagrostis arenaria*) made by emerging and rooting perennial plants able to tolerate some extent of salt concentration and with a wide ecological range.

Mixed sediments that are predominantly muddy tend to support infaunal communities. Habitats with sheltered gravel sandy mud, which are subject to reduced salinity, mainly on the mid and lower shore, may have abundant communities of polychaetes (e.g., *Aphelochaeta marioni*, *Capitella capitata*, *Cirriformia tentaculata*, *Sphaerosyllis taylori*, *Pygospio elegans*), bivalves (e.g., *Cerastoderma edule*, *Abra nitida*), oligochaetes (e.g., *Tubificoides pseudogaster*), crustaceans (e.g., *Aora gracilis*, *Melita palmata*, *Microtopopus maculatus*, *Corophium volutator*).

The fauna of the upper mediolittoral beaches with stones and pebbles is basically made up of scavengers of detritus and their predators; therefore, it is essentially unstable as it is highly dependent on the quality and quantity of detritus and sediment retained by the sediment. It is mainly characterised by two crustaceans, the amphipod *Pectenogammarus olivii* and the isopod *Sphaeroma serratum*, while stable boulders support epibiota such as fucoids and green seaweeds which are more commonly found on rocky shores.

In its lower mediolittoral part, below the mean sea water level and maintained wet by the waves, this habitat may overlap the shallower portion of marine angiosperms' meadows.

Associated species

The common reed *Phragmites australis*, the spiny rush *Juncus acutus* and *Carex arenaria*, and other sand grasses and sedges can be abundant.

The fauna associated to banks of dead leaves of macrophytes (and to deposits and wracks) is temporary and is made up mainly by detritivores, scavenging species and their predators (such as sea birds). The main macrofaunal taxa are represented by insects, *Araneae* dwelling spiders, crustaceans *Amphipoda* (e.g., *Orchestia* spp.), *Isopoda* (e.g., *Halophiloscia couchii*, *Tylos ponticus*) and *Decapoda*, molluscs (Gastropoda, e.g., *Truncatella subcylindrica*) and *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Abra alba*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Loripes orbiculatus*), *Polychaeta*, *Oligochaeta*, and *Sipuncula*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is highly vulnerable to various anthropogenic pressures along the coast, such as trampling and waste. The main threats are linked to coastal development and urban activities (direct destruction for land reclaim, dredging, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, pollution, eutrophication), living resources exploitation, global warming and sea-level rise.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Acosta, A.T.R., Ercole, S., Stanisci, A., De Patta, Pillar, V., Blasi C., 2007. Coastal vegetation zonation and dune morphology in some mediterranean ecosystems. *Journal of Coastal Research* 23 (6), 1518-1524.

Farris, E., Pisanu, S., Ceccherelli, G., Filigheddu, R., 2013. Human trampling effects on Mediterranean coastal dune plants. *Plant Biosystems* 147 (4), 1043-1051.

Forey, E., Chapelet, B., Vitasse, Y., Tilquin, M., Touzard, B., Michalet, R., 2008. The relative importance of disturbance and environmental stress at local and regional scales in French coastal sand dunes. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 19, 493-502.

Poeta, G., Battisti, C., Acosta, A., 2014. Marine litter in Mediterranean sandy littorals: spatial distribution patterns along central Italy coastal dunes. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 89 (1-2), 168-173.

Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Acosta, A.T.R., 2013. The fate of threatened coastal dune habitats in Italy under climate change scenarios. *PLOS ONE* 8 (7), e68850.

Santoro, R., Jucker, T., Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Battisti, C., Acosta, A.T.R., 2012. Effects of trampling limitation on coastal dune plant communities, *Environmental Management* 49, 534-542.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MA55. Mediterranean littoral sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150⁵⁴, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA5.5

General description

This habitat type describes Mediterranean sands of the supralittoral and mediolittoral zones. It may feature supralittoral associations with macrophytes (and related deposits of dead leaves and slowly drying wracks), and mediolittoral associations with indigenous marine angiosperms. The littoral pioneer vegetation enhances particle trapping and organic matter accumulation, contributing to the development of the dune systems, reducing turbulence and, thus, sediment erosion. Wracks and banks made by marine phanerogams, leaves, algae and other debris can be washed up and deposited in this zone.

In transitional waters (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets, marshes, littoral ponds) of the mediolittoral zone, associations with halophytic vegetation, mainly composed by succulent and perennial plants (which are able to evade and/or tolerate salinity) and/or with highly tolerant marine angiosperms may occur and develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea. They are particularly abundant in the Northwestern Adriatic Sea, where the habitats of transitional waters are dominant.

Characteristic species

In the supralittoral portion, humected by the sea only during storms and by salty spray from waves, this habitat may host associations characterised by halophytic vegetation, dominated by psammophylous-halophilous species (e.g., *Cakile maritima*, *Salsola* spp., *Thinopyrum junceum*, *Euphorbia peplis* and *Calamagrostis arenaria*) made by emerging and rooting perennial plants able to tolerate some extent of salt concentration and with a wide ecological range.

A characteristic species of unvegetated supralittoral sand is *Talitrus saltator*. Mediollittoral sands are characterised by the annelids *Ophelia radiata* and *Scolecopsis (Scolecopsis) squamata*, the isopod crustacean *Eurydice affinis* and the pelecypod mollusc *Donacilla cornea*.

In its lower mediollittoral part, below the mean sea water level and maintained in a wet state by the waves, this habitat may lap the shallower part of marine angiosperms' meadows (in particular, indigenous *Cymodocea nodosa* or the Lessepsian seagrass *Halophila stipulacea*). *C. nodosa* lives both along the coasts with considerable salinity and in coastal areas with hypoaline waters, especially in the presence of well sorted fine sands.

In transitional waters, the most abundant halophytes are *Sarcocornia* spp., *Salicornia* spp., *Limonium* spp., *Halimione portulacoides*, *Juncus* spp., *Spartina* spp., *Suaeda* spp., *Salsola* spp., *Kochia* spp., *Arthrocnemum macrostachyum*, *Atriplex portulacoides*, and *Scirpus* spp. Physiochemical proprieties of transitional intertidal habitats are stressful for most angiosperms, as only few species can tolerate the anoxic, chemically reduced, high-saline soils typical of these ecosystems, such as *Zostera* spp. and *Ruppia* spp.

⁵⁴ When occurring in transitional environments.

Associated species

The common reed *Phragmites australis*, the spiny rush *Juncus acutus* and *Carex arenaria*, and other sand grasses and sedges can be abundant.

The fauna associated to banks of dead leaves of macrophytes (and to deposits and wracks) is temporary and is made up mainly by detritivores, scavenging species and their predators (such as sea birds). The main macrofaunal taxa are represented by insects, *Araneae* dwelling spiders, crustaceans *Amphipoda* (e.g., *Orchestia* spp.), *Isopoda* (e.g., *Halophiloscia couchii*, *Tylos ponticus*) and *Decapoda*, molluscs (Gastropoda, e.g., *Truncatella subcylindrica*) and *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Abra alba*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Loripes orbiculatus*), *Polychaeta*, *Oligochaeta*, and *Sipuncula*.

Associated communities to marine angiosperms can be distinguished in sessile species living on the leaf blade (epiphytes), and vagile associated species such as gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, polychaetes, and fishes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This habitat is highly vulnerable to various anthropogenic pressures along the coast, such as trampling and waste. The main threats are linked to coastal development and urban activities (direct destruction for land reclaim, dredging, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, pollution, eutrophication), living resources exploitation, global warming and sea-level rise.

Cymodocea nodosa is listed in Annex II "List of endangered or threatened species" to the SPA/BD Protocol.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Acosta, A.T.R., Ercole, S., Stanisci, A., De Patta, Pillar, V., Blasi C., 2007. Coastal vegetation zonation and dune morphology in some mediterranean ecosystems. *Journal of Coastal Research* 23 (6), 1518-1524.

Farris, E., Pisanu, S., Ceccherelli, G., Filigheddu, R., 2013. Human trampling effects on Mediterranean coastal dune plants. *Plant Biosystems* 147 (4), 1043-1051.

Forey, E., Chapelet, B., Vitasse, Y., Tilquin, M., Touzard, B., Michalet, R., 2008. The relative importance of disturbance and environmental stress at local and regional scales in French coastal sand dunes. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 19, 493-502.

Orfanidis, S., Papathanasiou, V., Gounaris, S., Theodosiou, T., 2010. Size distribution approaches for monitoring and conservation of coastal *Cymodocea* habitats. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 20 (2), 177-188.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C.N., Boudouresque, C.F., Buia, M.C., Clabaut, P., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Mateo, M.A., Montefalcone, M., Morri, C., Orfanidis, S., Pergent-Martini, C., Semroud, R., Serrano, O., Verlaque, M., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Mediterranee. Resilience et contribution a l'attenuation des changements climatiques. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Poeta, G., Battisti, C., Acosta, A., 2014. Marine litter in Mediterranean sandy littorals: spatial distribution patterns along central Italy coastal dunes. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 89 (1-2), 168-173.

Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Acosta, A.T.R., 2013. The fate of threatened coastal dune habitats in Italy under climate change scenarios. *PLOS ONE* 8 (7), e68850.

Santoro, R., Jucker, T., Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Battisti, C., Acosta, A.T.R., 2012. Effects of trampling limitation on coastal dune plant communities, *Environmental Management* 49, 534-542.

Sfriso, A., Facca, C., Bonometto, A., Boscolo, R., 2014. Compliance of the Macrophyte Quality index (MaQI) with the WFD (2000/60/EC) and ecological status assessment in transitional areas: The Venice lagoon as study case'5, *Ecological Indicators* 46, 536-547.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MA65. Mediterranean littoral mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MA65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Littoral sediment

HD: #1130, #1140, #1150, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA6.5

General description

This habitat type describes Mediterranean shores of fine particulate sediment, mostly in the silt and clay fraction (particle size less than 0.063mm in diameter), though sandy mud may contain up to 40% sand (mostly very fine and fine sand). Littoral mud typically forms extensive mudflats, though dry compacted mud can form steep and even vertical structures, particularly at the top of the shore adjacent to saltmarshes.

This habitat may feature supralittoral associations with macrophytes (and related deposits of dead leaves and slowly drying wracks). Wracks and banks made by marine phanerogams, leaves, algae and other debris can be washed up and deposited in this zone.

In transitional waters (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets, marshes, littoral ponds) of the mediolittoral zone, associations with halophytic vegetation, mainly composed by succulent and perennial plants (able to evade and/or tolerate salinity) and/or with highly tolerant marine angiosperms may occur and develop at the scale of the whole Mediterranean Sea (they are particularly abundant in estuaries, such as the Ebro (Spain), Rhone (France) and Po (Italy), and Northwestern Adriatic coastal lagoons).

Characteristic species

In the supralittoral portion, humected by the sea only during storms and by salty spray from waves, this habitat may host associations characterised by halophytic vegetation, dominated by psammophyllous-halophilous species (e.g., *Cakile maritima*, *Salsola* spp., *Thinopyrum junceum*, *Euphorbia peplis* and *Calamagrostis arenaria*) made by emerging and rooting perennial plants able to tolerate some extent of salt concentration and with a wide ecological range.

Littoral mud may feature abundant infaunal communities of polychaetes (e.g., *Aphelochaeta marioni*, *Capitella capitata*, *Cirriformia tentaculata*, *Sphaerosyllis taylori*, *Pygospio elegans*), bivalves (e.g., *Cerastoderma edule*, *Abra nitida*), oligochaetes (e.g., *Tubificoides pseudogaster*), crustaceans (e.g., *Aora gracilis*, *Melita palmata*, *Microprotopus maculatus*, *Corophium volutator*).

In transitional waters, the most abundant halophytes are *Sarcocornia* spp., *Salicornia* spp., *Limonium* spp., *Halimione portulacoides*, *Juncus* spp., *Spartina* spp., *Suaeda* spp., *Salsola* spp., *Kochia* spp., *Artemisia maritima*, *Atriplex portulacoides*, and *Scirpus* spp. The brackish ponds show a vegetation community like that of coastal lagoons, but in the presence of salinities lower than 10 psu the reed *Phragmites australis* can be dominant. Physiochemical properties of transitional intertidal habitats are stressful for most angiosperms, as only a few species can tolerate the anoxic, chemically reduced, high-saline soils typical of these ecosystems, such as *Zostera* spp. and *Ruppia* spp.

Associated species

In transitional waters, the emergent and submerged vegetation shows a gradient from the upland to the open water, starting from the supralittoral community dominated by shrubs and trees and with an understory of halophytic emergent wetland plants. In correspondence of river deltas different transitional water habitats can develop, each showing a peculiar associated community. Communities associated with vascular plants are those of the euryhaline and eurythermal environments. Little oxygen penetrates muddy sediments, and an anoxic layer is often present only within a few millimetres of the sediment surface.

The fauna associated to banks of dead leaves deposits and wracks is temporary, and is made up mainly by detritivores, scavenging species and their predators (such as sea birds). The main macrofaunal taxa are represented by insects, *Araneae* dwelling spiders, crustaceans Amphipoda (e.g., *Orchestia* spp.), *Isopoda* (e.g., *Halophiloscia couchii*, *Tylos ponticus*) and *Decapoda*, molluscs (Gastropoda, e.g., *Truncatella subcylindrica*) and *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Abra alba*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Loripes orbiculatus*), *Polychaeta*, *Oligochaeta*, and *Sipuncula*.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Even though aquatic plants in transitional waters are well adapted to highly dynamic and often stressful environmental conditions, they are directly affected by various anthropogenic pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development and urban activities (direct destruction for land reclaim, dredging, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, pollution, eutrophication), living resources exploitation, global warming and sea-level rise.

Aquatic angiosperms *Zostera noltii* and *Z. marina* are listed in Annex II “List of endangered or threatened species” to the SPA/BD Protocol. *Z. marina* is also protected by the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment (Annex I, ‘Strictly protected flora species’).

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Acosta, A.T.R., Ercole, S., Stanisci, A., De Patta, Pillar, V., Blasi C., 2007. Coastal vegetation zonation and dune morphology in some mediterranean ecosystems. *Journal of Coastal Research* 23 (6), 1518-1524.

Pergent, G., Bazairi, H., Bianchi, C.N., Boudouresque, C.F., Buia, M.C., Clabaut, P., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Mateo, M.A., Montefalcone, M., Morri, C., Orfanidis, S., Pergent-Martini, C., Semroud, R., Serrano, O., Verlaque, M., 2012. Les herbiers de Magnoliophytes marines de Mediterranee. Resilience et contribution a l’attenuation des changements climatiques. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain, 80 pp.

Santoro, R., Jucker, T., Prisco, I., Carboni, M., Battisti, C., Acosta, A.T.R., 2012. Effects of trampling limitation on coastal dune plant communities, *Environmental Management* 49, 534-542.

Sfriso, A., Facca, C., Bonometto, A., Boscolo, R., 2014. Compliance of the Macrophyte Quality index (MaQI) with the WFD (2000/60/EC) and ecological status assessment in transitional areas: The Venice lagoon as study case'5, *Ecological Indicators* 46, 536-547.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Touchette, B.W., Kneppers, M.K., Eggert, C.M., 2019. Salt marsh plants: Biological overview and vulnerability to climate change. In: Hasanuzzaman M.S., Shabala S., Fujita M. (Eds), *Halophytes and climate change: Adaptive mechanisms and potential uses*, 115-134.

Group 7

MB35. Mediterranean infralittoral coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral coarse sediment

HD: #1110, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MB3511](#), [MB3521](#), [MB3522](#)

Barcelona Convention: MB3.5

General description

This broad habitat includes Mediterranean sedimentary habitats in the infralittoral zone, typically extending from the extreme lower shore down to the lower limit for vascular plants and characterised by coarse sands mixed with finer gravel and/or pebbles mixed by waves or under the influence of bottom current, at depths of between 3-4m and 20-25m on average (even if, locally, the depth may go down to 70m).

Characteristic species

Infralittoral coarse sediments may host associations with maerl (associations of non-nucleated, unattached and branched twig-like coralline algae, mainly *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*) or rhodolith beds and, when characterised by pebbles in shallow waters, facies with *Gouania willdenowi*.

Associated species

Maerl and rhodolith beds increase the complexity of detritic bottoms, leading to greatly diverse assemblages. Maerl provides a surface to which other seaweeds or invertebrates (hydroids, bryozoans) can attach. The maerl bed community is characterised by abundant vagile epifauna. Molluscs, small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may also be abundant in maerl beds.

In the presence of infralittoral pebbles, associated species are the two amphipods *Melita hergensis* and *Parhyale aquilina*, which feed on organic detritus, the crab *Xantho poressa*, and several turbellarians and nemertines. After long periods of calm, a thin film of diatoms can be found on the pebbles. During stormy weather, all the species escape from the moving pebbles to the lower parts of the boulders generally mixed with the pebbles, or to deeper bottoms, to return as soon as the sea becomes calm.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

This broad habitat, especially in presence of Maerl and rhodolith beds, may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by bottom trawling, degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of invasive alien species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming, and acidification.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplà, A.A., Salomidi, M., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. In: Riosmena-Rodríguez R., Nelson W., Aguirre J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, Springer-Verlag, Berlin 15, 281-298.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MB45. Mediterranean infralittoral mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB45](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Infralittoral mixed sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MA4.5

General description

This habitat type describes Mediterranean poorly sorted mixed sediments in the infralittoral zone, ranging from muds with gravel and sand components to mixed sediments with pebbles, gravels, sands and mud in more even proportions. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, which hosts Mediterranean offshore infralittoral assemblages that may have been classified considering specific elements, regardless of the degree of presence of mixed sediments. This occurs because at this hierarchical level, and for this specific habitat, the grain size of the sediment is the driver to define the “habitats”.

Characteristic species

To date, no habitats have been described under this level 3 habitat.

Associated species

None described.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may potentially be threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by bottom trawling, degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of invasive alien species, smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming, and acidification.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MB55. Mediterranean infralittoral sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1130, #1150, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS

habitats: [MB5521](#), [MB5534](#),

[MB5535](#), [MB5541](#), [MB5544](#),

[MB5545](#)

Barcelona Convention:

MB5.5

General description

This is Mediterranean broad habitat featuring clean medium to fine sands or non-cohesive slightly muddy sands on open coasts, offshore or in estuaries and marine inlets. Such habitats are often subject to a degree of wave action or tidal currents which restrict the silt and clay content to less than 15%. The habitat of well sorted fine sand is very well delimited by bathymetry (depths of 2-25m) and sedimentology (fine sand >90%, very low proportion of fine particles <63mm in diameter, organic matter <2%), and it occurs in zones with relatively strong water movements and occupies vast bottom areas along the coasts.

Characteristic species

This level 3 habitat lists numerous characteristic biocenoses (and relative facies and associations): fine sand in very shallow waters (e.g., Facies with *Bivalvia*), well sorted fine sand (i.e., associations with indigenous marine angiosperms, with *Halophila stipulacea*, with photophilic algae), fine sand in sheltered waters (i.e., associations with indigenous marine angiosperms, such as *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera noltii*, *Ruppia maritima* and *Potamogeton* spp., with *H. stipulacea*, with *Caulerpa* spp., with other photophilic algae; facies with *Bivalvia*, with *Polychaeta*, with *Decapoda*, with *Tritia* spp. and nematodes in hydrothermal vents).

In transitional waters (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets, marshes, littoral ponds), there may be associations with halophytic vegetation (e.g., *Stuckenia pectinata* and *Zannichellia palustris*) and/or with marine angiosperms (*C. nodosa*, *Zostera marina*, *Z. noltii*, *R. cirrhosa* and *R. maritima*), with Fucales, with other photophilic algae (except Fucales); facies with *Polychaeta* and with *Bivalvia*.

It should be noted that, although *Posidonia oceanica* meadows are considered the climax habitats of well calibrated fine sand bottoms, for both their ecological relevance and areal extension they are classified in EUNIS specifically within the Mediterranean infralittoral biogenic habitat (MB252).

Associated species

Soft-bottom macrobenthic communities are mainly composed by infaunal organisms (polychaetes, bivalves, gastropods, and amphipods).

The habitat of well sorted fine sand is characterised by an oligotrophic community, with relatively low number of dominant species but associated with a high diversity. It may present a certain impoverishment of the community when in presence of some euryhaline species. When the wave action becomes too strong, the associated community can also be impoverished.

Associated communities to marine angiosperms can be distinguished in sessile species living on the leaf blade (epiphytes), and vagile associated species such as gastropods, bivalves, crustaceans, polychaetes, and fishes.

The benthic invertebrate community of fine sand in sheltered waters is characterised made by the bivalves *Polititapes aureus* and *Loripes orbiculatus*, by polychaetes (*Paradoneis lyra*, *Heteromastus filiformis*, *Branchiomma luctuosum*), gastropods (*Cerithium vulgatum*), other decapods (*Clibanarius erythropus*, *Carcinus aestuarii*), and sipunculids (*Golfingia (Golfingia) vulgaris vulgaris*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Fine sand communities in shallow waters are directly subject to multiple pressures: outfalls of urban waste, dredging and beach nourishments with sand collected from this habitat at shallow depths (<10m), coastal development, industries, ports, etc. Fisheries may still have an impact, despite trawling prohibition at less than three nautical miles from the coastline. This habitat is also changing in response to global warming. As the habitat develops in high-energy environments, it is recurrently subjected to natural physical perturbations, implying that the community has a high resilience and can recover rapidly after a perturbation.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Dauvin, J.C., Bakalem, A., Baffreau, A., Delecrin, C., Bellan, G., Lardicci, C., Balestri, E., Sarda, R., Grimes, S., 2017. The well sorted fine sand community from the western Mediterranean Sea: A resistant and resilient marine habitat under diverse human pressures. *Environmental Pollution* 224, 336-351.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MB65. Mediterranean infralittoral mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MB65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Infralittoral mud

HD: #1130, #1150

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MB6.5

General description

This is a Mediterranean broad habitat featuring sublittoral mud and cohesive sandy mud, extending from the extreme lower shore to the lower limit of vascular plants. This biotope is predominantly found in sheltered harbours, bays, marine inlets and estuaries and stable deeper/offshore areas where the reduced influence of wave action and/or tidal streams allow fine sediments to settle.

Characteristic species

Infralittoral muddy habitats are often dominated by polychaetes and echinoderms, in particular brittle stars such as *Amphiura* spp. Estuarine muds tend to be characterised by infaunal polychaetes and oligochaetes. Infralittoral mud in ports and highly anthropised areas may be characterised by the proliferation of the polychaetes *Capitella capitata*, *Magelona papillicornis*, and *Malacoceros tetracerus* because of pollution and decomposition of organic matter.

In transitional waters (e.g., coastal lagoons, estuaries, sea inlets, marshes, littoral ponds), associations with halophytic vegetation (e.g., *Stuckenia pectinata* and *Zannichellia palustris*), marine angiosperms (*C. nodosa*, *Zostera marina*, *Z. noltii*, *R. cirrhosa* and *R. maritima*), red algae (*Halopithys incurve*, *Rytidhlaea tinctoria*, *Alsidium corallinum*) may occur.

Associated species

Soft-bottom macrobenthic communities are mainly composed by infaunal organisms (polychaetes, bivalves, gastropods, and amphipods). The biota living in transitional waters is made up by highly euryhaline and eurythermal species.

Among the most characteristic species of the sediment infauna are bivalves, polychaetes and the crab *Carcinus aestuarii*. The brown alga *Ectocarpus siliculosus*, the red alga *Gracilariopsis longissima* and green algae of the family *Ulvaceae* (*Ulva prolifera*, *U. rigida*, etc.) may be abundant. Many fish thrive in estuaries and lagoons. Many of them are marine euryhaline species that enter transitional waters to forage or find shelter. Numerous species of birds, either resident or migrant, thrive in paralic ecosystems, feeding on fishes and invertebrates.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Even though aquatic plants in transitional waters are well adapted to highly dynamic and often stressful environmental conditions, they are highly vulnerable to various anthropogenic pressures along the coast. The main threats are linked to coastal development and urban activities (direct destruction for land reclaim, dredging, modification of hydrodynamics and sediment budget, pollution, eutrophication), living resources exploitation, global warming and sea-level rise.

Aquatic angiosperms *Zostera noltii* and *Z. marina* are listed in Annex II “List of endangered or threatened species” to the SPA/BD Protocol. *Z. marina* is also protected by the Bern Convention on the conservation of wildlife and natural environment (Annex I, ‘Strictly protected flora species’).

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Touchette, B.W., Kneppers, M.K., Eggert, C.M., 2019. Salt marsh plants: Biological overview and vulnerability to climate change. In: Hasanuzzaman M.S., Shabala S., Fujita M. (Eds), *Halophytes and climate change: Adaptive mechanisms and potential uses*, 115-134.

Group 7

MC35. Mediterranean circalittoral coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral coarse sediment

[HD](#): #1110, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MC3517](#), [MC3521](#), [MC3523](#)

Barcelona Convention: MC3.5

General description

The coastal detritic bottom is one of the most extensive ecosystems on the Mediterranean continental shelf, occurring at depths between 30m and 150m. It is a soft bottom constituted by organogenic and bioclastic sediments. The habitat can vary greatly, depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and depends largely on the typology of the nearby coast and of nearby infralittoral formations: gravels and sands originating from predominant local rocks, debris and/or shell fragments of dead molluscs, bryozoans, echinoderms and rhodoliths or from adjacent ecosystems (e.g., coralligenous and photophilous infralittoral reefs). The interstices between these various components are partially filled by a variable proportion of sand and mud (usually less than 20%).

Characteristic species

The broad habitat may include two biocenoses, mainly differing for the presence/absence of rhodoliths, and various related facies and associations.

The Biocenosis of Mediterranean coastal detritic bottoms without rhodoliths are Characterised by associations of brown algae (*Arthrocladia villosa*, *Osmundaria volubilis*, *Laminaria rodriguezii*; the latter is very often associated with unattached big rhodoliths), of red algae (*Kallymenia patens*), facies with Ophiuroidea (*Ophiura ophiura*), with colonial tunicates (Ascidiacea), with large bryozoans (e.g., *Turbicellepora avicularis*, *T. incrassata*, *Pentapora fascialis*, *Smittina cervicornis*, *Reteporella* spp., *Myriapora truncata*, *Cellaria* spp., *Fron dipora verrucosa*, *Hornera lichenoides* and *H. frondiculata*). Many taxa are considered as characteristic of this habitat: large and erect sponges (e.g., *Sarcotragus* spp., *Axinella* spp.), *Alcyonacea* (e.g., *Alcyonium* spp., *Eunicella* spp., *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*), *Pennatulacea* (e.g., *Pennatula* spp., *Pteroeides* spp., *Virgularia mirabilis*).

Circalittoral coarse sediments may host associations with maerl (associations of non-nucleated, unattached and branched twig-like coralline algae, mainly *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*), rhodolith beds and/or coralline red algae (*Peyssonnelia rosa-marina*).

Associated species

The biocenosis of Mediterranean coastal detritic bottoms without rhodoliths may feature variable abundances of Bivalves (e.g., *Atrina pectinata*, *Venus casina*, *Dosinia exoleta*, *Donax variegatus*, *Glycymeris glycymeris*, *Laevicardium crassum*, *L. oblungum*, *Acanthocardia deshayesi*, *Pecten jacobaeus*), Echinoderms (e.g., *Spatangus purpureus*), Hydrozoans (e.g., *Lytocarpia myriophyllum*); Polychaetes (*Sigalion squamosus*, *Armandia polyophtalma*, *Salmacina-Filograna* complex), Ophiuroids (*Ophiopsila annulosa*), and Crustaceans (*Anapagurus breviaculeatus*, *Thia scutellate*, *Paguristes eremita*, *Anapagurus laevis*, *Ebalia tuberosa*, *E. edwardsi*).

Maerl and rhodolith beds increase the complexity of detritic bottoms leading to greatly diverse assemblages. Maerl provides a surface to which other

seaweeds or invertebrates (hydroids, bryozoans) can attach. The maerl bed community is characterised by abundant vagile epifauna. Molluscs, small decapods, amphipods, polychaetes, and echinoderms may be also abundant in maerl beds.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat, especially in presence of maerl and rhodolith beds, may be threatened by physical damage, mainly caused by bottom trawling, degradation of water quality (i.e., pollution from sewage or from aquaculture effluents), the spread of invasive non-indigenous species (e.g., *Pterois miles* in the Eastern basin), smothering effects resulting from changes in sedimentation rates, ocean warming, and acidification. The coastal detritic bottoms are subject to various sedimentary additions brought down either by rivers flooding that can increase the concentration of fine sediments and organic matter. The increase in fine sediments can lead to the shift toward muddy detritic bottom resulting in altered assemblages.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Astruch, P., Goujard, A., Rouanet, E., Boudouresque, C.F., Verlaque, M., Berthier, L., Daniel, B., Harmelin, J.G., Peirache, M., Peterka, A., Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., 2019. Assessment of the conservation status of coastal detrital sandy bottoms in the Mediterranean Sea: an ecosystem-based approach in the framework of the ACDSEA project. Proceedings of the 3rd Mediterranean Symposium on the conservation of Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretions (Antalya, Turkey, 15-16 January 2019). Langar H., Ouerghi A. (eds), SPA/RAC publ., Tunis, 23-29.

Basso, D., Babbini, L., Ramos-Esplà, A.A., Salomidi, M., 2017. Mediterranean Rhodolith Beds. In: Riosmena-Rodríguez R., Nelson W., Aguirre J. (eds), *Rhodolith/Maerl Beds: A Global Perspective*, Coastal Research Library, Springer-Verlag, Berlin 15, 281-298.

Boisset, F., Ferrer-Gallego, P.P., Furnari, G., Cormaci, M., Dennetiere, B., 2016. Typification of the Mediterranean endemic deep-water macroalga *Laminaria rodriguezii* Bornet (Laminariaceae, Phaeophyceae). *Cryptogamie Algologie* 37, 121-132.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

UNEP/MAP, 2017. Action Plan for the Conservation of the Coralligenous and Other Calcareous Bio-concretions in the Mediterranean Sea, UN Environment/MAP Athens, Greece, 20 pp.

Wood, A.L., Probert, P.K., Rowden, A.A., Smith, A.M., 2012. Complex habitat generated by marine bryozoans: a review of its distribution, structure,

diversity, threats and conservation. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 22 (4), 547-563.

Group 7

MC45. Mediterranean circalittoral mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC45](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Circalittoral mixed sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC4.5

General description

Habitats in the Mediterranean circalittoral zone (generally depths below 15-20m) are characterised by well mixed muddy gravelly sands or very poorly sorted mosaics of shell, cobbles and pebbles mixed with mud, sand or gravel, and are present throughout the Mediterranean Sea. Muddy detritic bottoms develop in areas where a detritus bottom is covered with mud formed by terrigenous deposits from rivers. Gravel, sand and mud are mixed in varying quantities, but mud always predominates.

Characteristic species

Due to the variable nature of the seabed, a variety of communities can develop. The biocenosis of Mediterranean muddy detritic bottoms develops when sedimentation rates are slow enough to allow the development of sessile epifauna. Muddy detritic bottoms are characterised by the presence of both fine sediment and organogenous/bioclastic sediment, and may feature facies with *Hydrozoa* (e.g., *Lytocarpia myriophyllum*, *Nemertesia* spp.), with *Alcyonacea* (e.g., *Alcyonium* spp., *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*, *Spinimuricea* spp.), with *Pennatulacea* (e.g., *Veretillum cynomorium*, *Ptereoides* spp.), with *Polychaeta*, with *Ophiuroidea* (in particular, *Ophiothrix quinque maculata*).

Associated species

Especially on prevalently muddy detritic bottoms, the associated fauna may include: Echinoidea (e.g., *Cidaris cidaris*), molluscs (*Serratina serrata*, *Turritellinella tricarinata*, *Abra prismatica*, *Nucula nitidosa*), polychaetes (*Aphrodita aculeata*, *Polyodontes maxillosus*, *Leiocapitella dollfusi*), Sipunculida (*Golfingia elongata*), Isopoda (*Natanolana neglecta*), Holothuridae (*Pseudothyone raphanus*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Mixed detritic bottoms may be altered by increased organic matter and river pollutants or by flooding, that can directly affect characteristic species in the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage caused primarily by trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Borja, A., Mader, J., Muxika, I., Rodríguez, J.G., Bald, J., 2008. Using M-AMBI in assessing benthic quality within the WFD: some remarks and recommendations. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 56, 1377-1379.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MC55. Mediterranean circalittoral sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral sand

HD: #1110, #1160

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MC5.5

General description

This is a Mediterranean broad habitat featuring circalittoral sands (clean fine sands with less than 5% silt/clay) and muddy sands. In presence of strong bottom currents, coarser sands and fine gravels occur. Compared to shallower sandy bottoms, while the process of sedimentation is constant, the movement of water masses is reduced, making it a more stable environment. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, which hosts Mediterranean circalittoral assemblages that may have been classified considering specific elements, regardless of the degree of presence of sand. This occurs because at this hierarchical level, and for this specific habitat, the grain size of the sediment is the driver to define the “habitats”.

Characteristic species

This habitat is potentially more stable than shallower infralittoral sands and consequently may support a more diverse, even if sciaphilic, community, featuring mainly infaunal species of polychaetes, bivalves, echinoderms, gastropods. Coarse sands and fine gravels under the influence of bottom currents may support a rich mesofauna, including foraminifera, nematodes, Copepods and Platyhelminthes.

Associated species

Associated communities may feature crustaceans and small fishes.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The major pressures on this habitat derive from fishing activities, mainly trawl fishing, and sand mining activities, which alter seabed structure and biodiversity.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Dauvin, J.C., Bakalem, A., Baffreau, A., Delecrin, C., Bellan, G., Lardicci, C., Balestri, E., Sarda, R., Grimes, S., 2017. The well sorted fine sand community from the western Mediterranean Sea: A resistant and resilient marine habitat under diverse human pressures. *Environmental Pollution* 224, 336-351.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MC65. Mediterranean circalittoral mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MC65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Circalittoral mud

HD: #1130, 1160⁵⁵

(adjacent)

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: MC6514

Barcelona Convention: MC6.5

General description

This is a Mediterranean broad habitat featuring mud and cohesive sandy mud, often of terrestrial origin, in the circalittoral zone at depths between 25m to about 150m. This biotope is predominantly found close to estuaries, and in stable deeper/offshore areas where the reduced influence of wave action and/or tidal streams allow fine sediments to settle.

Characteristic species

Biocenoses of coastal terrigenous muds, almost always of a fluvial origin, may host facies with *Alcyonacea* (*Alcyonium palmatum*) and *Holothuroidea* (*Parastichopus regalis*, *Holothuria tubulosa*, *Oestergrenia digitata*), with *Pennatulacea* (*Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea*) and with *Gastropoda* (e.g., *Turritellinella* spp.), even if the development of sessile epifauna is rarer than in other soft bottoms.

Associated species

Soft-bottom macrobenthic communities are mainly composed by infaunal organisms (polychaetes, bivalves, gastropods, and amphipods), decapods (e.g., *Medorippe lanata* and *Goneplax rhomboides*) and a variable and rich fish community.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The habitat is subjected to impacts such as coastal pollution, coastal development, fishing and sediment contamination. The combined effects of urbanisation, fisheries, aquaculture and sedimentation have led to a shift in the associated species assemblages.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Borja, A., Mader, J., Muxika, I., Rodríguez, J.G., Bald, J., 2008. Using M-AMBI in assessing benthic quality within the WFD: some remarks and recommendations. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 56, 1377-1379.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

⁵⁵ In the Mediterranean Sea, MC65 may be adjacent to the HD Annex I habitat "Large shallow inlets and bays" (1160).

Group 7

MD35. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MD3.5

General description

This habitat is distributed on the furthest part of the continental shelf and in offshore banks. It is characterised by soft bottoms with coarse organogenous/bioclastic sediment not covered by mud. It can vary greatly, depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and depends largely on the typology of the nearby coast and of nearby infralittoral formations: gravels and sands originating from predominant local rocks, debris and/or shell fragments of dead molluscs, bryozoans, echinoderms and rhodoliths.

Characteristic species

The broad habitat featuring offshore circalittoral detritic bottom is characterised by organisms of detritic soft bottoms: i.e., *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Neopycnodonte cochlear*), *Brachiopoda*, *Polychaeta*, *Crinoidea* (e.g., *Leptometra phalangium*), *Ophiuroidea*, *Echinoidea*, *Cnidaria* (*Alcyonium* spp., *Cerianthus membranaceus*, *Funiculina quadrangularis*), and *Porifera*.

Associated species

Several species may contribute to structuring the offshore circalittoral detritic bottom facies and associations: cnidarians, serpulids, bryozoans, scleractinians. Offshore detritic bottoms host a highly diversified fish assemblages also of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Trisopterus* spp., *Phycis blennoides*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Capros aper*, *Macroramphosus scolopax*, *Lepidorhombus boscii*, *Scyliorhinus canicula*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling and fishing gear directly entangling reef formations.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., 2020. Offshore *Neopycnodonte* Oyster Reefs in the Mediterranean Sea. *Diversity* 12, 92.

Astruch, P., Goujard, A., Rouanet, E., Boudouresque, C.F., Verlaque, M., Berthier, L., Daniel, B., Harmelin, J.G., Peirache, M., Peterka, A., Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., 2019. Assessment of the conservation status of coastal detrital sandy bottoms in the Mediterranean Sea: an ecosystem-based approach in the framework of the ACDSEA project. *Proceedings of the 3rd Mediterranean*

Symposium on the conservation of Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretions (Antalya, Turkey, 15-16 January 2019). Langar H., Ouerghi A. (eds), SPA/RAC publ., Tunis, 23-29.

Joher, S., Ballesteros, E., Rodríguez-Prieto, C., 2015. Contribution to the study of deep coastal detritic bottoms: the algal communities of the continental shelf off the Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean'. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 573-590.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MD45. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD45](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MD4.5

General description

This habitat is distributed on the furthest part of the continental shelf and in offshore banks. It is characterised by detritic soft bottoms with coarse organogenous/bioclastic sediment (e.g., subfossil dead shells, bryozoans and coral skeletons) often covered by mud. The habitat can vary greatly, depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and depends largely on the typology of the nearby coast and of nearby infralittoral formations: gravels and sands originating from debris and/or shell fragments of dead molluscs, bryozoans, echinoderms and rhodoliths.

Characteristic species

The broad habitat featuring offshore circalittoral detritic bottom is characterised by organisms of muddy and detritic mixed soft bottoms: i.e., *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Neopycnodonte cochlear*), *Brachiopoda*, *Polychaeta*, *Crinoidea* (e.g., *Leptometra phalangium*), *Ophiuroidea*, *Echinoidea* (e.g., *Neolampas rostellata*), *Cnidaria* (*Alcyonum* spp., *Cerianthus membranaceus*, *Funiculina quadrangularis*), and *Porifera*.

Associated species

Several species may contribute to structuring the offshore circalittoral detritic mixed bottom facies and associations: cnidarians, serpulids, bryozoans, scleractinians. Offshore detritic bottoms host a highly diversified fish assemblages also of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Trisopterus* spp., *Phycis blennoides*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Capros aper*, *Macroramphosus scolopax*, *Lepidorhombus boscii*, *Scyliorhinus canicula*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling and fishing gear directly entangling reef formations.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., 2020. Offshore *Neopycnodonte* Oyster Reefs in the Mediterranean Sea. *Diversity* 12, 92.

Astruch, P., Goujard, A., Rouanet, E., Boudouresque, C.F., Verlaque, M., Berthier, L., Daniel, B., Harmelin, J.G., Peirache, M., Peterka, A., Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., 2019. Assessment of the conservation status of coastal detrital

sandy bottoms in the Mediterranean Sea: an ecosystem-based approach in the framework of the ACDSEA project. Proceedings of the 3rd Mediterranean Symposium on the conservation of Coralligenous and other Calcareous Bio-Concretions (Antalya, Turkey, 15-16 January 2019). Langar H., Ouerghi A. (eds), SPA/RAC publ., Tunis, 23-29.

Joher, S., Ballesteros, E., Rodríguez-Prieto, C., 2015. Contribution to the study of deep coastal detritic bottoms: the algal communities of the continental shelf off the Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 16, 573-590.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): < Offshore circalittoral sand

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: MD5.51

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with sand sediment in offshore banks on the furthest part of the continental shelf (70m to 200m depth). Compared to shallower sandy bottoms, while the process of sedimentation is constant, the movement of water masses is reduced, making it a more stable environment. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, which hosts Mediterranean offshore circalittoral assemblages that may have been classified considering specific elements, regardless of the degree of presence of sand. This occurs because at this hierarchical level, and for this specific habitat, the grain size of the sediment is the driver to define the “habitats”.

Characteristic species

This habitat may include facies characterised by particular and ecologically important taxa, i.e., facies with Bivalvia (e.g., *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, *Pecten jacobaeus*, *Parvicardium scabrum*, *Acanthocardia* spp.), facies with Brachiopoda, facies with Polychaeta, facies with Crinoidea (e.g., *Leptometra phalangium*), facies with Ophiuroidea and facies with Echinoidea.

Associated species

Offshore circalittoral sand may host typical soft bottoms species, such as the sea pen species *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea*, the soft coral *Alcyonium palmatum* and the sponge *Thenea muricata*.

Soft bottom offshore circalittoral banks host many fish of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Trisopterus* spp., *Phycis blennoides*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Lepidorhombus boscii*), and they are important fishing areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are mechanical abrasion, dumps, sedimentary imbalances and the increase of fine sediments, pollution, invasive non-indigenous species, blooms of benthic mucilage, and climate change. Major negative effects on this habitat are the result of demersal fishing activities, mainly trawl fishing, which alter seabed structure and biodiversity. The continental shelf area in the Mediterranean countries is subject to a high intensity of trawled gear fishing activities, with the highest efforts and extent in the Adriatic Sea. Nutrient enrichment from land-based sources may also affect deep circalittoral areas in the Adriatic by leading to hypoxic conditions.

All available data indicate that a majority of the circalittoral zone (more than 80%) has suffered a decline in abiotic and biotic quality predominantly because of demersal fishing gear. In consequence, the communities in the deepest part of the circalittoral zone, extending down to a depth of 200m, are defined as ‘vulnerable’ by the IUCN European Red List of marine habitats (Code *MEDA5.27 Communities of Mediterranean lower circalittoral sand*).

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

[European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats, Publications Office, 2016.](#)

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MD65. Mediterranean offshore circalittoral mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MD65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Offshore circalittoral mud

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MD6512](#)

Barcelona Convention: MD6.5

General description

This habitat type is distributed on the furthest part of the continental shelf and in offshore banks. It is characterised by mud or sandy mud, clayey, often of terrestrial origin.

Characteristic species

The broad habitat is characterised by organisms of muddy, soft bottoms. Many taxa are considered as characteristic of this habitat, such as *Pennatulacea* (e.g., *Pennatula* spp., *Virgularia mirabilis*), Polychaeta, Bivalvia (e.g., *Neopycnodonte* spp.), *Brachiopoda*, *Ceriantharia* (e.g., *Cerianthus* spp., *Arachnanthus* spp.), *Holothuroidea* (e.g., *Parastichopus regalis*).

Associated species

Offshore muddy bottoms host highly diversified fish assemblages also of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lophius budegassa*, *Lepidorhombus boscii*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. It may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

ME35. Mediterranean upper bathyal coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME3.5

General description

The habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with coarse sediment in the Mediterranean upper bathyal zone. The habitat can vary depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and nearby formations. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, that may occur at a depth between 200m and 700m.

Characteristic species

The broad habitat is characterised by organisms of muddy, soft bottoms. Many taxa are considered as characteristic of this habitat, such as *Pennatulacea* (e.g., *Pennatula* spp., *Virgularia mirabilis*), *Polychaeta*, *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Neopycnodonte* spp.), *Brachiopoda*, *Ceriantharia* (e.g., *Cerianthus* spp., *Arachnanthus* spp.), *Holothuroidea* (e.g., *Parastichopus regalis*).

Associated species

Alcyonaceans forests are often interspersed with other sessile organisms, such as sponges, scleractinians, black corals, brachiopods, and bryozoans, and the associated vagile community, including echinoderms, cephalopods, nudibranchs, and crustaceans. Many benthonektonic and pelagic fishes may be found in the habitat (e.g., *Macroramphosus scolopax*, *Capros aper*, *Anthias anthias*, *Callanthias ruber*, *Pagellus* spp., *Polyprion americanus*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. It may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Cerrano, C., Bastari, A., Calcinai, B., Di Camillo, C., Pica, D., Puce, S., Valisano, L., Torsani, F., 2019. Temperate mesophotic ecosystems: gaps and perspectives of an emerging conservation challenge for the Mediterranean Sea. *The European Zoological Journal* 86, 370-388.

Danovaro, R., 2018. Climate change impacts on the biota and on vulnerable habitats of the deep Mediterranean Sea. *Rendiconti Lincei, Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 525-541.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

ME45. Mediterranean upper bathyal mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME45](#)
EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:
[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME4.5

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with mixed sediment, in the presence of clays, in the Mediterranean upper bathyal zone. The habitat can vary depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and of nearby formations. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, that may occur between depths of 200 and 700m.

Characteristic species

The species composition is largely dependent on the consistency and compactness of the sediment. The broad habitat is very sparsely populated and may be characterised by facies of organisms of muddy mixed soft bottoms: i.e., *Bivalvia* (i.e., *Neopycnodonte cochlear*), *Brachiopoda* (e.g., *Gryphus vitreus*, *Terebratulina retusa*) and *Cidaridae*.

Associated species

Several species may contribute to structuring the upper bathyal mixed bottom facies and associations: cnidarians, serpulids, bryozoans, echinoderms, sponges. Many benthic-nektonic and pelagic fishes may be found in the habitat (e.g., *Macroramphosus scolopax*, *Capros aper*, *Anthias anthias*, *Callanthias ruber*, *Pagellus* spp., *Polyprion americanus*).

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Angeletti, L., Taviani, M., 2020. Offshore *Neopycnodonte* Oyster Reefs in the Mediterranean Sea. *Diversity* 12, 92.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

ME55. Mediterranean upper bathyal sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

Barcelona Convention: ME5.5

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with sandy sediments in the upper bathyal zone of the Mediterranean (200m to 700m depth). Compared to shallower sandy bottoms, while the process of sedimentation is constant, the movement of water masses is reduced, making it a more stable environment. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, which hosts Mediterranean upper bathyal assemblages that may have been classified considering specific elements, regardless of the degree of presence of sand. This occurs because at this hierarchical level, and for this specific habitat, the grain size of the sediment is the driver to define the “habitats”.

Characteristic species

This habitat may include facies characterised by particular and ecologically important taxa, i.e., facies with *Bivalvia* (e.g., *Neopycnodonte cochlear*, *Pecten jacobus*, *Parvicardium scabrum*, *Acanthocardia* spp.), facies with *Brachiopoda*, facies with *Polychaeta*, facies with *Crinoidea* (e.g., *Leptometra phalangium*), facies with *Ophiuroidea* and facies with *Echinoidea*.

Associated species

Offshore circalittoral sand may host typical soft bottoms species, such as the sea pen species *Virgularia mirabilis* and *Pennatula phosphorea*, the soft coral *Alcyonium palmatum* and the sponge *Thenea muricata*.

Soft bottom offshore circalittoral banks host many fish of commercial interest (e.g., *Merluccius merluccius*, *Trisopterus* spp., *Phycis blennoides*, *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Lepidorhombus boschii*), and they are important fishing areas.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to the habitat are mechanical abrasion, dumps, sedimentary imbalances and increase of fine sediments, pollution, invasive non-indigenous species, blooms of benthic mucilage. Major negative effects on this habitat are the result of demersal fishing activities, mainly trawl fishing which alter seabed structure and biodiversity. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

ME65. Mediterranean upper bathyal mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [ME65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Upper bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [ME6514](#)

Barcelona Convention: ME6.5

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with (yellowish to blue greyish) clayed muddy sediments widespread in the upper bathyal zone of the Mediterranean (200m to 500m depth). The biocenoses of bathyal muds are often characterised by a constant homeothermy (around 13-15°C) and an almost total absence of light (<1% of the incident light). The granulometry, thickness and organic content of the sediment is not homogeneous: the sides of the canyons are covered with a fluid mud, sometimes merely a simple film, while sandy muds are quite frequent in the upper horizon but more exceptional underneath. Modifications in the granulometry and thickness of the mud, and additions of exogenous organic matter, result in the appearance of special facies.

Characteristic species

The faunal composition is characterised by foraminifera, sponges, polychaetes, echinoderms and crustaceans and, accordingly to the sediment composition, may host various typical facies: with small sponges (i.e., *Thenea muricata*, *Pheronema carpenteri*), with *Pennatulacea* (i.e., *Funiculina quadrangularis*), with *Alcyonacea* (i.e., *Isidella elongata*), with Scleractinia, with *Crustacea Decapoda* (e.g., *Palinurus mauritanicus*, *Parapenaeus longirostris*, *Nephrops norvegicus*), with *Crinoidea*, with *Echinoidea* (i.e., *Brissopsis lyrifera*), with *Bivalvia*, with *Brachiopoda*, with *Ceriantharia*, with *Bryozoa*, with giant *Foraminifera*.

Associated species

The upper bathyal muds show a high species richness, hosting nearly endemic and endemic species. Meiofauna, dominated by Nematoda, is a key component of the upper bathyal mud, together with infaunal macro- and megabenthos. Macrofauna is generally dominated by polychaetes. Epimegafauna tends to be sparse and constituted mainly by mobile species such as crustaceans and echinoderms. Other common mobile invertebrates are the gastropod *Aporrhais serresianus*, the heterobranchs *Tethys fimbria* and *Pleurobranchaea meckeli*, the cephalopods *Eledone cirrhosa*, *Bathypolypus sponsalis*, *Octopus salutii*, the polychaete *Hyalinoecia tubicola*, the holothurian *Parastichopus regalis*, the sea urchins *Cidaris cidaris* and *Brissopsis lyrifera*, the crinoids *Antedon mediterranea* and *Leptometra phalangium*, the asteroid *Anseropoda placenta*. Many benthic and benthonektonic fishes are also frequent.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Intensive deep-sea trawling is responsible for overfishing of target species, abrasion, changes in siltation, habitat destruction, bycatch or discard of non-target species, loss of biodiversity, changes in the trophic composition of the communities, and functioning of the ecosystem at all levels. The recovery ability of some communities to mechanical disturbances is reduced by the life cycles and slow growth rates of some species, defining resilience in the order of decades or more. Dumping activities and mining or drilling activities may

also directly impact deep-sea muddy ecosystems. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Danovaro, R., Snelgrove, P.V., Tyler, P., 2014. Challenging the paradigms of deep-sea ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 29, 465-475.

Danovaro, R., 2018. Climate change impacts on the biota and on vulnerable habitats of the deep Mediterranean Sea. *Rendiconti Lincei. Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 525-541.

Fanelli, E., Bianchelli, S., Danovaro, R., 2018. Deep-sea mobile megafauna of Mediterranean submarine canyons and open slopes: Analysis of spatial and bathymetric gradients. *Progress in Oceanography* 168, 23-34.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MF35. Mediterranean lower bathyal coarse sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF35](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with coarse sediment in the Mediterranean lower bathyal zone. The habitat can vary depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and nearby formations. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, that may occur at a depth between 500m and 2,180m.

Characteristic species

The broad habitat featuring coarse sediment in the upper bathyal zone may occasionally host aggregations and/or isolated patches of *Alcyonacea*, especially featuring species able to withstand high levels of sedimentation and in proximity to hardgrounds and coral bioconstructions (e.g., *Acanthogorgia hirsuta*, *Bebryce mollis*, *Chelidonisis aurantiaca*, *Muriceides lepida*, *Placogorgia* spp.).

Associated species

No information is available on macrobenthic assemblages typical of this zone.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Cerrano, C., Bastari, A., Calcinai, B., Di Camillo, C., Pica, D., Puce, S., Valisano, L., Torsani, F., 2019. Temperate mesophotic ecosystems: gaps and perspectives of an emerging conservation challenge for the Mediterranean Sea. *The European Zoological Journal* 86, 370-388.

Danovaro, R., 2018. Climate change impacts on the biota and on vulnerable habitats of the deep Mediterranean Sea. *Rendiconti Lincei, Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 525-541.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MF45. Mediterranean lower bathyal mixed sediment

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF45](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with mixed sediment in the Mediterranean lower bathyal zone. The habitat can vary depending on depth, hydrodynamic conditions, and nearby formations. There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, that may occur at a depth between 500m and 2,200m.

Characteristic species

The species composition is largely dependent on the consistency and compactness of the sediment. The broad habitat is very sparsely populated and may be occasionally characterised by aggregations of organisms of muddy mixed soft bottoms: i.e., *Brachiopoda* (e.g., *Gryphus vitreus*, *Terebratulina retusa*) and *Cidaridae*.

Associated species

No information is available on macrobenthic assemblages typical of this zone.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The broad habitat may be altered by the increase of organic matter and pollutants that can act directly on the characteristic species of the assemblages. This habitat may be threatened by physical damage mainly caused by abrasion from bottom trawling. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

Cerrano, C., Bastari, A., Calcinai, B., Di Camillo, C., Pica, D., Puce, S., Valisano, L., Torsani, F., 2019. Temperate mesophotic ecosystems: gaps and perspectives of an emerging conservation challenge for the Mediterranean Sea. *The European Zoological Journal* 86, 370-388.

Danovaro, R., 2018. Climate change impacts on the biota and on vulnerable habitats of the deep Mediterranean Sea. *Rendiconti Lincei, Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 525-541.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MF55. Mediterranean lower bathyal sand

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF55](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

MSFD: <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: Not defined

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with sandy sediments in the lower bathyal zone of the Mediterranean (500-2,200m depth). There are insufficient data to assess the real extent of this macro category, which hosts Mediterranean lower bathyal assemblages that may have been classified considering specific elements, regardless of the degree of presence of sand. This occurs because at this hierarchical level, and for this specific habitat, the grain size of the sediment is the driver to define the “habitats”.

Characteristic species

This habitat may include communities characterised by sandy substrata and by the presence of the brachiopod *Gryphus vitreus*, even if no information is available on the macrobenthic assemblages typical of this zone.

Associated species

No information is available on macrobenthic assemblages typical of this zone.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

The main threats to this habitat may result from mechanical abrasion, dumps, sedimentary imbalances and increase of fine sediments, pollution, invasive non-indigenous species. Major negative effects on this habitat may derive from demersal fishing activities, mainly trawl fishing which alter seabed structure and biodiversity. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

N/A

Bibliographic sources

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Group 7

MF65. Mediterranean lower bathyal mud

Mediterranean Sea

EUNIS code: [MF65](#)

EUNIS level: 3

Correspondence with other classifications:

[MSFD](#): <Lower bathyal sediment

Links to finer EUNIS habitats: [MF6511](#), [MF6513](#)

Barcelona Convention: MF6.5

General description

This habitat is characterised by soft bottoms with (yellowish to blue greyish) clayed muddy sediments widespread in the lower bathyal zone of the Mediterranean (500-3,000m depth). The biocenoses of lower bathyal muds are characterised by a constant homeothermy (around 13-14°C) and a total absence of light. Mud represents the main habitat of the lower bathyal depth range and shows a basin-scale extent. Differently from the upper bathyal mud, the lower bathyal one results mostly firm and compact. The granulometry and thickness of the sediment is not homogeneous, and, locally, areas with sandy mud or fluid mud can occur. Seamounts, ridges and canyons partially interrupt this habitat, nevertheless mud can also occur as large patches on deep hardgrounds.

Characteristic species

The lower bathyal range hosts a lower number of species with respect to the upper bathyal with differences occurring between canyons and deep-water coral areas (considered more diverse in terms of megafauna) with respect to open slopes. The faunal composition may host various typical facies: with small sponges (i.e., *Hyalonema (Cyliconema) thomsonis*, *Cladorhiza abyssicola*), with *Pennatulacea* (i.e., *Funiculina quadrangularis*), with *Alcyonacea* (i.e., *Isidella elongata*), with *Scleractinia*, with *Crustacea Decapoda* (e.g., *Geryon longipes*, *Paromola cuvieri*, *Polycheles typhlops*, *Aristeus antennatus*, *Aristaeomorpha foliacea*, *Pasiphaea* spp., *Acanthephyra eximia*, *Nematocarcinus exilis*, *Stereomastis sculpta* and different species of Anomura), with *Crinoidea*, with *Echinoidea* (i.e., *Brissopsis lyrifera*, *Cidaris cidaris*), with *Bivalvia*, with *Brachiopoda (Gryphus vitreus)*, with *Ceriantharia*, with *Bryozoa*, with giant *Foraminifera*.

Associated species

The faunal composition is characterised by foraminifera, sponges, polychaetes, echinoderms and crustaceans. The meiofaunal component, dominated by Nematoda, is a key component together with infaunal macro- and megabenthos. Epimegafauna tends to be sparse and constituted mainly by mobile species such as crustaceans and echinoderms. Other common mobile invertebrates are the cephalopod *Bathypolypus sponsalis*, the holothurians *Molpadia musculus*, *Pseudostichopus occultatus*, *Mesothuria intestinalis* and *Penilpidia ludwigi*, the sea stars *Ceramaster grenadensis*, *Hymenodiscus coronata*, and *Odontaster mediterraneus*. Many benthic and bentho-nektonic fishes are also frequent.

Human activities and anthropogenic pressures threatening the habitat

Intensive deep-sea trawling is responsible for overfishing of target species, abrasion, changes in siltation, habitat destruction, bycatch or discard of non-target species, loss of biodiversity, changes in the trophic composition of the communities, and functioning of the ecosystem at all levels. Therefore, in 2005 the GFCM established a permanent closure of the deep Mediterranean basin below 1,000m to benthic fishing gear (REC. GFCM/29/2005/1). Marine

litter (especially plastic debris and lost fishing gear) is also a potential threat to the lower bathyal zone. The recovery ability of some communities to mechanical disturbances is reduced by the life cycles and slow growth rates of some species, defining resilience in the order of decades or more. Dumping activities and mining or drilling activities may also directly impact deep-sea muddy ecosystems. Increasing evidence is emerging towards the effects of global changes also in the deep Mediterranean Sea.

Best practices in nature restoration

Management measures aimed at reducing/removing anthropogenic pressures affecting the habitat are essential to implement effective restoration.

Bibliographic sources

Cau, A., Bellodi, A., Moccia, D., Mulas, A., Pesci, P., Cannas, R., Pusceddu, A., Follesa, M.C., 2018. Dumping to the abyss: single-use marine litter invading bathyal plains of the Sardinian margin (Tyrrhenian Sea). *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 135, 845-851.

Danovaro, R., Snelgrove, P.V., Tyler, P., 2014. Challenging the paradigms of deep-sea ecology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 29, 465-475.

Danovaro, R., 2018. Climate change impacts on the biota and on vulnerable habitats of the deep Mediterranean Sea. *Rendiconti Lincei. Scienze Fisiche e Naturali* 29, 525-541.

Fanelli, E., Bianchelli, S., Danovaro, R., 2018. Deep-sea mobile megafauna of Mediterranean submarine canyons and open slopes: Analysis of spatial and bathymetric gradients. *Progress in Oceanography* 168, 23-34.

Ferra, C., Tassetti, A.N., Armelloni, E.N., Galdelli, A., Scarcella, G., Fabi, G., 2020. Using AIS to Attempt a Quantitative Evaluation of Unobserved Trawling Activity in the Mediterranean Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7, 1036.

SPA/RAC-UN Environment/MAP, 2019. Updated Classification of Benthic Marine Habitat Types for the Mediterranean Region and Interpretation Manual of Marine Habitat Types in the Mediterranean Sea (Draft 2021).

Tecchio, S., Ramirez-Llodra, E., Sarda, F., Company, J.B., 2011. Biodiversity of deep-sea demersal megafauna in western and central Mediterranean basin. *Scientia Marina* 75, 341-350.

List of abbreviations

CWC	Cold-water corals
DE	Red List Germany
EEA	European Environment Agency
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network
ETC-BE	European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and Ecosystems
EU	European Union
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
HD	Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC)
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
HELCOM HUB	HELCOM Underwater Biotope and Habitat Classification System
IE	Habitat Classification of Ireland
IMAP	Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Mediterranean Sea and Coast
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC)
NRR	Nature Restoration Regulation (EU) 2024/1991
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
SPA/BD	UNEP/MAP Specially Protected Areas and Biodiversity Protocol
SPA/RAC	UNEP/MAP Specially Protected Areas Regional Activity Centre
UNEP/MAP	United Nations Environment Programme/Mediterranean Action Plan
WFD	Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)

European Topic Centre on
Biodiversity and ecosystems
<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-be>

The European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and
ecosystems (ETC-BE) is a consortium of
European institutes under contract of the
European Environment Agency

European Environment Agency
European Topic Centre
Biodiversity and ecosystems

